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Cristina Grisot and Thalassia Kontino

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CLARIN 2025 submissions, review process and acceptance

- Call for abstracts: 18 December 2024 first call published on CLARIN website, disseminated, and submission system open
- Submission deadline: 11 April 2025
- In total 59 submissions were received and reviewed (three reviews per submission)
- Virtual PC meeting: 12 June 2025
- Notifications to authors: 16 June 2025
- 42 accepted submissions

More details on the paper selection procedure and the conference can be found at <https://www.clarin.eu/content/call-extended-abstracts-clarin-annual-conference-2025>.

Preface

We present with great pleasure the proceedings of the CLARIN Annual Conference 2025. The conference is held in Vienna from September 30 to October 3, 2025.

CLARIN conferences have been organised since 2012 and are the place where the people from the various countries participating in the CLARIN pan-European research infrastructure meet with each other and with the users of the infrastructure. Together, we form the CLARIN community. This year, we are pleased to welcome 222 on-site participants and 115 online participants to the conference.

For this year's edition, 59 extended abstracts were submitted from a total of 22 different countries. After peer reviewing conducted by the members of the National Coordinators Forum, 42 papers were accepted (0.71 success rate): 16 oral presentations and 38 poster presentations. We have organised the 16 oral presentations (and the written proceedings) thematically into three categories: 'Resources and usage', 'CLARIN and beyond', and 'Design and construction of CLARIN infrastructure'.

We would like to acknowledge the work of the PC Committee, the National Coordinators and the other sub-reviewers in ensuring the quality of the papers.

A new addition to this year's conference is the Panel *Language Technology: AI, Industry, and Research Infrastructures in Collaboration*, which will address the challenges and opportunities of AI-powered language technologies in fostering collaboration between academia and industry.

We are also very pleased to have two keynote speakers. Andreas Baumann from the University of Vienna (Austria) will talk about *Language change as an epidemiological phenomenon: why interdisciplinary linguistic research inevitably needs open data*. Lonneke van der Plas from the Università della Svizzera italiana (Switzerland) will give a talk titled *Creativity and AI*. We hope that both these talks will provide us with inspiration and reflection in an era where language technology and artificial intelligence developments have become omnipresent.

We hope you enjoy your stay in Vienna, that you have an inspiring conference and enriching interactions with other members of the CLARIN community.

Cristina Grisot, CLARIN-CH
Programme Committee Chair
National Coordinators Forum

Thalassia Kontino
CLARIN ERIC

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A Collaborative Approach to the CLARIN Resource Families

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Abstract

This paper presents the new backend for the CLARIN Resource Families (CRF) initiative. After introducing the CRF initiative and laying out its primary aim, we present the functioning of this new backend, which uses a JSON-based workflow publicly accessible on GitHub. We then present the guidelines for working with the JSON files and describing the metadata. Finally, we discuss how the new workflow enables a collaborative approach to maintaining the families.

1 Introduction

A key aim of the CLARIN Resource Families (CRF) initiative (Lenardič & Fišer, 2022b) is the promotion of mature language resources and technologies (LRTs), such as language corpora, lexical resources, and tools, that are provided by national CLARIN consortia. The way in which the CRF initiative specifically contributes towards this goal is by offering access to manually curated overviews of LRTs, which are grouped together along thematic lines into ‘families’, such as *parliamentary corpora*, *tools of sentiment analysis*, *language models*, and so on. Importantly, all other key CLARIN services that automatically collate LRTs dispersed throughout the CLARIN infrastructure, such as the Virtual Language Observatory (Van Uytvanck et al., 2010, 2012), do not provide search facets that would allow researchers to pick out tools or resources belonging just to a particular family to the exclusion of everything else. The lack of such search options also follows in part from the fact that taxonomic categories like parliamentary corpora do not correspond to metadata components in CMDI (Windhouwer & Goosen, 2022). By providing the manually curated thematic groupings, the CRF initiative fills this gap in resource and tool discovery, and thereby facilitates the increased findability of CLARIN LRTs from the perspective of the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

When the CRF initiative launched in 2018, it consisted of just 4 corpus families, whose creation had a project-internal motivation at the time (Fišer et al., 2018).¹ However, the initiative soon proved popular especially amongst non-CLARIN-affiliated researchers in the (digital) humanities and social sciences, who often first encounter the CLARIN infrastructure through a CRF webpage.² Consequently, the CRF overviews have been iteratively expanded throughout the years with the addition of new families and LRTs, so that on 29 August 2025 there are 16 corpus families, 6 families of lexical resources, and 5 tool families, which together amount to 1598 manually curated LRTs.

Because of this expansion, there is a growing danger that the individual families will sooner or later become deprecated, especially since the upkeep of the families has thus far been largely a CLARIN ERIC-internal affair. We have therefore developed a new backend for the CRF overviews that is more geared towards collaboration than what was previously the case. In this paper, we present the functioning of this new backend and the ways in which involvement has now become possible.

The rest of the paper is in two parts. We first introduce the technical aspects of the new workflow and

¹Specifically, it was tied to workshops organised in the context of the CLARIN Plus project: <https://www.clarin.eu/content/factsheet-clarin-plus>.

²CRF webpages are typically the first result on Google for search terms like ‘parliamentary corpora’ or ‘parallel corpora’.

guidelines for using it (Section 2). We then present the ways in which collaborators can become involved as well as our own ongoing efforts for facilitating a greater degree of external involvement (Section 3).

2 The GitHub-based workflow for creating CRF overviews

2.1 Main characteristics

The new CRF backend is using a Python-based workflow on GitHub.³ The workflow takes as input a set of JSON files located in three folders (*corpora*, *lexical-resources* and *tools*) and then, with the help of Drupal, converts them to tabular HTML code that is periodically and automatically fed into the online overviews hosted at <https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families>. Each JSON file corresponds to a tabular row in the online overviews.

For instance, the workflow maps the JSON file for the Slovenian parliamentary corpus *siParl 4.0* (Pančur et al., 2024) shown in Figure 1 to HTML code that is then included as part of the Parliamentary corpora resource family.⁴ The organisation into subsections seen on the CRF webpages, such as the distinction between CLARIN-affiliated and CLARIN-external LRTs as well as the division between monolingual or multilingual corpora,⁵ is derived from name/value pairs such as the one for *Infrastructure* (line 10 in the figure; here concretely specified as CLARIN-internal) and the number of values in the *Language* array (specified just for Slovenian in line 6; hence, the JSON CRF entry for *Gigafida 2.0* is mapped to the Monolingual subgroup).

```

1 {
2   "Name": "Slovenian parliamentary corpus siParl 4.0",
3   "URL": "http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1936",
4   "Family": "Parliamentary corpora",
5   "Description": "The corpus contains Slovenian parliamentary debates from 1990 to
6     2022.\nThe corpus is encoded according to the <a href=\"
7     https://github.com/clarin-eric/parla-clarin/\">Parla-CLARIN</a> schema. In
8     terms of linguistic annotation, the part-of-speech tags, morphological
9     analyses, and syntactic parses in the corpus follow the <a href=\"
10    https://universaldependencies.org/sl/\">Universal Dependencies</a> framework
11    .\nThe corpus is available for download from the CLARIN.SI repository and
12    for online querying through the noSketch Engine concordancer.",
13   "Language": ["slv"],
14   "Licence": "CC BY 4.0",
15   "Size": ["13,233 texts", "1,223,250 utterances", "239,224,540 words",
16     "273,023,945 tokens"],
17   "Annotation": ["tokenised", "PoS-tagged", "lemmatised", "syntactically parsed",
18     "annotated for named entities"],
19   "Infrastructure": "CLARIN",
20   "Access": {
21     "Concordancer": "https://www.clarin.si/ske/#dashboard?corpname=siparl40",
22     "Download": "http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1936"
23   },
24   "Publication": "https://www.zotero.org/groups/562080/clarin/items/K24SGCXC"
25 }

```

Figure 1: A CRF JSON file.

The name/value pairs shown in the figure mostly recur throughout the corpus and lexical-resource families, but not the tool families, so potential users of the workflow are instructed to re-use an existing file in the repository whenever they begin to work on a particular family.

³<https://github.com/clarin-eric/clarin-resource-families/>

⁴<https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/parliamentary-corpora>

⁵From 2025 onwards, CRF no longer accepts submissions of CLARIN-external LRTs; however, the existing 'CLARIN external' subsections are for now being kept as legacy pages. If these are removed at one point (though the JSONs will not be lost due to GitHub's Version Control), then the 'Infrastructure' name-value pair (line 10 in the figure) might acquire another function, perhaps to specify the CLARIN centre associated with the LRT.

2.2 The guidelines for the workflow

For working with the GitHub-based workflow, a set of guidelines has been prepared by Lenardič and König (2025). In the first part, the guidelines present a beginner-friendly tutorial for editing and creating the JSON files. This tutorial assumes no prior knowledge of JSON syntax, so it also highlights rather trivial but often recurring JSON requirements, such as the obligatory use of $\backslash n$ operators for line or paragraph breaks and the usage and function of quotation marks.⁶

The second part of the guidelines, however, is more descriptive in nature, and is crucial for researchers both with or without experience in working with JSON syntax. This part lays out the requirements for the JSON values, some of which have been semi-standardised. For instance, the values for the *Language* array in line 6 in Figure 1 must be specified using the ISO 639-3 language set, which is in line with the recommendation of the CLARIN Standards and Interoperability Committee (Bański & Hedeland, 2022). The licence (line 7) is written using the canonical abbreviation (i.e., CC BY 4.0 in this case), although in the future another name–value pair might be added for licence URL, which would be especially helpful for less known licences such as CLARIN PUB.⁷ *Annotation* (line 9 in the figure) currently uses past-participle forms, but this may change in the future given that common annotation processes such as ‘named entity recognition’ do not trivially admit such forms.⁸ In any case, the aim of such recommendations is to ensure a high degree of descriptive metadata consistency between the CRF entries, which is particularly important now that external collaborators have become more involved in the initiative (Section 3).

Lastly, the guidelines pay particular attention to the value of the *Description* field (line 5 in the figure). A problem that commonly recurs across the CLARIN infrastructure is that deposited LRTs are described in various under-informative ways so that it is difficult to determine what kind of data the LRT actually consists of or what the functionality is in the case of tools, especially if the name of the LRT in question is opaque (see Lenardič & Fišer, 2022a, for concrete examples). According to the guidelines, the *Description* should focus on a brief recap of characteristics important from the perspective of the LRT’s (re-)usability,⁹ such as the time period (e.g., the publication date of the original written data), data sampling procedures and decisions, and any possible domain-specific features, such as the range of the participants’ ages and first languages in L2-learner corpora.¹⁰

2.3 Metadata curation

Importantly, CRF entries are rarely just repeats of the metadata records in the CLARIN repositories; rather, they also try to produce concise descriptions comparable across the resources and tools, as well as fill in potential gaps in metadata. The latter happens whenever any metadata are missing from the CMDI record of the deposited entry but turn out to be actually available elsewhere – typically in presentational materials related to the LRT or directly from the author(s).

As a by-product of this, the CRF initiative also contributes to ongoing curation efforts at the CLARIN ERIC level. This is done by maintaining a list of GitHub issues that spell out all the missing or unclear metadata identified whenever a new LRT is added to the CRF overviews or even when a new family is created. These GitHub tickets are assigned via the labelling system to national consortia whose representatives are then expected to resolve them.¹¹ While these issues were until recently collated in

⁶The paragraph breaks in the CRF descriptions do not necessarily correspond to the breaks in the ‘free-text’ description in the original metadata. Sometimes, the latter descriptions do not use paragraph breaks at all, or any other textual formatting either, in contrast to the CRF ones, which strive to be consistent about text placement and layout. Note that CRF descriptions are not meant to be copies of the descriptions in the repository entries, but rather serve as partially unified descriptions briefly recapping the main research-domain-specific characteristics of the data.

⁷<https://www.clarin.eu/content/licenses-and-clarin-categories#1-pub-language-resources>

⁸In case of future changes, we will strive to keep our recommendations in line with the results of ongoing European projects on metadata standardisation, such as ATRIUM, whose objective in WP 3 is amongst others ‘Metadata harmonisation and enrichment’ (<https://atrium-research.eu/work-packages/>).

⁹See <https://office.clarin.eu/v/CE-2022-2138-qualitative-depositing-recommendations.pdf> for further details.

¹⁰<https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/L2-corpora>

¹¹Thus far approximately 70% of the tickets have been closed, with many existing metadata records having also been updated directly because of this. This curation effort has also led to the systematic overhaul of deprecated metadata records of corpora belonging to the legacy LRT collection. An example of such metadata correction pertains to the *Croatian National Corpus* (Tadić, 2014), which initially had a non-working hyperlink to an access page where it had once been browsable.

a dedicated repository,¹² they are now going to be listed as part of the new workflow (Section 2.1) and linked to the JSON files themselves.

3 Involvement

3.1 Using the GitHub-based workflow

In addition to having a more robust technical backend in general, the new setup for the CRF also provides a much easier way for collaboration. With each item of each family being contained in its own JSON file in the GitHub repository, collaborators can simply use the normal git-based way of collaboration. They can fork the repository, edit the specific items that they want to contribute to, or suggest adding new ones or deleting deprecated ones. Then they can create a pull request, which will notify the maintainers of the CRF working at the central hub, who will in turn review the suggested changes. The accepted changes will immediately be picked up by the CI pipeline and will be reflected on the CLARIN website as well. As described in Section 2.3, the repository also stores open issues in GitHub tickets, so less tech-savvy users can simply create tickets with their suggested changes which will be picked up by the CRF maintainers.

3.2 Domain expertise via CLARIN K-centres

Having the possibility for easy collaboration also means that it makes sense now to involve domain experts in helping with the curation of the CRF. In collaboration with the Knowledge Infrastructure Committee,¹³ we have started reaching out to various CLARIN Knowledge Centres that seem to have an obvious connection to one of the families, such as the CKCMC centre¹⁴ for the CMC corpora family¹⁵ and the ACE CLARIN Knowledge Centre for Atypical Communication Expertise¹⁶ for the Corpora of Disordered Speech,¹⁷ and ask them for their assistance. As of 29 August 2025, nine K-centres have agreed to become maintainers, each of their own resource family. Such collaboration is beginning to ensure that the work of maintaining the CRF is shared over many people, which will help make the effort more sustainable in the long term.

Acknowledgments

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¹²<https://github.com/clarin-eric/resource-families-issues/issues>

¹³<https://www.clarin.eu/governance/knowledge-infrastructure-committee>

¹⁴<https://cmc-corpora.org/ckcmc/>

¹⁵<https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/cmc-corpora>

¹⁶<https://www.clarin.eu/k-centres/ace>

¹⁷<https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/corpora-disordered-speech>

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Govorjena slovenščina: Structured Conversational Data Collection through Online User Interface

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Abstract

Spoken language resources are crucial for linguistic research and speech technology development. However, compared to written corpora, spoken data—especially conversational speech—remain significantly underrepresented due to challenges in data collection, transcription, and legal compliance. This paper presents the Govorjena slovenščina platform, an online infrastructure offered as the CLARIN.SI service for speech data collection, provided by the University of Maribor. The platform is designed to facilitate the collection, transcription, and archiving of spoken Slovene. It addresses key challenges, including legal aspects of speech data collection, participant recruitment, metadata standardization, and transcription guidelines.

1 Introduction

Spoken language resources remain underrepresented compared to written resources, particularly when it comes to everyday human-human interaction. However, spoken data are essential to enable comprehensive linguistic descriptions, to capture variation in spoken language use, and to gain deeper theoretical insights into how humans interact and convey meaning. Furthermore, spoken corpora are crucial for the development of speech technologies, particularly automatic speech recognition and dialogue systems.

Large amounts of spoken data can be gained from sources such as parliament, media, YouTube, etc. However, such specialized datasets cannot substitute for a diverse range of spoken data, as there are substantial differences across domains. Research has shown that conversational data are in higher demand and used more frequently in linguistic research than context-governed data (Love et al., 2017). Yet, conversational data are still scarce and are the most challenging to collect. It takes significant effort to recruit and engage the broad network of field collaborators and speech donators needed to collect the data. Furthermore, a lot of people may hesitate to allow their speech to be recorded for personal reasons. Handling speech data is also complex, requiring a clearly defined policy and declaration on personal data protection. Additional challenges in speech data collection relate to the quality of recordings, which can be affected by background noise, microphone variations, and recording conditions. Ensuring speaker diversity in terms of age, gender, dialect, and sociolect is also crucial, but difficult to achieve.

This paper presents an online platform Govorjena slovenščina (Spoken Slovene)¹, launched in March 2025 as part of the LLM4DH project and financed by the Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency. The platform is designed to address the challenges of conversational data collection by providing scenarios and guidelines for field recording of conversational data, consent forms for speakers to allow the use of recordings, standardized forms for documenting information about speeches and speakers, remote submission of the data, secure and long-term archiving of the data, and unified guidelines for transcribing speech in Slovene. The platform is offered as the CLARIN.SI service for speech data collection, and is provided by the University of Maribor, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science as the CLARIN.SI consortium partner.

¹This work is licenced under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence. Licence details: <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

¹<https://govorjena-slovenscina.um.si/>

This paper focuses on challenges related to creating the Govorjena slovenščina platform, which are: (1) Resolving legal aspects of conversational speech data collection and distribution, (2) Attracting participating individuals, (3) Defining scenarios for who, where, what, and how to record, (4) Facilitating recording submission and standardizing the metadata on speakers and speeches, (5) Standardizing and supporting the transcription processes digitally.

2 Comparable Initiatives and Govorjena slovenščina

Traditional methods of recording speech (e.g., studio and field recordings) often struggle to capture substantial amounts of authentic spontaneous speech. Crowdsourcing, citizen science, and initiatives such as Games-With-A-Purpose and Collect4NLP present viable alternatives, but introduce challenges related to speaker motivation, quality control, and ethical considerations. To identify best practices, a review of 45 crowdsourcing initiatives led to the selection of three successful European projects—CorCenCC (Welsh), Anneta kõnet (Estonian), and Lahjoita puhetta (Finnish)—based on the number of speakers, purpose of data collection, and type of speech recorded. CorCenCC (2016–2020) collected over 11 million words, including 2.8 million words of spoken language, with 240,000 words recorded in private settings (Knight et al., 2020). The project’s mobile app (iOS, Android) facilitated participation, allowing speakers to upload consent forms and metadata in addition to their speech recordings (Knight et al., 2001), (Neale et al., 2017). Anneta kõnet (2022–2023) gathered over 100 hours of Estonian speech. Lahjoita puhetta (2020–2021) collected over 4,000 hours of Finnish speech within just a few months. Nearly 90 percent of the 220,000 recordings lasted between 10 seconds and 3 minutes, with an average duration of 30–60 seconds (Lindén et al., 2022).

All of the three were large-scale initiatives supported by national institutions and media organizations. In contrast, Govorjena slovenščina is an academic project with no budget for mobile application development or large-scale promotional activities. Its primary focus is not on data collection per se, but on preparing legal frameworks, developing infrastructure, maintaining unified standards, and conducting preliminary investigations into citizens’ intrinsic motivations to participate. The portal can be used by any individual researcher or project team from any institution who finds its solutions useful for their own data collection campaigns. There is no dedicated mobile recording application or similar platform; participants use their own recording devices, install an available recording software from the internet, and upload the recorded files themselves. Furthermore, the contribution of any single speaker is limited to a maximum of two hours of speech in order to ensure adequate data distribution. The project prioritizes longer recordings, with a minimum duration of five minutes and a maximum of ninety minutes, to allow conversations to develop naturally, give speakers time to relax, and provide sufficient contextual material for higher-level analyses such as those focusing on semantics or pragmatics.

3 Platform Govorjena slovenščina

This section outlines solutions for key challenges in creating the Govorjena slovenščina portal.

3.1 Legal Aspects

Legal experts in personal data protection from APHAI were hired to define a personal data protection protocol in accordance with European Union law. Their initial findings were that a speech recording of an individual is considered personal data; that consent from the speaker is the most appropriate legal basis; that the processing of portal users’ data for reward purposes requires a separate legal basis from that used for processing the recordings themselves; and that spontaneous speech recordings collected on the portal are unlikely to qualify as copyrighted works.

Furthermore, the legal experts prepared the ‘Privacy Policy Statement’, which is published on the portal, as well as the ‘Consent for the Publication of Speech Recordings and Related Personal Data’ and the ‘Terms of Contribution of Recordings and Contest Participation’, both also available through the portal.

3.2 Attracting Participating Individuals

As the Govorjena slovenščina portal lacks the financial resources for a marketing campaign, we have placed greater emphasis on identifying intrinsic motivational factors for participant engagement. On the homepage, we therefore highlight potential intrinsic motivators, such as donating speech to preserve samples of their language as part of the cultural heritage; supporting the development of digital tools for the Slovene language and its dialects; and supporting research on child speech. Furthermore, we offer simple, yet practical small rewards such as memory card or headphones for participants who submit appropriate recordings with a total duration of 50 minutes.

Second, we try to establish trust in us as data keepers, as this is essential that speakers feel confident in contributing their speech data, knowing it will be handled responsibly, securely, and in ways that respect their privacy and serve the broader public interest. We offer a clear presentation of how the recordings will be used and how the data will be anonymized. We include information about the people responsible for the portal. We publish popular science writings about speech to share our knowledge.

Third, we place particular emphasis on providing clear task descriptions to prevent the loss of potential contributors due to uncertainty about how to approach the task. We aim to deliver concise, clear, and comprehensible instructions, we outline potential recording scenarios and suggest speech topics.

Fourth, we prioritized a clear, user-friendly, and visually appealing web page design with an engaging and playful aesthetic. The design includes illustrative graphics and authentic speech examples from previously collected conversational data. Ongoing improvements include adding motivational videos to encourage participation and reduce uncertainty.

The usability of the platform has been critically evaluated by experts in linguistics and design; however, its systematic testing remains a future challenge.

3.3 Recording Scenarios

Conversational data is often categorized in a limited manner. Existing classifications typically distinguish between direct and distanced contact, between dialogue and multilogue, and domains such as face-to-face conversation, telephone conversation, interview, business transaction (Oostdijk, 2000). In the Slovene reference corpus GOS (Verdonik et al., 2013), conversational data domains were defined, such as conversations between friends or within families. However, such classifications offer limited guidance to contributors regarding suitable conversational form and topics.

To address this limitation, we have placed particular emphasis on providing more illustrative suggestions for participants, both in terms of speech genre and topic selection. The Govorjena slovenščina platform defines recommended speech genres, including interviews, discussions, instructions, narrations, explanations, and casual conversations. The suggested speech topics cover a broad range of everyday subjects, such as hobbies, sports, music, travel, technology, food, health, and the environment. Additionally, contributors are advised explicitly to select only topics they are comfortable sharing publicly, ensuring that participants are fully aware of the public nature of their recordings.

Special attention is given to technical guidelines to ensure high-quality recordings. These include instructions on minimizing background noise, positioning the recording device correctly, adjusting the recording settings, and the option to submit a test recording in case of uncertainty.

3.4 Submission and Metadata Standardization

The submission of recordings is facilitated through an online interface, which categorizes users into three distinct roles: participating citizens, administrators, and transcribers. Participating citizens—individuals submitting recordings—are required to register before contributing. For each submission, they must complete metadata forms detailing information about both the speaker and the recorded speech, upload an image of the speaker's signed consent, and submit the recording. The administrators are responsible for overseeing the data and recordings. They have the ability to download and approve submissions, edit the metadata associated with recordings and speakers, and export summarized spreadsheet data pertaining to registered users, recordings, and speakers. Transcribers are tasked with processing the submitted recordings. They can download audio files and upload transcriptions, which may be provided in both literal and

standardized forms as separate entries.

Participating citizens are required to collect metadata on both speakers and recorded speeches alongside the recordings. The categorization of these metadata is based on the Slovene reference speech corpus GOS 2.0 (Verdonik, Dobrovoljc, et al., 2024), with additional metadata fields incorporated to address requirements identified across various disciplines utilizing such data. The final list of speaker metadata includes: transcription ID; recording ID (and source ID); corpus ID; personal ID; speaker order; gender; age; first language; information on bilingualism; register; dialect group; dialect; degree of dialect retention; education; parent or guardian education in the case of minors; permanent residence (settlement, region, and country); childhood residence (settlement, region, and country); other residences (settlement, region, and country); and whether the speech is atypical and, if so, its description. The final list of speech metadata includes: transcription ID; recording ID (and source ID); corpus ID; language of speech; modality of recording; a manual description of the recorded situation; date; source; text region; genre; speech type; channel; number of speakers; keywords; a description of the recording device; recording location; original recording format; a manual rating of recording quality; length of the recording; and any additional field notes.

The online interface for data submission is built as a Flask-based web application, and is available under the domain of the University of Maribor². The system uses a database for all user data and metadata. At each edit, change log files are stored, enabling backtracking of all the changes. The uploaded files are stored safely, separately on the server. The platform source code will be available by the end of the project in the CLARIN.SI GitHub³.

3.5 Transcription standardization and digital support

The transcription guidelines utilized in previous Slovene speech collection campaigns (Verdonik et al., 2013); (Verdonik, Bizjak, et al., 2024); (Verdonik, Dobrovoljc, et al., 2024) have been revised, updated, and published systematically on the Govorjena slovenščina platform⁴ in a clearly structured format. The guidelines are organized into sections covering tools, segmentation, literal transcription, standardized transcription, punctuation, transcription specifics, additional marks, and frequent mistakes. The most recommended transcription tools are Transcriber (Barras et al., 2001) or EXMARaLDA (Schmidt & Wörner, 2014), with segmentation into utterances advised for clarity. The transcription Standard follows an established tradition in Slovene speech transcription, employing a dual-mode approach: literal transcription, where the words are transcribed exactly as pronounced, and standardized transcription, where each word form is recorded in its standardized form (Verdonik, Bizjak, et al., 2024). Punctuation is required, with uppercase letters used at the beginning of sentences. Speech is segmented into semantically coherent units (statements or sentences). In the case of overlapping speech, the segment is separated down to the word level, regardless of statement boundaries. Special transcription tags are designated for specific cases, including incomprehensible speech, laughter, crying, non-verbal sounds, foreign language segments, and anonymization of personal data when necessary.

4 Conclusion

Govorjena slovenščina is an academic platform for the systematic collection, transcription, and archiving of spoken Slovene, addressing the need for diverse, high-quality conversational corpora. The platform addresses legal frameworks, unified standards, participant recruitment, data submission, and transcription guidelines, but lacks funding for mobile app development, large-scale promotion, or citizen mobilization. So far, it has yielded 5 hours of speech for ROG-dialog and 3 hours for Krohot, recorded by hired students to ensure balanced data. Occasional promotion via social media and a radio podcast received no response; a targeted communication strategy is planned for autumn 2025. Recordings will be available under Creative Commons licences; however, downloaders' contact information must be retained for possible notifications regarding data rectification or erasure requests. Through its open, standards-driven

²<https://govorjena-slo-portal.ietk.um.si/>

³<https://github.com/clarinsi>

⁴<https://govorjena-slovenscina.um.si/transkribiranje/>

design and collaborative approach, Govorjena slovenščina supports the sustainable growth and utility of spoken Slovene resources for research and technology development.

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How to make research software FAIR: building the SOFAIR dataset with the help of the CLARIN-PL Inforex annotation tool

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Abstract

The paper describes the collaboration of CLARIN-PL with the SoFAIR project in building a gold standard multidisciplinary dataset of scientific texts annotated with software mentions and relations between them. The process involved text collection from the CORE database, automatic pre-annotation by the SoftCite software mention recognizer, and manual annotation performed within the Inforex annotation system. The produced dataset includes 504 texts from 18 disciplines, annotated with about 9000 software mentions (grouped into 10 types) and about 2200 relations between them. It is available in TEI XML format under the CC-BY license. Creating such a resource was essential from the perspective of the SoFAIR project goals, which encompass the promotion of research reproducibility and data reuse, as well as the improvement of software extraction tools and the evaluation of language models. At the same time, it gave CLARIN-PL an opportunity to test and adapt their Inforex tool for the purposes of a complex annotation task.

1 Introduction

Proclaiming the famous FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) for the sharing of digital objects set a milestone in the open science paradigm (Wilkinson, Dumontier, et al., 2016). Originally, FAIR principles were coined to advance sharing of data, but recently they have been extended to all products that can facilitate research and study, such as tools, software, teaching materials, etc. One of such initiatives is the SoFAIR project¹, 'Making Software FAIR: A machine-assisted workflow for the research software lifecycle funded within the EC CHISTERA program. The project aims to foster the reusability of research software by supporting their proper documentation, citation and discoverability. In this respect, the SoFAIR project follows in the footsteps of the earlier SoftCite project (Du et al., 2022) which also focused on proper citation of software in scientific texts, as well as developing software mention recognition tools. The results of the prior project were the SoftCite Software Mentions Recognizer (Lopez et al., 2021) and the SoftCite dataset of scientific texts annotated with software mention types and relations (Du et al., 2021). Continuing the mission of the SoftCite project, the SoFAIR project plans to further develop software recognition, classification, and extraction tools. For this reason, scientific texts annotated with software mentions are key research data. In the first stage of the project, the SoFAIR team used the SoTA SoftCite dataset. However, this resource is already 10 years old and has limited domain coverage (Life Sciences and Economics). To achieve the goals of the SoFAIR project, a more recent and domain-variant dataset was needed.

The task of creating a new gold standard dataset was sub-contracted to the CLARIN-PL team due to their experience and expertise in carrying out similar tasks. CLARIN-PL brings together highly qualified linguistic annotators who possess extensive knowledge and practical experience in creating and analyzing language corpora. In addition, CLARIN-PL is equipped with modern tools and technologies that support the annotation process, enabling efficient, effective, and accurate processing of large data sets. The manual annotation requirements were quite extensive, largely determined by the need to make the new dataset comparable to the SoftCite dataset, which was used as a training and testing dataset at the start of the SoFAIR project. Thus, annotation was expected to be carried out in a 2+1 model (two annotators

¹<https://sofair.org/about/>

supervised by a superannotator), generally following the SoftCite guidelines². This involved verifying automatic pre-annotations, annotating every software mention and assigning a type to it, and establishing a relation between mentions where applicable. Moreover, the annotation tool needed to comply with the TEI XML format.

There are many annotation tools on the market, such as INCEpTION (Klie et al., 2018), WebAnno (Eckart de Castilho et al., 2016), Doccano (Nakayama et al., 2018), brat (Stenetorp et al., 2012), (see the extensive survey in (Neves & Ševa, 2019)). Some of them offer the functionalities mentioned above, yet they would require adaptations for the purposes of the SoFAIR project. CLARIN-PL decided to employ their own custom-designed Inforex annotation system (Marcinićzuk & Oleksy, 2019). Inforex enables the integration of automatic pre-annotation with manual annotation within a 2+1 framework. A similar method was used in the morphological annotation of the Polish part of the NTU Sherlock Holmes Multilingual Corpus³. Moreover, Inforex supports the TEI XML format. The tool is freely available as a web service for registered users via the CLARIN-PL webpage⁴.

2 Setting the scene for manual annotation

The starting corpus of research papers for annotation was collected pseudo-randomly from the CORE database from across 18 discrete disciplines. The domains were chosen to provide a representative selection from natural sciences, social sciences, business and management, and digital humanities. Detailed selection criteria were used. The key criterion was the Open Access status of the paper guaranteed by its full-text version published under Public Domain, CC-O or CC-BY license, while its PDF version available in the CORE service. This was important because the designed dataset is also meant to be made available under an open license. Another requirement was that the TEI XML document could be produced from PDF using Grobid, which ensures that the PDF has usable text layers. The papers were supposed to be in English and 3 to 15 pages. To expand the coverage of the document domain compared to the SoftCite dataset, papers were searched by domain using Wikidata concepts as key words.

In the next step, the corpus was automatically pre-annotated (with software mentions) using the SoftCite Software Mentions Recognizer (Lopez et al., 2021). Pre-annotation involves automatically annotating blank documents using the latest model which provides the best possible annotations at the time. Every software mention is assigned a type out of the following four types: software, version, url and creator. The SoftCite software outputs PDF-based XML-TEI-like files with predicted annotations.

The collection of texts provided to CLARIN-PL consisted of more than 3500 papers including more than 30k pre-annotations. Out of this set, the super-annotator selected papers for 10 iterations of manual annotation. Each iteration had one dominating scientific discipline, some share of documents for which the pre-annotation tool did not find any mentions, and shorter texts were preferred over longer ones to facilitate human annotation. The number of texts per iteration was growing starting from 20 and reaching 85 as a maximum. This was motivated by choosing shorter texts in the later iterations and with the growing experience of annotators in their work. The growing number of texts also resulted in an increase in the disciplines covered in a single iteration, from 1 to 6.

The selected texts were imported into the Inforex annotation system, which supports the TEI XML format in terms of the basic document content and structure (high-level structure for TEI document). However, to interpret pre-annotations, a special script needed to be written that would map the annotation information provided in the TEI format to the database annotation schema used by the Inforex. The script processes the files and adds the pre-annotation layer. We also defined a new annotation set in the Inforex for correct TEI attribute mapping. Next, each text could be displayed in a structured simple text format (titles, paragraphs, etc.) including pre-annotations. A similar script was also developed for the subsequent export of data from Inforex. A distinguishing feature of this script was its capacity to also account for the inclusion of relations between software mentions (pre-annotated texts did not provide such type of information). This approach reduces the complexity of similar tasks (such as adaptation to other schemas)

²https://github.com/softcite/softcite_dataset_v2/blob/master/annotation_guidelines_tei_xml.md

³<https://clarin-pl.eu/dspace/handle/11321/667>

⁴<https://clarin-pl.eu/tools/inforex>

in the future.

3 Manual annotation

The actual manual annotation was preceded by a study of the SoftCite guidelines by the annotation team. They define the notion of a software mention as well as its ten types such as: bibr (bibliographic reference), language, publisher, publisher person, software, software component, software environment, software implicit, version, and url. It is a longer list than in preannotations, since we have a subtype of publisher and three sub-types of software. On the other hand, creator is absent, while bibr and language appear. This complicated the annotators' work and reduced agreement with automatic annotation, for example, they had to delete all automatic 'software' labels if a more specific subtype applied.

Manual annotation was performed in a 2+1 model in Inforex. Both annotators read and independently annotated all texts from every iteration, analysing whole texts, not just preannotated fragments. Next, the super-annotator compared their choices and produced the final annotation. This applied to both the annotated fragments and the types ascribed to them. In the subsequent step, the 'correspond' relation between the annotated software mentions was added, where applicable. The relation is established between the two mentions within the same text that are referentially related to each other, such as, for instance, the name of a publisher to the name of the software published, the name of the component of the software to the name of the software itself, and the url under which one can download or read about a given software to the software itself. This task also ran in two stages: first, each of the annotators added correspond relations to the previously created final annotation, and then the super-annotator resolved inconsistencies and produced the final annotation with the agreed-upon correspond relations.

The Inforex system's analytics module facilitated the calculation of inter-annotator agreement (IAA), the agreement between annotators and final annotation (AFA), the agreement between automatic pre-annotation and annotators (PAA), and between automatic pre-annotation and final annotation (PFA). The calculations were performed both on an ongoing basis (after each iteration) and at the end of the annotation process. PSA was used as a measure of agreement (Hripcsak & Rothschild, 2005). The results are presented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Averaged results of calculating different types of annotation agreement of SOFAIR dataset

Our findings show that the manual annotations exhibited consistency and demonstrated a high level of agreement with the final annotations. This applies both to the annotation boundaries and to the categories assigned to them. The agreement with pre-annotation did not exceed the 0.5 threshold, indicating that the automatic pre-annotation tool only provided a partial aid to manual annotation. This sub-optimal level of compliance is primarily attributable to the fact that the automatic pre-annotation tool failed to identify a significant number of software mentions.

4 Results and conclusions

The gold-standard dataset built comprises more than five hundred texts from 18 scientific disciplines annotated with more than 9k software mentions and more than 2k relations between them. It is available under the CC-BY license in the Github repository⁵. The produced dataset is crucial from the perspective of the SoFAIR project goals, since it can be used as new training-testing data for language models and software mention recognition and classification tools, such as the Softcite Software Mentions Recognizer. The SoFAIR dataset has significant potential for future applications, particularly in the development of new metrics for research evaluation and in the automation of software mention extraction. It offers high precision, detailed metadata, and structured relationships that automated methods cannot reliably capture.

More research infrastructure projects are already seeing great potential in the developed dataset and the standards produced. The LUMEN project⁶, which envisions creating a software catalog and doing similar work finding software mentions, could benefit significantly from such annotated data and the experience of the teams working on SoFAIR. Another such project is GRAPHIA⁷, where activities are heavily based on the use of graph technology and the creation of AI-based modules. Qualitative datasets are the foundation of this kind of work. A recent example is the SCIROs project, which studies Open Science in the Humanities and Social Sciences (SSH). The project intends to use a Cost-Benefit Analysis framework to measure the impact of research software mentions on the development of Research Open Infrastructures.

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Putting things on top of other things

The ZuMult platform for multimodal corpora and its ecosystem

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Abstract

We present ZuMult, a platform for multimodal corpora and its ecosystem. ZuMult has a flexible three-layer architecture that enables integration with different types of backend, and development of frontend applications tailored to the needs of highly diverse user groups. The paper puts a special emphasis on the way that ZuMult is built upon existing best practices, standards and technologies arguing that such an “ecosystem” makes it easier to integrate the technology with different workflows and technical environments.

1 Introduction

ZuMult (Zugänge zu multimodalen Korpora gesprochener Sprache / Access to multimodal corpora of spoken language, Fandrych et al. 2023a, <https://zumult.org>) is a corpus platform for accessing multimodal (oral, audiovisual) corpora. It was developed in a project funded by the German Science Foundation between 2018 and 2022 as a flexible, versatile three-layer architecture allowing different types of data sources (e.g. file system, Relational Database) in the backend and different types of user-group specific adaptations in the frontend. The latter point is of special relevance because audiovisual corpora are used across a large spectrum of disciplines, ranging from interactional linguistics over dialectology to oral history studies or qualitative social sciences, and the respective user groups have highly differing needs and expectations regarding access and usage of audiovisual data (Fandrych et al. 2016). In the project phase, applications were developed with the user group of language teachers and learners in mind. Currently, public instances of ZuMult exist at the Archive for Spoken German (<https://zumult.ids-mannheim.de>), where the platform provides access to the largest corpora of spoken German (such as the Forschungs- und Lehrkorpus Gesprochenes Deutsch, Research and Teaching Corpus of Spoken German, FOLK, Schmidt 2016, the corpus ‘Deutsch Heute’, Brinckmann et al. 2008, documenting regional variation of spoken German, and the corpus ‘Gesprochene Wissenschaftssprache Kontrastiv’, GeWiss, , Fandrych et al. 2012, documenting spoken academic language in different situations and language constellations), and at the University of Texas in Austin (<https://tgdp-zumult.la.utexas.edu/>), where the data of the Texas German Dialect project can be accessed via ZuMult (Boas et al., submitted). Further public instances are under construction for the French ESLO corpus (Enquêtes Sociolinguistiques à Orléans, archived at HumaNum, Schmidt 2025), and a number of multimodal and multisensorial corpora at the University of Duisburg-Essen (see section 4 below). As this paper intends to show, ZuMult can be viewed as a piece of technology that both contributes to an infrastructure such as CLARIN, and profits from other technology already integrated into or developed alongside the infrastructure. In the words of Monty Python (1970), ZuMult is thus a “thing that is put on top of other things”, and other things can be put on top of it (see figure 1 in the appendix). The remainder of the paper will explain in more detail what this means: Section 2 briefly sketches the most important features of ZuMult from a user’s point of view. Section 3 then goes into more technical detail, emphasizing the interplay of different tools, standards, and services that underlies the architecture. Section 4, finally, gives an outlook on current and future development of the platform.

2 Browsing, Selecting, Visualising and Querying multimodal corpora

Generally speaking, a multimodal (spoken, audiovisual) corpus platform like ZuMult transfers functionality of written corpus platforms and extends it with functionality that is needed for and specific

to the work with audiovisual language data and their transcriptions and annotations (Schmidt/Frick 2025). Most importantly, this means that such platforms need to enable users:

- to browse through (read, listen to, view) the primary (audio/video) and secondary (transcribed/annotated) data,
- to select those (and only those) datasets that are relevant to their research questions,
- to visualise selected aspects of the data for qualitative analysis, and
- to carry out, and possibly quantify, queries on transcriptions and their annotations with the option to re-contextualise query results (i.e. view them in the context of the underlying transcript and/or recording).

Metadata (on speech events and participating speakers) can guide or supplement all of these processes (see Frick/Schmidt (subm.) for a comprehensive overview).

ZuMult’s architecture is designed in such a way that the required information (e.g.: What corpora are in the platform? What’s in corpus XY? Can I get transcript #123? What is the result of query Z?) can be delivered from one and the same backend to different frontends (“applications”), which are optimised for a specific usage scenario or user group.

For example, the application ZuMal (Fandrych et al. 2023b) supports the selection of suitable material for language teaching through an interface displaying selectors for relevant metadata and so-called “measures” reflecting the difficulty or degree of orality of a given dataset.

This material can then be inspected more closely using the application ZuViel (Schmidt et al. 2023), an interactive transcript viewer which offers different, synchronised views (e.g. line transcripts, musical score transcript, lemma frequency list, density viewer, video with subtitles) of a transcript in which parameters (such as: display of transcribed vs. normalized forms, visualisation of speech rate) can be set by users according to their preferred perspective on the data.

With the application ZuRecht (Frick et al. 2023), the platform also includes an interface for CQP queries to a corpus, the results of which are displayed in a KWIC concordance with special features (e.g. audio playback for KWIC lines, inclusion of video stills, see Frick/Schmidt 2025) for audiovisual data.

CQP-Suche

Suche mittels der Corpus Query Language (CQP)

Bitte geben Sie Ihren CQP-Suchausdruck ein

[Beispiele](#)
[XML](#)

Ergebnisse

für die Suchanfrage `[(norm="on")][(norm="of")][(norm="über|auf|above)"]` (in EXMARaLDA-DemoCorpus)

Insgesamt: 51

Ergebnis	Corpus	Speaker	KWIC Concordance	Media
1	EXB_Anne_Will	AW	... damit sich ratzfatz auf Seite eins katapultiert ...	▶ 🔊 📄 🖼️
2	EXB_Anne_Will	GL	... könnten doch mal über das Wahlrecht nachdenken ...	▶ 🔊 📄 🖼️
3	EXB_Anne_Will	GL	... was die Bildzeitung auf Seite eins Gut ...	▶ 🔊 📄 🖼️
4	EXB_Anne_Will	AW	... Sie wollten nur auf die Seite eins ...	▶ 🔊 📄 🖼️
5	EXB_Anne_Will	GL	... bei der Bildzeitung auf Seite eins gekommen ...	▶ 🔊 📄 🖼️
6	EXB_Anne_Will	GL	... die gesamte Zeit über Hartz vier Sätze ...	▶ 🔊 📄 🖼️
7	EXB_Anne_Will	HG	... da natürlich nicht auf die Schulter klopfen ...	▶ 🔊 📄 🖼️
8	EXB_Beckhams	VIC	... really good friends. on top of everything. W do ...	▶ 🔊 📄 🖼️
		0041	VIC (0:3s) You know he was sitting there with his family and/ and I really liked that.	
		0042	VIC And he is a very kind (0:5s) person.	
		0043	VIC And we/ we are really good friends. on top of everything.	
		0044	PAR W/ do/ what's been the lowest?	
		0045	PAR That's the/ the nice part of the marriage.	
9	EXB_HartAberFair	RP	... Dieselpreisentwicklung natürlich auch auf ah uns ausgewirkt ...	▶ 🔊 📄 🖼️
10	EXB_HartAberFair	FP	... sich die Dieselpreisenerhöhung auf Sie aus ? Also ...	▶ 🔊 📄 🖼️
11	EXB_HartAberFair	FB	... ich im Winter über und jetzt ist ...	▶ 🔊 📄 🖼️

Figure 1: The result of a CQP query in ZuMult, displayed as a KWIC concordance with links to audio/video and still images in the concordance

3 ZuMult and its ecosystem: Things on top of other things

The starting point for ZuMult was experience gained in the development of EXMARaLDA (Schmidt/Wörner 2014) and the Database for Spoken German (Schmidt 2014) as well as in the compilation of the corpora FOLK and GeWiss. ZuMult reuses ideas and concepts that have proven

fruitful in long-standing application of these resources and attempts to add and improve things that have turned out to be missing, deficient or hard to use. On a more concrete level, ZuMult reuses EXMARaLDA’s data model and API with its extensive interoperability, meaning that, from the outset, ZuMult is built on top of a technology compatible with the most widely used audiovisual annotation tools (ELAN, Praat, EXMARaLDA, FOLKER, CLAN, Transcriber and others) and formats for multi-layer annotation of audiovisual data (Schmidt et al. 2009). More recently, this interoperability has been extended to output formats of ASR technology (e.g. the JSON format of OpenAI Whisper). On top of this level of exchangeability of tool formats sits a standardisation via “ISO 24624:2016 Language resource management — Transcription of spoken language” (ISO 2016) which itself rests on top of the long-standing efforts of the Text Encoding Initiative (Schmidt 2011).

Beyond the level of formats, ZuMult is compatible with (and thus can be made to sit on top of) workflows developed for larger corpus projects. A ZuMult integration has been established as a final step of the workflows for the ongoing compilation of FOLK (Schmidt 2016) and the TGDA (Boas et al., in print), and, most importantly, is now also an element in the Git-based continuous integration (CI) workflows described in Ferger et al. (2023). In the latter form, using the ZuMult platform also becomes an option in more dynamic setups, i.e. contexts in which corpora do not follow a strict release schedule, but are built up in smaller research projects in a fluid iteration of data collection, curation and analysis. Integration into different environments is further facilitated by using Maven and Docker as distribution methods for the code.

ZuMult’s query capabilities (see figure 2 in the appendix) are developed on top of the Multi Tier Annotation Framework (MTAS, Brouwer et al. 2016) which itself is built on top of the industry level search software Lucene. MTAS can read and index transcription files adhering to ISO 24624:2016, and make them queryable via the Corpus Query Processor Language (CQP, Evert et al. 2022), which has been identified (Fandrych et al. 2016) as the most promising candidate for a query language that is both widely known and suitable for the complexity of spoken language data.

Other components of ZuMult also rest on top of existing technology: For instance, for fine-grained multimodal analysis, transcript excerpts are force-aligned with their audio on the phoneme level using the CLARIN service WebMaus (Kisler et al. 2017) and still images extracted from the corresponding video file via the FFMPEG suite (<https://ffmpeg.org/>). This is supplemented with an F0 pitch contour extracted from the audio using Praat scripts and visualised as an SVG drawing.

Figure 2: A micro-view of a transcript excerpt in ZuMult: phoneme-level alignment achieved via MAUS web service, pitch contour calculated via Praat

Last but not least, data published on an instance of the ZuMult platform can be directly integrated into the CLARIN infrastructure. This is the case, for example, when the platform obtains its actual data (transcripts, audio, video, metadata) from a CLARIN repository, as is the case in the ongoing development of a ZuMult instance for the ESLO corpus (Schmidt 2025) which is tied to the Cocoon *CLARIN Annual Conference Proceedings, 2025*

platform of the French HumaNum infrastructure (<https://cocoon.huma-num.fr/>). Conversely, ZuMult can serve CLARIN protocols for Federated Content Search (FCS) and become an endpoint for an FCS aggregator. This will be demonstrated on the EXMARaLDA demo corpus.

4 Current and future developments

Current development of ZuMult at the University of Duisburg-Essen focuses on:

- a tighter integration of ZuMult with the CI pipelines described in Ferger et al. (2023), especially with respect to the automation of complex annotation tasks in multilingual data,
- an optimization of the distribution of the platform, most importantly including a mavenization and dockerization of the code so that effort for further installations of the platform is reduced, the software becomes more sustainable, and reproducibility is facilitated,
- an extension of functionality towards massively multimodal and multisensorial data, i.e. interactions recorded on video from multiple perspectives, annotated for gestures, facial expression and other bodily manifestations of communication, and supplemented with time-series sensor data like mobile eye tracking glasses or motion capturing devices,
- an exploration of interfacing ZuMult with the R platform to exploit this framework's strengths in statistical analysis and data visualisation.

We expect to be able to showcase results of these developments by the time of the conference, using examples from human-machine interaction data collected in the context of the ZAT project (Centre for Assistive Technology: <https://zat.nrw/>).

Conclusion

Figure 3: ZuMult and the things on top of which it is built

As a piece of technology, ZuMult is built on top of lots of other pieces of technology which, in turn, are also built on top of each other, and it can be integrated in and with other solutions. The fact that the spread of best practices and the establishment of standards for the relevant technology is advancing, and that ties between such solutions are strengthening, makes an undertaking such as ZuMult easier to realise, easier to maintain and, hopefully, relevant to a larger community of users. In our current work, we observe especially that, compared to large “monolithic” solutions, building a platform with such a modular approach, makes it more manageable also for smaller projects to adapt and run it locally. In the medium-term, this may have a positive effect on the community’s ability to contribute to an infrastructure like CLARIN.

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The Language Data Commons of Australia: Towards a Nationally Distributed Research Infrastructure

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Abstract

The Language Data Commons of Australia (LDaCA) is a national project supported by the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy which aims to establish a nationally distributed research infrastructure for languages in Australia and its region. This paper outlines progress to date and plans for future development, including potential synergies with CLARIN.

1 Introduction

Australia is a massively multilingual country, in one of the world's most linguistically diverse regions. Significant collections of this intangible cultural heritage have been amassed, including collections of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander languages, Australian Englishes, and regional languages of the Pacific, as well as collections important for cyber-security and for emergency communication. The Language Data Commons of Australia ([LDaCA](#)) is integrating this existing work into a national research infrastructure while also securing at-risk collections and improving access to under-utilised collections. LDaCA is thus ensuring that these invaluable resources will be available for analysis and reuse in the future, and that they will be managed in a culturally, ethically and legally appropriate manner guided by FAIR and CARE principles. The project aims to make nationally significant language data available for academic and non-academic use while providing a model for ensuring continued access with appropriate community control.

LDaCA is led by The University of Queensland (Brisbane, Australia). The project is part of the Australian Research Data Commons ([ARDC](#)) HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons ([HASS&I RDC](#)) with co-investment currently from the following institutions and organisations: AARNet, ARDC, Australian National University, Batchelor Institute of Indigenous Tertiary Education First Languages Australia, Queensland University of Technology Digital Observatory, The University of Melbourne, The University of Queensland, The University of Sydney, and The University of Western Australia. LDaCA commenced in 2021 with the initial phase of funding through the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy ([NCRIS](#)) taking it through to mid-2024 (HIR001). It is now in the first year of a second phase of development through to 2028 ([HIR024](#)).

In this presentation, we first outline the five key streams of activity within the LDaCA project, and then briefly survey what has been accomplished to date in each of these streams. This is followed by a summary of plans for the next three years. We then reflect on potential points of synergy between LDaCA and CLARIN. We conclude with brief remarks about the diverse range of stakeholders we are engaging in the development of LDaCA.

2 Overview of LDaCA

To deliver on the above-mentioned aims, the LDaCA project is executed within the following five key activity streams:

1. Develop the social and technical foundations for a national, distributed archival repositories ecosystem, including:
 - a. shared, collaborative data governance and standards framework;
 - b. shared data access, authentication and authorisation policies, procedures and processes;
 - c. shared technical infrastructure for curation and storage of language data;
 - d. shared technical infrastructure for collection and annotation of language data.
2. Continue securing vulnerable and nationally significant collections of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander languages, Indigenous languages in Australia's Pacific region, (varieties of) Australian English and migrant languages, and sign languages of Australia and its region.
3. Develop a national portal for accessing and repurposing language data of significance to researchers and communities, including data held in GLAM institutions, including libraries, archives and museums, as well as language collections held in distributed archival repositories supported through LDaCA.
4. Establish an integrated analytics environment for researchers to create fully described, reproducible research on written, spoken, multimodal and signed text in accordance with Open Science principles, and aligned with community expectations for research of practical benefit.
5. Provide training and develop resources for researchers and communities to support best practice in accessing, analysing and archiving language data in line with FAIR and CARE principles.

Achievements to date in each of these activity streams are briefly outlined in the following subsections.

2.1 Social and Technical Foundations

LDaCA has built [archiving infrastructure](#) based on the Oxford Common File Layout standard and the RO-Crate metadata and packaging standard. This work has led to discussion of basic data governance standards which in turn has led to the publication of the Protocols for Implementing Long-term Archival Repositories Services ([PILARS](#)). Access and authorisation are handled by the REMs resource management package and CILogon alongside the facilities of the Australian Access Federation (Sefton et al., 2023; Foley et al., 2024). A metadata profile, based on schema.org principles and including categories from the OLAC metadata scheme (Bird & Simons, 2001), has been developed and is implemented in a tool for editing metadata to create RO-Crates (Crate-O).

2.2 Collections

LDaCA currently provides access to nine data collections with an additional six collections at various points on the path to being accessible. Preliminary work on adding further collections has also begun. LDaCA is committed to ensuring that collections are made available in ways that meet community expectations following the maxims of 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary' and 'respectful sharing'. Implementing both FAIR and CARE (Carroll et al., 2020) principles is particularly important when working with Indigenous language data (Sefton et al., 2023), and LDaCA is developing CAREful FAIRness Principles for Indigenous Data Governance to ensure its collections are managed and made available in ways that are appropriate to Indigenous community expectations (McLellan & Fewster, 2024). These include ensuring appropriate mechanisms for implementing Indigenous Cultural and Intellectual Property (ICIP) are in place. Publications which cite these collections have begun to appear (e.g. Clews, 2024; Musgrave, 2025; Sheard, 2024; Travis, 2024; Willoughby et al., 2024).

2.3 Portal

LDaCA provides access to data via a portal application (Oni) which is built to display metadata from RO-Crates with indexing of relevant fields and capability for faceted search. The app can be used with any data packaged with RO-Crates which means that metadata from GLAM institutions can be reworked into the more general LDaCA tech stack and access to their material enabled by Oni. This means that the LDaCA data portal will be able to provide federated access to materials distributed across different archival repositories that have been implemented through different (proprietary) systems. A proof of concept trial of this process with Indigenous materials held by The University of Queensland library system was successful; this trial also included a metadata enrichment component

2.4 Analytics Environment

The Language Technology and Data Analysis Laboratory ([LADAL](#)) provides a set of tutorials and illustrative tools for text analytics and statistical text analysis (including concordancing, collocations, keywords, pos-tagging, corpus text cleaning, network analysis, topic analysis, sentiment analysis). These resources are complemented by the Australian Text Analytics Platform ([ATAP](#)), which also includes various notebook-based tools developed by the Sydney Informatics Hub (University of Sydney), such as Discursis (to analyse topics over the time course of conversational interview data), Quotation Tool (to extract quotes from texts), and Document Similarity (to compare different corpora). There still remains work to be done to create clear pathways linking LDaCA data sources to tools (see below for future plans in this area), but publications drawing on LDaCA Analytics have begun to appear (Bednarek, 2024; Hames et al., 2025; Schweinberger, 2024; Schweinberger & Haugh, 2025).

2.5 Training and Support

LDaCA has delivered training in a range of formats and venues. [Workshops](#) have been run both in online and face-to-face modes at relevant conferences (Australian Linguistics Society, Australian Society of Archivists), at research training events (HASS+I RDC Summer Schools, ResBAz events in Queensland, Victoria and NT), and as stand alone events. LDaCA is also collaborating with a range of stakeholders through providing advice and direct support for a range of community and industry-facing projects (e.g. Hames & Marsh, 2025; Hutchinson et al., 2025).

3 Future Plans and CLARIN

In the current investment cycle, LDaCA will continue to work in all five of the focus areas already described:

- The technical and social foundations of the project will be improved by refinement of the tools built on the basic stack architecture (and the introduction of additional new tools), by continuing attention to governance, particularly governance for Indigenous data, and by advocating for national facilities for the long-term storage of data.
- The scope and size of the data included in the LDaCA ecosystem will be enlarged, with a particular focus on data for Indigenous languages and non-Indigenous languages other than English spoken in Australia.
- Redesign and refinement of the main Oni portal in response to user needs is an ongoing process, and the possibilities of portals for specific communities or user groups will also be explored.
- The Language Technology and Data Analysis Laboratory and Australian Text Analytics Platform will be integrated into a consolidated LDaCA Analytics ecosystem, which will be focused on making clear pathways between data and tools.
- LDaCA will continue to provide training, looking to expand the types of training offered to include modules which can be offered to research students in universities and self-guided online training materials.

LDaCA and CLARIN are both fundamentally concerned with language data. CLARIN is a collaborative network of participating centres that have relative independence, a model which is viable given the scale of activity across Europe. LDaCA focuses on advancing good data management and practice that are fitted to the Australian context through a strategic, collaborative co-investment model supported by a distributed network of partner institutions, including universities, industry partners, and the Australian Government. This suggests that the most fruitful engagement between the two organisations starts with the sharing of information to the benefit of both parties, especially for LDaCA to learn from the emerging themes, international standards and considerable experience embodied within CLARIN today. For example, LDaCA is part of a proposal to make public interest documents, including Parliamentary Proceedings and public inquiries, in Australia more accessible for researchers and the success of the [ParlaMint](#) project in CLARIN has informed this work. There are also possibilities for LDaCA to offer expertise which can enrich CLARIN. For example, LDaCA could be the base for the establishment of a knowledge centre focusing on issues raised in working with data from Indigenous (and otherwise minoritised) languages.

4 Concluding Remarks

The establishment of LDaCA over the past four years has been dependent on developing collaborative partnerships across institutional boundaries and closely engaging with a range of different communities. This has involved, in turn, the need to foster new connections and raise awareness and capacity amongst a diverse range of stakeholders. The success of LDaCA depends not only on leveraging existing and previous language infrastructures in Australia in ways that support their respective aims, but also in ways that ensure researchers and communities have a real voice in the development of Australia's languages infrastructure. It has become increasingly evident that the success of LDaCA relies not only involves meeting a diverse range of needs, but also on ensuring that researchers and communities can see themselves in that infrastructure.

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Synergies between CLARIN-IT and OPERAS-IT within H2IOSC: Monitoring Communities and Orchestrating Digital Services

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Abstract

This paper introduces the Humanities and Cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) Marketplace, a digital environment designed for the discovery, access, and integration of diverse digital resources, tools, and services in the fields of Language, Digital Humanities, and Cultural Heritage. The Marketplace is closely integrated with the H2IOSC Observatory - an analytical framework for monitoring the evolving landscape of digital resources - which provides insights into research infrastructure usage, allowing to align service offerings with user needs and expectations. Together, the Marketplace and Observatory promote interoperability and enhance collaboration between the CLARIN-IT and OPERAS-IT infrastructures.

1 Introduction

The Italian nodes of four European Research Infrastructures - CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RIHS.it and OPERAS-IT - are jointly contributing to the H2IOSC (Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud) project, aimed at fostering an open, federated digital ecosystem for SSH research communities in Italy, with solid connections with the corresponding European counterparts. Although not initially conceived as an explicit collaboration, CLARIN-IT and OPERAS-IT partnership has naturally emerged from the complementary roles assigned to these infrastructures within the H2IOSC initiative. CLARIN-IT contributes specialized language technologies and text-based analysis tools, while OPERAS-IT focuses on open scholarly communication, workflow orchestration, and service integration. A significant outcome of this unintended yet productive synergy is the joint development of an innovative Marketplace alongside a dedicated Observatory. These tools monitor community needs, service uptake, and user experiences, allowing data-driven optimization of the SSH digital ecosystem. Through this integration, previously separate research communities benefit from seamless, interoperable access to advanced research tools and services, promoting a more dynamic and collaborative SSH research environment.

2 H2IOSC Marketplace: Workflow Orchestration for Digital SSH/Services

The H2IOSC Marketplace is conceived as a one-stop platform for discovering, accessing, and combining a variety of digital research services. It functions not just as a catalog of tools, but as an orchestration hub (Sichera, Marras, & Pasini, 2024) that enables modular workflows for digital scholarship. Through standardized interfaces and interoperability protocols (such as the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting, OAI-PMH,¹ which provides a low-barrier mechanism for repository interoperability), the Marketplace allows disparate services to communicate and exchange data seamlessly. Adherence to FAIR (M. Wilkinson, 2016) principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) in service design ensures that outputs from one tool can be readily used as inputs for another, fostering an ecosystem where tools and data are inherently compatible. This framework supports dynamic research workflows: researchers can flexibly chain services together to suit their specific needs, rather than being confined to a single, static platform.

Unlike traditional digital service catalogs, the H2IOSC Marketplace operates on multiple levels of service integration. At its core, it hosts an extensive catalog of research tools (Level 1 services) which

¹<https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

can be dynamically combined into more complex workflows (Level 2 services). A distinctive feature of the Marketplace is its sophisticated API orchestration capabilities, implemented using tools such as the WSO2 Micro Integrator. API orchestration refers to the automated arrangement and coordination of different application programming interfaces (APIs), allowing them to communicate and exchange data efficiently. This process is akin to conducting an orchestra, where each API plays a distinct role in a larger workflow, ensuring that data flows smoothly between various services without requiring manual intervention. This system enables researchers to automate and execute chained processes involving various remote endpoints without burdening the central infrastructure with heavy computational loads. Instead, the Marketplace functions as a mediator and coordinator, managing metadata, authentication, and the flow of requests between services through APIs, significantly enhancing efficiency and scalability.

For example, a practical workflow involving the CLARIN-IT service *eScriptorium* — a leading Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) tool provided through the H2IOSC Transnational Access (TNA) calls — demonstrates the Marketplace’s capabilities:

1. **Data Ingestion:** Retrieve digitized manuscript images and metadata from a heritage repository via OAI-PMH, then feed them into *eScriptorium* for Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) and transcription proofreading.
2. **Text Analysis:** Automatically forward the transcribed text from *eScriptorium* into a linguistic analysis or lexicographic tool (e.g. CLARIN’s lexical platform or DARIAH’s text analysis service) for annotation and interpretation.
3. **Publication:** Pass the enriched text results to an OPERAS-IT publishing platform or repository to create an open-access digital edition or dataset.

This entire workflow can be executed via the Marketplace’s integrated interface, sparing the researcher from manual data transfers or format conversions between each step. Each component produces outputs in standard formats (for instance, XML-TEI for transcriptions), exemplifying the FAIR, interoperable design of the ecosystem. By supporting such end-to-end scenarios, the Marketplace greatly enhances efficiency and fosters cross-domain innovation: scholars are empowered to mix and match tools in creative ways, accelerating research cycles and enabling new insights.

This seamless orchestration is technically underpinned by standards such as OAI-PMH, ensuring robust interoperability among distributed repositories and services. Consequently, resources external to the H2IOSC project, including those from SSHOC or future EOSC EU Node marketplaces, can be dynamically imported and integrated.

3 The H2IOSC Observatory: Monitoring the Evolving Landscape of Digital Services

The H2IOSC Observatory is conceived as a long-term, research-driven structure dedicated to monitoring the development and socio-economic impact of the four Research Infrastructures (RIs) of the H2IOSC federation. In particular, it serves as a dynamic, continuous, and comprehensive mechanism for analyzing the evolving landscape of digital resources, tools, and services in the domains of Linguistics, Digital Humanities, and Cultural Heritage. Originally designed as a project-internal instrument, the Observatory was soon redefined as a stable online service, in recognition of its potential to provide ongoing, high-quality monitoring of both RI activities and their actual and prospective usage by reference user communities. As such, it fulfills well the function of bridging the gap between the activities of the H2IOSC research communities and the digital environment of the Marketplace.

Methodologically, the Observatory adopts a mixed-methods approach Tashakkori and Creswell, 2007 that integrates quantitative and qualitative analyses, including surveys, focus groups, interviews, and landscape mappings. These inquire on the behaviors, needs, and practices of current and prospective RI users. In addition to its analytical function, the Observatory also serves as an instrument for community engagement and building, designed to foster the co-construction of research infrastructure offerings. By actively involving researchers and institutional stakeholders as well as prospective users in the proposal and assessment of tools and services, it supports the emergence of participatory and responsive infrastructures. This orientation aims to stimulate and sustain higher quality and innovative research outcomes. Details of the Observatory design process and about its methodological components are better described in Luzietti et al., 2024.

The Observatory is implemented as a modular online platform, complementing the H2IOSC Marketplace. Its Home Page outlines the Observatory's scope and offers a dashboard with dynamic visualizations and links to key outputs. Specialized modules reflect its core instruments and include:

- survey results and analyses, offering an overview of community behaviours and needs, showing an overview of community behaviours and desiderata;
- interview and Focus Group outcomes, providing qualitative insights into research practices and innovation dynamics, offering qualitative insights into research behaviors, community needs and innovation dynamics;
- landscape mapping, outlining available tools, datasets, and services;
- marketplace statistics, such as page views, search terms, bounce rates, and click-through rates, analyzing user behaviours;
- a Call for Contributions area, where users can participate to active initiatives and contribute to the censused, encouraging active engagement from the research community (Sichera, Cristofaro, et al., 2024).

The Observatory Scientific Committee is responsible for ensuring methodological rigor, analytical depth, and coordinating high-quality contributions. In terms of long-term sustainability, the Committee will play a crucial role as both supervisory body and theoretical-methodological reference point for favoring Open Science principles. The entire H2IOSC project, indeed, aligns with the definition of Open Science as an approach to the scientific process based on collaboration, timely and open sharing of results, digital network-based knowledge dissemination, and transparent validation and evaluation methods (Rossi et al., 2022).

The Observatory thus operates both as a reflective research environment and a dynamic user-oriented platform.

By enriching the H2IOSC Marketplace with evidence-based insights, it enables a continuous feedback loop between user engagement and infrastructure development. Moreover, the data, analyses, and models it produces will be of value to a wide range of stakeholders, including: research communities beyond SSH, policy makers, public and private innovation actors, and other scientific marketplaces.

4 Observatory and Marketplace integration

The Marketplace is tightly coupled with monitoring tools and the H2IOSC Observatory to ensure that integrated services continuously improve and align with user needs. Every interaction – from selecting a service to executing a workflow – can be logged (in compliance with data privacy regulations) to collect usage analytics. These analytics are aggregated in the Observatory, which serves as a dashboard for the infrastructure providers to monitor the uptake and performance of services. For instance, usage data might reveal that *eScriptorium* is frequently used in tandem with a particular text analysis tool; such insights help identify successful tool combinations and inform best practices. The Observatory's monitoring also flags under-utilized services or potential bottlenecks, guiding infrastructure developers to refine tools or provide additional training and support where needed.

Figure 1: Marketplace usage dashboard

Figure 2: Observatory Home page

This feedback loop, powered by real-world usage data, ensures the soundness and relevance of the

platform. The Marketplace and its services evolve based on evidence of what researchers actually do and require, rather than on assumptions. In turn, this dynamic adaptation drives greater impact – researchers benefit from more robust, well-integrated tools that lower barriers to complex digital research. Ultimately, the synergy between CLARIN-IT and OPERAS-IT in developing the Marketplace (with its accompanying Observatory and monitoring framework) demonstrates a sustainable model for SSH research infrastructures. It not only provides state-of-the-art tools, but also enables their reuse and recombination in a living ecosystem, adding significant value for scholars. By blending a shared vision with technical interoperability, the H2IOSC collaboration is paving the way for an open, collaborative digital scholarship landscape in the humanities and social sciences.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

In the near future, the Observatory aims to evolve into an even more sophisticated analytical environment, supplementing current data collection methods with new monitoring strategies and impact assessments. The goal is to develop analytical tools that can promptly identify significant shifts in community needs and service usage patterns, thereby uncovering opportunities to broaden the range of tools or propose technical innovations. In this regard, requests for additional or specific data from the Marketplace — such as performance indicators or engagement metrics — could offer valuable insights for refining both the Observatory’s investigative methodologies and its overall development trajectory.

At the same time, the Marketplace will have the opportunity to expand its functionality and interoperability, drawing on the feedback and requirements emerging from the Observatory’s community-oriented activities. In the future, new modules for orchestrating complex workflows could be piloted, or procedures introduced for integrating third-party services and external infrastructures. The effectiveness of these enhancements will be ensured by a continuous dialogue between the two components: on one hand, the Observatory will provide ongoing monitoring and pinpoint areas for improvement; on the other, the Marketplace will supply the data and resources necessary to make the system increasingly responsive, modular, and aligned with the needs of a rapidly evolving research community.

In this context, the partnership between CLARIN-IT and OPERAS-IT will continue to evolve through iterative feedback loops between the Observatory and Marketplace. This collaboration lays a foundation for a truly integrated Open Science ecosystem, where continuous dialogue between research infrastructures stimulates innovative tool design, broadens user engagement, and ultimately raises the bar for digital scholarship in the humanities and social sciences.

Finally, as the name itself suggests, the H2IOSC initiative is conceived in continuity with the EOSC vision, positioning itself as a federation of Italian nodes of European ESFRI RIs already engaged in EOSC. Also, CNR is a member of the EOSC Association, and several H2IOSC team members have participated in EOSC-related and SSHOC initiatives. H2IOSC draws substantial inspiration from SSHOC and EOSC. Both the H2IOSC Marketplace and Observatory, in particular, are inspired by the EOSC and SSH Open Marketplace, while aiming to improve upon them and address finer-grained, domain-specific needs. The Observatory is intended to complement the EOSC Observatory by offering more detailed, community-driven insights into research practices and service uptake. These developments point to a layered integration model, in which national infrastructures contribute specialized enhancements that may be valorised through their European counterparts. In this perspective, CLARIN-IT within H2IOSC aligns with and extends the mission of CLARIN ERIC. Likewise, OPERAS-IT strengthens its role within OPERAS, ensuring that both infrastructures contribute to and benefit from broader open science initiatives at national and European levels.

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The AI Act and its impact on Large Language Models and the CLARIN Infrastructure

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Abstract

The EU Artificial Intelligence Act (Regulation 2024/1689), which entered into force in August 2024, represents the world's first comprehensive regulatory framework for AI. While it explicitly excludes AI systems developed solely for scientific research and development, its implications for the CLARIN community are far-reaching, especially given the growing reliance on large language models (LLMs) and general-purpose AI (GPAI). This extended abstract examines the scope of the research exemption in the AI Act (Section 2), and provides a detailed overview of the obligations imposed on providers of GPAI models, including those with systemic risk (Section 3). Given CLARIN's role as a data provider, special attention is paid to the requirement for dataset documentation under the upcoming GPAI Code of Practice.

1 Introduction

EU Regulation 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence, better known as the AI Act, is a recent addition to the legal framework affecting language data and language technology. The Act was officially proposed in 2021; the proposal was then substantially modified to better address the issues related to General-Purpose AI (Bertuzzi, 2023), which delayed its adoption. The Act entered into force on 1 August 2024, and it will become applicable, in principle, 24 months after that date, but with many exceptions (in particular, the rules on General-Purpose AI have entered into force on 2 August 2025).

The AI Act is, globally, the first comprehensive attempt to legally regulate AI (see e.g. Ruschemeier 2022, Wörsdörfer 2025). As such, it cannot go unnoticed by the CLARIN community. For the typical academic researcher employed by a university or research institute, the impact of the AI Act may, at first glance, appear to be negligible, as the Act “exclude[s] from its scope AI systems and models specifically developed and put into service for the sole purpose of scientific research and development”¹. But even with a clear exception for scientific research, the AI Act has the potential to impact the CLARIN community's sources of tools and methods, funding, collaborations with industry, corporations that may be hiring academics and students in the future, stakeholders beyond the typical academic researcher, and a myriad of end-users of CLARIN community members' research. An exploration of the impact of the AI Act on CLARIN-related activities is thus important.

This extended abstract will discuss the general exclusion of research from the scope of the AI Act (Section 2), before analysing the rules on General Purpose AI (a category in which LLMs fall) in greater detail (Section 3).

¹ Recital 16 and Article 2(6) of the AI Act.
CLARIN Annual Conference Proceedings, 2025

2 General Exclusion of Research and Development Activities from the AI Act

One of the stated objectives of the AI Act is to promote innovation, safeguard academic freedom, and avoid hindering research and development activities. From the perspective of the CLARIN community, a particularly important provision of the AI Act is that it does not apply to AI systems and models—including their outputs—that are specifically developed and used exclusively for scientific research and development purposes. Furthermore, even in cases where systems or models are developed for broader applications, the AI Act does not extend to research, testing, and development activities carried out prior to their placement on the market. It is important to note, however, that this exemption does not include testing conducted under real-world conditions.

However, models and systems that are primarily designed for other purposes but are employed within research and development contexts still fall under the scope of the AI Act. Given that research does not operate in isolation from broader societal and technological developments, it is reasonable to expect that the AI Act will influence researchers—particularly when they develop or deploy models and systems intended for general use, or when they test such technologies in real-world conditions. Since CLARIN serves not only the academic community but also a broader range of stakeholders, it is essential for the CLARIN community to remain informed about the evolving regulatory landscape. The rapidly advancing capabilities of AI in solving complex tasks (see, e.g., Kaur et al., 2024) suggest that general-purpose or fine-tuned large language models (LLMs) may increasingly replace many of the specialized NLP tools and packages traditionally used by CLARIN researchers (see, e.g., Min et al., 2021). Therefore, understanding and analysing the implications of the AI Act for CLARIN-related activities is both timely and crucial.

3 General-Purpose AI Models under the AI Act

A general-purpose AI model (GPAIM) is defined as: “an AI model, including where such an AI model is trained with a large amount of data using self-supervision at scale, that displays significant generality and is capable of competently performing a wide range of distinct tasks regardless of the way the model is placed on the market and that can be integrated into a variety of downstream systems or applications, except AI models that are used for research, development or prototyping activities before they are placed on the market” (Article 3, (63) of the AI Act).

The key characteristic of a GPAIM is its capability to perform a wide range of distinct tasks. Typically, such models are trained on large amounts of data using machine learning methods and can be made available for direct download, as physical copies, or through libraries or APIs. LLMs, and other large generative models, are considered GPAIMs (Recital 99 of the AI Act). In case of doubt, the generality of a model can also be determined by the number of its parameters – models with a billion or more parameters are presumed to be GPAIMs (recital 98 of the AI Act). Most modern Large Language Models, at least those released after 2019, meet this criterion; remarkably, BERT, originally released in 2018 is still significantly smaller (despite being considered an LLM)².

In the spirit of the general exclusion of research and development activities from the AI Act (see above), models used for research, development and prototyping and not available on the market are not considered GPAIMs.

The rules on high-risk AI systems and GPAIM are not mutually exclusive and can be cumulated: a GPAIM can be part of a high-risk AI system.

Within the category of GPAIM, the AI Act distinguishes two additional sub-categories: GPAIM with systemic risks (which are subject to a stricter framework) and “free open source” GPAIM.

The providers of all GPAIM need to comply with the four rather generally phrased obligations listed in [Article 53](#) of the AI Act, i.e.:

1. Prepare and keep up to date the technical documentation of the model, including its training and testing process and the results of its evaluation. The documentation should at the very least contain the information listed in Annex XI of the AI Act, and upon request be provided to the competent national authorities and the AI Office.
2. Prepare and keep up to date information and documentation that should be made available to the systems providers who want to integrate the GPAIM in their AI systems. It should give said providers a “good understanding of the capabilities and limitations” of the model, and enable them

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_large_language_models -- last visit 31.03.2025.
CLARIN Annual Conference Proceedings, 2025

to comply with their obligations under the AI Act (e.g., for providers of high-risk AI systems, the obligation to risk management, transparency, and their own documentation obligations). At the very least, the documentation should contain the information listed in Annex XII of the AI Act;

3. Put in place a policy to comply with copyright and related rights, and in particular to respect the opt-out (reservation of rights) under the “general” TDM exception (Article 4(3) of the [DSM Directive](#));
4. Prepare and make publicly available a sufficiently detailed summary about the datasets used for training the model.

Obligations 1. and 2. do not apply to GPAIM released under free and open source licenses, and whose parameters (including the weights), information about their architecture, and the information on model usage are publicly available (Article 53(2) of the AI Act), unless these models qualify as GPAIMs with systemic risks (see below).

A GPAIM with systemic risks is a GPAIM that meets one of the following conditions:

- a) it has high impact capabilities evaluated on the basis of appropriate technical tools and methodologies OR
- b) It has been officially recognised as such in a Commission decision.

The criteria mentioned in a) will be fine-tuned by the Commission in a delegated act. The AI Act only mentions one criterion: a GPAIM is presumed as carrying a systemic risk “when the cumulative amount of computation used for its training measured in floating point operations is greater than 10^{25} ”. Over 25 modern GPAIMs, including GPT-4, are believed to meet this threshold³.

Providers of GPAIM with systemic risk need to comply with additional obligations under Article 55 of the AI Act:

1. Perform model evaluations, including adversarial testing to identify and mitigate systemic risk.
2. Assess and mitigate possible systemic risks, including their sources.
3. Track, document and report serious incidents and possible corrective measures to the AI Office and national competent authorities;
4. Ensure an adequate level of cybersecurity protection.

One can assume that currently only very large LLMs will be considered as GPAIMs with systemic risks; to what extent this framework will be relevant for CLARIN remains to be seen.

The rules regarding GPAIM became applicable on 2 August 2025. However, according to Article 111 of the AI Act Providers of general-purpose AI models that have been placed on the market before 2 August 2025 shall take the necessary steps in order to comply with the obligations laid down in the AI Act by 2 August 2027.

In recent weeks and months, these rather abstractly formulated lists of obligations have gradually been filled up with practical meaning - some elements are already in place, others are still being developed. To a large extent, this is due to the adoption of the GPAI Code of Practice, whose final version was published on July 10, 2025 (<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/contents-code-gpai>). It is complemented by Commission guidelines on key concepts related to GPAIM (<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/guidelines-scope-obligations-providers-general-purpose-ai-models-under-ai-act>). The Code contains, among other interesting elements, a Model Documentation form for GPAIM, which may seem surprisingly simple and straightforward, totaling only 3 pages.

CLARIN, as a provider of data for GPAIM (LLM) training, should also pay special attention to the details concerning the obligation laid down in Article 53(1)(d) of the AI Act, i.e. to provide a sufficiently detailed summary of the training data. In July 2025, the European Commission published an Explanatory Notice and a standardized Template for the Public Summary of Training Content for general-purpose AI models to support providers in meeting their transparency obligations under Article 53(1)(d) of the AI Act (<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/explanatory-notice-and-template-public-summary-training-content-general-purpose-ai-models?utm>).

It may be also worthwhile to consider providing descriptions of CLARIN datasets following the template in the final version of the GPAI Code of Practice:

³ <https://epoch.ai/data-insights/models-over-1e25-flop> (last visit: 11.03.2025)
CLARIN Annual Conference Proceedings, 2025

Information on the data used for training, testing, and validation				AIO	NCAs	DPs	
Data type/modality: <i>Select all that apply.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Text	<input type="checkbox"/> Images	<input type="checkbox"/> Audio	<input type="checkbox"/> Video	If any other please specify:		
Data provenance: <i>Select all that apply</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Web crawling	<input type="checkbox"/> Private non-publicly available datasets obtained from third parties	<input type="checkbox"/> User data		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
For definitions of each listed category, see the Template for the Public Summary of the Training Content of General-Purpose AI models provided by the AI Office	<input type="checkbox"/> Publicly available datasets		<input type="checkbox"/> Data collected through other means		If any other please specify:		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Synthetic data that is not publicly accessible (when created directly by or on behalf of the provider)						
How data was obtained and selected:	A description of the methods used to obtain and select training, testing, and validation data, including methods and resources used to annotate data, and models and methods used to generate synthetic data where applicable. For data previously obtained from third parties, a description of how the provider obtained the rights to the data if not already disclosed in the public summary of training data published in accordance with Article 53(1), point (d). <i>[Recommended 300 words]</i>				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Number of data points:	The size (in number of data points) of the training, testing, and validation data respectively, together with the definition of the unit of data points (e.g. tokens or documents, images, hours of video or frames), recorded with at least one significant figure (e.g. 3x10 ¹³ tokens).				<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	The size (in number of data points) of the training, testing, and validation data respectively, together with the definition of the unit of data points (e.g. tokens or documents, images, hours of video or frames), recorded with at least two significant figures (e.g. 1.5x10 ¹³ tokens).				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Scope and main characteristics:	A general description of the scope and main characteristics of the training, testing and validation data, such as domain (e.g. healthcare, science, <u>law</u>), geography (e.g. global, restricted to a certain <u>region</u>), language, modality coverage, where applicable. <i>[Recommended 200 words]</i>				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Data curation methodologies:	General description of the data processing involved in transforming the acquired data into training, testing, and validation data for the model, such as cleaning (e.g. filtering out irrelevant content such as advertisements), <u>normalisation</u> (e.g. tokenizing), augmentation (e.g. back-translation). <i>[Recommended 300 words]</i>				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Measures to detect unsuitability of data sources:	A description of any methods implemented in data acquisition or processing, if any, to detect the presence of unsuitable data sources considering the model's intended uses, including but not limited to illegal content, child sexual abuse material (CSAM), non-consensual intimate imagery (NCII), and personal data leading to its unlawful processing. <i>[Recommended 400 words]</i>				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Measures to detect identifiable biases:	A description of any methods implemented in data acquisition or processing, if any, to address the prevalence of identifiable biases in the training data. <i>[Recommended 200 words]</i>				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Interfacing CLARIN with H2IOSC: Metadata Interoperability through Ontology-based Mediation

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Abstract

We present an ontology-based approach for integrating CLARIN language resources into the H2IOSC semantic framework, promoting interoperability across the Social Sciences and Humanities. Building on CMDI and the CLARIN Concept Registry, our work extends CMD2RDF beyond syntactic conversion to formal semantic integration. CMDI metadata is mapped to CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro, with extensions for CLARIN-specific needs. This ontology-first strategy keeps CMDI fully operational while ensuring theoretical consistency and long-term sustainability. The resulting semantic layer enhances discoverability, enables cross-disciplinary integration, and contributes to a scalable knowledge graph aligned with FAIR principles and the EOSC vision.

1 Introduction

H2IOSC, the Humanities and Cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud,¹ brings together the Italian nodes of four European research infrastructures—CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RIHS.it, and OPERAS-IT—into a collaborative cluster that offers an open, multidisciplinary environment for advanced research on complex digital data and cultural objects.

In this context, interoperability is a cornerstone: it enables collaboration, data sharing, and resource integration across disciplines and technologies, and aligns H2IOSC with the EOSC FAIR principles. H2IOSC adopts an ontology-based methodology for integrating each RI's domain, consistently with CLARIN's long-standing FAIR trajectory (de Jong et al., 2018).

Within CLARIN, language-related datasets and tools are described through CMDI (Windhouwer & Goosen, 2022), supported by the CLARIN Concept Registry (CCR; Schuurman and Windhouwer 2015) (Section 2). Earlier work such as CMD2RDF (Windhouwer et al., 2017) showed the feasibility of serializing CMDI into RDF, but structural conversion alone is insufficient for cross-infrastructure interoperability. In H2IOSC, CLARIN CMDI descriptions are therefore embedded in a formal ontology to ensure semantic stability across infrastructures (Section 3).

CLARIN-IT maps CMDI profiles to CIDOC CRM (Bekiari et al., 2024) and SSHOCro (Bekiari et al., 2022) (Section 4). The mapping is non-invasive—CMDI remains fully operational—while the ontology adds a semantic layer that enables broader discovery and integration. Section 4.1 outlines the workflow and Section 4.2 illustrates it with a case study.

2 CLARIN Domain and Focus

CLARIN is an extensive federation of repositories, service centres, and centres of expertise that facilitate sustained access to digital language resources and advanced tools for linguistic analysis. Certified CLARIN centres describe hosted resources using CMDI, a standardized yet flexible metadata framework, while the CLARIN Concept Registry (CCR) ensures semantic consistency through controlled

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¹Official website <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/>

vocabularies with persistent identifiers. Together, they provide the structural and semantic scaffolding that underpins the CLARIN ecosystem.

Researchers typically explore resources through the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO)², a unified discovery interface that aggregates metadata from all CLARIN centres. Complementing the VLO, the CLARIN Resource Families³ organize datasets into intuitive, user-oriented classes such as Parallel Corpora, Treebanks, or Spoken Corpora, offering a thematic overview that supports both newcomers and experienced users. On the services side, the CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard (LRS)⁴ catalogs available linguistic tools (Zinn, 2018) and enables users to connect datasets with appropriate web applications for further processing. Viewed together, these three catalogues—VLO, Resource Families, and LRS—offer complementary perspectives on the same ecosystem: discovery, classification, and deployment.

2.1 CLARIN Metadata Framework: CMDI and CCR

CMDI is a modular, XML-based metadata schema that enables centres to describe linguistic resources with both structural consistency and descriptive flexibility. Metadata profiles are built from reusable components, making it possible to represent resource-specific features—whether textual corpora, lexica, or annotation workflows—while maintaining overall coherence across the infrastructure. This modularity is a distinctive strength of CMDI: it allows local adaptation to specific needs while preserving interoperability across centres.

The CCR complements CMDI by providing a registry of authoritative, controlled vocabularies. Each concept in the CCR is assigned a persistent identifier, ensuring that metadata values are standardized and semantically unambiguous across CMDI profiles. This not only guarantees cross-centre interoperability but also significantly enhances resource discoverability.

Taken together, CMDI and CCR form the semantic backbone of CLARIN. CMDI provides the structural framework for resource description, while the CCR anchors metadata values in a shared semantic space. This combination ensures that CLARIN's resources are not only richly described and consistently interpretable but also well-prepared for ontology-based integration within initiatives like H2IOSC.

3 Interoperability through ontology-based mediation

H2IOSC integrates data, tools, and services from E-RIHS.it, DARIAH-IT, CLARIN-IT, and OPERAS-IT through a Common Semantic Framework (CSF), inspired by SSHOC (SSHOC Consortium, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c). The CSF adopts a layered design: a top-level conceptual backbone which, following the SSHOC example, is based on CIDOC CRM and the SSHOC reference ontology (SSHOCro); below this upper backbone, more specific domain ontologies enrich the framework, capturing the richness of disciplinary perspectives while preserving overall coherence. CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro serve as key reference models, providing widely recognised semantics for cross-domain interoperability.

This design secures interoperability not only at technical or syntactic levels but—crucially—at the semantic level. Ontology-based mediation harmonizes resource descriptions, supports extensibility, and provides a stable foundation for cross-disciplinary collaboration.

3.1 The H2IOSC Marketplace as catalogue and orchestrator

The CSF's principles are put to use in the H2IOSC Marketplace through a dedicated data model—implemented within H2IOSC to support its dual role as catalogue and orchestrator. Structured around attributes, properties, and controlled vocabularies, this model is explicitly aligned with the CSF and its reference ontologies (CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro). Thus, the ontology supplies the semantic backbone for consistency and traceability, while the Marketplace is supplied with a data model that acts as a practical layer for cataloguing and workflow execution.

The Marketplace enables discovery, classification, and interaction with resources across infrastructures, and orchestrates workflows that combine datasets and tools into coherent pipelines (Sichera et al.,

²Virtual Language Observatory accessible at <https://vlo.clarin.eu/>

³Overview available at <https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families>

⁴CLARIN Switchboard accessible at <https://switchboard.clarin.eu/>

2024, 2025). Descriptions authored once in the ontology can be projected into the Marketplace without semantic drift and reused across heterogeneous platforms. A representative workflow and proof-of-concept pipelines are currently being developed to illustrate this orchestration capability.

Grounding the Marketplace in the ontology-based CSF avoids lock-in to a specific technical format and strengthens conceptual stability, adaptability, and long-term sustainability.

4 Mapping to CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro

Among the various ontological frameworks available for semantic interoperability, CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro were selected to meet the requirements of H2IOSC, drawing on the experience gained within the SSHOC project. CIDOC CRM, recognized as an ISO standard (ISO 21127), is widely adopted in the cultural heritage and humanities sectors for its event-centric modeling of entities, activities, and contextual relationships. SSHOCro builds on this foundation with SSH-specific extensions, adding constructs for linguistic resources, annotation workflows, and the research data lifecycle. Together, they provide a layered framework that combines cross-domain interoperability with the descriptive precision needed in the SSH domain.

4.1 The Mapping Strategy

The integration followed a combined top-down and bottom-up approach to align the CLARIN Metadata Framework with CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro. In the top-down phase, high-level CMDI metadata elements—such as Resource Type, Authors, and Funding—were mapped to CIDOC CRM classes selected for their semantic proximity to CMDI descriptors. Categories were chosen based on their ubiquity across profiles and their relevance for cross-infrastructure alignment.

The entry point was established at the level of *E1 CRM Entity*, the most abstract superclass in CIDOC CRM, ensuring that all mapped resources inherited a coherent semantic foundation. Subsequent mappings linked CMDI descriptors to entities such as *E21 Person* (authors), *E73 Information Object* (resources), and event-oriented classes like *E65 Creation* and *E7 Activity*.

To capture the specificity of the CLARIN domain, the mapping was refined through SSHOCro, which extends CRM with constructs for contributors' roles, linguistic resource types, and annotation workflows. Here, the catalogues already familiar to CLARIN users provided the natural entry point for ontology extensions:

Datasets. Under *SHE1 Dataset*, we introduced top-level nodes for *Corpus* and *LexicalResource*, further enriched with subclasses inspired by the CLARIN Resource Families (e.g., *ReferenceCorpus*, *ParallelCorpus*, *Lexicon*). This anchors the Resource Families taxonomy in a formal ontology, enabling precise alignment across infrastructures.

Tools and Services. Under *SHE10 Tool*, we defined the superclass *LinguisticTool*, extended with categories inspired by the Language Resource Switchboard (LRS). Examples include *CorpusQueryTool*, *Part-of-SpeechTagger*, and *NamedEntityRecognitionTool*. This gives formal semantic representation to classifications already used in practice, ensuring that Switchboard categories can be embedded within the H2IOSC framework.

This dual extension shows how community-driven catalogues—datasets from the Resource Families and services from the Switchboard—can be systematically formalized and aligned with SSHOCro and CIDOC CRM. In this way, the ontology both preserves community practices and enables rigorous integration.

This hierarchical modeling increases the semantic granularity of the ontology while maintaining alignment with SSHOCro. It facilitates more precise classification, discovery, and integration of CLARIN resources. All mappings and extensions were formalized in RDF and OWL to ensure compatibility with Semantic Web technologies. Collaborative modeling was carried out in Protégé,⁵ with OntoGraf used for visual inspection and validation.

In the CLARIN Switchboard, matching between datasets and tools is pragmatic: metadata and formats are compared (e.g., a `.txt` resource can be sent to a tool that declares `.txt` compatibility). Effective

⁵Protégé official website: <https://protege.stanford.edu/>

for operations, this remains a technical compatibility check. In the ontology, by contrast, relations are explicit semantic assertions—e.g., *UDPipe ANALYSES ParlaMint* or *ParlaMint IS PROCESSED WITH NameTag*—embedded in the CSF and extensible with activities, agents, and outputs. This provides stable, reusable semantics across infrastructures.

4.2 Mapping example of CLARIN resources and tools

Datasets: Musisque Deoque. A representative case study is the Musisque Deoque (MQDQ) corpus, a multilingual digital library of Latin poetry enriched with philological and linguistic metadata (Boschetti et al., 2021). MQDQ was chosen for its structural complexity and interdisciplinary scope, sitting at the intersection of philology, literary studies, and computational linguistics. Metadata elements from its CMDI profile—such as Resource Type, Authors, and Funding—were mapped to SSHOCro and CIDOC CRM classes. The corpus itself was modeled as a *LiteraryCorpus* under *SHE1_Dataset*, contributors were aligned with *E21 Person*, and funding information with entities such as *nationalFunds*. These mappings, expressed as RDF triples, support Linked Open Data integration and links to external authority files (e.g., ORCID), funding registries, and cultural heritage datasets. MQDQ thus becomes discoverable both as a CLARIN corpus and as part of a wider semantic network, while CMDI structures remain intact.

Services: UDPipe and NameTag. The same methodology was applied to services exposed in the Language Resource Switchboard. Two illustrative examples are the parsing pipeline *UDPipe* and the named entity recognizer *NameTag*. *UDPipe* was modeled as an individual instance of the *PartOfSpeechTagger* and *DependencyParser* classes under *LinguisticTool*, while *NameTag* was aligned with the *NamedEntityRecognitionTool* class. The mappings, expressed as RDF triples, describe the tools in the same semantic framework as the datasets they are meant to process.

Although focused here on MQDQ and two selected services, the approach is generalizable. The same modeling principles can be applied across CLARIN resources and tools, enabling their gradual incorporation into an interoperable SSH knowledge graph. In this sense, this mapping example highlights the added value of ontology-based mediation in H2IOSC: datasets and services remain CLARIN assets, yet simultaneously become nodes in a larger, semantically coherent ecosystem.

5 Future Directions

H2IOSC promotes interoperability as a cornerstone of open science, with particular emphasis on the humanities and cultural heritage domains. By integrating data, tools, and services from E-RIHS.it, DARIAH-IT, CLARIN-IT, and OPERAS-IT into a shared environment, H2IOSC enables a harmonized infrastructure where resources will be semantically aligned and will be delivered through a unified Marketplace platform. This paper contributes to that goal by defining a reference framework for integrating CLARIN language resources into a collaborative and accessible ecosystem. A key achievement is the alignment between the CLARIN Metadata Framework and the H2IOSC Common Semantic Framework, which paves the way for cross-domain interoperability and future innovation.

Future work may focus on extending the mapping strategy to a broader range of CMDI profiles, promoting best practices in ontology-based metadata modeling within CLARIN. Publishing enriched CMDI metadata as RDF—aligned with CIDOC CRM and SSHOCro—could improve discoverability and facilitate interconnection with other SSH infrastructures on the Semantic Web.

To ensure broad adoption of this ontology-based approach, dedicated tools—such as guided interfaces and semi-automated mapping services—could be essential to support consistency, scalability, and long-term sustainability not only to CLARIN’s ecosystem, but to the broader research landscape across the SSH domain and the EOSC ecosystem. Because the ontology-first strategy ensures compatibility with both ontology-based systems and pragmatic data models, CLARIN enriched metadata can be harvested directly into the H2IOSC Marketplace and, in parallel, interoperate with external platforms such as the SSHOC Marketplace. This dual alignment reinforces the purpose of this broader H2IOSC ambition.

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Building up the CLARIN-CH Training Program

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Abstract

The CLARIN-CH ecosystem is unique in its approach to language resources, as it brings together a diverse range of research infrastructures distributed across the various language regions of Switzerland. In this paper, we present the CLARIN-CH training program, which plays a central role in Switzerland's efforts to advance sustainable Open Research Data (ORD) practices within the evolving landscape of Open Science. The program is structured around five principal axes of action: (i) assessing the needs of researchers across disciplines who work with language data, both within linguistics and beyond; (ii) collaborating with stakeholders—including researchers and training providers—to develop offerings tailored to these specific needs; (iii) organizing diverse training events using a variety of educational formats; (iv) co-developing Open Educational Resources aligned with the FAIR-by-design methodology; and (v) ensuring the publication and long-term accessibility of these resources via Zenodo for the CLARIN-CH community. In this contribution, we outline these core components of the training program and showcase three training events—two already completed and one forthcoming—delivered through multiple educational formats. The long-term goal of the CLARIN-CH training program is to contribute to capacity building among researchers working with language data, by promoting a spirit of lifelong learning and interdisciplinary collaboration.

1 Introduction

The CLARIN-CH training program is a central component of Switzerland's efforts to promote sustainable Open Research Data (ORD) practices and to strengthen interdisciplinary collaboration among researchers working with language data. Rooted in the CLARIN-CH ecosystem, the program supports the development of a robust training infrastructure that addresses the evolving needs of a multilingual and multidisciplinary research community. Its overarching goal is to enhance researchers' capacities to engage with language data in alignment with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) (Wilkinson et al. 2016) by supporting a culture of open science across diverse fields including linguistics, medicine, law, journalism, theology, and beyond. While other CLARIN countries, as well as CLARIN ERIC, have already put in place training programs (see for instance, Ljubešić et al. 2024, de Smet et al. 2024, Filiposka et al. 2024), in Switzerland training for the CLARIN-CH community has not previously addressed in a systematic manner.

2 Axes of action of the CLARIN-CH training program

The CLARIN-CH training program is created within the collaborative and community-driven approach and is structured around five principal axes of action, each contributing to the development of a sustainable training infrastructure that supports researchers working with language data across Switzerland's multilingual and interdisciplinary research landscape.

First, a key priority is the systematic **evaluation of the needs of researchers** who work with language data across various disciplines, both within linguistics and beyond. This includes researchers in fields

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such as medicine, law, journalism, theology, and business, where language data plays an increasingly central role. By conducting targeted needs assessments—such as national surveys and case studies—the program aims to gain a comprehensive understanding of the existing competencies, practices, and gaps in knowledge related to ORD and the use of Natural Language Processing techniques. This evidence-based approach ensures that the training offer is built on a clear understanding of actual research needs, grounded in the day-to-day challenges faced by researchers.

Second, the program places strong emphasis on **collaboration with key stakeholders** across the Swiss research ecosystem. This includes engaging both researchers and training providers in co-developing educational content and formats that are tailored to specific disciplinary and linguistic contexts. Through these partnerships, CLARIN-CH fosters a participatory and community-driven model of training design, ensuring that the resulting materials and activities are relevant, adaptable, and aligned with institutional and national priorities related to Open Science and FAIR data practices.

Third, the training program is committed to **organizing a diverse portfolio of training events**, delivered in a variety of educational formats to maximize accessibility and impact. These include interactive working groups, thematic webinars, and practical workshops held both onsite and online. This multimodal approach allows the program to reach a broad and varied audience, from early-career researchers to experienced data stewards, while accommodating different learning preferences and institutional contexts. Importantly, many of these events are designed to foster interdisciplinary exchange and knowledge-sharing, creating spaces where participants can learn from one another and explore how tools and methods can be applied to their specific datasets but also across disciplinary boundaries.

Fourth, CLARIN-CH works closely with training providers and domain experts to **develop high-quality Open Access Educational Resources** that are aligned with the FAIR-by-design methodology developed in the [skills4EOSC](#) project. These resources cover each stage of the language data life cycle—from data collection, processing, and annotation to ethical considerations, legal compliance, sharing, and long-term archiving. Special attention is given to discipline-specific needs and to demonstrating the added value of tools such as the [LiRI Corpus Platform](#) (University of Zurich) and [Swiss-AL](#) (Zurich University of Applied Sciences ZHAW) for researchers working outside linguistics. The materials are designed to be modular, reusable, and adaptable for both self-directed learning and formal teaching contexts.

Fifth and finally, the training program ensures the **publication and long-term accessibility of all educational resources** via Zenodo. By using this open and trusted repository, CLARIN-CH guarantees that training materials are freely available to the broader research community and can be easily cited, shared, and integrated into other teaching or training initiatives. This axis of action reflects the program's strong commitment to sustainability and transparency, and its role in advancing open science practices not only in Switzerland but also within the wider CLARIN and European research infrastructures.

3 Educational program

Guided by these core principles, CLARIN-CH is developing a training infrastructure designed to meet the needs of researchers working with language data within Switzerland's linguistically and disciplinarily diverse academic environment. In this section, we highlight three initiatives led by the CLARIN-CH team, each utilizing distinct educational formats and addressing the needs of different target audiences involved in language data research.

3.1 Working Groups

As part of the CLARIN-CH training program, several Working Groups (WG) have been created. One of them was dedicated to sensitive and personal data management: [Working Group on the management of sensitive and personal data, ethical and legal issues for linguistic data](#). Launched in September 2023, this WG aims to serve as a national platform for disseminating information, promoting best practices, and offering tailored guidance to researchers across disciplines who engage with language data, especially in multilingual and cross-disciplinary settings. The WG began its activities with a kick-off event

that brought together experts and researchers to discuss critical issues related to data collection, protection, and long-term preservation. Particular attention was given to the specificities of various types of linguistic data, such as multimodal, historical, experimental, sociolinguistic, and social media-based data, as well as data collected from diverse demographic groups. The event featured three keynote presentations—recorded and made available on the [CLARIN-CH Documentation Platform](#)—alongside an open call for questions from the community. These questions, often discipline-specific, highlighted widespread concerns around the management of sensitive and personal data, as well as copyright and licensing issues, particularly in relation to digital and online sources. In response to these expressed needs, the WG designed and launched a [monthly webinar series](#) for the 2024 spring and autumn semesters. These lunchtime talks feature a 30-minute expert presentation followed by a 30-minute open discussion, and target researchers, data stewards and other RDM professionals. The topics covered include both legal and technical aspects of working with sensitive data, as well as practical case studies, such as anonymization techniques for textual, video, and audio data, and legal considerations for cross-border research or social media data use. Each session is documented through recordings and presentation slides, which are made publicly available via the CLARIN-CH Documentation Platform and on the [CLARIN-CH Zenodo community](#) (Grisot & Röthlisberger 2025). In addition to the webinars, the WG produces concrete outputs designed to support researchers in practice. These include: (i) a growing FAQ section compiling answers to community questions; (ii) slides and video recordings from the keynote talks and webinars; (iii) personalized advice (when needed) and guidance provided by the WG members or through collaboration with legal and institutional experts.

3.2 Training sessions for linguists

As part of its commitment to fostering sustainable and inclusive practices in working with language data, the CLARIN-CH training program organized a series of online training sessions in Spring 2025, titled [Exploring Swiss Language Resources and Tools](#). This initiative aimed to introduce researchers—both newcomers and experienced users—to the rich ecosystem of infrastructures, tools, and services developed within CLARIN-CH, while offering practical, hands-on guidance on how to effectively leverage these resources for research purposes. The training series was designed to support the growing community of researchers relying on language data across a wide range of disciplines. Participants were introduced to a variety of topics, including corpus querying and analysis, media data processing, multimodal data modeling, and best practices for data sharing and reuse. The sessions were developed with the support of two nationally co-funded projects: Upgrading the Linguistic ORD Ecosystem ([UpLORD](#)) and Moving towards a National FAIR-Compliant Ecosystem of Federated Infrastructure for Language Data ([FAIR-FI-LD](#)).

In line with FAIR principles and the Open-by-Design philosophy, the materials produced for these sessions were developed as Open Educational Resources (OER) and published on the CLARIN-CH Zenodo Community, ensuring long-term accessibility and reusability. The series was delivered collaboratively by key institutions and stakeholders in the CLARIN-CH network, including the CLARIN-CH Coordination Office, the Linguistic Research Infrastructure (LiRI) at the University of Zurich, the ZHAW Digital Discourse Lab, the Language Repository of Switzerland (LaRS@SWISSUbase), and Università della Svizzera italiana (USI). Each session featured expert contributions from representatives of these institutions, ensuring the dissemination of up-to-date knowledge and the showcasing of current best practices. The sessions were held biweekly and offered participants a structured journey through the CLARIN-CH ecosystem and its tools for working with language data. The series began with an introductory session that provided an overview of the CLARIN-CH research infrastructures and their relevance in the ORD context, setting the stage for more specialized topics to follow. Subsequent sessions focused on the LiRI Corpus Platform, starting with its data model and querying functionalities, and then moving on to advanced methods for analyzing various data types—including text, audio, and video—within the platform. One session explored the modeling of multimodal data, addressing the challenges and strategies for working with complex datasets that integrate multiple forms of linguistic input. An-

other session introduced participants to `Swissdox@LIRI`, showcasing how Swiss media data can be queried and analyzed for research purposes. In the second half of the series, attention shifted to data analysis with `Swiss-AL`, a platform particularly useful for working with large-scale textual data. The final sessions addressed the later stages of the data lifecycle: one focused on best practices for publishing datasets in the Language Repository of Switzerland (`LaRS@SWISSUbase`), while the closing session explored how previously collected data can be reused effectively for teaching or for conducting secondary analyses. Collectively, the series provided comprehensive, practice-oriented training designed to strengthen the capacity of researchers working with linguistic data in line with FAIR principles and ORD standards (see Grisot et al. 2025).

3.3 Emerging initiative for non-linguists

As part of its ongoing efforts to enrich its educational offering, CLARIN-CH has begun laying the groundwork for developing training programs tailored to non-linguistic disciplines. As language data continues to gain prominence across a broad spectrum of research disciplines beyond linguistics—including medicine, history, theology, business communication, translation and interpretation, and language education—new challenges have emerged regarding the management of such data in line with ORD principles. Researchers in these fields often use language data in ways that diverge significantly from traditional linguistic approaches. For instance, while a linguist may examine syntactic structures, a medical researcher might analyze communication strategies to improve patient care. More specifically, corpus-based studies have become a valuable—and often indispensable—tool for analyzing the specialized language of these domains, since they are crucial for addressing such domain-related research questions effectively. In recent years, however, conducting corpus-based research has become increasingly regulated, driven by growing positive pressure to define requirements and implement ORD practices.

A survey conducted by CLARIN-CH within the Swiss community in 2023 highlighted an acute need for structured training in ORD practices (Grisot 2024). Researchers expressed a strong desire for guidance in technical, legal, and ethical aspects of working with language data. While past initiatives, such as webinars, workshops, and training programs, have made strides toward addressing these needs, they have often been limited in scope, sporadic in implementation, and focused primarily on linguistics. Researchers from other disciplines who use language data have been left underserved, due to their unique approaches and specific research objectives. To address this gap, the CLARIN-CH ecosystem has launched a new initiative—*Language Data Across Disciplines (The LaDaD initiative)*—aimed at strengthening ORD competencies across the broader research community in Switzerland. *The LaDaD initiative* is currently in its conceptualization phase and includes the following fundamental disciplines: medicine, history and political sciences, theology, film studies, financial and business communication, translation, terminology and interpretation, and language education. It has three main objectives. The first objective is to develop a comprehensive understanding of the competencies needed to manage language data in these fields at each step of the data life cycle. A needs assessment, conducted through a national survey, will identify specific challenges faced by researchers in adhering to ORD practices. The second objective is to promote the development of a collaborative research community—*The CLARIN-CH LaDaD Network*—gathering researchers from different fields working with language data and data stewards. The community will seek to exchange knowledge, address common challenges, and establish a network of researchers and data stewards skilled in managing language data in compliance with FAIR principles. As a result, the community will provide actionable recommendations for composing a comprehensive compendium of ORD best practices. The third objective is the development of training sessions to address gaps in ORD knowledge and skills. These resources will include tutorials and practical guides that showcase best practices for working with language data tailored to the disciplinary needs of researchers working with language data. By promoting a deeper understanding of ORD practices and creating reusable training resources, the project aims to contribute to the sustainable advancement of research data management of language data in the spirit of open science beyond linguistics.

4 Conclusion

The CLARIN-CH training program stands as a key pillar in fostering sustainable and inclusive ORD practices for researchers working with language data in Switzerland. Through its multidimensional approach based on five axes of action—ranging from targeted needs assessment to the development of FAIR-aligned educational resources—it supports a growing, interdisciplinary community engaged in Open Science. By continuing to expand its initiatives and reach beyond linguistics, CLARIN-CH is laying the foundation for a robust and collaborative research environment across disciplines.

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An infrastructure for Historical Dutch Corpus Development

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Abstract

We describe an infrastructure for linguistic annotation of historical Dutch texts, consisting of tagging and lemmatisation guidelines, gold standard data, trained tagging models, the GALaHaD platform for automatic linguistic annotation and evaluation and the LAnCeLoT manual annotation tool. Users can upload unannotated materials to the GALaHaD platform, where trained PoS taggers and lemmatizers (including modern deep learning models) enrich the data. Results can be evaluated against newly expanded gold standard corpora (13th to 19th centuries) with various metrics, then exported for further analysis. The LAnCeLoT tool supports manual annotation correction at both type and token level, thus supporting the development of in-domain gold standard material.

1 Introduction

Historical texts are essential source material for both linguistic and digital humanities research. Adding linguistic annotation layers (e.g. part of speech and modern Dutch lemma) to historical text helps to make the data more accessible. Users need not be concerned with historical spelling variation when querying and analysing the data. High quality linguistic annotation of historical Dutch, however, is very problematic. Even though several tools have been made available, efforts were fragmented, training material was scarce (even absent for some periods) and diverse in adopted tagset and annotation guidelines. A common strategy to deal with typical issues of historical Dutch - nontrivial word segmentation, spelling variation, and inflectional features which are hard to classify, was lacking. This became very clear in the Nederlab project¹, where an attempt was made to annotate a large diachronic corpus of Dutch from the 6th - 21st century. Not only the quality of the linguistic annotation was not sufficient, the tagset and tagging principles, originally developed for modern Dutch, turned out to be unsuitable for historical Dutch. Supported by additional funding of both CLARIAH+ and currently SSHOC-NL, we have been developing an infrastructure, officially released in April 2025, to tackle the above mentioned issues. The infrastructure currently consists of:

- A diachronic tagset (TDN) and lemmatization guidelines for historical and contemporary Dutch
- Gold standard training and evaluation material (13th–19th century)
- Trained tagger-lemmatizers (currently PIE framework and Hugging Face transformers framework)
- Detailed evaluation of PoS tagging and lemmatization to allow for a methodologically sound choice of the appropriate annotation tool
- A user-friendly platform, GaLAHaD for corpus annotation and evaluation and LAnCeLoT, a service (tool) for creating gold standard corpus data

2 Tagset, tagging guidelines and lemmatisation principles

There are several tagsets for linguistic enrichment of text corpora containing historical and contemporary Dutch, such as the tagset of GiGaNT (Groot Geïntegreerd lexicon van de Nederlandse Taal, Ruitenberg et al., 2012), the corpus tagsets CGN/D-Coi (Van Eynde, 2005), the tagset used in the Corpus Gysseling (van Dalen Oskam and Depuydt, 2000) and Corpus Van Reenen-Mulder, the tagset for the Corpus

¹<https://www.nederlab.nl/>, a project funded by NWO (Dutch research council) that ran from 2013-2017

Oudnederlands². These tagsets differ in degree of detail (which features are tagged), in naming (what is called A in one tagset is called B in another) and in the method of tagging (lexical or functional). This makes the comparison of tagged corpus material difficult.

The Tagset for Diachronic corpus data of Dutch (TDN, Haga et al., 2024) was developed as a result of the re-evaluation of the GiGaNT tagset and after careful analysis of the mentioned corpus tagsets.

Core requirement for its development was that the TDN would be mappable to the existing tagsets, that TDN should be applicable to all stages of Dutch language and that a core tagset should be defined to allow production of large amounts of training and evaluation data. The proposed tagset was submitted to a large number of (historical) linguists who critically read along and provided valuable comments. Lemmatization principles are described in Depuydt et al., 2024.

The main design principles of the tagset and lemmatization are:

- TDN allows different levels of linguistic detail to enable projects with different aims to profit from each others efforts – the tag set and guidelines covers both extremely coarse-grained tagging (main PoS and lemma) and detailed annotation up to the annotation of difficult features like case.
- Token vs word: we characterize a word as a linguistic unit as opposed to a token which is separated from other tokens by whitespace and/or punctuation. Tagging is applied on the word level.
- Functional tagging: a word is assigned a part-of-speech without making any statement about the degree to which the combination of that word and part-of-speech is “lexicalized”.
- Mapping to other tagsets is possible: Corpus Gysseling/CRM tagset, CGN/D-COI, Universal Dependencies.
- Etymologically-based lemmatization: we uniformly assign modern Dutch lemmata throughout the whole period, based on etymological principles.

3 Gold standard corpora

The main gold standard corpora of historical Dutch available before the project were: Corpus of Old Dutch³, 500–1200; Corpus Gysseling⁴, 1200–1300; Corpus van Reenen-Mulder⁵, 1300-1400; Corpus Letters as Loot⁶, 1661-1783. Obviously, there are significant gaps in the coverage of these corpora. Moreover, the four corpora use three different tagsets and levels of detail. Within the project, we have unified the labeling of the Old Dutch, Gysseling, CRM, and Letters as Loot corpora.

In order to fill the gaps, we have extended the available material. Our aim is to ensure that at least 100,000 tokens per century are available, tagged according to the “core” level of the TDN tagset. Currently, a corpus of 583,254 tokens is available on <https://github.com/INL/galahad-corpus-data>.

4 Linguistic annotation: software tools

Pre-existing systems

We mention: *Adelheid*⁷, *PIE*⁸, *Frog*⁹ models for Middle Dutch, trained on CRM and Gysseling, *RNNTagger*¹⁰, *Nederlab* word normalization based approaches¹¹

²<https://corpusoudnederlands.ivdnt.org>

³<https://taalmaterialen.ivdnt.org/download/corpus-oudnederlands-online/>

⁴<https://taalmaterialen.ivdnt.org/download/tstc-corpus-gysseling/>

⁵<https://www.middelnederlands.nl/corpora/crm14/>

⁶<https://taalmaterialen.ivdnt.org/download/tstc-bab-gouden-standaard/>

⁷Developed by Hans van Halteren. (van Halteren and Rem, 2013)

⁸<https://github.com/emanjavacas/pie>, developed by Enrique Manjavacas, Ákos Kádár, and Mike Kestemont, (Manjavacas et al., 2019)

⁹van den Bosch et al., 2007, <http://languagemachines.github.io/frog/>

¹⁰<https://www.cis.uni-muenchen.de/~schmid/tools/RNNTagger/>, (Schmid, 2019)

¹¹Normalize spelling to modern Dutch, followed by application of tools for modern Dutch. (Tjong Kim Sang et al., 2017)

Transformer-based tagging

In order to benefit from advances in deep learning, we have developed a tagger-lemmatizer based on the BERT token classifier, implemented using the Hugging Face framework¹², and the GysBERT historical Dutch language model¹³.

Currently, GaLAHaD provides tagging and lemmatization models for the PIE framework (slightly adapted for the GaLAHaD platform) and for the transformer-based taggers.

5 GaLAHaD: Generating Linguistic Annotations for Historical Dutch

The platform serves two purposes. One is to make annotation and tool evaluation easily accessible to researchers, the other to make it easy for developers to contribute their tools and models in the platform, and thus compare them to other tools with gold standard material included in the platform.

Apart from the basic task of uploading and annotating corpus material, *GaLAHaD*¹⁴ is designed to enable end users to choose the optimal path for their material. The platform provides options to inspect and evaluate the result of the annotation process, in order to raise the awareness of typical errors and biases in the tools. The functionality of comparing annotation layers enables users to assess the accuracy of different tools on their data. It can be used both to evaluate a layer added by an automatic tagger with respect to a gold standard reference layer, or to compare layers added by different taggers. Disagreement between layers is not only represented by global statistics, but also illustrated by examples which are immediately visible in the tool. Different metrics and targeted evaluations for certain token types may lead to different conclusions as to the path of choice, cf. fig. 2, where the evaluation of clitic combinations with macro F1 (on the right) contradicts the rosy picture of the standard micro accuracy metric on the left. The resulting annotated material can be uploaded to the *Autosearch* corpus exploration environment and to the *LAnCeLoT* tool for manual correction of linguistic annotation.

For tool developers, the docker-based application architecture¹⁵ ensures easy contribution of tools to the platform. The application and taggers are hosted by the INT and are accessible with any CLARIN account. There is also the option to self-host an instance using the publicly available docker images from the INT docker hub or the open source code available on GitHub.

Annotation:	Group by:	Single/multiple analysis:
PoS	PoS	Both

TAGGER	MACRO PRECISION	MACRO RECALL	MACRO F1	MICRO ACCURACY	DETAILED EVALUATION
hug-tdn-all-enhanced	0.73	0.69	0.70	0.96	Details
hug-tdn-1600-1900	0.72	0.69	0.70	0.95	Details
hug-tdn-all	0.71	0.69	0.70	0.95	Details
hug-tdn-1400-1600	0.52	0.51	0.51	0.92	Details
pie-tdn-all	0.72	0.70	0.70	0.92	Details

Annotation:	Group by:	Single/multiple analysis:
PoS	PoS	Multiple

TAGGER	MACRO PRECISION	MACRO RECALL	MACRO F1	MICRO ACCURACY	DETAILED EVALUATION
pie-tdn-all	0.44	0.43	0.44	0.66	Details
hug-tdn-1600-1900	0.42	0.37	0.39	0.66	Details
hug-tdn-all-enhanced	0.43	0.37	0.38	0.64	Details
hug-tdn-all	0.40	0.37	0.38	0.64	Details
hug-tdn-1400-1600	0.23	0.22	0.22	0.57	Details

Figure 2: “Best” *Couranten corpus*¹⁶ tagger depending on evaluation type and token type

6 LAnCeLoT: Manual (correction of) linguistic annotation

We have developed a new version of the CoBaLT annotation tool, developed to construct corpus-based computational lexica and to correct word-level annotations in corpora (Kenter et al., 2012).

¹²<https://github.com/INL/int-huggingface-tagger>

¹³<https://huggingface.co/emanjavacas/GysBERT>

¹⁴<https://portal.clarin.ivdnt.org/galahad/>, <https://github.com/INL/galahad>

¹⁵<https://github.com/INL/galahad-taggers-dockerized>

¹⁶<https://couranten.ivdnt.org>

Key features of LAnCeLoT are:

- From type to token: Verification is not done token by token in running text, but at both the type and token level.
- Lexicon suggestions: For each type, suggestions for possible analyses are provided, using the INT GiGaNT lexicon.
- LAnCeLoT search: Used to index the uploaded corpora and display the concordances of each type in your corpus; can also be used to search within your uploaded corpus.

7 Future work

In the SSHOC-NL project, we are working on extending the platform with linguistic annotation tool types (named entity recognition, dependency parsing) and evaluation modes (document-level comparison of annotations, span-level annotation evaluation).

8 Acknowledgments

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Implementing and Promoting Data Citation for CLARIN Resources at FIN-CLARIN

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Abstract

Citation instructions are provided for all corpora in the Language Bank of Finland (LBF) to promote good reference practices in the use of research data. By utilizing persistent identifiers (PIDs) and curated metadata, uniform citations can be constructed automatically, even for forthcoming resources. This work outlines how citation components such as authors, publication year, versions, and publisher are currently managed in the LBF, and discusses challenges related to metadata accuracy and interoperability. Data citation practices could be harmonized across CLARIN repositories by supporting data citation more directly via CLARIN compliant metadata.

1 Introduction

Today, the use and reuse of shared data is commonplace in scientific research. In order to ensure that studies can be verified and replicated, researchers should provide persistent references to their data. Data referencing is technically possible, but the practices of citing data are not yet well established in all fields and may require additional effort from the researcher. Data repositories can support researchers by systematically offering citation information for the data sets distributed by them, as recommended in the data citation guide by the Publications Office of the European Union and Jessop, 2022.

In this article, we describe how data set citation practices are encouraged and supported by the Language Bank of Finland (LBF)¹. The LBF is a national research infrastructure (RI) service offered by the FIN-CLARIAH RI² through the University of Helsinki and CSC - IT Center for Science. It is partly funded by the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture through various funding instruments. The Ministry and its affiliated organizations are committed to promoting the FAIR principles (data should be

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¹<https://www.kielipankki.fi/language-bank/>

²<https://www.kielipankki.fi/organization/fin-clariah/>

Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, see Wilkinson et al., 2016) and are developing Fair-data services together to support the curation and storage of research data.

2 Citation Instructions at the Language Bank of Finland

The LBF maintains a public website (the Portal)³ with information about the services of the LBF, including lists of the hosted language resources, e.g., corpora and tools. The list of corpora⁴ is automatically generated from a separate resource database (DB). The citation instructions for each corpus in the LBF are generated from the resource metadata stored in the DB. The instructions appear in the Portal via dynamic links using the resource PID as the citation key. The citation instructions for corpora consist of the following elements: **Creators (Authors), Publication year, Title and Version, Publisher, and PID**.

It is essential to provide a persistent identifier (PID) for each data set (Wittenburg, 2019). In the LBF, the PID used in the citation instruction always points to the metadata record of the resource in question. The metadata record provides the necessary details and can be updated when required, while the citation text can remain short and efficient. The citations work in a persistent and uniform way for all resources, regardless of the platform where the contents are.

In case a new resource is known to have been completed by a researcher and the deposition with the LBF is expected to take place in the near future, the LBF can provide citation instructions for the forthcoming resource, even before it is officially available.⁵ The citation instruction can be reliably generated in the Portal as soon as the necessary details, including the PID, are included in the DB.

License information is not included in the resource-specific citation instructions of the LBF since licenses may be updated in the metadata. Moreover, since the individual resources are centrally maintained by the LBF and are not expected to change significantly after their publication date, the date of last access or retrieval has been excluded from the citation instructions in the LBF. The PID alone makes sure that a referenced dataset can be reused later, regardless of when it was accessed⁶.

Accurate resource metadata are essential for the automatic generation of reference instructions. In this section, we describe why and how certain fields of information are included in the citation instructions of the LBF. We also point out some issues that researchers and repositories need to consider.

2.1 Creators (Authors)

According to the current practices in the LBF, the ordered list of authors or **creators** is set in the deposition agreement of the resource. When negotiating agreements, the Language Bank encourages depositors to list individual people as creators, as recommended by, e.g., Lenardič and de Maiti Tekavčič (2024), as this is good practice in terms of merit, provenance, and scientific replicability. However, in some cases, it can be appropriate to attribute organizations instead of or in addition to individuals. The depositors make the final decision on authorship.

When reviewing the older resource metadata records of the LBF, we discovered that deposition agreements and email archives play a crucial role when defining the parties that should be attributed. Without a written agreement, additional efforts are often required in case any information about authorship is missing. For instance, the 'IPR holders' or 'Licensors', defined in some metadata records, are not necessarily the same parties that should be cited as the 'creators' or 'authors'. For some original data that is available under a public license, attribution information may not have been explicitly stated at the source.

For each resource in the LBF, information about the creators is stored in the DB as the first and last names, listed in the order of appearance in the citation. For a more general solution, the list of authors/creators including their contact details, affiliations and the order of citation, should be stated in the metadata record.

³<https://www.kielipankki.fi/language-bank/>

⁴<https://www.kielipankki.fi/corpora/>

⁵"Data should be properly cited, even if not generally available, not fully available, or available only on restrictive terms." (Publications Office of the European Union & Jessop, 2022)

⁶For a discussion on assigning new PIDs when datasets change over time, see Matthiesen and Dieckmann (2019).

2.2 Publication Year

For citation instructions, the publication year is interpreted as the year the corpus was published in the Language Bank (even if the collection was previously made available elsewhere), since this is the publication time of the specific resource edition over which the repository has control. The publication year is retrieved from the DB and formatted as a four-digit number. For resources that have not yet been published, the text "forthcoming" is shown instead.

2.3 Title and Version

The title of the resource is agreed with the depositor. The same title is stored in the database and in the corresponding metadata record in English and Finnish. The resource title usually includes extensions describing the variant (e.g., Korp or Download⁷) and the version of the resource. Like books, data sets might be published again as new versions or editions. More recent versions can contain more data, or some annotation layers may have been added or updated, e.g. by using an improved annotation method.

2.4 Publisher

In the citation instructions generated by the LBF, the publisher of every data set is LBF, since the LBF is responsible for maintaining the deposited data and for curating the metadata (see Publications Office of the European Union and Jessop, 2022). Only LBF staff can make changes to the metadata.

2.5 Persistent Identifier (PID)

At the LBF, the PID of a resource points to the metadata record of the resource in question⁸. Consequently, it is possible to provide unambiguous citation instructions even before the resource has been officially published by the repository. This approach also allows the LBF to implement persistent tombstone pages after the data itself is no longer available, according to the FAIR principle A2⁹. In the citation instructions of the LBF, the PIDs are also made "actionable", i.e., clickable, as recommended in the data citation guide by the Publications Office of the European Union and Jessop (2022). The link to the data access location is not included in the citation instructions. The metadata record provides the data access location in CMDI¹⁰ compliant format for humans and machines.

The LBF uses URN-based PIDs supported by the National Library of Finland¹¹. Handles are also supported as a backup system¹². In line with Broeder et al. (2009), our PIDs do not contain semantic information. For practical reasons, new PIDs are constructed from dates and running numbers¹³.

By clicking on the PID of the resource, the user is directed to the metadata record that provides information on how to access and use the resource in an efficient and appropriate way (specific license restrictions, technical documentation or guidelines for the user, annotation anomalies, etc.). The metadata can be updated by the LBF, e.g., to fix typos or to add new or previously missing information. Minor updates of the content of the resource itself do not result in a new metadata record and a new PID as long as the content is expected to be compatible with the resource version prior to the update. A minor update can be described just by editing the metadata record and the version number after the resource title that appears in the citation. For a more in-depth discussion, see Matthiesen and Dieckmann (2019, section 6).

2.6 Formatting the Output

The citation instructions are offered via the list of corpora in the LBF Portal in two languages, English and Finnish. Links to the instructions for individual resources can also be found in the metadata records. The links can be manually constructed if the resource PID is known¹⁴.

⁷See <https://www.kielipankki.fi/support/corpus-location/>

⁸For a discussion of the special status of a "citable PID", see Matthiesen and Dieckmann (2019, section 7).

⁹<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/a2-metadata-accessible-even-data-no-longer-available/>

¹⁰<https://www.clarin.eu/content/cmdr-component-metadata-infrastructure>

¹¹<https://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi-fe2024051430651>

¹²The PIDs can be resolved if one of the systems is unavailable: https://urn.fi/urn:nbn:fi:lb-201710212#Persistent_identifiers

¹³However, the PIDs created by the LBF do not carry semantics. Not even the minting date can be derived from the identifier.

¹⁴For example, <https://www.kielipankki.fi/viittaus/?key=urn:nbn:fi:lb-2024051601&lang=en>.

The plain text citation instructions are constructed roughly according to the APA style¹⁵ with one exception: the version information is included in the title. The general structure is in line with other CLARIN centres, e.g., CLARIN DSpace at LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ¹⁶. Unlike LBF, CLARIN DSpace does not use the type attribute (e.g., “[data set]”).

In addition to the citation instructions in plain text, the BibTeX and Zotero codes are also provided. The most commonly used bibliographic styles for BibTeX do not include an entry type for data sets especially. The reference text is generated at the LBF with the BibTeX entry type `@misc`, which is also used by CLARIN DSpace and produces reasonable-looking reference items. For Zotero, the format instruction is rendered in BibTeX syntax as `@techreport`, since this produced the best result (in 2015). Finally, an additional link is generated to search for references to the resource from Google Scholar.

3 Conclusions and Future Prospects

The LBF system for generating citation instructions was developed in 2015. Although it has stood the test of time, the instructions could be improved and harmonized with the present standards in CLARIN.

Research data should not be cited by referencing related articles or books alone. A published article cannot be modified after publication and can easily become outdated, whereas the metadata record of the data set can be updated when necessary. However, citation indices may still reward researchers for their traditional publications rather than their published data sets. In individual cases, researchers should be able to cite both the data set and some specific publications related to the data. If necessary, the metadata record can highlight the most relevant publication to be cited in addition to the resource itself.

At the LBF, the information for all components in the citations is currently retrieved from the internal resource DB. This allows the LBF to generate citations for forthcoming resources, since the DB includes information about the publication status of each resource. The DB also supports the order of author/creator names, unlike the current CMDI metadata profile used by the LBF.

Ideally, the details required for generating citation instructions should be included in the public metadata records of all data sets in CLARIN. CMDI components supporting consistent citations should be designed by the community and deployed over time by all repositories. This would allow for the development of central citation services, whereas the local consortia could focus on providing high-quality metadata. At the LBF, we are working on augmenting the CMDI schema to achieve this goal.

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¹⁵<https://apastyle.apa.org/style-grammar-guidelines/references/examples/data-set-references>

¹⁶<https://doi.org/10.17616/R30G6W>

Users' Experience and Development Priorities for CLARIN.SI

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1 Introduction

CLARIN.SI, the Slovenian node of the CLARIN infrastructure, recently celebrated its 10th anniversary. Since its establishment, the infrastructure has evolved considerably, engaging in a range of activities at both national and international levels. An overview of its organisation, main areas of activity, and impact on the research community is presented in Erjavec et al., 2025.

To mark this milestone and support planning for the next decade, we set out to gather user feedback that would highlight what works well, what needs improvement, and how we might reach new users who are not yet familiar with the infrastructure. With these goals in mind, we designed a survey, focusing on the quality of the tools, resources, and services offered by CLARIN.SI. To engage both current and potential users, we shared the survey not only within our usual networks but also more broadly, aiming to reach as wide an audience as possible.¹

2 Method

User opinions were collected through an online survey (in Slovenian), designed and administered using the IKA survey platform. The questionnaire consisted of 50 questions divided into 8 thematic sections. To structure the survey, we first catalogued the full range of CLARIN.SI's existing tools and services, and organized the sections around key anticipated user activities, such as depositing or downloading resources, using tools, and attending events. An additional section addressed potential future activities, focusing on areas not yet covered by the infrastructure.

The survey began by collecting basic participant information and identifying which CLARIN.SI tools and services—if any—they had experience with. Based on their responses, participants were directed to relevant subsections where they could evaluate specific aspects of the infrastructure. In each section, they were also invited to comment on what they felt was missing. These questions were open-ended to allow for unanticipated input and will be presented in more detail in the extended version of this paper.

The survey ran from 28 February to 1 April 2025 and was disseminated through academic, educational, and professional networks in Slovenia, aimed at current and potential CLARIN.SI users. A total of 170 participants submitted valid partial or complete responses. The average completion time was 11 minutes and 15 seconds. Although the survey included prompts to encourage answering all questions, participants were allowed to skip items, so the number of responses (denoted below by N) varies by question.

3 Results

3.1 The Participants

The affiliations (N=169) of participants was mainly with academic and research institutions. Almost half of them (47%) reported working in a research institution and 34% worked or studied at a higher education institution. Some were employed in private or public companies (7%), public administration

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¹The survey was limited to users in Slovenia.

(4%), primary or secondary schools (2%), cultural institutions (2%), and non-profit organizations (1%). An additional 4% selected "Other," for instance, media houses and libraries.

In terms of professional roles (N=169), over half of the participants (54%) were engaged in research, including doctoral and postdoctoral work. Other were students (19%) or educators (7%) at different education levels, or involved with technical and development work (7%), administrative tasks (6%), and management (3%). The remaining 4% specified other roles, such as translation or language editing. Disciplinary backgrounds (N=169) were mainly in the humanities (51%), social sciences (20%) and technical sciences (19%), followed by natural sciences (7%), and medicine (1%).

Most participants (N=167) reported they conduct language-related work, however, 13% reported no language-related activities. Their main fields of work (multiple answers were possible) were language technologies (37%), natural language processing (26%), linguistic description (30%), translation (19%), and language teaching (16%). Other fields, such as theoretical linguistics (14%), linguistic prescription (14%), literary studies (5%), historiography (5%), journalism (4%), sociology (2%), library science (2%) and law (2%), were also represented. The sample (N=169) was diverse in age, with the largest groups aged 35–44 (26%), 45–54 (24%), and 25–34 (21%). Smaller segments included respondents aged 55–64 (14%), 18–24 (12%), 65 or older (2%), and one respondent under 18. 57% of the participants were women, 36% were men, 3% another gender, and 4% preferred not to disclose.

The participants (N=158) reported their experience with various components of the CLARIN.SI infrastructure (multiple answers were possible). 29% had deposited resources, and 44% had downloaded resources from the CLARIN.SI repository. 49% had experience with CLARIN.SI provided concordancers and text analysis tools. 30% followed CLARIN.SI news, 19% had attended a presentation of CLARIN.SI, and 16% had integrated CLARIN.SI into their own teaching or presentations. Nearly one-third of respondents (32%) reported no direct experience with the infrastructure.

3.2 Depositing Resources in CLARIN.SI

The core service offered by CLARIN.SI is its repository of language resources and tools. The repository, set up in 2016, runs on the open-source CLARIN-DSpace platform and now archives around 700 entries.

Among the respondents who had deposited resources in the CLARIN.SI repository (N = 46), the experience was overall positive. The highest-rated items on a 5-point scale included trust in data storage (avg. = 4.8), the importance of deposition for open science (4.8), the belief that deposition of resources supports their reuse in the community (4.5) and increases resource visibility (4.2). The efficiency of the editorial review process was rated highly (4.2), but the ease of different technical aspects slightly lower: the ease of license selection (3.9), submission workflow (3.6), technical file preparation (3.5), and metadata entry (3.5). Among those who used support services (N = 27), the helpdesk received very high ratings: communication clarity and friendliness averaged 4.7, and effectiveness and timeliness of help averaged 4.9. The availability (3.8) and clarity (3.8) of instructions were rated lower. Open-ended user suggestions also included, for instance, simplifying the update process and metadata entry, enabling post-submission edits, and adding the option to monitor downloads of deposited resources.²

3.3 Finding and Downloading Resources from CLARIN.SI

Users with experience retrieving resources from the CLARIN.SI repository (N = 64) reported an overall positive experience. The most highly rated aspects were download reliability and speed (avg. = 4.5), followed by the quality (4.2) and diversity (4.2) of available resources. Participants also emphasized that CLARIN.SI resources are important for their work (4.1) and help save time in preparing their own data (4.1). Licensing information was considered clear and understandable (4.0). Slightly lower, but still positive ratings were given to the currency of resources (3.9), metadata clarity (3.8), ease of search (3.7), and the suitability of formats for further use (3.7). Open-ended suggestions for improvement included more precise and user-friendly search functions, data formats better suited for integration (e.g., JSON), concrete examples of how the data can be used, and improved language accessibility, such as providing Slovenian descriptions for Slovenian-language corpora.

²Even though this option in fact exists.

3.4 Using CLARIN.SI Concordancers and Language Tools

CLARIN.SI hosts several concordancers, in particular noSketch Engine (Kilgarriff et al., 2014) and KonText (Machálek, 2020). Furthermore, we have three installations of noSketch Engine: the old “Bonito”³ and the new “Crystal” version, as well as Crystal that requires log-in but allows more functions. Two further on-line tools are included among the CLARIN.SI services: Korpusnik (Kosem et al., 2023), gives an overview of word usage based on five Slovenian corpora, while SENTA aims to simplify complex Slovenian sentences while preserving the original meaning (Žagar et al., 2024).

Across all tools, user engagement levels varied (N=58), with Bonito (52%) and Crystal (50%) being the most widely used, followed by the KonText concordancer (38%), Korpusnik (12%), Senta (5%), and NoSketch Engine with login (11%). NoSketch Engine Crystal was described as easily accessible (avg. = 4.0), fast (4.0) and clear (3.9), albeit lacking certain functionalities (3.0). Similarly, NoSketch Engine Bonito was described as easily accessible (avg. = 4.1), fast (3.8) and clear (4.0), while lacking certain functionalities (2.9) and visual appeal (2.8). The version with login was rated lower, with scores ranging from 2.7 to 3.7. The users of KonText highlighted the ease of access (4.2), speed (3.9) and user-friendliness (3.8), with functionalities rated the lowest (2.8). Korpusnik was rated particularly well for ease of use (4.6) and clarity (4.8), while Senta – though less used – was positively received in terms of interface design (avg. = 4.7) and user-friendliness (4.6). The open-ended user suggestions for different concordancers and tools will be provided in the full paper.

3.5 Staying Informed about CLARIN.SI

Among the respondents who addressed the topic of communication and updates from CLARIN.SI (N = 37), most reported receiving information via the CLARIN.SI website (62%) and the CLASSLA mailing list (35%), while other channels such as X/Twitter, LinkedIn, and Discord reached a smaller share of users (14–19%). Ratings in this category were slightly lower compared to those for services and tools. Participants found the news relatively clear and engaging (avg. = 3.8), and the frequency of updates generally appropriate (3.6). There was less agreement with statements that the updates motivated them to use CLARIN.SI services or resources (3.4), that they were useful for their work (3.3), and that they were sufficiently visible (3.0). The idea of a dedicated CLARIN.SI newsletter received mixed support (3.4). In open-ended responses, users suggested more frequent and concise updates, aggregated formats such as weekly or monthly summaries, and a greater focus on practical tips, new resources, and tool promotion.

3.6 Attending CLARIN.SI Related Presentations and Events

Among respondents who had attended a CLARIN.SI event (N = 22), most referenced participation in the Language Technologies and Digital Humanities conferences, held biennially in Ljubljana, and related events, including the JOTA lectures and the CLASSLA-Express workshops. The overall experience was rated highly: the average rating of usefulness for their work or research was 4.1, with even higher scores for clarity (4.3), appropriate level of expertise (4.5), and event organization (4.4). Participants also appreciated the opportunities for interaction (4.3), while the worst-rated in this category was the accessibility of materials after the event (3.7). In open-ended feedback, some users called for more practical, tool-oriented workshops, broader thematic coverage (e.g. in digital humanities), and better promotion.

3.7 Including CLARIN.SI in Presentations and Lectures

Incorporating CLARIN.SI into their lectures or presentations (N = 21) was activated in various ways (multiple responses were possible). The most common type of integration included citing resources from the CLARIN.SI repository (81%), demonstrating the usability of tools or data through their own practical use (67%), and referencing CLARIN.SI in discussions of research methodology (57%). An equal share (57%) reported showcasing tools or resources through live demonstrations. Just under half presented related concepts such as open data or language resources (52%) or explicitly directed audiences to the

³Note, however, that we have recently shut down Bonito, as it was continuously and very aggressively harvested, leading to outages of the infrastructure.

infrastructure (48%). A smaller group (24%) provided comprehensive overviews of CLARIN.SI's structure and purpose. However, users did not find CLARIN.SI content to be particularly well-suited or easily accessible for use in presentations. The availability of materials for citation was rated the highest (avg. = 3.7), followed by the usefulness of tools and resources for clear demonstration (3.6), the accessibility of general information (3.3), and the perceived success in encouraging further engagement among audiences (2.7). Suggestions for improvement focused on offering ready-made slides and handouts, pedagogical materials based on real use cases, and more substantial support for educational integration.

3.8 Learning about CLARIN.SI

For respondents who had not (yet) used CLARIN.SI (N = 41), primary motivators for future use included better awareness of the infrastructure's structure and purpose (66%) and more examples of good practice and concrete applications of resources (44%). Many desired more accessible information about updates, events, and opportunities (27%), as well as targeted training or workshops (22%). Less common were requests for increased technical support, a wider range of language resources, and customisation options (10–17%). 12% indicated that CLARIN.SI was in no context relevant to their work. In terms of perceived barriers, the suggestions for improvement largely revolved around visibility and accessibility. Several respondents reported they were unaware of CLARIN.SI, or had only vague knowledge of its existence. It was noted that the website is challenging to navigate, and that stronger outreach is needed, including integration into formal education, and increased social media presence and promotional visibility.

3.9 Priorities for Further Development

The respondents were asked to rate the importance of various future development priorities for CLARIN.SI on a scale from 1 (not a priority) to 5 (top priority). The highest-rated priorities were the development of new language tools (avg. = 3.2), better maintenance and updates of existing tools (3.0) and integration of CLARIN.SI with other services (3.0). Improving data search and download processes (2.9) and increasing the diversity of language resources (2.9) followed closely. Slightly lower priorities included improved user support and documentation (2.8), data quality control (2.7), increased and targeted training opportunities (2.7), and clearer presentation of the infrastructure's composition and accessibility (2.7). Lower still were more frequent and tailored updates on news and events (2.5), better presentation of CLARIN.SI organization (2.4), and improving the data deposition and storage process (1.9). Importantly, a relatively high proportion of respondents selected "I cannot assess" for several items, suggesting a need for further clarification of certain aspects of the infrastructure. A recurring theme in open-ended questions was visibility and discoverability—both in terms of finding specific resources via the search interface and increasing the general awareness of CLARIN.SI within the broader research community. Several noted the importance of keeping corpora up to date, especially by filling historical gaps (e.g. 20th century texts) and incorporating more diverse or under-represented data types. Users also expressed a strong interest in greater pedagogical integration, particularly in university curricula.

4 Conclusion

The survey results provide a comprehensive insight into user experiences, needs, and expectations regarding CLARIN.SI. Overall, the infrastructure is well-regarded by its users, particularly in terms of data reliability, open science support, and perceived usefulness of deposited resources. The deposition process is generally seen as straightforward, though some aspects—such as metadata preparation and updating existing entries—still present challenges. Users value the availability of concordancers and tools, commenting mainly on the limited functionalities for their work. Events receive high rates for professional quality, although more ready-made materials are needed for further use. Communication about CLARIN.SI could be improved, also to attract new potential users. Finally, the highest urgency was expressed for developing and maintaining language tools, improving search functionality, and expanding resource diversity. In the full version of the paper, we will discuss the most urgent user-identified priorities as a complement to the CLARIN.SI strategy 2024-2030, also situating them within the broader context of similar evaluative initiatives (De Smedt, 2020, Nicolas et al., 2018).

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CLARIN in the UK Digital Research Infrastructure

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Abstract

This paper describes the initiatives within the UK to develop a national digital research infrastructure. This infrastructure brings together different aspects, including digital resources, computing services, and associated skills to build an interconnected, human, FAIR and sustainable infrastructure which addresses the needs of Arts and Humanities (A&H) researchers and practitioners. Key elements include the CLARIN-UK repository, the CLARIN Knowledge Centre for Digital Resources for the Languages in Ireland and Britain, and Digital Skills in the Arts and Humanities Network (DISKAH). The paper explores these developments as well as the opportunities to interact with CLARIN infrastructures and initiatives to benefit the wider community.

1 Introduction

In the United Kingdom (UK), ongoing initiatives to establish a homogenous Digital Research Infrastructures (DRI) that supports researchers in disciplines related to the Arts and Humanities are taking place. Building on efforts to connect communities to data services, institutional and national computing infrastructures, as well as software, workflows, and digital skills curricula, the outcomes of these initiatives are of interest beyond disciplinary and national boundaries. Some of these efforts are funded via the Infrastructure for Digital Arts and Humanities (iDAH) programme of the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC), which is part of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), the umbrella organization for research funding in the UK. The following sections are organised as follows. Section 2 introduces the AHRC's Infrastructure for Digital Arts and Humanities (iDAH), while Section 3 and Section 4 describe elements of this infrastructure, including the data service, the Oxford Text Archive (OTA), and a digital skills community, and the Digital Skills in the Arts and Humanities Network (DISKAH). Together, they bridge communities and resources to create and showcase humanities-led use cases for DRI.

2 UK Infrastructure of Digital Arts and Humanities (iDAH)

The Infrastructure for Digital Arts and Humanities (iDAH) programme encompasses a set of data services to underpin Arts and Humanities research, including the Oxford Text Archive (OTA), the national repository for literary and linguistic resources. Other data services include repositories in the domains of archaeology, scientific collections, museums, and performing arts. The iDAH programme runs alongside wider efforts from UKRI to identify and support software, workflows, compute services and digital skills.

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While there is some discussion of shared resource discovery, data interoperability, and possible federation of computing and data services, progress is cautious in these areas, because the specialised repositories recognise the benefits of domain-specific services and maintaining close connection with research communities, and the possible dangers of moving towards one-size-fits-all generic services.

Within IDAH, the Oxford Text Archive (OTA) is the leading CLARIN repository. This data service has operated uninterrupted since 1976, supporting literary, linguistic and historical disciplines by taking deposits of digital datasets created by researchers, preserving those resources, and making them available for reuse. From 1996 to 2010, it hosted the Arts and Humanities Data Service (AHDS) Centre for Literature, Languages and Linguistics, funded by AHRC and JISC. It was a founding centre in CLARIN, as well as a key participant in the preparatory phase of CLARIN.

2.1 CLARIN-UK consortium

Participation in CLARIN is organized via a consortium of the leading centres in corpus and computational linguistics in the UK, including teams at the British Library, University of Birmingham, Cardiff University, Coventry University, University of Edinburgh, University of Glasgow, Lancaster University, University of Leeds, University of Wolverhampton, King's College London, University of Sheffield, with a national coordinator at the University of Oxford. The CLARIN-UK consortium also includes those responsible for key resources in the international research community, including #LancsBox, CQPweb, GATE, PyMusas tools, Edinburgh NLP software, the National Corpus of Contemporary Welsh, Scottish Corpus of Texts and Speech and WMatrix, curated by centres of expertise of international standing. The consortium is committed to contributing to CLARIN's goals in the areas of open science and contributing in-kind resources and effort. It is important to note that UK full membership of CLARIN means that the entire research community can benefit.

3 Oxford Text Archive (OTA)

From its inception to 2016, the Oxford Text Archive was hosted in the Oxford University Computing Services. It was the start of a number of services in support of the digital humanities, including the Computers in Teaching Initiative (CTI), and the CTI Centre for Textual Studies (Fraser, Sutherland, & Condron, 2000), Humbul Humanities Hub resource discovery service, Centre for Computing in the Humanities, Humanities Computing Unit and the AHDS. After these activities were discontinued, the OTA was hosted in the Bodleian Libraries between 2016 and 2020. Once again, tensions between the priorities of institutional infrastructure and the external, worldwide remit of the OTA came to the surface, and in the next phase of development, the OTA moved to the Faculty of Linguistics, Philology and Phonetics in the Humanities Division of the University of Oxford (FLPP).

The services to the community, which include depositing and downloading resources, and support for users, have been funded at times as a national service, for example, as part of the AHDS 1996-2010, and for long periods have been offered pro bono and on a 'best efforts' basis, without dedicated funding.

Throughout this time, deposits with the OTA have ensured the ongoing availability, sustainability and long-term preservation of resources after the end of the lifetime of research projects, increasing the return on investment for funders of research projects. The current funding from AHRC has put these services onto a more professional and sustainable basis, while also offering full access to legacy collections.

3.1 OTA technological platform

The OTA migrated to the CLARIN DSpace repository platform in 2019. This has offered numerous advantages. As well as providing the key repository functions, it offers secure cross-border authentication and authorisation, enabling researchers in many countries worldwide to log in with their own institutional logins. The following stages of development will involve upgrading to DSpace7 and improving the functionality for users to submit resources for deposit via the website, as well as offering enhanced repository services for audio and video resources. The deployment of DSpace as a repository solution has been key to leveraging pan-European expertise and deepening and improving connections with CLARIN.

The OTA is committed to taking the necessary steps to ensure compliance with FAIR principles, and an application is in preparation for certification as an approved CLARIN centre, which includes CoreTrust-Seal certification. Collaboration with international initiatives is essential when it comes to expertise in multilingual digital resources for literary and linguistic research. CLARIN offers important benefits for the visibility, usability and sustainability of the digital collections. For visibility, it means that resources in the repository can be discovered not only via the OTA website, but also via the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory. For usability, CLARIN is developing cutting-edge solutions for linking datasets to tools for search, analysis, exploration and visualisation, via web services and the CLARIN Language Resources Switchboard. For sustainability, partnership with CLARIN provides access to research infrastructure, funding opportunities, and expertise from peer institutions acting as expert centres and national repositories in the network. The UK became a full member of CLARIN in 2025, but the ongoing integration with the infrastructure has already been under way for a long time, with the OTA offering a gateway to CLARIN for all researchers in the UK.

3.2 New accessions

In terms of collections, the OTA has over 70,000 deposits that include texts dating from BCE to the present day, and that cover a range of languages, including, of course, widely used languages like English, Arabic, and French, but also some less common languages such as Algonquin, Middle Irish, and Fulah. However, in addition to texts, the OTA also contains linguistic corpora, lexica, and dictionaries, with the capacity to contain language models, grammars, and tools for the processing and analysis of texts.

Latest acquisitions include the Open English WordNet, a lexical network of the English language useful for natural language processing and for visualising English as a graph. The OTA has also recently received numerous corpora - including the multimedia corpus Interactional Variation Online, which is a corpus of recorded virtual meetings. Efforts are also being made to collect resources related to the study of other languages of Britain and Ireland, including a subset of *Geiriadur Prifysgol Cymru: A Dictionary of the Welsh Language* (GPC), which is in the process of being deposited.

Finally, the OTA has recently set up a new collection for Taylor Editions, which are student-created digital editions of segments of texts stored within Oxford Libraries. In this way, the OTA is now integrated into teaching students the pipeline for creating, publishing, and disseminating digital texts.

3.3 DR-LIB

The OTA is also at the centre of a new CLARIN Knowledge Centre on Digital Resources for the Languages in Ireland and Britain, or DR-LIB. This distributed centre aims to run a help desk manned by a network of language experts to help answer questions related to resources available to aid research on languages native or present within the UK and Ireland, including historical varieties. While the DR-LIB is still in its infancy, having been established in 2024, the ambition is for it to serve as the foundation for a network of researchers working on Celtic languages, providing recommendations for best practices in working with under-resourced languages in a digital setting.

As part of this effort, the DR-LIB is collaborating with the Multilingual Digital Humanities community interest group of the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association to further discussions on how under-resourced languages can draw on each other's resources and expertise. Moreover, the OTA is currently leading efforts to map Celtic resources with the goal of eventually adding them to CLARIN resource discovery services, such as the CLARIN resource families, and, where appropriate, to the OTA. Per these efforts, 65 resources have been identified so far, and - as previously mentioned - a subset of the GPC, the Welsh Language Dictionary, is being added to the OTA.

3.4 Collaborations with other infrastructures and initiatives

The UK membership of CLARIN aligns with UK participation in other European research infrastructures, particularly EHRI, with which CLARIN-UK experts have been working closely through several projects and workshops on utilising language technology to facilitate new forms of digital research involving Holocaust testimonies. CLARIN-UK also plays a role in the Multilingual Digital Humanities

in the UK and Ireland community interest group and collaborates with the Digital Skills in Arts and Humanities Network (DISKAH), which is described in the following section.

4 Digital Skills in the Arts and Humanities Network

Addressing the digital and data literacy gap within the A&H community to utilise DRI fully requires a unified, yet customisable and context-dependent, approach. UK efforts to tackle this challenge have seen various projects piloting activities funded by iDAH and UKRI-DRI. These initiatives focus on the challenges posed by the expanding adoption of computational and data-driven research methods, also known as data science approaches, and particularly Artificial Intelligence algorithms, in the collection, analysis, and access of large-scale data within A&H research.

The Digital Skills in Visual and Material Culture project, led by the University of Brighton from 2023-2024, developed a training framework, including a curriculum and a train-the-trainer approach. Skills are organised according to the data life cycle: 1) Planning and management, 2) Creation and processing, 3) Archiving and preservation, 4) Use/reuse and analysis, 5) Publishing and sharing. Various activities were conducted following this curriculum using scaffolded learning with A&H communities. The training resources designed for scaffolded learning were structured according to the Skills4EOSC approach (Filiposka et al., 2023), incorporating Open and FAIR principles by designing training materials and datasets open access which learners can access and adapt according to their own needs. These resources cover topics including digitisation (Rodriguez Echavarria et al., 2024a, 2024b), FAIR data (Rodriguez Echavarria, 2023), copyright (Rodriguez Echavarria & Samaroudi, 2024), and data ethics (Samaroudi, 2024). These resources are available through the DARIAH campus platform (<https://campus.dariah.eu>). The training utilises the D4Science platform (Candela, Castelli, & Pagano, 2023), which provides access to Virtual Research Environment, on-the-cloud platforms and datasets to support training.

Since 2024, the Digital Skills in the Arts and Humanities Network (DISKAH) has brought together the University of Brighton, Durham University, University of Exeter, London College of Communication, University of Edinburgh, Kings Digital Lab at King's College London, University College London, and DARIAH-UK. During the next two years, DISKAH will engage with researchers to investigate use cases of large-scale compute through a 12-month training programme in which several existing AI-driven workflows, including data mining/data analytics (e.g. authorship attribution, information processing strategies, image-pattern recognition) and data visualisation approaches, will be scaled up so that they can benefit from the capabilities of large-scale compute. The network outcomes will include training opportunities as well as open access training materials for researchers in the UK and beyond, including those communities within CLARIN, to benefit from. The aim is for these outcomes to reach A&H researchers at large, to introduce them to the capabilities and opportunities afforded by high-performance computing. In the medium- and long-term, the expected impact is to challenge established assumptions about digital methods and computing resources traditionally designed for technically oriented fields, and to drive multidisciplinary innovation.

For DISKAH, a preliminary evaluation was conducted to assess the early efforts via the Digital Skills in Visual and Material Culture project (Rodriguez Echavarria & Samaroudi, 2025). The evaluation consisted of pre-training and post-training surveys for learners attending training activities to assess the overall experience, quality, and effectiveness of the training. The evaluation indicated that strong catalysts for long-term adoption of data and digital skills amongst learners are having a sense of *agency* and *self-reliance*. In addition, supporting research and working practices, professional development and career advancement motivate people to seek out training; these efforts are often hampered by not knowing what to look for and where to access training. Affordable, inclusive and effective *scaffolded learning*, including clearly structured and communicated *skills curricula*, as well as effective learning methods, training infrastructure and FAIR resources, are also key. Also, expanding and democratising *access to research infrastructures*, through which learners can continue to build capacity past the training and share their knowledge with others, is important to ensure the long-term impact of training efforts.

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CLARIAH-AT: Back (and) to the Future

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Abstract

This contribution presents the CLARIAH-AT consortium which coordinates and drives Austrian activities in the European research infrastructures CLARIN and DARIAH. The paper describes the CLARIAH-AT infrastructure and its activities.

1 Introduction

The Austrian consortium CLARIAH-AT with members from Austrian universities, research institutions, and libraries, coordinates and drives Austrian activities in the European research infrastructures CLARIN and DARIAH. Since Austria is one of the founding members of CLARIN and DARIAH, before we describe the current activities of the consortium, we will go back into the history of CLARIAH-AT. Then we will describe the CLARIAH-AT infrastructure with the CLARIN B-Centres and CLARIN K-Centres. Furthermore, we will look into the initiatives in building and fostering the Austrian community and give a brief outlook into future activities.

2 History of CLARIAH-AT

Austria was already active in the preparatory phase of CLARIN, acting under the umbrella of CLARIN-AT. One of the first initiatives in this phase was a survey on existing language resources and language technologies (Wissik and Budin, 2010) to prepare the weaving of a network and infrastructure in Austria. At this time the coordinating institution was the University of Vienna (Mörth and Wissik, 2018). When also DARIAH became an European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), the Austrian national actors in CLARIN and DARIAH joined forces to use synergies and started the core group to conduct their activities as CLARIAH-AT network under the coordination of the Austrian Academy of Sciences on behalf of the Austrian Federal Ministry of Science, Research and Economy (Mörth and Wissik, 2018). However, it took until 2019 for the informal CLARIAH-AT network to become an official consortium acting under CLARIAH-AT. Before that, the activities presented to the public were disseminated under the umbrella of the virtual network Digital Humanities Austria. In this period the *CLARIN Annual Conference Proceedings, 2025*

first Digital Humanities Austria Strategy was published (Alram et al., 2015).

3 CLARIAH-AT Infrastructure

In 2019, a formal CLARIAH-AT consortium was established by signing a consortium agreement. The consortium brings together Austrian institutions with relevant expertise in research, development and teaching for the humanities in general.¹ CLARIAH-AT and its activities are visible on the web under <https://clariah.at/>. The CLARIAH-AT Infrastructure includes two CLARIN B-Centres and two CLARIN K-Centres, which will be described in more detail below.

3.1 CLARIN B-Centre ACDH ARCHE

The Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities - A Resource Centre for the HumanitiEs (ACDH ARCHE) is a CLARIN B-centre located in Vienna (Trognitz 2021). The ACDH is a research institute at the Austrian Academy of Sciences founded with the intention to promote digital methods and technologies for humanities research. The ACDH hosts ARCHE, a certified repository launched in 2017, which is dedicated to the long-term preservation and dissemination of digital research data from the Austrian humanities community. ARCHE accepts a broad range of data types that include images, texts, structured and tabular data, audio recordings, videos, 3D models, and geographic information (Trognitz et al., 2022). As of April 2025, ARCHE holds 50 top collections with a total of 440944 individual resources amounting to 9.0 TB of data. The current technical setup behind the repository, an open source set of microservices called the ARCHE Suite, was designed with flexible and fast handling of machine-readable and interoperable metadata at its core and the principles of Linked Open Data in mind (Žóltak et al., 2022). To search and retrieve data and metadata hosted in ARCHE, a core API for creating, reading, updating, and deleting (CRUD) entities is available. On top of the core API, a growing set of bespoke dissemination services allows users to preview, download, serialise or disseminate the stored data and metadata in various ways. In 2024, the graphical user interface (GUI) of ARCHE was overhauled after carrying out an user research to evaluate the current state. The new GUI does not only include a complete graphic redesign but also includes new search options, and makes use of the ARCHE APIs for an improved performance. To ensure sustainable preservation of FAIR research data, ARCHE maintains high quality standards, which require not only reliable technology, but also transparent policies, clear procedures, and essential human curation and interaction.

3.2 CLARIN B-Centre DH Graz

The CLARIN B-Centre DH Graz, officially recognized as CLARIN B-Centre since 2020, is located in Graz and is operating the "Geisteswissenschaftliches Asset Management System" (GAMS). It is an OAIS (Open Archival Information System)² compliant asset management system for the management, publication and long-term archiving of digital resources from the Humanities, with a particular focus on digital scholarly editions. Designed and developed by the Department of Digital Humanities at the University of Graz (previously known as the Centre for information Modelling)³ in cooperation with partners inside and outside the university since 2003, the repository covers the full life cycle of digital objects from receiving the SIP (submission information package), archiving the AIP (archival information package) and delivering the DIP (dissemination information package) to the public. GAMS was conceived and developed on the basis of the Open-Source project Fedora (Flexible Extensible Digital Object Repository Architecture)⁴ and has been continuously improved in the course of cooperative projects, addressing the specific needs of university research. GAMS is based on XML (eXtensible Markup Language) -based standards and technologies for data storage and representation. If the data in question does not conform to any XML-based international standard, the repository will implement

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¹ The current members include: Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austrian National Library, University for Continuing Education Krams, University of Graz, University of Innsbruck, University of Klagenfurt, University of Salzburg and University of Vienna, which are full members. Then there are 3 Observers: University of Music and Performing Arts Vienna, Central European University and Natural History Museum Vienna. The consortium is represented by the speaker (Walter Scholger, University of Graz) and vice-speaker (Tanja Wissik, Austrian Academy of Sciences). They also respectively act as National Coordinators for DARIAH (Walter Scholger) and CLARIN (Tanja Wissik).

² see <http://www.oais.info/>

³ see <https://digital-humanities.uni-graz.at/de/>

⁴ see <https://fedorarepository.org/>

suitable workflows for the conversion of the content in agreement with the project partners. In addition, the infrastructure includes a Handle server⁵, offering the possibility to assign a persistent identifier in this system. (Centre for Information Modelling, University of Graz, 2023). Central and integral to the GAMS operation and principles is the observance and promotion of the FAIR data principles. For this reason, the data available via GAMS is published - in agreement with the depositors - under the most open Creative Commons license possible (CC-BY or CC-BY-NC)⁶.

In addition to the repository and the publication platform, the department has been developing and sharing tools and workflows, offered project-specific consulting in DH methods and processes, and hosted seasonal training Schools as well as Master degree in Digital Humanities which introduces students to the practical implementation of DH-related skills inside and outside the GAMS framework.

3.3 CLARIN K-Centre *Phonogrammarchiv*

Since 2015, the *Phonogrammarchiv* of the Austrian Academy of Sciences has been registered as a Knowledge Centre (K-Centre) within CLARIN. As an Austrian K-Centre the *Phonogrammarchiv* is part of CLARIAH-AT.

Already 125 years ago, the *Phonogrammarchiv* – at what was then the Imperial Academy of Sciences – was founded with an open science approach: Right from the start, its goal was to produce recordings for re-use in academic research, and languages and dialects were one of its main concerns. Still an active archive, the *Phonogrammarchiv* now houses large collections of audio recordings – since 2002 also video recordings – from all over the world, covering global developments in language and dialect as well as music and other cultural expressions over more than a century. Its physical collections encompass about 35,000 carriers; its digital collections amount to about 16,000 hours of archived recordings (digitized & born digital). Some of the *Phonogrammarchiv*'s holdings have been registered as UNESCO Memory of the World or Memory of Austria.

As the oldest sound archive in the world, the *Phonogrammarchiv* has a long tradition and rich experience in knowledge sharing and capacity building. As a CLARIN K-Centre it gives access to its collections (data & metadata) – depending on legal and ethical clearance either online, on demand or onsite. Researchers have always been the *Phonogrammarchiv*'s main users, but its aim now is to make its collections as widely available as possible, e.g., to educators, museums, the media, artists and the general public. Particularly important in the *Phonogrammarchiv*'s activities are collaborations with the descendants of those who were recorded.

In addition to access to its resources, the *Phonogrammarchiv* offers advice and training in the following fields: preservation, restoration and digitization of historical audio and video carriers, recording and transfer equipment, methods and technologies of AV-supported research in the social sciences and humanities with a focus on fieldwork, annotation and contextualization, provenance research and recirculation, legal and ethical issues. In October 2025, the *Phonogrammarchiv* will move to new premises after almost 100 years in its current location. This move will greatly enhance its possibilities for offering trainings and workshops and accommodating guest researchers.

3.4 CLARIN K-Centre TRTC

The CLARIN Knowledge Centre for Terminology Resources and Translation Corpora (K-centre TRTC)⁷ is one of the 34 knowledge centres within the CLARIN Knowledge Infrastructure⁸. Established in 2019, it is a single-site facility located at the Centre for Translation Studies at the University of Vienna. As one of the transversal knowledge centres within the CLARIN Knowledge Infrastructure (Vaičėnienė et al., 2024), it provides comprehensive coverage of terminology resources and translation corpora from a methodological perspective. This initiative builds upon the significant and longstanding expertise in terminology science and translation studies at its host institution (Lušický & Budin, 2024).

The K-centre offers a variety of resources, best practices, guidelines, and training materials related to translation-related resources, specifically terminology resources and translation corpora. It primarily focuses on providing access to termbases, with notable examples including higher education

⁵ see <http://handle.net/>

⁶ see <https://creativecommons.org/>

⁷ see <https://trtc.univie.ac.at>

⁸ see <https://www.clarin.eu/content/knowledge-centres>
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terminology and Austrian administrative terminology. Additionally, the K-centre organizes courses and training events and hosts guest researchers.

Like all K-centres, the K-centre TRTC operates a helpdesk, providing support to users on the preparation and documentation of terminology and translation corpora. This includes handling inquiries related to methods, tools, data, and guidance in seeking further expert support. The service is language-independent. In cases of particular language-dependent inquiries, the K-centre TRTC forwards the inquiry to one of the other K-centres in the network with that specific expertise. The K-centre TRTC addresses and assists a diverse range of users and stakeholders, both from within the CLARIN network and external entities. In terms of volume, it is comparable to most other K-centres, handling up to 50 human-processed requests per year (Vaičėnienė et al., 2024). The requests received by the K-centre span various application scenarios, reflecting the centre's broad scope. Beyond the academic audience, TRTC has supported professional associations, public bodies, and other organizations within and outside of the CLARIN network. An illustrative example of a wide-ranging request addressed to the K-centre TRTC led to a collaborative project with the Mongolian Academy of Sciences and the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage.⁹ The primary objective of this project was to support the establishment of a terminology planning strategy and infrastructure for the Mongolian language. This initiative encompassed several key components, including capacity building and the establishment of a virtual terminology centre, thereby transferring the knowledge of building and operating a knowledge centre beyond the scope of the CLARIN network.

4 Building and Fostering a Community: Funding, Dissemination and Outreach

Based on the CLARIAH-AT consortium's experience and an open consultation of the Austrian professional DH community, the consortium authored a vision for the further development of Austrian Digital Humanities, along the four respective pillars of Research infrastructures and networks, Research data and repositories, Methods, services and tools and Education, training and knowledge transfer (CLARIAH-AT Consortium, 2021). Closely tied to these focal points, the consortium has engaged in several activities to bring their vision to life, such as issuing project funding calls¹⁰, funding opportunities for early-stage researchers¹¹ and hosting training events and workshops¹². The 2024 edition of the Summer School "Vom Archiv zum Algorithmus. Digital Humanities in der Praxis" at the University of Salzburg attracted a group of more than 20 early career colleagues from Austria and beyond¹³. The upcoming School in September 2025 at the University of Graz will focus on "Machine Learning for Digital Scholarly Editions"¹⁴. Furthermore, CLARIAH-AT initiated the workshop series "Austrian Meeting on Digital Linguistics", held in conjunction with the *Österreichische Linguistiktagung (ÖLT)* each year. Members of the CLARIAH-AT consortium are also involved in teaching activities, where they integrate resources and tools from the infrastructure. Another tangible result of CLARIAH-AT's reputation and efforts in community building are close cooperations with Austrian Cultural Heritage institutions. This is evident in from the most recent observing member of the consortium, the Natural History Museum Vienna, which is running "Kulturpool" (Scholger, 2024).

5 Concluding Remarks and Outlook

This contribution has presented the Austrian CLARIAH-AT infrastructure and its activities. Recently a new CLARIN K-Centre on German in Austria (GermanAT¹⁵), hosted by the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities was established, adding an additional infrastructure component to the Austrian network. In the near future, a new CLARIAH-AT website will be launched, that will enhance the search and visibility of Austrian contributions to the European Research Infrastructures via the SSH Open Market place as well as via the Federated Content Search (FCS). Furthermore, the *Digital Humanities Austria Strategy 2021+* will be evaluated and adapted to the evolving landscape, integrating for example also artificial intelligence into the strategy.

⁹ <https://trtc.univie.ac.at/news-and-events/terminology-planning-strategy-and-terminology-infrastructure/>

¹⁰ see <https://clariah.at/en/project-funding/>

¹¹ see <https://clariah.at/en/funding-opportunities-for-junior-researcher/>

¹² see <https://clariah.at/de/events/>

¹³ see <https://dhsalzburg.hypotheses.org/1429>

¹⁴ see <https://clariah.at/en/news/cfp-summer-school2025/>

¹⁵ <https://www.clarin.eu/centres/germanat>
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Towards FAIR Metadata for Specialised Corpora: A Community-Informed Empirical Study of Schema Development in Two Communities

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Abstract

This paper investigates the development of domain-specific metadata schemata to support FAIR data management within specialised research communities. We report on the community-informed development of the Core Metadata Schema for Learner Corpora (LC-meta) and the metadata schema developed for interpreting corpora within the Unified Interpreting Corpus (UNIC) project. We address how metadata are described and standardised, as well as the principles for schema design and the technical implementation of metadata frameworks. Our findings underline the importance of stakeholder involvement, iterative design, domain-oriented approaches to metadata standardisation and a demand for technical support.

1 Introduction

The FAIR Principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016) have become a cornerstone of data management, promoting Open Science by making resources Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Although existing repositories such as CLARIN B Centres (Hinrichs & Krauwer, 2014) make Findability and Accessibility relatively easy to achieve, realising Interoperability and Reusability remains a challenge (Frey et al., 2020): the generic metadata standards these repositories employ are meant for a broad range of content types and seem too coarse for domain-specific corpora.

Metadata standards already exist for CLARIN communities (e.g. by Erjavec and Pančur (2021) for Parla-CLARIN) as well as for other fields (e.g. by Riley (2024) for cultural heritage). However, many research communities still lack their domain-specific metadata standard, although individual communities need customised metadata schemata to reflect their unique characteristics and reuse contexts.

This study examines two community efforts to develop such standards: 1. the Core Metadata Schema for Learner Corpora (LC-meta) (Paquot et al., 2024), developed collaboratively by researchers and infrastructure experts in a community-informed iterative process; 2. the metadata schema for interpreting corpora (Liu & Russo, in press) implemented on the UNIC platform,¹ developed in the value-sensitive paradigm based on conceptual, empirical, and technical investigations.

In the following, we will address: How are domain-specific corpora currently described with metadata across communities? What principles and values underpin metadata schema development? These questions aim to bridge conceptual ideals and practical implementations, and through the examination of two real-world schema development projects, we highlight both shared challenges and divergent solutions emerging from domain-specific needs and infrastructure contexts.

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¹<https://unic.dipintra.it/> – Code available under the Apache 2.0 License at <https://github.com/F-technology-srl/unic>

2 Metadata Schema – but Domain-Specific

Metadata was often defined in very general terms as “data about data” (Greenberg, 2005) but has evolved to encompass complex systems of description that encode the provenance, structure, semantics, and accessibility of digital objects (Gilliland, 2008). Today, metadata contains information on the definitions of the data, rules that govern the data’s inner logic and contextual information. It may also include information on the process used when creating derived data to better understand its meaning and significance.

The development of metadata schemata has been central to data stewardship initiatives in digital humanities and linguistics. Text Encoding Initiative (TEI),² Dublin Core (DC),³ and Component MetaData Infrastructure (CMDI)⁴ provide formal structures, yet often require—and allow for—domain-specific adaptation and schema customisation to meet disciplinary needs while preserving interoperability.

Despite the theoretical advancement of metadata frameworks, practical challenges persist, for example, metadata quality is often uneven across corpora and resource types (Fišer et al., 2018); and specific user groups are dissatisfied with the searchability and metadata transparency in CLARIN’s VLO (Lušický & Wissik, 2017). Such findings underscore the gap between schema availability and usability.

On the other hand, the effectiveness of metadata schemata depends on the extent to which they enable accurate, context-sensitive resource discovery and reuse (Greenberg, 2005). To this end, “metadata need to comply with standards that are relevant for the domains and disciplines involved . . . [and] they need to be properly applied drawing on the controlled vocabularies created by or in close consultation with the practising domain experts” (Velterop & Schultes, 2021). A domain-specific metadata schema can then capture and represent the unique characteristics, requirements, and interpretation of the data and resources within a particular domain.

3 Case Studies

3.1 LC-meta

LC-meta was developed through a collaborative, community-informed iterative process. The development process consisted of three phases: Granger and Paquot conducted a comprehensive review of existing learner corpora and consulted resources such as the Learner Corpora around the World webpage,⁵ the Talkbank website,⁶ the TEI and the Corpus Encoding Standard⁷ to identify common metadata variables and best practices in related fields like first language acquisition and corpus linguistics and proposed an initial draft of the core metadata schema. Their draft⁸ was presented at the CLARIN *Workshop on Interoperability of Second Language Resources and Tools*⁹ for feedback and direct input.

The authors then expanded to a group of specialists in learner corpus research and/or research infrastructures from three different institutions. They gathered to test the initial draft proposal, trying to apply it to several learner corpora from different institutions and with different corpus designs, which led to changes that were presented at two domain-specific conferences to collect feedback from the wider community. Further feedback was gathered via mailing lists, online platforms and online questionnaires.

After all feedback had been clarified, evaluated and, where appropriate, incorporated, LC-meta was released.¹⁰ Subsequently, a working group was established within the relevant domain-specific Learner Corpus Association (LCA)¹¹ to further develop, maintain and promote the metadata schema. For this working group to be representative of the research community, it will be further developed collaboratively with both the CLARIN Knowledge Centre for Learner Corpora (CKL2CORPORA)¹² and the LCA.

²<https://tei-c.org/guidelines/>

³<https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dces/>

⁴<https://www.clarin.eu/content/cmdi-component-metadata-infrastructure>

⁵<https://uclouvain.be/en/research-institutes/ilc/cecl/learner-corpora-around-the-world.html>

⁶<https://talkbank.org/>

⁷<https://www.cs.vassar.edu/CES/>

⁸<https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12124/61>

⁹<https://sweclarin.se/swe/workshop-interoperability-12-resources-and-tools>

¹⁰<https://doi.org/10.14428/DVN/AAUEM2>

¹¹<https://www.learnercorpusassociation.org/working-group-on-metadata-in-learner-corpus-research/>

¹²<https://uclouvain.be/en/research-institutes/ilc/clarin-knowledge-centre-for-learner-corpora.html>

3.2 UNIC

UNIC's approach to metadata standardisation built on LC-meta's ideas for structuring the metadata design and refinement phases, but also integrated conceptual, empirical and technical dimensions tailored to its specific needs: The schema was grounded in both the FAIR and CARE¹³ principles, emphasising data sovereignty, ethical access, and collective benefit. This was especially important in sensitive contexts such as healthcare and asylum interpreting.

The authors collected metadata from 125 spoken and signed language interpreting corpora. Empirically, they conducted 'overlap and gap analyses' to identify essential schema elements, and technically, automatic FAIRness evaluation revealed weaknesses in existing infrastructures. Further, they gathered feedback from students, interpreters and researchers through surveys and software demos on the perceived usefulness of filters, which correspond to the compulsory metadata elements.

4 Findings

Despite the existence of general metadata schemata like TEI, Dublin Core and CMDI, the granular needs of subfields like interpreting studies or learner corpus research require more fine-grained domain-specific schema. The LC-meta and UNIC schemata underscore this gap: TEI, DC and CMDI offer broad, flexible structures, but lack dedicated components for interpreting-specific variables (e.g., transcript–recording alignment, interpreter professional status) or learner-specific information (e.g., age of onset, multilingual background, learning context).

LC-meta includes roughly 170 elements, which may be obligatory (~85) or optional (~85), and may be repeatable or singular. These elements are organised into eight interrelated main components: 1. Administrative metadata; 2. Corpus design metadata; 3. Learner metadata; 4. Text metadata; 5. Situational and task-related metadata; 6. Annotation metadata; 7. Annotator metadata; 8. Transcriber metadata;

The UNIC metadata includes 22 obligatory and 73 optional elements in ten components: 1. Corpus metadata; 2. Event metadata; 3. Actor (as an umbrella term for speaker and signer) metadata; 4. Source text metadata; 5. Interpreter metadata; 6. Target text metadata; 7. Transcriber metadata; 8. Annotator metadata; 9. Annotation metadata; 10. Alignment metadata.

The schema was implemented on the UNIC online platform (see Footnote 1), which supports metadata registration, filtering, search, and communication between corpus creators and (re)users. User feedback indicates greater perceived usefulness of the UNIC filters than those on the VLO. The authors are collecting data use plans when users register and further feedback to refine UI features and metadata categories.

Domain-specific schemata like LC-meta and UNIC enable richer, more nuanced metadata tailored to the theoretical and empirical needs of their fields. The schemata are complementary—not redundant—to broader frameworks. They provide the precision and context required to move from general interoperability to discipline-optimised reusability and research impact. On the other hand, it is possible to reuse and adapt ideas and techniques from another community despite individual requirements.

5 Conclusion

Although general-purpose metadata schemata and infrastructures like TEI, DC and CMDI offer a solid foundation, they often fall short when addressing the specific needs of specialised corpora. Our case studies show that domain-specific metadata schemata—such as LC-meta and the UNIC schema—are essential for ensuring accurate description, discovery, and reuse within particular research contexts.

Rather than replacing existing standards, these schemata extend them, enabling more precise, community-relevant metadata. To support this, CLARIN should take a more active role—similar to its approach with the Resource Families—by facilitating community-led schema development and offering the technical infrastructure needed to integrate these efforts with platforms like the VLO. By doing so, CLARIN can help bridge the gap between general interoperability and domain-optimised reusability, advancing FAIR data practices across diverse linguistic research communities.

¹³<https://www.gida-global.org/care>

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Using Word Rain to visualise ParlaMint debates between countries

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Abstract

This study takes two resources available through CLARIN: the Word Rain text visualisation technique and ParlaMint, a corpus collection of debates from 29 parliaments across Europe, and extends Word Rain to fit the multilingual nature of ParlaMint. Using multilingual word embeddings provided by the MUSE library, we show that cross-language studies on lexical frequency with Word Rain are possible in the same way as has previously been available for monolingual corpora. To illustrate the technique, a tentative study of common word groups and cross-language frequency similarities and differences is also performed.

1 Introduction

Comparing corpora across languages can be approached in several different ways. One method is to analyse each corpus separately and then compare the analyses. In a recent analysis of Hungarian and Slovenian parliamentary corpora (Sárossy & Ligeti-Nagy, 2024), the authors divided each corpus into two subcorpora (coalition MPs and opposition MPs), and then compared these subcorpora with each other. If we instead want to compare lexical differences directly, we can use visualisation methods like Word Rain (Skeppstedt et al., 2024). However, Word Rain in its current implementation does not handle multiple languages, and would need to be extended.

In this study, such an extension is carried out, and the Word Rain technique is then used to visualise lexical similarities and differences in ParlaMint corpora from the United Kingdom, France and Austria.

2 Data

We used the ParlaMint (Erjavec et al., 2024) corpora ParlaMint-GB, ParlaMint-FR and ParlaMint-AT from the resource repository CLARIN.SI. We extracted the data for the 2017 parliamentary debates in .txt format. For 2017, ParlaMint-AT had 1 699 623 tokens, ParlaMint-FR had 4 680 332 tokens, and ParlaMint-GB had 14 573 789 tokens when processed through Word Rain's default tokeniser.

3 Method

We chose Word Rain (Skeppstedt et al., 2024) as the visualisation method. Word Rain shows the top n words in a corpus just as a traditional word cloud, but words are semantically sorted along the horizontal axis according to their positions in a word embedding model, making it possible to compare different corpora. Word Rain is available through the CLARIN and DARIAH infrastructures.

We extended Word Rain to handle multiple languages in two ways. First, we added the ability to use different stop word lists for each corpus. Second, we added the ability to use different word embeddings for each corpus. These changes enable us to use English embeddings for the UK data, French embeddings for the French data, and German embeddings for the Austrian data. This was not enough, however, since just using any word embeddings for each language would make the words *präsident* in German and *président* in French, both meaning 'president' have word embeddings that were totally unrelated. To

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make the word rains aligned, we have to use word embeddings that are aligned between the languages. In this study, we use the aligned multilingual word embeddings provided by the MUSE library (Lample et al., 2018).

Word Rain was configured to transform all words into lower case before any comparisons. The stop word lists used were the standard NLTK stop word lists. The number of words per word rain was set to the 500 most frequent words. The Word Rain functionality to automatically identify frequent n-grams was not enabled.

4 Results and discussion

The resulting word rains can be seen in figure 1. In the same way as in a traditional word cloud, the words have a larger font size if they are more frequent. Since the words are semantically ordered along the horizontal axis according to their positions in the word embedding model, words with similar meaning are placed together horizontally with a high probability. With the modifications carried out in this study, this is now also the case for semantically related words in different languages.

The bars form an additional indication of the relative frequency of each word, but a more precise one than the font size of the word. The colours only illustrate the horizontal position of the words, and are chosen to more easily compare horizontal positions.

As an example of similar words being placed closely, the words *präsident* 'president' in German and *président* in French are very close to each other on the horizontal axis. The same is true for *wissen* in German, *savoir* in French and *know* in English. This indicates that the word embeddings are indeed fairly aligned.

An area with a high frequency in all word rains is the green area around German *herr*, French *parole* and English *hon*. These words do not mean the same thing, but if we study the common words more closely, we can see a pattern. In Austria, they use several forms of *herr* 'Mr', *frau* 'Ms', *kollege* 'colleague' and *geehrte* 'honourable'. In France, they use *monsieur* 'Mr', *mme* 'Ms', *madame* 'Ms' and *collègue* 'colleague'. In the UK we find *hon*, *noble*, *lord*, *lady*, *gentleman*, *mr*, *baroness* and *colleagues*. These are ways of addressing other members of parliament and other persons, for example government ministers, and we can see the influences of the House of Lords in the UK, where the titles baroness and lord are used.

The very high frequency French word *parole* 'speech' also mentioned above has corresponding words on the same position on the horizontal axis in English (*speech*) and in German (*reden* 'speak, speech'). Even though they are not nearly as frequent, they are still in the top 500 most frequent words in the respective corpus.

If we instead look at the far left of the word rains, there is a high frequency area (in orange) that is only present in the Austrian data, with one of the most prominent words being *österreich* 'Austria'. This word and the various forms of it is, perhaps naturally, not among the 500 most frequent words in either France or the UK. There are also names of political parties in Austria: *övp*, *fpö*, *spö*, *grünen* and *neos*.

A difference where the words are present in the other languages but with very different frequencies is *cette* 'this' in French and *would* in English. The first is probably explained by it not being in the stop word list for French, even though it is the feminine form of the masculine *ce*, which is present in the stop word list. The second can perhaps be a real difference in language use, since constructions with *would* like *I would disagree* and *I would urge* seem to be very common, and maybe even used as something close to a discourse particle rather than having its usual syntactic function, but further studies would be needed to draw any solid conclusions.

As a last example, *amendement* in French has its counterpart in English *amendment* at the same horizontal position, but is used much more frequently in French. This is probably because *amendement* is a very important term in French lawmaking.

5 Conclusions and future work

We have been able to successfully extend Word Rain to produce multilingual word rains, making it possible to compare corpora of different languages. We have also used the CLARIN ParlaMint resource

to tentatively investigate what words are commonly used in the parliaments of different countries based not only on raw frequency lists, but grouped according to cross-language semantic information.

The stop word lists used were not ideal for the task, and should be amended to include common words that are not relevant to the analysis. One word of caution, however, is that some commonly used words, such as *would*, might be relevant for some types of analysis. The resulting word rain could probably also have been improved by using specifically Austrian stop word lists and word embeddings instead of the generic German used in this study.

When comparing different languages, a term used in one language might correspond to several terms in another language even when the terminological domain is the same. This will dilute the frequency of the terms, and they would therefore be less likely to appear in the word rain. Taking this into account could be a subject of a future study.

This study has only used three of the 29 corpora in ParlaMint, partly due to limited time and space, but also because of the need for the authors to understand the languages, and thereby the ability to validate the quality of the resulting alignments. The study has also been limited by not having co-authors that are experts in parliamentary debates and political science. We therefore hope future studies can be made with authors from various parts of Europe and different scientific fields, and we will therefore make our improvements to Word Rain available for everyone to use.

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***MetaCat* suite**
Towards a systematic analysis of catalogues

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Abstract

One of the central objectives of the ATRIUM project is to improve the discoverability of resources in the arts and humanities by aligning metadata curation and enrichment workflows between major data catalogues in the domain (ARIADNE Knowledge Base, CLARIN VLO, GoTriple, SSH Open Marketplace). Towards this end, the ATRIUM team is developing *MetaCat*, a suite comprising a systematic, high-level, machine-readable overview of the data represented in the catalogues, together with the semantic artefacts used, accompanied by tooling that allows interactive exploration, analysis and comparison of this information.

1 Background

The ATRIUM (Advancing frontTier Research In the arts and hUManities) project brings together four leading research infrastructures in Europe: ARIADNE (for archaeology), CLARIN (for language resources and technology), DARIAH (for arts and humanities), and OPERAS (for open scholarly communication). One of the aims of the project is to improve access to the datasets and services provided through these research infrastructures, as well as to strengthen data management practices in the research community, resulting in digital resources that are more findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.

Each of these infrastructures maintains one or more catalogues aggregating and disseminating digital resources from a wide range of data providers. The most relevant in the context of ATRIUM are: the ARIADNE Knowledge Base, the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory (VLO), OPERAS's GoTriple,

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and DARIAH's SSH Open Marketplace (SSHOMP). Among the objectives of ATRIUM are facilitating discoverability of and access to humanities resources, building bridges between data catalogues, inventorying the data formats and semantic artefacts (such as ontologies and controlled vocabularies) used in the arts and humanities community, analysing the European repository landscape (including catalogues such as those of Europeana and OpenAIRE), and proposing solutions and best practices to improve the discoverability and interoperability of data.

This poster describes the ongoing efforts in ATRIUM to provide a comprehensive and machine-readable overview of data in the mentioned catalogues, including an inventory of the controlled vocabularies and other semantic artefacts they use. This overview will be accompanied by tooling that allows interactive exploration, analysis and comparison of this information. The collection of the data together with the tooling will form a suite called *MetaCat*.

2 Challenges & Potential

Catalogues are central services developed and maintained by research infrastructures, serving as the primary means to ensure the findability of resources within their respective domain. Confronted with metadata from different providers that can be both syntactically and semantically inconsistent – and sometimes incomplete – all cataloguing efforts rely on complex processing and curation workflows to harmonise and consolidate this heterogeneous data into one coherent data collection.

For example, in the case of CLARIN VLO, dealing with metadata records based on a large number of distinct *Component Metadata* profiles (Windhouwer & Goosen, 2022) entails identifying which metadata properties in the respective profiles can be mapped to a single field, or “facet”, which will be shown in the interface of the VLO – thus providing a uniform information retrieval solution across the resources catalogued in the VLO (Đurčo & Windhouwer, 2013; Van Uytvanck et al., 2012).

While such bespoke solutions optimise findability within individual catalogues, they disregard or even hamper discoverability across multiple catalogues. Local solutions may rely on different formats, standards and classification schemes. Varying identifier systems and practices further hinder cross-catalogue linking and comparability.

Efforts to harmonise this heterogeneous information domain by introducing additional aggregation layers suffer the inevitable accumulation of data quality issues and the loss of detailed information. This hinders the usability of data catalogues for researchers, who must familiarise themselves with the peculiarities of each catalogue and face challenges in using and combining information from different sources. Such challenges have been identified multiple times previously, for example in relation to CLARIN VLO (King et al., 2016; Odijk, 2014).

Despite these challenges, data catalogues and their technical infrastructures open possibilities to improve data FAIRness and discoverability, significantly enhancing this scenario. For some of the semantic artefacts used by the catalogues, there might already be a wealth of mappings which are scattered in different locations or used only internally. For example, mappings to widely used vocabularies are an integral part of the processing pipelines of several catalogues (Binding & Tudhope, 2024; Manguinhas et al., 2016), and mappings to other formats (Windhouwer et al., 2017) have been explored to enhance resource dissemination. In addition, most of the catalogues offer programmatic access to their content, enabling to some extent automated analysis, cross-catalogue comparison, and continuous monitoring through regularly updated statistics. Some catalogues also provide documentation of their processing and curation pipelines; this documentation is often scattered or informal, but – if available – can nonetheless offer valuable insights for comparing catalogue practices and identifying alignment opportunities.

3 Approach

This contribution proposes to build a shared analysis and alignment layer across catalogues as a first step towards understanding and addressing these challenges. It aims to equip catalogue managers and end-users with tools to explore differences, identify overlaps, and progressively align semantic artefacts and data descriptions through mappings and visual comparisons.

The approach adopted here is novel in that it considers not only the contents of the catalogues in the form of the different resources (datasets, services, publications etc.) the metadata of which are aggregated, but also the catalogues themselves as entities worth describing. This comprehensive analysis of the catalogues can provide valuable insights into the current status of the (European) repository landscape as well as its limitations and potentialities. The work can be divided into the following three tasks:

1. collection of information about (the content of) the data catalogues and about data formats and semantic artefacts used by the catalogues and in the arts and humanities community;
2. creation of a knowledge graph which represents the collected information in a formalised and semantically consistent form and can be (at least for some parts) updated automatically;
3. a set of tools to explore and visualise the collected information, in order to perform more in-depth analyses.

3.1 Data collection

The initial, and now completed phase of this endeavour involved mainly data collection, followed by intensive exchange with and between the representatives of the catalogues involved in ATRIUM. Information on individual catalogues was collected from the respective representatives via a questionnaire covering several technical aspects in order to provide as much information as possible, even on features still under development or only planned. Concurrently, an inventory of data formats and semantic artefacts deemed relevant in the arts and humanities community was compiled and organised into a structured form using the low-code database tool Baserow. This inventory formed the basis for the deliverable “Overview of Models and Formats in the Field” (Arikan-Caba et al., 2024).

The following step, which is currently in progress, is to gather into a single place (references to) semantic artefacts used in the different catalogues. This includes controlled vocabularies formalised as SKOS (and potentially made available through a browsing tool like Skosmos), as well as vocabularies offered in other forms (e.g. controlled vocabularies defined in CMD profiles and components, to be extracted from the CLARIN Component Registry) or unformalised lists of keywords originating from depositors or users (so-called folksonomies) (Vander Wal, 2007). Some of these vocabularies are already available in online repositories; in this case, the *MetaCat* data will only include pointers to and metadata about the vocabularies. Less accessible or non-publicly available vocabularies, on the other hand, will be included directly in the *MetaCat* data.

In addition, the project is collecting mappings between semantic artefacts, at the level of both ontology and concept. These could be, for example, mappings created for the harvesting of metadata from a specific source (e.g. through an OAI-PMH endpoint) or specific semantic relations established between concepts of different vocabularies (e.g. through the `skos:exactMatch` property).

3.2 Knowledge graph creation

The aim is to provide all collected data in a machine-readable, semantically expressive way using the AO-Cat ontology (Richards et al., 2022). AO-Cat enables a structured and extensible description of catalogues and their contents, including sources, endpoints, resource types and usage statistics. Being based on the well established CIDOC CRM, it ensures the interoperability of the dataset with other Linked Open Data datasets.

The conversion to AO-Cat is currently performed by exporting the data through the API of Baserow and creating the mapping through the 3M Mapping Tool (Marketakis et al., 2016) developed by FORTH. This facilitates the creation of a knowledge graph, which makes connections between data catalogues more easily explorable and more evident.

In the next steps of the project, this knowledge graph will be enhanced by the integration of information automatically (and periodically) retrieved from the catalogues by querying their endpoints. For example, this will include aggregate item counts based on different facets and metadata properties in the catalogues, with an initial focus on the following dimensions: *resource type*; *format/media type*; *discipline*; *source*; *subjects/keywords*. This will allow users and repository managers to have an overview of the current coverage and scope of the catalogues in terms of these facets.

The collection of all this information into a unified space will require normalisation and semantic alignment at different levels, since data catalogues, for instance, describe resource types according to different classifications, or use uncontrolled properties for keywords and subjects. Therefore, a further step of the process will be the comparison and – where possible – semantic alignment of the concepts and terms used across the catalogues. This will make use of the mappings collected in the previous phase of the project, which will be – where possible – formalised into a shared, interoperable representation, ideally as SKOS semantic relations, individual mapping files (e.g. in X3ML or YARRRML), or RDF alignment graphs. Where mappings are not available, the alignment process will employ a variety of methods from simple string-based comparison (with exact or fuzzy matching) to experimental application of AI/LLM-based methods. Manual curation and validation of the alignments on small sample sets will accompany the whole process. The goal is not only to align the vocabularies, but also to explore and compare the usefulness of the different approaches.

3.3 *MetaCat* suite - tools for exploration

The final objective of the activity is to expose the collected information as a knowledge graph, accompanied by a set of tools to analyse, explore and visualise this information, completing the *MetaCat* suite. A central component will be a dashboard application, currently under development, based on the Plotly Dash library for Python. This will be accompanied by a set of Python notebooks that interactively show the different query processes and processing of the data, and allow for the customisation/refinement of the queries, aggregation, and analysis methods to specific research projects and use cases. Importantly, by making the various existing mappings available, this tooling will allow users to flexibly apply the mappings for querying and aligning heterogeneous sources, supporting a wide range of possibilities enabled by the mappings, such as query translation and semantic enrichment workflows across catalogues. These tools are meant to be extensible, i.e. they can be used to analyse data sources other than the initial set of catalogues.

4 Conclusions & Outlook

Beyond the immediate objectives of ATRIUM, this effort could provide the catalogues with possible directions for strengthening their modelling choices and data services offered: for example, by introducing controlled vocabularies for previously uncontrolled properties, or by further developing APIs, as in the case of CLARIN VLO. It could also encourage a richer exchange of experience and tools between the catalogues, with semantic artefacts and services from one catalogue being adopted by another.

Finally, by making the diversity of semantic artefacts across catalogues explicit, *MetaCat* supports a more transparent and informed understanding of the European research data landscape. This not only enables cross-catalogue discovery and reuse, but also helps catalogue managers identify inconsistencies, gaps, or alignment opportunities that may otherwise remain hidden, and contributes to integration efforts with large-scale initiatives like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) and the Common European Data Spaces.

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FAIR Assessment of CLARIN datasets in the CLARIAH-NL INEO pipeline

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Abstract

In the Dutch CLARIAH-NL project a new central catalog, named INEO, has been developed. It contains data sets and tools from both the CLARIN and the cultural heritage communities in The Netherlands. To show its commitment to the FAIR principles, the original aim was to only include FAIR enough datasets and tools. To do so, one has to assess the FAIRness of datasets and tools. This paper reports on the journey to enable this: via a FAIR Implementation Profile, to make CLARIN's strategies to implement the FAIR principles explicit, a FAIR assessment tool, called pyFAT, to be able to assess a CMDI metadata record, and extensions to the CLARIN harvesting pipeline.

1 Introduction

The Dutch CLARIAH-NL infrastructure combines several communities: the Dutch CLARIN centers and cultural heritage institutions that work together in the Dutch Heritage Network (NDE). To show its achievements, the infrastructure decided to set up a central catalog called INEO¹. To show its commitment to FAIR principles, tools and data sets should only appear in INEO if they have been proven to be FAIR (Wilkinson et al., 2016). However, to prove this, tools and datasets have to be assessed against a set of rules that specify what CLARIAH-NL deems FAIR. In this abstract, we will focus on how this was done in the pipeline built for datasets. For tools, the harvesting pipelines and the FAIR requirements are described in (van Gompel, 2024). The first step taken was to create a FAIR implementation profile (FIP) for CLARIAH-NL. How this went is described in the first section. As there are too many datasets to be assessed by hand, there has to be a FAIR Assessment Tool (FAT), which is able to inspect the (meta)data of these datasets and determine if it adheres more or less to the choices made in the FIP. This tool, pyFAT, is described in the second section. The final section describes the complete dataset harvesting pipeline, which is based on an adapted instance of the CLARIN harvesting pipeline for the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO)². The necessary adaptations are described with special emphasis on the ones that are coming available in the CLARIN harvester as well.

2 FAIR Implementation Profile

The European GO FAIR project developed the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP, Schultes et al., 2020). A FIP consists of a questionnaire of 21 carefully crafted questions that help a FAIR Implementing Coalition (FIC) to outline the strategies they take to implement the FAIR principles. In CLARIAH we started

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with the aim for creating one FIP spanning both involved communities, but that turned out to be too ambitious at this point in time. The communities were not yet on the same level of making decision-making on strategies to implement the FAIR principles. So we were not yet able to compare them and decide on the overlap and/or differences to align them in one CLARIAH-NL FIP. Instead, FIPs per community are created as a first step. In the SSHOC-NL follow-up project, which includes, next to the CLARIN and NDE communities, the Dutch ODISSEI social sciences community, this effort continues in a working group.

CLARIN recognizes two kinds of centers: technical (B) centers and knowledge (K) centers. The CLARIN FIP created is mainly based on the CLARIN B centre requirements³. These requirements are governed by the CLARIN Technical Centres Committee. New or existing B centres fill in a self-assessment using the guidelines for these requirements, this assessment is then validated by the CLARIN Assessment Committee. The resources of these B centres are harvested by CLARIN for its central catalogue, i.e., the VLO. These resources should thus follow the requirements and hence could also be checked by a FAT based on the CLARIN FIP. The created FIP is shown in Table 1. The table shows the questions, the type of FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) expected in the answer, and the FERs employed by CLARIN. Some CLARIN FERs are in italics, indicating these are proposals and in various degrees already considered by the Technical Centres Committee.

For the NDE community the FIP is currently still under construction and no FAIR assessment of their resources could take place, which meant that CLARIAH-NL decided to adjust the scope for INEO to include the unassessed NDE resources. Still the CLARIN resources are assessed, so this is the topic of the next section.

3 FAIR assessment of CLARIN resources

There is a growing set of FATs, e.g., F-UJI (Huber and Devaraju, 2021), FOOPS (Garijo et al., 2021) and FAIR Checker (Gaignard et al., 2023). Tools like FAIR Enough (Jacobsen et al., 2020) then try integrate the analyses of various FATs. In the article (Valdestilhas et al., 2025) the authors ran several of these FATs on representative data sets for both CLARIN and ODISSEI and compared the outcomes with the FIPs. These experiments show that results among FATs are hard to compare due to varying interpretations of what the FAIR principles mean, and technical choices made by the communities don't align with the technical representations the FATs expect. A prominent example is the use of CMDI for metadata by CLARIN. Only F-UJI recognizes and acknowledges CMDI as a valid metadata format. It process it a little bit to find, e.g., some provenance information in the header. But it lacks the understanding of CMDI to go deeper and properly understand, e.g., resource proxies or concept links in the profile, which are needed to properly assess Findability and Accessibility.

To be able to have a FAT that has deep enough knowledge of CMDI and other CLARIN technologies, CLARIAH-NL developed pyFAT¹⁰. pyFAT is still generic, as it uses path expressions to traverse metadata records and do the assessment. The expressions are part of assessment test specifications (see Listing 1 for an example), so they are never hardcoded in PyFAT itself, and it is thus possible to specify tests for any metadata format. The path language currently supported is XPath 3.0¹¹, which enables pyFAT to assess the XML-based CMDI records. The implementation is prepared to use other path languages, e.g., SPARQL property paths¹² or JMESPath¹³, for Linked Data-based metadata, or fall back to python itself.

Listing 1: A pyFAT metric & test

```
- metric_test_identifier: CLFIP-F1-01M-1
  metric_test_name: "Check to see if the selflink is a handle"
  metric_test_requirements:
    - test: "xpath: starts-with (//cmd:MdSelfLink, 'hdl:')
```

The output specification of pyFAT is based on the FAIR assessment exchange format under development by the ongoing european project OStrails¹⁴. OStrails is working in its FAIR Interoperability Framework (FAIR-IF) task on overcoming many of the problems mentioned in this section. It does so

Principle	FIP Question	FER types	CLARIN FERs
F1-MD	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers do you use for metadata records?	Identifier type	handles, DOIs
F1-D	What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers do you use for datasets?	Identifier type	handles, DOIs, URLs
F2	Which metadata schemas do you use for findability?	Metadata schema	CMDI ⁴ , Dublin Core
F3	What is the technology that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?	Metadata-Data linking mechanism	CMDI resource proxies
F4-MD	In which search engines are your metadata records indexed?	Search engines	CLARIN VLO
F4-D	In which search engines are your datasets indexed?	Search engines	depends
A1.1-MD	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?	Communication protocol	HTTPS, OAI-PMH
A1.1-D	Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?	Communication protocol	HTTPS
A1.2-MD	Which authentication & authorisation technique do you use for metadata records?	Authentication & authorisation technique	none
A1.2-D	Which authentication & authorisation technique do you use for datasets?	Authentication & authorisation technique	SAML, OIDC
A2	Which metadata longevity plan do you use?	Metadata longevity	CTS ⁵ , CLARIN B Center status ⁶
I1-MD	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?	Knowledge representation language	CMDI & its concept links, SKOS-based vocabularies
I1-D	Which knowledge representation languages (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?	Knowledge representation language	depends
I2-MD	Which structured vocabularies do you use to annotate your metadata records?	Structured vocabularies	CMDI vocabularies, SKOS-based vocabularies
I2-D	Which structured vocabularies do you use to encode your datasets?	Structured vocabularies	vocabularies registered in the <i>CLARIAH FAIR Vocabulary Registry</i> ⁷
I3-MD	Which models, schemat(s) do you use for your metadata records?	Metadata schema	public CMDI profiles
I3-D	Which models, schemat(s) do you use for your datasets?	Data schema	a model registered in the <i>Standard Information System</i> ⁸
R1.1-MD	Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?	Data usage license	Creative Commons CC0
R1.1-D	Which usage license do you use for your datasets?	Data usage license	depends
R1.2-MD	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?	Provenance model	none
R1.2-D	Which metadata schemas do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?	Provenance model	depends

Table 1: CLARIN FIP (for the machine actionable version see ⁹)

my making more layers, e.g. tests, metrics and benchmarks, explicit and allowing communities to mix and match the tests implemented by FATs to match their own strategies for the FAIR principles.

All the test scores of the validation of a pyFAT run for a specific resource result in a score between 0 and 1, which could be used in the INEO harvesting pipeline to determine if a dataset is FAIR enough to be included in INEO. However, as mentioned before currently NDE resources cannot be assessed, which lead to the decision to allow all resources, but their assessment score will be available as a filter.

4 Harvesting

The harvesting pipeline reuses the software from the CLARIN pipeline for the VLO up to its FAIRy datasets registry (see Figure 1). However, some extensions were needed:

- the OAI harvester was opened up to dynamically load code to support other protocols, as NDE has a dataset registry that exposes its Linked Data-based metadata via SPARQL;
- the harvester runs normalization actions on the metadata to make records as uniform as possible, as protocols can provide new kinds of data new actions can also be dynamically loaded to transform the records;
- the VLO has some limited functionality to make a distinction between collections, datasets and resources within them, to align CLARIN and NDE datasets an extra facet based on heuristics per provider determines if a record actually describes a dataset and should be included in INEO
- for these datasets pyFAT is run and the score is included as a facet.

The figure also shows that INEO is filled based on the facets extracted by the pipeline, where the information is potentially merged with "rich user content", e.g., screen shots, tutorials and references. The filter on FAIRness is not yet activated.

Figure 1: INEO's data set harvesting pipeline

The extensions of the harvester manager, which due to these lost the OAI prefix, are also incorporated in the CLARIN harvesting pipeline. This also allows CLARIN to go beyond OAI-PMH as the primary API.

5 Conclusion

Although, INEO in the end does not limit itself to only datasets and tools that are FAIR enough, the development of its harvesting and assessment pipeline does showcase improvements and progress on various aspects and moves closer towards that goal. Next steps include ongoing efforts in The Netherlands to create and align FIPs for various communities. And to improve and align automatic assessment using various FATs, including more generic ones like F-UJI. To achieve this also work has to be done on the repository side of the Dutch CLARIN B centres, e.g., by embedding basic metadata as RDF in the landing pages of data sets. In this way a FAT will not need a deep understanding of CLARIN's "proprietary" component metadata format.

Notes

- ¹<https://www.ineo.tools/>
- ²<https://vlo.clarin.eu/>
- ³<http://hdl.handle.net/11372/DOC-78>
- ⁴<https://www.clarin.eu/cmdl>
- ⁵<https://www.coretrustseal.org/>
- ⁶<https://www.clarin.eu/content/certified-b-centres>
- ⁷<https://registry.vocabs.dev.clariah.nl/>
- ⁸<https://standards.clarin.eu/sis/>
- ⁹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15261774>
- ¹⁰<https://github.com/CLARIAH/pyFAT>
- ¹¹<https://www.w3.org/TR/xpath-30/>
- ¹²<https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-property-paths/>
- ¹³<https://jmespath.org/>
- ¹⁴<https://ostrails.eu/>

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Multilevel Annotation of Informativeness in Linguistic Corpora: INFOLEXIS

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Abstract

This proposal presents an ongoing manual semantic annotation project (INFOLEXIS) focused on the multilevel analysis of linguistic informativeness. We expound the key components of the methodology developed in the framework of the project: its novel multistep annotation scheme, the annotated English and Spanish datasets, and the tools we developed for different phases of the annotation. We also elaborate on its relevance for the theoretical linguistic and computational linguistic communities, and on its contribution to several of the CLARIN Resource Families.

1 Introduction

Manual annotation is still of crucial importance for the machine learning used in natural language processing inasmuch as it highlights the specific knowledge components that are relevant for each learning task (Pustejovsky and Stubbs, 2012). In CLARIN, manually annotated corpora are singled out as a specific resource type of the Corpora Resource Family. High quality human-annotated datasets are particularly relevant for semantic reasoning systems.

In this paper, we present the manual annotation project INFOLEXIS, which addresses linguistic informativeness at the lexical, syntactic and pragmatic level. We specifically focus on its methodology and on its contribution to several CLARIN Resource Families. In alignment with the FAIR Guiding Principles, INFOLEXIS aims to maximize the utility of its research outputs for the scientific community. In pursuit of findability and accessibility, we will ensure that project outputs, specifically the tools, workflows, and final dataset, are easily discoverable and freely accessible via comprehensive metadata and clear documentation. Resources will be distributed in standardized, widely-accepted formats to facilitate integration with existing workflows, promote reuse in diverse research contexts, and assure interoperability. While the derived annotations generated as dataset by INFOLEXIS will be openly shared following these principles, it must be pointed out that copyright protections inherent in the original source material prevent the redistribution of the raw sentences upon which the annotations are based (i.e., the original annotated corpora, see section 3).

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly introduces linguistic informativeness as the target phenomenon of INFOLEXIS. Section 3 presents the key components of the methodology developed in the framework of the project: the annotation scheme, the annotated dataset, and the annotation tool. Section 4 sums up the main contributions of INFOLEXIS as far as the CLARIN objectives are concerned.

2 Informativeness as a multilevel phenomenon in INFOLEXIS

INFOLEXIS focuses on one specific aspect of the general issue of selectional constraints involved in the predicate construction, which we will be referring to as *informativeness*. The examples in (1) illustrate its impact on the acceptability of different phrase and sentence-level constructions: active predicative (1a, b), participial modification (1c, d), passive (1e, f), and middle (1g, h).

Following standard syntactic criteria, both members of the English and Spanish pairs in (1) are supposed to be acceptable because the arguments and modifiers satisfy the selectional requirements of the syntactic head: *eat* selects as its direct objects NPs that denote edibles, and *ravioli* and *food* have this exact semantic type; *write*, *rewrite*, *publish* and *read* must be combined with NP complements that refer to informational objects and data storage media, such as *novel* and *book*; lastly, *book* is also compatible

with *yellow* because it denotes a physical object. However, the second member of each pair of examples does not seem fully acceptable, unless combined with an additional modifier¹, because the argument or modifier encodes information already provided by the syntactic head: all the direct objects of *eat* refer to *food*, all the *novels* are created through the process of *writing*, all the *books* are meant to be *read*, etc. This is what we call the *informativeness constraint*, as explained in detail in Batiukova and Pustejovsky (2013) and Batiukova (2024).

- (1) a. (eng) Eat ravioli – eat ??(organic) food
 b. (spa) Comer ravioli - comer alimentos ??(ecológicos)
 c. (eng) {Rewritten / published} novel - ??(recently) written novel
 d. (spa) Novela {reescrita/ publicada} – novela ??(recién) escrita
 e. (eng) This novel was {rewritten / published} – This novel was written ??(recently)
 f. (spa) Esta novela fue {reescrita/ publicada} – Esta novela fue escrita ??(recientemente)
 g. (eng) This book is yellowing - This book reads ??(fast).
 h. (spa) Este libro amarillea - Este libro se lee ??(rápido).

INFOLEXIS is based on the premise that informativeness is a compositional phenomenon, wherein lexical-semantic, syntactic and pragmatic factors are involved (Batiukova and Pustejovsky, 2013). In the first place, in order to be acceptable, a phrase must be consistent (that is, the arguments and modifiers must be compatible with the syntactic head), as are all the expressions in (1). In the second place, it must be informative, as in the first part of each example in (1): an argument or modifier must not refer to an inherent property of the syntactic head, as encoded in its lexical entry. When uninformative constructions appear in real data (as in the second part of the examples in (1)), they are licensed by a syntactic or a pragmatic rescue mechanism: syntax can supply adjuncts that introduce non-presupposed information (as in 'eat *organic* food' or '*recently* written novel'), and pragmatics can provide a contrastive reading, which introduces a binary division of the elements present in the discourse (e.g., when a *written* novel is opposed to all those novels that never came to exist).

3 Annotation scheme

INFOLEXIS represents the first attempt to annotate informativeness in a corpus based on sound linguistic criteria and in a bottom-up fashion, namely starting at the lexical level to see how lexical features determine whether a given syntactic construction is coherent and informative, and further including the pragmatic level, wherein uninformative combinations are often salvaged. The existing computational-linguistic studies of informativeness are based on the subjective judgment of the annotators, without discriminatory tests (as in the sentence-level annotation described in Lahiri, 2015), and are carried out

Figure 1: INFOLEXIS annotation scheme

¹The double question mark before the parenthesis indicates that the expression is semantically odd or not quite acceptable without the modifiers enclosed in parentheses.

in the context of keyword extraction (Nishikawa et al., 2010), named entity recognition (Rennie and Jaakkola, 2005), and text summarization (Molina et al., 2013), where informativeness is calculated statistically through corpus-based distribution.

In order to capture the compositional nature of informativeness, a multilevel annotation scheme has been developed, as represented in Figure 1. The questions that the annotators will be answering are enclosed in solid line boxes. Questions 1-3 require a yes/no answer, and question 4 an answer from a closed list. Questions 1 and 2 concern phrases or constructions, and questions 3 and 4 are about the sentences that contain these constructions. Depending on the given answers, each sentence will be classified in one of the groups defined in the dashed line boxes.

In Step 1, all the sentences in (1) would be classified as *consistent*, following the list of selectional requirements previously defined for all verbs (Di Fabio et al., 2019). An example of an “inconsistent” sentence would be *The novel was devoured*, because *novel* does not comply with the selectional requirements of *devour*, which is a subtype or troponym of *eat*. In Step 2, the first member of each pair in (1) will be classified as *informative* and the second member as *uninformative*. In Step 3, broader sentential context will be analysed to see what renders informative a priori uninformative constructions: additional modifiers (e.g., ‘recently written novel’, ‘this book reads fast’) or the contrastive interpretation (as in the above mentioned example of *a written novel*, which is informative when opposed to nonexistent novels).

Figure 2: Screenshot of the INFOLEXIS Corpus Searcher (Step 1 annotation tool)

A total of 50 semantically equivalent transitive English and Spanish verbs are being analyzed, which are representative of the most important 11 semantic groups as far as their meaning and frequency of use are concerned.

- Acquisition: *atrapar/catch, capturar/capture, cosechar/harvest*
- Caused motion: *arrastrar/drag, conducir/drive, deslizar/slide, empujar/push*
- Communication: *contar/tell, confesar/confess, revelar/reveal, difundir/spread*
- Consumption: *comer/eat, devorar/devour, ingerir/ingest, consumir/consume, emplear/employ, leer/read*
- Creation: *escribir/write, construir/build, producir/produce, fabricar/manufacture, desarrollar/develop, confeccionar/craft, cultivar/grow, diseñar/design*
- Physical change of state: *cortar/cut, hornear/bake, lonchar/slice, picar/chop, pintar/paint, romper/break*
- Perception: *oír/hear, ver/watch*
- Psychological state: *sentir/feel*
- Putting: *enterrar/bury, insertar/insert, plantar/plant*
- Transfer: *comprar/buy, conceder/grant, confiscar/seize, donar/donate, equipar/equip*
- Light verbs: *coger/take, dar/give, hacer/make*

Given that the factors that determine linguistic informativeness may be deemed as universal, this annotation scheme can be applied to any human language with minor adjustments related to the information encoded in the lexical entries (e.g., the selectional requirements of the syntactic head) and language-specific syntactic properties (e.g., the adjunct realization).

We are currently annotating two corpora: Corpus del Español Web/Dialects (Davies, 2008a) and Corpus of Contemporary American English (Davies, 2008b). All the occurrences of the analyzed verbs were

extracted from both corpora and loaded into the INFOLEXIS Corpus Searcher, our own tool designed for Step 1 annotation. The corpus searcher allows extracting the relevant constructions with the 50 English and Spanish verbs following the carefully defined syntactic search criteria and manually classifying them as ‘consistent’ (‘include’ in Figure 2), ‘inconsistent’ or ‘exclude’. The latter allows filtering out non-target expressions, e.g. *well-read electorate* (with *electorate* being the syntactic subject of the base verb *read* rather than its direct object) or *eat-or-be-eaten environment* (where the modifier of *environment* is *eat-or-be-eaten* and not just *eaten*).

At the time of writing, Step 1 annotation is almost completed for the <Participle+N> construction. For English, a total of 54,407 sentences have been classified, of which 33,234 will be annotated in Step 2. For Spanish, 92,050 sentences have been sorted out, of which 49,671 will be annotated in Step 2.

4 Main contributions of INFOLEXIS

Here we sum up the main contributions of INFOLEXIS as far as the CLARIN objectives are concerned. In the first place, this project puts forward a novel annotation scheme potentially applicable to all natural languages and all kinds of corpora. In the second place, it will provide three manually annotated datasets, generated in each step of the annotation process:

1. Syntactic constructions classified as consistent or inconsistent and linked to their original syntactic context: active predicative constructions, participial modification constructions, passive constructions, and middle constructions (Step 1 annotation).
2. Consistent syntactic constructions annotated as either informative or uninformative (Step 2 annotation). One of the innovative aspects of INFOLEXIS consists, precisely, in that construction-level annotation in Step 1 and 2 will provide negative linguistic data (which should not occur in actual use): inconsistent and/or uninformative expressions.
3. Sentences containing uninformative constructions, annotated with the syntactic components that make them acceptable (Step 3 annotation).

In the third place, it will generate annotation tools that can be reused in other manual annotation projects (e.g., the INFOLEXIS Corpus Searcher, described in section 3 above).

As far as theoretical linguistics is concerned, INFOLEXIS will be a valuable empirical tool for the study of informativeness as an interface phenomenon, involving lexical-semantic, syntactic, and pragmatic factors. In particular, INFOLEXIS contributes to the understanding of the mechanisms underlying selectional constraints at the phrasal and sentential level. The analysis of the <Participle + N> construction with ten of the annotated Spanish verbs reported in Batiukova (2024) yielded relevant results, which link the argument structure of the base verb and its degree of specificity with the number and kind of additional modifiers appearing within the construction.

The contribution of INFOLEXIS is also relevant for the computational linguistic community, in particular for logical knowledge representation of the informativeness phenomenon that can be used for more practical tasks such Question Answering (QA) systems, textual entailment tasks, text simplification tasks, and for extraction of multiword expressions.

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LLM-based Models for Transforming of Diachronic Bulgarian Spelling to Contemporary Bulgarian

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1 Introduction

Within CLaDA-BG several partners¹ are working on digitization of documents in the period from 1878 to 1950. The documents include newspapers, magazines, organizational documents, books, and other. These documents are valuable sources of research data in many domains such as linguistics, history, ethnography, social sciences, etc. As expected, there exist some problems with the digitization of older documents such as the poor quality of paper copies, which leads to worse OCR-ed texts, as well as the usage of various spelling norms in different periods, sometimes even competing during the same period.

In the work reported in this text, we implemented approaches similar to the ones reported in the following papers, among others. In Beshirov et al. (2024) post-OCR Text Correction techniques for Bulgarian Historical Documents are presented. The authors released a small benchmark dataset called the Drinov Orthography for Post-OCR Correction dataset. The corpus was created by annotating a collection of historical periodicals and books provided by the National Library “Ivan Vazov” (NLIV) in Plovdiv. The best performing model uses synthetic data. The datasets used in this work include: *ICDAR 2019 Competition on Post-OCR Text Correction*² and two other datasets created by the authors (datasets not available at the moment). In our work, we divided the task of processing Bulgarian diachronic texts with a post-OCR text correction to contemporary Bulgarian in two steps: (1) correction of OCR output to old spelling representation and (2) transforming the old spelling to the contemporary one. Thus, in the work reported here, we present the conversion of historical documents to a dataset with contemporary spelling. These historical documents were written in the period from 1878 to 1945, when several competing spellings were employed depending on the school behind it, the region in Bulgaria, etc.

Kanerva et al. (2025) evaluate the use of open-weight LLMs for OCR error correction in historical English and Finnish datasets. In addition, the authors focus on the limitations of using LLMs for scaling this task to large historical corpora.

Before 1945 the competing spelling systems were numerous, thus, our efforts were directed to an LLM that handles all of them together, instead of one by one.

In the next section, the specificities of the different spellings are discussed. Then we introduce the pretraining of different models over it. Later on evaluation is presented and the results are commented.

2 The Diversity of the Bulgarian Spelling Systems in the Period 1878-1945

Here we present the context of the various spellings used during the period from the liberation of Bulgaria from Turkish occupation (1878) until the acceptance of the contemporary spelling norm of Bulgarian (1945).

From 1870 to 1945 eight spelling forms were proposed and applied either officially or non-officially:

- the Marin Drinov’s spelling
- the spelling project by the philological committee from 1893

¹The largest collection of scanned and OCR-ed historical documents is created within the National Library “Ivan Vazov” (NLIV) in Plovdiv. In our work, we are using documents from this collection.

²<https://hal.science/hal-02304334/document>

- the spelling project from 1895
- the Ivan Vazov’s spelling system from 1899
- the Drinov-Ivanchevski spelling system from 1899
- the Omarchevski spelling system (1921 - 1923)
- the spelling project of the Historic-philological branch of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (1899)
- the Tsankov’s spelling system (1923)

The most prevalent one until 1945 (with small interruptions) remains the Drinov-Ivanchevski spelling system from 1899 that adheres to the traditional/etymological spelling to great extent.

The linguistic phenomena that usually show heterogeneous features across various spelling systems are as follows:

- *phonetic*: changing of *ya* to *e*; order of the assembly of a *shwa* and *r* or *l*; reduction of the open vowels to non-open ones; the usage of the small *er* at the end of the nouns.
- *grammatical*: long and short forms of the definite article in masculine singular nominals; deverbal nouns ending in *-ne* and *-nie*; vocative; pronouns.
- *other*: small and capital letters; spelling of foreign words; spellings with a dash; punctuation.

3 Creation of Parallel Corpora for Fine-tuning

The source data for the task are selected the collection of periodicals and books provided to us by the National Library “Ivan Vazov” (NLIV) in Plovdiv. The documents were OCR-ed by ABBYY FineReader. The OCR was performed with the best OCR model for the specific newspaper, etc. Although such an approach resulted in a high quality of OCR, errors still remained. The side effect is that each model introduces some model-dependent errors. In order to be able to address such kind of errors we created a corpus of parallel documents which consists of: aligned OCR documents, corrected OCR documents with the original spelling (from the ones listed above), and documents with contemporary spelling.

In the experiments reported here we selected pairs of a corrected OCR document and its related document with the contemporary spelling. The data were created in two ways: (1) through an alignment between books with diachronic spelling, and the digital form of the same book published several decades later according to the contemporary spelling; and (2) through a lexicon-based “translation” from the old to the new spelling. This lexicon was created on the basis of the Bulgarian inflectional lexicon. Each lexical entry in it contains the paradigms of nearly 80 000 lemmas. It is denoted as **OldNewLex**. Through the usage of a set of rules we converted the word forms to their representation according to the Drinov-Ivanchevski spelling system. We selected this system, because it was in use for the longest period of time, and thus the biggest amounts of texts that were OCR-ed adhered to it. The result from the rules was matched to the word forms from a spelling dictionary published in 1934, and digitized within CLaDA-BG. We also corrected all the forms that did not match. In order to cover the earlier publications, we extended the lexicon with word forms in several texts from the period of the predominant Marin Drinov’s spelling. The two datasets used in this work were constructed through both approaches, i.e. the alignment-based and the lexicon-based ones. The first dataset (about 200 000 running words) consists of novels and short stories published in the period of 1910-1944 for which we found also electronic versions published after 1945. It is denoted as **DS-1**. We used some heuristics in the alignment, with manual checks on the result for nearly half of the texts. In the second dataset newspaper articles were included (about 5 000 tokens). It is denoted as **DS-2**. We consider the task of mapping between the old and the new spelling norms as a spell checking task where the old spelling is considered erroneous in the contemporary spelling of the corresponding words. Thus, the aligned texts were used for the fine-tuning of LLMs for such a task. One observation on the varying spelling systems, presented above, is that they

mainly differ in the alphabets which include or exclude a small number of special letters. All the competing spelling letters however were included in the Drinov-Ivanchevski's spelling system. Our assumption in this work is that the dataset **DS-1** demonstrates all the combinations of letter sequences to support the correspondences between each old spelling system and its contemporary form. For that reason, we used **DS-1** for fine-tuning the models with respect to both spelling systems in the experiments. **DS-2** was used only for testing. **DS-1** was divided respectively into training, development and test sets.

In the next section the language models are presented that we exploit in our experiments. For this task several LLMs were pretrained with different model architectures. The goal was to investigate the most appropriate architecture for this task. The reason behind the performance of our own pretraining was that the task could be solved with LLM with a much smaller number of parameters.

4 Pretraining of the Large Language Model for the Task

In this section we present the Large Language Models which we pretrained for our experiments. The spelling correction is viewed as a sequence-to-sequence task. For this kind of a task, the encoder-decoder architecture seems to be the most suitable. We thus selected the architecture of the T5 model (Raffel et al., 2020).

Furthermore, texts used for training language models are usually tokenized at the word or subword level. Since the difference in spelling usually involves the change of letters in a word, a model operating with characters appears to be more suitable. A Character or Byte level T5 was proposed in Xue et al., 2021. To test this hypothesis, we pre-trained two T5 models - one trained on texts tokenized at a subword level, and the other trained on texts tokenized at a character level.

The character level T5 training corpus consists of 4B Bulgarian words. The model was trained with a context of 1024 characters on the T5 masked language modeling objective with noise density of 0.25 and mean noise span of 7 characters (statistics on a large Bulgarian corpus showed that 7 letters is the mean word length in Bulgarian). The training was done for 3 epochs. The subword level T5 model was pre-trained for 3 epochs on a corpus with 20B Bulgarian words with a context of 512 subwords on the T5 masked language modeling objective with a noise density of 0.25 and mean noise span of 3 subwords. Both models have a similar architecture of 12 encoder and decoder layers with a hidden dimension of 1024. The character level T5 has 353M parameters, while the subword level T5 has 403M. The difference is in the input embedding parameters because the subword level model has a larger vocabulary of 50176 tokens.

We also experimented with pre-training of two decoder-only models based on the Llama architecture (Touvron et al., 2023) with the same two types of tokenization, trained on the same corpora with comparable parameter counts. For further comparison to a publicly available model, we also considered the EuroLLM 1.7B decoder model (Martins et al., 2024), trained on a dataset consisting of European languages, including Bulgarian.

5 Experiments and Results

We fine-tuned the models on the dataset **DS-1** for 10 epochs with a peak learning rate of $1e-04$. The best checkpoint according to the validation set is selected. The Llama models, being decoder ones only, were trained on the context of the input - output pairs separated by a special token. The next token prediction loss for the input part was ignored - in this way the model was trained only on the output part.

The T5 models follow the ordinary fine-tuning procedure, in which the loss is calculated on the output of the decoder. The results from these experiments on a test split of **DS-1** are presented in Table 1. As a baseline we used **OldNewLex**. We substituted each old word form with its new word form as presented in the lexicon. It can be observed that the baseline is already quite high. The rest of the experiments correspond to the expectations that the character-based models are better in comparison to the subword-based models. In our view, the number of parameters is of less importance. This observation is supported by the fact that the performance of EuroLLM 1.7B is lower than the best character-based model. We also demonstrate that the T5 models are better than the Llama ones.

Model type	Architecture	Tokenization level	Whole-Word BLEU
Lexicon substitution (baseline)			87.69%
Llama	Decoder	Character	93.01%
Llama	Decoder	Subword	89.07%
T5	Encoder-Decoder	Character	95.32%
T5	Encoder-Decoder	Subword	92.01%
EuroLLM 1.7B	Decoder	Subword	94.21%

Table 1: BLEU Scores of the tested fine-tuned models on the test split of **DS-1**

The same models were also tested on **DS-2** to assess whether they retain their abilities across a (although incomplete) set with slightly different spelling. The results are presented in Table 2. We do not include a lexicon substitution baseline, because the dataset **DS-2** was constructed with the same lexicon, and the result is extremely good. The overall results show that our assumption of the training on **DS-1** being sufficient for the construction of a model, applicable also to other spelling systems, is wrong, because the drop in performance is quite high. On the other hand, the results show that the performance of the character-based T5 dropped with the smallest difference. The manual investigation shows the same preferences – most of the errors were related to the direct copying of wordforms from the old text to the new one. In many of these cases, the character-based models work well for word forms that are presented in the fine-tuning dataset.

Model type	Architecture	Tokenization level	Whole-Word BLEU
Llama	Decoder	Character	72.17%
Llama	Decoder	Subword	72.76%
T5	Encoder-Decoder	Character	87.02%
T5	Encoder-Decoder	Subword	80.02%
EuroLLM 1.7B	Decoder	Subword	78.76%

Table 2: BLEU Scores of the tested fine-tuned models on **DS-2**

In addition to the above experiments, we performed also experiments to evaluate the models with respect to producing a correct transfer to the contemporary spelling. In the worst case, we would need to edit the whole result to perform the task. But in order to reduce the editing efforts, we decided to use the input text as well as the results from more trained models. Thus, in this experiment, we used the two best models: *Character-based T5* and *EuroLLM 1.7B*. We created a new dataset similar to **DS-1** containing 6 696 tokens. This dataset was named **DS3**.

Then the three texts were aligned: the two results from the corresponding models and the **DS3**. Before applying each model to **DS3**, we separated it into sentences to align the texts within smaller contexts. We first aligned the two results from the models. We scanned the two texts from the beginning to the end looking for the same tokens. Initially, some tokens were skipped. In the next iterations we already allowed partial overlapping on the strings, starting again from the beginning. Then we allowed the addition of empty tokens in the results. After the completion of the first alignment, we performed a new alignment of it with the text in **DS3**. First, we applied a substitution of word forms in the old spelling with word forms in the new spelling when the correspondence was unique. The results from the alignments were sequences of triples $\langle tok_{T5}, tok_{EuroLLM}, tok_{DS3} \rangle$. In some cases, the values of the tokens could be empty. The triples containing one of the new introduced empty tokens were grouped together if such triples happened to be next to each other. We consider that such a group of triples has to be examined by an editor. We assume that a triple represents a correct transfer from the old spelling to the new one if one of the tokens produced by one of the models (tok_{T5} or $tok_{EuroLLM}$) is the same as tok_{DS3} .

Here are the results from the experiments. The groups of inserted tokens are 147. These groups contain 962 tokens. In the rest of tokens (5 734) there are three cases. The number of triples for which tok_{T5}

= tok_{DS3} is 4 736 — 82.59% correct correspondences. The number of triples for which $tok_{EuroLLM} = tok_{DS3}$ is 4 470 — 77.95% correct correspondences. The number of triples for which $tok_{T5} = tok_{DS3}$ or $tok_{EuroLLM} = tok_{DS3}$ is 4 866 — 84.86% correct correspondences.

This experiment demonstrates that a combination of the model output with the input dataset could minimize the number of wrong cases to be checked. We assume that the introduction of more models might improve the results significantly.

6 Conclusions

In this text, we presented a number of experiments for transforming the combined diachronic Bulgarian spelling system to contemporary Bulgarian. Needless to say, there is more work to be done in several directions. These are, among others: (1) Extending the datasets further not only in quantity but also in text variety; (2) Performing similar experiments for improving the OCR quality. We started with the creation of datasets of OCR-ed texts and texts in Old spelling; (3) Testing the task with bigger language models. Also pre-training language models on data that contain texts in Old spelling. The old texts differ not only in the alphabet, but also in the vocabularies including archaic word forms and some variants of the contemporary word forms. Thus, we will have to create models to update the vocabulary of final texts; (4) Providing a deep enough error analysis.

We showed that the character-based T5 models are good for this task since they incorporate an encoder-decoder schema. It is interesting that *Character-based T5* and *EuroLLM 1.7B* have quite similar outputs. One possible explanation of these similarities is that the tokenizer of *EuroLLM 1.7B* does not perform well on old texts, and in many cases the input word forms are tokenized at the letter level.

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Current State of the UWebASR - Web-Based ASR Service for Czech, Slovak, German, and English

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Abstract

We describe the current state of UWebASR, a web-based automatic speech recognition (ASR) service tailored for academic use, supporting Czech, Slovak, German, and English. Developed initially within LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ, the system has evolved by integrating domain-tuned wav2vec 2.0 models, an open HTTP API, and feedback-driven enhancements. UWebASR is used across diverse research contexts, including oral history and sign language dataset preparation. The service is integrated with the CLARIN infrastructure via the LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ services webpage and also via the BAS transcription portal, facilitating its reuse and access across Europe's research community.

1 Introduction

Despite the availability of numerous off-the-shelf automatic speech recognition (ASR) solutions, these systems often fail to address the specific needs of specialized research communities. Many such tools lack the flexibility to adapt to unique linguistic domains, oral history recordings, or other nuanced data types commonly encountered in academic research. In contrast, UWebASR – a web-based ASR system developed within the LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ project – is specifically designed to bridge this gap by offering a customizable and domain-adapted ASR service tailored to the requirements of researchers. Since its inception, the service has been adopted in various projects across the domain of social sciences and humanities and continues to evolve in quality, accessibility, and interoperability.

2 The Evolution of UWebASR service

The development of UWebASR began in 2018 when the first version of the system was deployed as part of the LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ infrastructure. At that time, the engine relied on the (then) state-of-the-art architecture combining Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) with Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) for acoustic modeling and a standard word-based trigram language model for decoding (Švec et al., 2018). This configuration allowed for creating a functional web-based ASR service capable of transcribing Czech and Slovak speech, marking one of the early attempts to make ASR technology broadly accessible to CLARIN users.

Since then, the ASR paradigm has shifted significantly, driven by advances in end-to-end learning and the rise of Transformer architectures. The flexibility of UWebASR allowed us to easily integrate the models based on wav2vec 2.0 (Baevski et al., 2020), which has become a new standard for robust speech

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recognition. Our models are fine-tuned in a two-phase process: initially on general domain speech data for each target language, followed by further adaptation to oral-history-style recordings. This enables us to offer two model variants—generic and oral history-adapted—depending on the needs of the research use case.

In addition, we moved from a simple web page GUI to a more generic system that also provides an HTTP API, allowing large-scale integrations into the researcher’s pipeline. The language set has expanded to include Czech, Slovak, German, and English. Output formats include plain text, WebVTT, JSON, and Transcriber XML, supporting flexible downstream processing and annotation pipelines.

2.1 Automatic Punctuation and Casing Restoration

Because ASR produces punctuation-free outputs (and in the case of wav2vec 2.0, even lowercase), we introduced a postprocessing pipeline using Transformer-based models to restore sentence boundaries, punctuation, and proper casing (Švec et al., 2021).

This restoration step significantly improves the readability and usability of ASR outputs, particularly for applications targeted to digital humanities or education domain. The punctuation and casing restoration model is a monolingual BERT-based predictor trained on CommonCrawl web text dumps. The model predicts terminal punctuation following the word (full stop, comma, question mark) and the word’s original casing (lowercase, uppercase, capitalized).

The general finding that the Transformer-based models consistently outperform all previously used approaches in the task of automatic punctuation has been shown also in (Guhr et al., 2021). Unfortunately a direct comparison of the results with (Švec et al., 2021) is not possible even for the one language – English – that the articles have in common due to the different evaluation datasets. However, such a comparison would be highly interesting since the models developed by (Guhr et al., 2021) utilize cross-language transfer and would therefore allow easy adaptation to new languages.

2.2 ASR Engine Architecture

Our current ASR engine is based on the wav2vec 2.0 architecture introduced by (Baevski et al., 2020). This model comprises a deep neural network with three main components: a multi-layer convolutional feature encoder, a multi-layer Transformer encoder (Vaswani et al., 2017), and the Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) layer presented in (Graves et al., 2006). The convolutional encoder processes the raw audio waveform to produce a sequence of latent speech representations. These are then passed to the Transformer, which generates contextualized representations using self-attention mechanisms. Finally, the CTC layer maps the contextualized features to a sequence of graphemes. During CTC decoding, our system integrates an external language model, which enhances recognition accuracy by incorporating linguistic context and penalizing unlikely sequences in the target language. The output of the ASR engine is a lowercase transcript without any punctuation.

Our ASR engine utilizes the Transformers Python library¹ with PyTorch backend for inference. It employs a sliding window approach during transcription to manage long audio inputs efficiently. Experimental results – see (Lehečka et al., 2023) – show that our models substantially outperform publicly available systems—including the large Whisper model (Radford et al., 2022)—in both decoding speed and transcription accuracy.

First, we pre-trained a monolingual wav2vec 2.0 base model for each supported language using a large-scale, unlabeled speech dataset. We used 80 thousand hours of unlabeled speech to pretrain Czech and German models, and 20 thousand for Slovak. We then fine-tuned this model to produce two distinct ASR systems: (1) a general-domain ASR model trained on a diverse mix of speech data from various domains, and (2) a domain-adapted ASR model obtained by further fine-tuning the general model on oral-history-style speech exclusively. The general-domain training data was a combination of public and private datasets with the following amounts: 6k hours for Czech, 140 hours for Slovak, 6k hours for German, and 12.5k hours for English. Users of the UWebASR platform can select the model that best aligns with the characteristics of their input data.

¹<https://huggingface.co/docs/transformers/index>

The Czech base model, CITRUS, was trained from scratch on a large Czech corpus and reused as a starting point for the Slovak model due to the languages’ close similarity. We used a publicly available `facebook/wav2vec2-base` as a pre-trained model for English. The German model was trained using the same procedure as the Czech. For all languages, we used the two-phase fine-tuning.

Our recent preliminary experiments have demonstrated promising results with a Zipformer-based ASR model introduced by (Yao et al., 2023). The Zipformer architecture features a modified Transformer encoder that operates at multiple lower frame rates, enabling faster decoding and improved performance. In future work, we plan to train production-ready Zipformer models, rigorously evaluate their performance against the wav2vec 2.0 architecture, and potentially integrate them into the UWebASR system.

Table 1 shows the evolution of ASR performance on oral history archives, starting with early GMM-HMM systems in 2004 that produced error rates around 40%. Over the following almost two decades, neural networks such as DNNs, TDNNs, and CNN-TDNN steadily reduced error rates. The most dramatic improvements came more recently with self-supervised Transformer architectures: The Czech wav2vec 2.0 reached below 10% in 2022, and the preliminary Zipformer results suggest further gains.

Year	Model Architecture	Czech	Slovak	German	English
2004	GMM-HMM (basic)	40.2	40.7	–	39.6
2013	GMM-HMM (improved)	26.0	–	–	34.3
2017	DNN (feedforward)	23.2	–	–	30.9
2019	TDNN (time-delay)	21.0	–	–	27.5
2021	CNN-TDNN (hybrid)	14.4	–	–	17.9
2022	Wav2vec 2.0 (Transformer)	8.5	11.6	16.6	12.9
2025	Zipformer (improved Transformer)	*7.1	–	*14.0	–
2023	Whisper-large-v3 (Radford et al., 2022)	19.1	22.0	25.9	18.0

Table 1: Word error rates (WER) of ASR architectures evaluated on oral history archives in Czech, Slovak, German, and English. Asterisk (*) indicates preliminary results that are subject to further validation.

3 Integration into the CLARIN Infrastructure

UWebASR has been integrated into the CLARIN ecosystem. The first option is to use the web frontend page at <https://lindat.mff.cuni.cz/services/uwebasr/>. This portal also provides the HTTP API, and the documentation and usage examples are provided. Another option is to access it via the BAS (Bavarian Archive for Speech Signals) Transcription Portal.

Based on user feedback from the joint EHRI-CLARIN workshop, a new export feature was introduced: the inclusion of configurable pause durations in sentence-level output. The motivation is that in some applications (especially in oral history research), the annotated pauses in the interviews are significant for understanding. The output format *Text with pauses* now marks all pauses longer as 0.3s as `<sp>` (*short pause*) and longer than 2s as `<pau>`.

4 Selected Use Cases

Oral History and Holocaust Testimonies – UWebASR has supported several oral history projects, including the MEMORISE project² and a joint EHRI and CLARIN workshop on Holocaust testimonies in London (2023). Transcription of pause durations was added based on user requests from these communities.

Sign Language Corpus Preparation – UWebASR was also employed in the creation of a Czech Sign Language dataset, where ASR provided aligned transcriptions for over 4,000 weather forecast segments used to generate sign language glosses and annotations. For more details, see (Snajder and Krejsa, 2024).

²<https://memorise.sdu.dk/>

BAS Web Services ASR – The UWebASR system was integrated into the BAS Transcription Portal as one of the backend options for automatic speech recognition. Through this integration, users can benefit from the synergies of UWebASR and BAS pipeline, including the ability to route output through subsequent modules like MAUS (for alignment) or anonymization services. The REST API interface allows the BAS platform to programmatically send audio recordings and receive high-quality transcriptions in various export formats (e.g., ELAN EAF, TextGrid, tab-delimited). See the detailed description in (Draxler et al., 2024).

Hackathons & rapid prototyping – The lightweight HTTP API and robust multilingual capabilities of UWebASR make it an ideal tool for rapid prototyping and experimentation in speech-enabled applications. Its ease of integration has been particularly valuable in educational and innovation-driven environments. Over the past years, we have mentored several student teams and individuals who incorporated UWebASR into their projects during hackathons, student projects, or even in their diploma theses and other qualification works. A notable example is the Aimtec Hackathon³, which focused on assistive technologies for people with disabilities. In these contexts, UWebASR has enabled participants to quickly build functional proof-of-concept systems for speech-driven interaction, accessibility enhancement, or intelligent transcription services.

5 Conclusion

UWebASR exemplifies how speech recognition technology can be effectively tailored and deployed to meet the specific needs of diverse research communities. Through its continuous evolution in model architecture, language coverage, and export options, the system has become an invaluable tool for researchers working across linguistic and disciplinary boundaries. Its integration with CLARIN research infrastructure enhances accessibility and interoperability, while its responsive development approach ensures that new features align with actual research needs. As a next step, we plan to replace our current ASR backend with Zipformer-based models, which offer a significant speed-up and improved accuracy.

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³<https://www.aimtechackathon.cz/en/hackathon/>

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From tweets to networks: Introducing four large network-based social media corpora

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Abstract

We introduce an algorithmic approach to enriching large-scale social media data with social network information for research in the social sciences and humanities (SSH). We present the Digital Social Network (DSN) corpora, a collection of over 19,000 ego networks compiled from social media data across four regions. Utilizing concepts from digital humanities, graph theory, and set theory, we classify networks by tie strength and provide insights into how people interact in digital settings. Our method is agnostic to social media platforms, and while we pilot it with one social media application (old Twitter), it can be easily scaled to other data sources (such as Bluesky). The enriched corpora support research on language variation, digital communities, and innovation diffusion. Our work aligns with CLARIN infrastructure goals by promoting data accessibility and reusability.

1 Introduction

This presentation introduces an algorithmic data enrichment process developed for more effective use of large-scale social media data in SSH research. Our work, carried out as part of a digital humanities infrastructure project funded by the Research Council of Finland, is aimed at enriching social media data with interactional social network information. The purpose is to enable novel research on social media in disciplines such as sociolinguistics, digital anthropology, and political science, where understanding how people are connected to each other could add depth to the analysis of language use, identity, and information flow.

Our approach opens up novel research opportunities using social media data. Data from social media are increasingly used across different fields, but this research predominantly focuses on text content and treats social media as massive text corpora or uses directly observable spatio-temporal information (Grieve et al., 2018; Matteo Di Cristofaro, 2024; Rüdiger & Dayter, 2020). However, many studies tend to overlook the fact that individuals use these digital social media platforms to connect with other people and belong to networks and communities (Mohammad et al., 2013; Tumasjan et al., 2010). It has been suggested that establishing personal networks using available metadata is difficult (Eisenstein et al., 2014), and recent approaches have primarily quantified users' connections based on reply patterns (Del Tredici & Fernández, 2018; Zhu & Jurgens, 2021). Consequently, these studies miss the opportunity to explore the value of personal ego networks. Our approach builds on understanding the structure of a whole network, which is built around an ego, a randomly selected anchor individual, and includes all the people connected to the ego (Laitinen et al., 2020; Milroy & Milroy, 1985; Sharma & Dodsworth, 2020). We propose that this type of data-intensive ego network approach has substantial theoretical potential for many disciplines.

The structure of our presentation is such that we first present the algorithmic method and then introduce four large-scale social network datasets in which network-related information has been added for each user. The algorithmic method employs concepts from digital humanities, graph theory, and set theory, and it quantifies interactions among entities in ego networks in social media. The method

is multidimensional, taking into account a number of interactional parameters, such as similarity, frequency of communication, and various centrality measures, and it results in a network strength index (NSI) that indexes how loosely or strongly connected people in a network are. The method assigns a value to each ego network based on tie strength.

This method considerably expands the practical and theoretical possibilities for utilizing social media data in SSH research, since it enables researchers to investigate language use by taking into account the social setting and the structural properties of networks in which people operate. Understanding social settings is integral according to the weak-tie model of social change (Granovetter, 1973), which predicts that novel information tends to spread through weak ties, while settings in which people are closely linked to each other are more resistant to change, and such environments tend to support local norms. Therefore, our approach supports researchers investigating language change, regional variation, or digital communities by encoding different interaction types and social network structures.

After presenting the method, we introduce four large-scale, location-based social network datasets, Digital Social Network (DSN) corpora, that were collected from Twitter (currently X). The datasets were collected, cleaned, and processed using Python and the now-discontinued Twitter Academic API in early 2023, before the APICALypse (Bruns, 2019; Montag et al., 2024). The APICALypse started after the Cambridge Analytica controversy, leading many online social media platforms to restrict data access (Bruns, 2019). Twitter was among the last major platforms influenced, discontinuing its academic API only after rebranding in early/mid-2023. The method is not platform dependent and can easily be applied to any social media data that form directed graphs in which the direction of interaction is observable.

2 Digital Social Network corpora

The network datasets cover four geographic areas: Australia (DSN Ozzie), the Nordic countries (DSN Nordic), the United Kingdom (DSN British), and the United States (DSN America). In total, they include 19,345 ego networks, consisting of a central node (ego), its directly connected neighbors (alters), and the connections between the alters. These networks were filtered using a semi-automated method to target what we call genuine human accounts, meaning that we aimed to exclude accounts with unusual network qualities, such as bots, celebrities, politicians, organizations, and businesses. Recreating a comparable dataset to the DSN corpora under the current paid data access policies of X would cost over 3 million euros and take around 58 years, given the current limitations of data access policies.

The network datasets contain material from 829,608 users, and the data ranges from 2006 to 2023. Altogether, they contain more than 700 million messages and nearly 10 billion words keyed in by users. Table 1 summarizes the basic statistics for the DSN corpora.

Table 1: Basic statistics of the compiled geo-located network dataset.

Region	Networks	Nodes	Edges	Avg. net size	Messages	Tokens (mil)
DSN British	940	54,290	425,280	58	68M	960
DSN Ozzie	1,840	201,686	1,299,618	110	256M	3,943
DSN America	2,995	179,484	1,300,649	60	238M	2,931
DSN Nordic	13,570	394,148	2,041,108	29	190M	2,092
Total	19,345	829,608	5,066,655	43	752M	9,923

Figure 1 illustrates an overview of the data collection process and the four steps we followed to construct the DSN corpora. In step 1, we started by streaming geo-location-enabled tweets from the US, UK, and Australia over a two-week period. For the Nordic region, we used material from a large dataset collected in an earlier phase of the same infrastructure project in Finland. We benefited from the Nordic Tweet Stream (NTS), an online platform that contains material from the Nordic region over 11 years

Figure 1: Overview of data collection.

(2013–2023), and used this material as the starting point for data collection in that region (Laitinen et al., 2018). In step 2, we extracted all users and their details from the geo-located material gathered in the first step, forming a set of seed accounts for each region.

In step 3, to access genuine human accounts, we applied four filters aimed at improving data quality and excluding certain account types. First, we filtered out the least and most active accounts by removing the bottom 1% and top 1% of accounts based on the frequency of posting messages. Specifically, we excluded those who tweeted less than 3 times or more than 12,000 times per year on average. This enabled us to exclude one-timers who signed up for the service but did not remain active, as well as very active accounts whose activity profiles resemble automated bots. Next, we excluded verified accounts, typically celebrities and businesses with millions of followers but very few friends. To improve location accuracy, we kept only those users whose self-reported profile location matched the location in their geo-tagged tweets. Lastly, based on prior empirical observations that people can maintain around 150–200 social connections (Dunbar, 2020; Laitinen et al., 2020), we removed users with very large network profiles. For this, we used a conservative estimate of fewer than 500 total contacts (friends and followers combined) from the seed list. In the final step, we collected data for all candidate accounts that passed the filtering process. This data collection included entire ego networks with interactions and the 3,200 most recent messages for each account in these networks (both the ego node and its alters). This figure was the maximum allowed by the API.

The resulting datasets are extremely large but contain carefully curated social networks with user-generated textual material. With their detailed structure, massive size, and coverage over 17 years, the DSN corpora support new research and enable re-examining old questions in the humanities. A case in point is the role of weak ties in the spread of innovations, where prior empirical evidence in sociolinguistics comes from ethnographic observations (Milroy & Milroy, 1985). One clear limitation of ethnographic network investigations is that participant observation methods are limited to networks of 30–50 individuals. As seen in Table 1, the networks in the DSN corpora are substantially larger, making it possible to investigate a variety of networks of different sizes and structures (Laitinen & Fatemi, 2023).

In general, the DSN corpora are particularly useful for sociolinguists and computational linguists investigating language use in online environments. They offer a rich and diverse resource that captures digital activity across different cultures. Using computational methods like sentiment analysis and thematic clustering allows us to study how patterns in social networks evolve over time. For example, Goel et al. (2016) analyzed language change using reply networks, as data on friend connections were not available; a gap the DSN corpora help fill by providing detailed ego network information based on actual interaction and complex network structure. These corpora also open new ways to explore how linguistic innovations spread in digital social media. While past studies on lexical change have identified when and where new words emerge (Grieve et al., 2017, 2018), the DSN corpora allow us to examine the social environments of the users driving those changes.

Additionally, the DSN corpora and the proposed data enrichment pipeline could be further extended through integration with CLARIN’s infrastructure. This includes enriching metadata through CMDI-compliant schemas, enabling federated access via the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO), and

supporting reusability through persistent identifiers and licensing transparency. Our work provides a concrete example of how large-scale, user-generated datasets can be aligned with FAIR principles in a CLARIN-compatible framework.

Additionally, the DSN corpora and the proposed data enrichment pipeline could be further extended through integration with CLARIN's infrastructure and could easily be used to enrich data from other social networking sites. This includes enriching metadata through CMDI-compliant schemas, enabling federated access via the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO), and supporting reusability through persistent identifiers and licensing transparency. Our work provides a concrete example of how large-scale, user-generated datasets can be aligned with FAIR principles in a CLARIN-compatible framework.

3 Conclusion

This project contributes to the broader CLARIN mission by enhancing the availability and usability of large-scale social media data for research in the humanities and social sciences. By aligning our data enrichment process with established practices in CLARIN, such as infrastructure integration, we aim to promote the reusability and accessibility of social media data and expand the field to cover social networks through digital social network corpora. The project demonstrates how enriched social media data can support new research questions in sociolinguistics, digital culture, and language dynamics while also addressing critical issues around access and sustainability in the post-APIcalypse era. Furthermore, the DSN corpora and enrichment process can be directly applied in SSH research use cases such as studying regional language variation, the spread of misinformation, digital activism, or the evolution of online communities—making the resource valuable not only for linguistics but for broader interdisciplinary investigations.

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CorpSum - a corpus visualization tool

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Abstract

In this paper, we present CorpSum, a corpus visualization tool built on top of NoSketch Engines Rest API. Originally developed as a dedicated visualization front-end for the Austrian Media Corpus (amc), a corpus that makes nearly the entire Austrian print media production of the past decades accessible for linguistic research, its recent iteration has been generalized in a way that enables it to query any NoSketch Engine instance exposing a public Rest interface.

1 Introduction

With approximately 51 million articles and 12.7 billion tokens (including 9.6 billion running words), the Austrian Media Corpus (amc) ranks among the largest German-language text corpora. (Mörth & Wissik, 2018) Beyond its considerable size, the amc is distinguished by its comprehensive coverage of Austria's print media landscape over the past several decades and is as such part of the Austrian CLARIN activities bundled in CLARIAH-AT. The amc primarily comprises journalistic prose, including full issues of newspapers and magazines, newswire releases from the Austrian Press Agency (APA), and transcripts of television productions, predominantly news broadcasts. (Ransmayr et al., 2013)

The corpus is the result of a collaboration between the Austrian Press Agency (APA) and the Austrian Academy of Sciences (ÖAW), particularly the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH). The APA is responsible for collecting the text output of Austrian print media and making it available to the ACDH-CH. The ACDH-CH subsequently enriches the material using linguistic annotation techniques, including lemmatization, part-of-speech tagging, and named entity recognition. The annotated data are then made accessible through the NoSketch Engine (NoSkE), a corpus query tool enables the analysis of the amc through functionalities such as word sketches and concordancing (Kilgariff et al., 2014).

NoSkE, which is an open source version of the commercial sketch engine (SkE) by Lexical Computing Ltd., is a highly efficient and widely used corpus search software providing a wide array of linguistic corpus analysis tools. It is equipped with both a well-defined and -documented REST-API as well as a comprehensive front-end web application named Crystal. Because the Crystal web interface's aim is to provide access to the full bandwidth of functionalities the NoSkE query engine is capable of, it can be difficult to navigate for novices. Moreover, some key features, such as the visualization of query results and guided collocation and word combination queries, have been reserved to its commercial sibling. The latter shortcomings compelled the ACDH-CH to develop its own bespoke query tool - CorpSum. It is a web application that enables user-friendly, dynamically generated queries in text corpora along different extralinguistic dimensions of variation such as the dimensions time and space.

2 Related tools

Next to crystal, NoSkE's native web based GUI, there already are a number of publicly accessible tools designed to summarize and visualize corpus data. Among those available, two platforms—AntConc,

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maintained by Dr. Laurence Anthony, Professor in the Faculty of Science and Engineering at Waseda University, Tokyo, Japan (Laurence Anthony, 2025), and CQPweb, a web-based corpus analysis platform developed at Lancaster University (Andrew Hardie, 2021), provided particularly valuable input to our project.

2.1 AntConc

AntConc is a free, cross-platform toolkit designed for corpus analysis, with a particular emphasis on concordancing and textual data exploration. Originally implemented in Perl, the software was later reengineered using Python in conjunction with the Qt graphical user interface framework, enhancing both its functionality and usability. AntConc operates as a standalone desktop application, compatible with major operating systems including Microsoft Windows, macOS, and Linux.

2.2 CQPWeb

CQPweb is designed to provide a user-friendly interface to the Corpus Workbench (CWB) system, which was also created at the same institution. The platform is accessible online via <https://cqpweb.lancs.ac.uk> and is also distributed as open-source software, allowing users to download and install it on local servers or individual machines.

As a web-based application, CQPweb provides a suite of core corpus analysis functionalities, including concordancing, query result sorting, collocation analysis, distributional statistics, subcorpus creation, and support for a simplified query language. These features make it a powerful and accessible resource for both novice and experienced corpus linguists.

2.3 Crystal

More sophisticated corpus analysis tools, such as the Sketch Engine and its Crystal interface, offer only limited forms of data visualization. These platforms provide charts and graphs primarily for analyzing corpus-wide text types or for observing the distribution patterns of queried items.

In sum, although progress has been made toward making corpus data more accessible to researchers with limited experience in corpus linguistics, significant barriers remain. These tools often require a considerable investment in learning, both in terms of understanding their structure and interpreting their outputs. Moreover, the potential of visualizations to enhance corpus exploration is far from fully realized.

3 CorpSum - a query and visualization tool

Originally developed to facilitate work with the amc based on the use of the NoSkE Crystal interface by domain experts (Çetin, 2019), the following common analysis tasks were identified and implemented:

- Analysis of Regional Linguistic Varieties - display frequency results divided by regions on geographic map
- Diachronic Lexicographic Analysis - display temporal trends of frequency results and the keyword-in-context in different time periods
- Display sources / topics of frequency results - search and filter by other words using the keyword-in-context results as well as the attached corpus and document metadata

3.1 Technologies used

Whilst the current implementation is bespoke to these use cases vital to the work with the amc, initial tests with other NoSkE-hosted corpora have shown that due to its modular architecture it is already usable on other corpora as well. Because it builds directly on top of NoSkE's swagger-documented REST-API, it can technically be connected to any NoSkE instance. The software is being realized as an open source project¹ using well established technologies and frameworks:

- TypeScript - a strongly typed superset of JavaScript

¹<https://github.com/acdh-oeaw/corpsum-ts>

- VueJS - a performant and versatile framework for building web user interfaces
- D3JS - a JavaScript library for visualizing data
- TanStack Query - an asynchronous state management and caching library for TypeScript applications

3.2 User experience considerations

One major consideration was that, long-running queries on large corpora such as the amc can significantly diminish the user experience by causing slow load times, delayed interactions, and a generally unresponsive interface. Caching addresses this issue by storing and reusing previously fetched data, dramatically reducing the need for repeated network requests. This is particularly useful for queries on relatively constant datasets, where data changes infrequently but is accessed often, such as concordances or corpus configuration data, making repeated fetching redundant. Using cached responses, CorpSum can deliver faster load times and a more seamless user experience.

Another consideration was low-barrier accessibility in CorpSum's design, ensuring that users of varying expertise can easily engage with the tool. The support for both simple queries and the full power of the corpus query language (CQL) significantly enhances the user experience by catering to a broad range of users, from students to experienced researchers. For those new to corpus analysis, the simplicity of basic queries allows for easy exploration of data without requiring deep technical knowledge. At the same time users can take full advantage of CQL's advanced capabilities to conduct complex searches and analyses, offering flexibility and precision.

4 Conclusion

At the time of writing, the next iteration of CorpSum was nearing completion. A live demonstration of the tool is scheduled to be presented at the conference, accompanied by a detailed overview of its architecture, including an API designed to enable third-party visualizations and built-in stable referencing of the queries and visualizations produced by CorpSum.

It is our hope that CorpSum will attract a broader audience of researchers and students who have not yet engaged with corpora and gather valuable feedback on the application itself.

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UPSKILLS Two Years on: Teaching about Language Resources and FAIR Data Principles with CLARIN

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Abstract

The ongoing technological developments have a major impact on language-related research and professional activities. This highlights an increasing demand for new skills and profiles, as well as a greater focus on making language data and resources open and FAIR. In this paper, we present long-term efforts that address these issues, starting from the Erasmus+ project UPSKILLS. We focus on follow-up activities at the University of Bologna in collaboration with CLARIN ERIC, illustrating how key topics related to the use of research infrastructures for language resource discovery, sharing, and archiving can be incorporated into language-related curricula and specific classes at the BA, MA, and PhD levels.

1 Introduction

The rapid advances in language technologies require adaptation not only on the part of individual researchers and language professionals, but also through initiatives of higher education institutions offering language- and linguistics-related degree courses. One of the recent projects with related objectives was the Erasmus+ partnerships UPSKILLS–*UPgrading the SKills of Linguistics and Language Students*.¹ This three-year project (2020-2023) sought to identify and address the gaps and mismatches in the skills of linguistics and language students with respect to the demands of the current job market and the broader research landscape. The project's results received the Erasmus+ good practice label² and were classified as the second runner-up in the 2023 competition for the best Digital Humanities training materials.³ Two years later, we revisit the results by zooming in on the impact the project has had on one of the partners, the University of Bologna (UNIBO) and its Department of Interpreting and Translation (DIT). We specifically explore how the CLARIN research infrastructure can be integrated into teaching practices to raise awareness among students about the basic principles of FAIR research data management.

The paper is structured as follows. In section 2, we summarise the main results of UPSKILLS and describe the spin-off materials created and hosted at UNIBO, as well as the changes that DIT implemented in its study programmes. Section 3 is dedicated more specifically to the recent CLARIN-UNIBO

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¹<https://upskillsproject.eu>

²<https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/projects/search/details/2020-1-MT01-KA203-074246>

³<http://dhawards.org/dhawards2023/results/>

collaboration focused on the educational use of CLARIN's resources, with a focus on Open Science and FAIR principles. Finally, section 4 concludes with insights on how to ensure a lasting impact.

2 From UPSKILLS to UpskilLing@UNIBO

2.1 A summary of UPSKILLS outputs

In the UPSKILLS project, researchers from 8 partner institutions across Europe worked toward developing a new curriculum component and a new teaching approach targeting the skills needed for industry and academic research among (primarily) undergraduate students of language-related subjects. The deliverables comprise: (1) a needs analysis, based on several components and summarised through a new target profile of **language data and project specialist**, skilled in the disciplinary domain, but also in technology, research and data and project management (Miličević Petrović et al., 2021), (2) a series of guidelines and best practices on research infrastructures and research-based teaching (Simonović et al., 2023; van der Lek et al., 2023), (3) a set of Moodle-based materials for online and blended teaching and learning in the areas identified as in need of improvement (<http://hdl.handle.net/11356/1865>), and (4) educational games developed for, or adapted within the project (<https://upskillsproject.eu/deliverables/io4/>).

UNIBO's and CLARIN's shared interests featured in a particularly prominent way in some of the guidelines and teaching materials, in particular those focused on language resources, namely the *Processing Text and Corpora* course (<https://upskillsproject.eu/project/text.processing/>) and the *Guidelines for Integrating Research Infrastructures into Teaching* (van der Lek & Fišer, 2023).

2.2 One step beyond

The UNIBO team developed additional materials, partly adapted to meet the needs of the local target community, students of intercultural communication, translation and interpreting. The needs analysis was complemented by a survey that gives students an initial indication of the UPSKILLS subprofile they might wish to pursue—language data analyst, language data scientist, language data manager, language project manager—depending on their inclination towards data analysis versus organisational tasks. Furthermore, the original UPSKILLS corpus of job advertisements—a central component in the needs analysis—was accompanied by an updated 2023 edition.⁴ The resources converged in a website⁵ that helps students discover a suitable profile and leads them towards relevant learning materials.

At the same time, DIT started reforming its degree programmes in line with the UPSKILLS findings. At the MA level, the degree course in Specialized Translation gained a new curriculum in Translation and Technology, heavily focused on research skills, and incorporating courses such as *Profession-Based Research*, *Machine Translation*, *Natural Language Processing*, and *Language Data Analysis*. Later on, a module called *Language, Technology, Research* was introduced as an option in the BA course in *Languages and Technologies for Intercultural Communication*, with courses in *Computational Thinking* (I year), *Text Processing* (II year) and *Researching Language* (III year). Finally, the principles of research-based teaching have been implemented, most notably in the MA course in *Corpus Linguistics*, jointly with an evaluation approach based on peer assessment.

3 Scaling up with CLARIN

3.1 Focus on FAIRness

Several initiatives⁶ acknowledged a lack of awareness—among lecturers, students and researchers—of research data management practices, including knowledge of principles to make digital resources FAIR—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. Consequently, the *FAIR Competence Framework for Higher Education* (Demchenko et al., 2021) proposed a set of core competencies for FAIR data education that universities can use to integrate relevant content in their curricula. Students, teachers, and

⁴<https://bellatrix.sslmit.unibo.it/noske/upskills/#open>

⁵<https://upskilling.dipintra.it>

⁶In addition to UPSKILLS, especially the EOSC Working Group on Skills & Training (<https://eosc.eu/opportunity-area-exp/oa5-skills-training-rewards-recognition-upscaling/>) and their publication *Digital Skills for FAIR and Open Science* (<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>).

researchers from all disciplines are encouraged to acquire fundamental skills for **open science**, including the ability to effectively interact with **federated research infrastructures** and open science tools for collaborative research.

To further support the integration of these skills, CLARIN created its UPSKILLS course *Introduction to Language Data: Standards and Repositories* (van der Lek & Fišer, 2023) and *Best Practice Guidelines for Integrating Research Infrastructures into Teaching* (van der Lek et al., 2023) to show teachers and trainers how they can teach FAIR data skills to students in language- and linguistics-related programmes using CLARIN’s research data repositories and integrated tools, showing how to search for digital text collections, process them, analyze them, archive and share own language resources. The course was built on existing resources, such as the handbook *How to be FAIR with your data* (Engelhardt et al., 2022), comprising ready-made lesson plans and guidelines for teachers, and *The Open Handbook of Linguistics Data Management* (Berez-Kroeker et al., 2022), a useful toolkit for linguists.

3.2 Lectures on CLARIN resources at UNIBO

In March 2025, a total of three 90-minute guest lectures were delivered in two courses within DIT’s degree programmes at UNIBO, with the objective of familiarizing the students with the CLARIN research infrastructure. The lecturers reused some of the learning content developed in the UPSKILLS course, *Introduction to Language Data: Standards and Repositories*.

For the undergraduate course in *Language, Technology, Research II: Text Processing*, two sessions were organized, attended by 10 students with different language combinations, and three lecturers with a background in translation and interpreting studies. The first session shared best practices in project and research data management, with a particular focus on teamwork for collecting and building resources such as corpora. Students also learned how to find research data, starting from their institutional repository, and using registries like re3data.org to locate domain-specific repositories used in linguistics, such as CLARIN, TROLLing (<https://site.uit.no/trolling/>), and OLAC (<http://www.language-archives.org/>). The second session demonstrated how to discover language data in the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory and Resource Families. The students learned about the FAIR data principles through a hands-on activity that involved evaluating available corpora from a FAIR perspective.

In the master’s course in *Profession-Based Research*, part of the Translation and Technology curriculum, a CLARIN guest lecture was organized to provide an overview of the research infrastructure, focusing also on potential career paths for students with a background in languages (data stewards, communication specialists, training and education officers). Approximately 10 students and two lecturers attended this session. The students, who had a background in modern languages and translation, were just beginning to learn about the application of language technologies in their field.

3.3 Experience-based recommendations on how to teach about language resources

Based on recent teaching experience at UNIBO, the authors propose refining the initial learning outcomes developed in the UPSKILLS learning content by distinguishing learning objectives by study level. Table 1 provides the level-specific keywords, further explained below; a more comprehensive table version is available at <https://tinyurl.com/yyhckrtj>.

Topic	Learning objectives		
	BA	MA	PhD
Open Science and FAIR Data Principles	Recognise	Use	Apply
Research Infrastructures and Data Repositories			
Finding and (Re)Using Language Resources	Define	Assess	Solve
Analyzing Language Resources			
Building and Managing Language Resources	Explain	Analyze	Contribute
Sharing and Archiving Language Resources			

Table 1: A summary of language resource topics and learning objectives.

Bachelor's level: At the undergraduate level, students can be made aware of the added value of Open Science and taught basic concepts in project and research data management, from which they will benefit at a later stage. According to the *Minimum Viable Skillsets* framework developed in the Skills4EOSC project⁷ in the domain of Open Science and FAIR data principles and practices (White & Green, 2022), students at this level need to have foundational digital research skills, understand why it is important for society that research data is open and FAIR, and have good organisation and documentation skills. The CLARIN infrastructure can be used to give examples of published digitized text collections that are available and can be explored with free tools and services. By browsing the resources in the Virtual Language Observatory (VLO),⁸ students can learn that published data and tools are described with consistent metadata, carry licences with different possibilities of reuse (public, academic, restricted), and can be located and cited using a persistent identifier (e.g., Handle or DOI). Teachers can also use the VLO to show students how to search for text collections in plain text format, download them and upload them to their preferred corpus-building tool. For basic quantitative text analysis, Voyant Tools⁹ can be accessed directly from the VLO via Switchboard,¹⁰ and they are a free, open-source, browser-based data analysis and visualization environment that can quickly process texts in different formats. For more advanced text analysis, the CLARIN resource families of corpora can be used to show students how they can explore specific corpora through the integrated concordancers (NoSketch Engine, Korp, or KonText).¹¹

Master's level: At the MA level, students are expected to be able to integrate Open Science skills in their project workflows and assess FAIR concepts in their respective field of study, understand the data life cycle when conducting research. The research infrastructure can be used to encourage students to explore available resources and services, starting from a research question, and to apply the FAIR guiding principles to assess whether the published resources are suitable for reuse. For example, the CLARIN resource families of corpora can be used for interdisciplinary and comparative research; the Language Resource Switchboard can be used to incorporate natural language processing (NLP) tools in the classroom and teach students basic NLP methods, such as text segmentation, tokenization, part-of-speech tagging, syntactic parsing, and named entity recognition. After getting acquainted with basic NLP methods, students can be taught more advanced digital skills, such as programming in Python and R.

Doctoral level: Students at this level are usually required to follow general Open Science and Research Data Management courses, and are expected to be able to apply OS practices and FAIR data principles in their research (e.g., research data storage and archiving, handling legal and ethical issues surrounding the research data, selecting appropriate licences to protect potentially sensitive data). The infrastructure can be used to teach students how to find a certified CLARIN repository to deposit language resources they may have created in their PhD project (e.g., corpora, audio and video recordings, annotations, grammars), and make them available to the community in a reliable manner, following established good practices in research ethics. If the resources contain sensitive data, they can be safeguarded through an institutional login, data encryption, and specific terms and conditions for data protection.

4 Concluding remarks

Drawing on the UPSKILLS project, and the subsequent teaching experience of the project partners, this paper proposed a revised (check)list of learning objectives for the *Introduction to Language Data: Standards and Resources* course. We also invite lecturers and trainers within the CLARIN network to use the checklist and contribute their expertise by commenting on it. Such a collaboration will lead to enhanced future versions of the course and lay the ground for the integration of more advanced topics, such as the use of large language models for text analysis.

⁷<https://www.skills4eosc.eu/>

⁸<https://vlo.clarin.eu/?0>

⁹<https://voyant-tools.org/>

¹⁰<https://switchboard.clarin.eu/>

¹¹<https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families>

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Methodology for Converting and Publish Tabular Data into SKOS Resources via Python Notebooks

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Abstract

This paper presents a methodology for creating and converting tabular data into SKOS linguistic resources using Python notebooks. Designed to support users with limited technical skills, the approach offers a structured and reproducible process through interactive notebooks. The methodology covers metadata preparation, data scraping from repositories, information mapping, and data normalization for standardized vocabulary publication. Various specialized multilingual vocabularies, including those related to textile description and smart city terminology, were analyzed to evaluate the approach. Guidelines were also developed to optimize LOD environment deployment, including resource uploading and web application configuration. The methodology supports linguistic data management as Linked Open Data, offering a platform for hosting SKOS resources and training users to create structured data efficiently. The system was tested through external user engagement, demonstrating its scientific relevance and practical utility.

1 Introduction

The increasing adoption of Linked Open Data (LOD) practices in linguistic resource management highlights the need for efficient and accessible methods to convert tabular data into RDF¹. While progress has been made in promoting Linked Data principles, transforming non-standardised formats such as CSV or TSV into SKOS² remains a challenge. Existing tools (Fiorelli & Stellato, 2021) often require advanced technical skills and are not always user-friendly. OpenRefine³ stands out as a powerful tool for data transformation, but lacks a training-oriented approach.

To address this gap, we propose a methodology based on Python Jupyter notebooks⁴, designed to guide non-expert users step by step through the process of converting tabular data into SKOS. This approach combines user accessibility with data interoperability and quality, serving both as a practical tool and a training resource. Unlike general-purpose tools or language models like ChatGPT, our notebooks offer structured, domain-specific, and reproducible workflows aligned with LOD best practices.

The methodology has been tested in a real-world use case as part of a pilot initiative (described in Section 2.1), where external users applied the notebooks in a research context. This evaluation confirmed their usability and potential for broader adoption within linguistic data platforms.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of related work and contextual background. Section 3 details the methodology, including data acquisition, transformation, and deployment. Section 4 presents case studies to illustrate the practical application of the proposed

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¹<https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

²<https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/>

³<https://openrefine.org/>

⁴<https://github.com/cnr-ilc/ilc4clarin-jupyter-skos-notebook>

approach; in this section we discuss also the results and challenges encountered, followed by conclusions and suggestions for future work in Section 5.

2 Background and context

The landscape of linguistic data management is increasingly shaped by the principles of Linked Open Data (Berners-Lee, 2006), which aim to enhance the accessibility, interoperability, and usability of structured data across digital platforms. The integration of linguistic data into LOD frameworks is particularly significant, as it fosters the development of interconnected language resources, contributing to a more dynamic and semantically enriched web of data (Khan et al., 2022). In the following article we will focus on resources which are based on the SKOS vocabulary⁵, which are part of the Linguistic Linked Open Data Cloud⁶ under the category of 'Terminologies, Thesauri and Knowledge Bases'.

2.1 H2IOSC LLOD Pilot

The project described in this paper is part of a broader pilot initiative within the H2IOSC project⁷ (Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud), which aims to promote open and FAIR (Lamprecht et al., 2020) access to services and data in the domain of humanities and cultural heritage. As part of this initiative, the LLOD pilot⁸ (Linguistic Linked Open Data pilot) focuses on advancing LLOD technologies for managing and disseminating linguistic resources in interoperable and semantically rich formats. The LLOD pilot is developing a comprehensive infrastructure to support the entire lifecycle of linguistic data as Linked Data. This includes components for the transformation of tabular or XML-based resources into RDF, tools for browsing and editing language data, and services for publishing and querying linked data via SPARQL endpoints. The platform also integrates with Skosmos for vocabulary browsing, and features a quality assessment dashboard to ensure data consistency, adherence to LOD principles, and compliance with vocabularies such as OntoLex-Lemon⁹ and SKOS.

To ensure long-term accessibility and sustainability, resources are ingested into a central CLARIN repository¹⁰, which supports version control, metadata management, and integration into the broader European research infrastructure. Moreover, the pilot places strong emphasis on training and community support, providing tutorials, interactive Jupyter Notebooks for data conversion, and dedicated assistance to facilitate adoption by researchers, educators, and institutions. Through this approach, the LLOD pilot within H2IOSC contributes to the creation of a national infrastructure for linguistic Linked Data that is open, reusable, and aligned with European Open Science practices.

3 Methodology

In this section, we describe a comprehensive pipeline for creating SKOS resources from tabular data, focusing on the transformation and publication processes.

3.1 Overview of the LLOD Pipeline

This methodology outlines a streamlined approach for creating SKOS-formatted linguistic resources. The process begins with metadata collection and normalisation, followed by a manual alignment between structured files (e.g., CSV, TSV, XLSX) and the processed metadata to construct a SKOS ConceptScheme. The structured data is then converted into RDF triples using standard transformation tools. Finally, the resulting dataset is prepared for deployment on standard knowledge graph platforms,

⁵<https://www.w3.org/TR/swbp-skos-core-spec/>

⁶<https://linguistic-lod.org/>

⁷H2IOSC Project – Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud funded by the European Union NextGenerationEU – National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) – Mission 4 “Education and Research” Component 2 “From research to business” Investment 3.1 “Fund for the realization of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructures” Action 3.1.1 “Creation of new research infrastructures strengthening of existing ones and their networking for Scientific Excellence under Horizon Europe” – Project code IR0000029 – CUP B63C22000730005. Implementing Entity CNR. <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/>

⁸<https://pllod.clarin-it.it/>

⁹<https://www.w3.org/2019/09/lexicog/>

¹⁰<https://dspace-clarin-it.ilc.cnr.it/repository/xmlui/>

such as a triplestore and a SKOS-compliant interface, depending on the needs of the dataset creators, ensuring easy access and exploration of the lexical resources.

3.2 Data Acquisition and Preparation

The first phase of the pipeline focuses on metadata collection and normalisation as a pre-requisite for creating SKOS-formatted resources. Metadata is primarily retrieved from institutional repositories—such as DSpace—using its REST API, which enables the automated extraction of key information including authorship, licensing, and classification. The collected metadata is then structured into standardized JSON files to support downstream processing. Following metadata preparation, a manual alignment is performed between the structured data files (e.g., CSV, TSV, XLSX) and their corresponding metadata records in order to construct a coherent SKOS `ConceptScheme`. The structured data is subsequently cleaned and normalised to ensure consistency, with particular attention given to the addition of language tags and label formatting. Once this preprocessing is complete, the data is transformed into RDF triples using standard tools, described below. The resulting dataset is then either deployed on a triplestore and published through a SKOS-compliant platform, enabling efficient access, querying, and visualization of the vocabulary content. In the next subsection, we go through the process of RDF generation in detail. Subsequently we describe the publication of the lexicon.

3.3 Data Transformation and RDF Generation

This process of transformaing tabular data into RDF triples involves the following several critical steps:

- **Mapping Tabular Data to SKOS:** To convert data into RDF, the pipeline first generates YARRRML¹¹ mapping files. These files define the rules that link structured data elements (e.g., labels, definitions) to RDF properties (e.g., `skos:prefLabel`, `skos:altLabel`).
- **Generating RML Files:** The YARRRML files are subsequently converted to RML format using the Yatter library¹². This conversion produces RDF mapping files compatible with tools that support RML processing.
- **RDF Triple Generation:** The `morph-kgc`¹³ library processes the RML files to generate RDF triples. These triples are serialized in Turtle. During this phase, the pipeline ensures that encoding is consistent, particularly for multilingual data, by normalizing character sets and language tags.
- **Concept Aggregation and Linkage:** Once the RDF triples are generated, they are aggregated to form coherent SKOS concept schemes. This involves linking each SKOS concept to a corresponding concept scheme using properties such as `skos:hasTopConcept` and `skos:topConceptOf`. This step ensures that the generated data forms a coherent and navigable hierarchy.
- **Quality Assurance and Encoding Normalisation:** To ensure data quality, the pipeline includes a normalisation step that checks for special characters and encoding issues within URIs. This step is crucial for maintaining consistency when publishing data on platforms that may have encoding constraints.

3.4 Publishing and Visualizing the Lexicons

The final phase of the pipeline is the publication and visualization of the generated RDF data. Depending on the requirements of the data providers the LLOD pilot allows users to host their SKOS on a

¹¹YARRRML (Yet Another RDF Mapping Language) is a human-readable syntax based on YAML, designed to make the creation of RML mappings more accessible. It allows users to describe how structured data should be transformed into RDF triples without requiring deep technical knowledge of RML.

<https://rml.io/yarrml/>

¹²Yatter is a Python library for converting YARRRML mapping files into RML in Turtle syntax.

<https://github.com/citiusus/yatter>

¹³`morph-kgc` is a Python library for generating RDF from structured data using R2RML or RML mappings.

<https://github.com/morph-kgc/morph-kgc>

SKOSMOS-based platform, which provides a user-friendly interface for exploring and querying the lexical data. The platform supports multilingual search, hierarchical browsing, and concept visualization, making the generated vocabularies accessible to both technical and non-technical users. To facilitate data integration and visualization, the SKOSMOS configuration is optimised to reflect the structure of the generated RDF. The resulting vocabulary collections are thus not only interoperable within the LOD ecosystem but also easily navigable through a web interface tailored to the needs of linguistic data users.

4 Case Studies: REALITER Pan-Latin lexicons

The methodology has been applied in a use case involving the processing of specialised vocabularies (Grimaldi & Zanola, 2021) developed within the Pan-Latin Terminology Network (REALITER¹⁴), which brings together experts, associations and institutions from Romance language countries specialising in terminology. The network promotes plurilingual communication in specialised fields and activities aimed at harmonising Romance languages and fostering linguistic diversity. It develops and manages multilingual terminological resources to support experts, citizens, and academic communities, emphasising methodological consistency and variation (Gilardoni et al., 2011; Zanola et al., 2014). Since its foundation, several vocabularies across domains such as economics, environment, medicine, biology, digital technologies, education and fashion have been produced. These resources take into account terminological variation and cultural aspects of each language and variety (Lo Presti & Dankova, 2021; Zanola et al., 2022); they are indexed in the REALITER – OTPL collection¹⁵ and published on the ILC4CLARIN Skosmos Service¹⁶.

This case study addresses the conversion of several multilingual vocabularies into SKOS and their hosting on the LLOD pilot SKOSMOS platform. The vocabularies, mainly in CSV format, contain labels, definitions and notes. Currently, 18 REALITER lexicons are available, with 3,467 entries in seven Romance languages (Catalan, Spanish, French, Galician, Italian, Portuguese, Romanian), including varieties such as Canadian French, Argentinean Spanish and Brazilian Portuguese, as well as in English. Definitions are usually given in the Romance source language; in some cases they are missing or expressed through drawings, as in the *Pan-Latin Lexicon of Collars and Sleeves in Fashion and Costume*. Each entry contains a preferred term (prefLabel) and often several alternative terms (altLabel), with grammatical information following language-specific conventions (e.g. s. m. for masculine singular nouns in Romanian). Terms are marked with language and, for geographical variants, country (e.g. Spanish (Mexico), Portuguese (Brazil)). Additional information is provided in notes. The collaborative nature of the data required dedicated parsing algorithms. By analysing the syntax of these taxonomies, an algorithmic foundation was defined to guide the conversion workflow. After conversion, the resources were integrated into an institutional vocabulary platform based on SKOSMOS, enabling browsing, multilingual search, and REST API access.

The Figure 1 represents the lexical entry *città intelligente* (smart city) of the *Pan-Latin Smart City Lexicon* in the SKOSMOS vocabulary platform.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

The methodology proposed in this article provides a structured approach for transforming linguistic data into SKOS resources, using Python notebooks to support data conversion and training. The pipeline integrates data acquisition, transformation, and publication, demonstrating its effectiveness in generating high-quality LLOD resources. The integration of these resources into a SKOSMOS-based platform enhances their accessibility and practical utility. Applying this methodology to Pan-Latin vocabularies has shown its ability to handle complex, multilingual data. Integrating these resources into the institutional vocabulary platform increases their visibility and supports reuse within the Linked Open Data community, both through a web interface and REST APIs.

¹⁴<https://www.realiter.net/>

¹⁵<https://dspace-clarin-it.ilc.cnr.it/repository/xmlui/handle/000-c0-111/565>

¹⁶<https://vocabs.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr.it/skosmos/gl/?clang=sv>

The screenshot shows the ILC4CLARIN - Skosmos Service interface. At the top, there are navigation links: 'Vocabolari', 'Informazioni', 'Feedback', 'Aiuto', and 'Linguaggio della interfaccia: italiano'. The main header is 'Pan-Latin Smart City Lexicon' with a search bar and a 'Trova' button. Below the header, there are two tabs: 'Ordine Alfabetico' and 'Gerarchia'. The 'Gerarchia' tab is active, showing a list of terms: 'sakeholder', 'sistema di trasporto intelligente', 'Smart City', 'città intelligente', 'smart device', 'smart grid', 'smartphone', 'social network', 'start up', 'success fee', and 'sviluppo sostenibile'. The 'città intelligente' term is selected, and its details are shown in the main content area. The details include: 'TERMINE PREFERITO: città intelligente', 'DEFINIZIONE: Città caratterizzata dall'integrazione tra saperi, strutture e mezzi tecnologicamente avanzati, propri della società della comunicazione e dell'informazione, finalizzati a una crescita sostenibile e al miglioramento della qualità della vita.', 'TERMINI ALTERNATIVI PER IL CONCETTO: Smart City', 'NOTA: città intelligente (n.f), Smart City (n.f)', 'IN ALTRE LINGUE: ciutat intel·ligent (catalano), ville intelligente (francese), cidade inteligente (galiziano), smart city (inglese), cidade inteligente (portoghese), oraj inteligent (rumeno), ciudad inteligente (spagnolo)', 'URI: https://vocabils.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr.it/vocabularies/PLSmartCity/città_intelligente', and 'SCARICA QUESTO CONCETTO: RDF/XML, Turtle, JSON-LD'. The last modification date is 'Ultima modifica 31/07/23'.

Figure 1: Città intelligente, *Pan-Latin Smart City Lexicon*.

Future developments will include adopting the Mapheator tool¹⁷ to simplify mapping rule creation in formats like R2RML, RML, and YARRRML. The spreadsheet-based approach will make mapping more accessible for non-expert users and streamline the transformation process. The training materials from this project will be integrated into the H2IOSC training platform¹⁸, which is currently being developed to support users in replicating the workflow and adopting LLOD best practices.

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¹⁷<https://github.com/oeg-upm/mapeathor>

¹⁸<https://h2iosc-training-platform.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr.it/>

CLARIN in CLARIAH-VL+: Plans for 2025-2028

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1 Introduction

In Belgium, the Flemish research organisation FWO, together with the Department of Economics, Science and Innovation, has approved the next phase of the CLARIAH-VL international research infrastructure. Building on the achievements of the CLARIAH-VL Open Humanities Service Infrastructure (2018–2020) (Chambers et al., 2019) and CLARIAH-VL Advancing Open Humanities Service Infrastructure (2021–2024) (Vandeghinste et al., 2021), this new phase (CLARIAH-VL+) will consolidate previous efforts. This paper presents the CLARIN-related roadmap for this next phase. The project will develop several new Service Infrastructure Components (SICs) focused on generative AI and natural language processing, as described in section 2.

2 Generative AI and NLP

The *Service Infrastructure Components* (SICs), that will be developed are described in the following sections: Section 2.1 describes an infrastructure for accessible fine-tuning of large language models (LLMs) with configurable scripts and HPC integration. Section 2.2 discusses an explainability framework using retrieval-augmented generation for more transparent AI interactions. Section 2.3 talks about an enhanced cross-lingual linguistic query interface combining syntactic (Universal Dependencies) and semantic search. And Section 2.4 a multimodal annotation environment supporting collaborative, machine-learning-enhanced annotation across text, speech, image, and video is discussed.

These components aim to strengthen digital humanities research and language technology through improved accessibility, interoperability, and interdisciplinary collaboration within the CLARIN network.

2.1 Infrastructure for fine-tuning LLMs

Large language models (LLMs) have grown in size (Xiao et al., 2024), making task-specific fine-tuning less feasible on consumer hardware or free cloud-based tools like Google Colab. We therefore endeavour to improve the availability of easy-to-adapt, easy-to-use fine-tuning scripts. By means of straightforward configuration files for coarse-grained tasks (e.g. text or token classification, generation, summarisation), our users will be able to fine-tune an LLM for their specific use-case without the need of writing any code.

We have access to the server network of CLiPS¹ (maintained at the faculty level) which contains 6 recent GPUs, and to the HPC infrastructure of the Flanders region through our universities.

Furthermore, as these models are getting larger, the scripts will be tailored for use in server and high performance computing (HPC) environments (e.g. the Flemish Supercluster VSC² or the European

¹<https://www.uantwerpen.be/en/research-groups/clips/>

²<https://www.vscenrum.be/>

LUMI cluster³), lowering the threshold for non-technical users to utilise advanced hardware.

In this light, we emphasise the training of our users to improve their technical literacy and skills while at the same time lowering the learning curve with the pre-made scripts. We will organise training sessions and create tutorials with real-world use-cases based on the pre-made, configurable scripts in collaboration with VSC.

2.2 Explainability infrastructure

The goal of this Service Infrastructure Component is to provide researchers and practitioners with a reliable, state-of-the-art architecture for generating explanations in the context of interactions with LLMs. In normal LLM interaction it is already possible to have the model generate explanations of its solutions or answers, but this is error-prone (viz., the retrieval and construction of the answer and explanation are unconnected). This leads to spurious and misleading interpretations, presenting a clear gap in both applied contexts (particularly in domains such as education or healthcare) and when used for research purposes, where trustworthy explanations are critical.

To address this gap, we will rely on current developments in fine-tuning and in-context learning (RAG, Retrieval-Augmented Generation (Gao et al., 2024)) on open source LLMs. By integrating the retrieval of relevant knowledge with explanation generation, spurious explanations that are unconnected to the answers provided can be avoided. This will make explanations more accurate and relevant, responding to user needs for interpretability and reliability in AI-assisted workflows.

The development of this infrastructure will follow incremental, yearly iterations. First, we will create a general baseline infrastructure that integrates RAG-based explanation generation. This infrastructure will be tested on initial use cases from externally funded projects, including:

- dialogues between physicians in training and (role-playing) patients (explanations of diagnoses and feedback on the communicative behaviour of both patients and physicians), and
- explanation in an educational environment (feedback for learners of Dutch).

Based on systematic user studies and feedback on these use cases, the infrastructure will be updated and generalized for broader applications (depending on funding decisions: either again from externally funded projects or newly developed use cases). Finally, the infrastructure will be made available as a methodology and a software service.

2.3 Interface for Cross-lingual Linguistic analysis

The goal of this Service Infrastructure Component is to upgrade the GrETEL syntactic query engine (Augustinus et al., 2012, 2017) to the realm of Universal Dependencies (UDs) (de Marneffe et al., 2021) and LLMs to allow querying corpora both for syntactic and semantic phenomena, and for many different languages.

One of the limitations of the current GrETEL engine is that it uses the ideosyncratic Alpino xml format (van Noord, 2006) as tree representation. Although there have been efforts to use this model for other languages than Dutch (Augustinus et al., 2016), the UD format has become a *de facto* multilingual standard for syntactic parsers and treebanks. So, a first extension will incorporate UD to enable precise example-based queries. This will simplify the process of identifying and analysing syntactic structures across a wide range of languages.

Secondly, the capabilities of the tool will be extended with semantic search functionalities. This addition will be achieved through the adoption of transformer-based representations, which are designed to capture deeper semantic relationships within text (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019). By sequentially addressing both syntactic and semantic dimensions, this will result in a more comprehensive and versatile linguistic search tool.

These upgrades should result in a flexible and extendible multilingual example-based treebank query system for universal dependency treebanks.

³<https://www.lumi-supercomputer.eu/>

2.4 Multimodal Annotation Environment

In this Service Infrastructure Component we implement a multimodal and machine learning-driven annotation platform that addresses gaps in existing cross-modal annotation workflows, particularly the lack of integrated, collaborative tools for text, speech, image and video across varied linguistic domains. The proposed platform builds on existing open-source annotation modules, and allows

- manual annotation of text, image, video, and speech;
- validation and manual post-editing of automatic annotation through communication with APIs integrating machine-learning models; and
- fine-tuning existing models with newly annotated gold standard data.

The integration of machine learning modules enhances both the efficiency of manual annotation, by automating preliminary labeling, and accuracy of automatic annotation, by supporting domain-specific fine-tuning using newly created gold standard data. Each feature of the annotation platform, viz. manual input, model-assisted validation, and fine-tuning, directly responds to user demands for adaptability, ease of collaboration, and support for under-resourced or complex linguistic varieties. This will stimulate collaboration between researchers from different disciplines working on different genres, dialects or variants of various languages. We will evaluate the framework through a number of use cases from externally funded projects:

- The annotation of Byzantine Greek Book Epigrams project (Swaelens et al., 2023);
- Research carried out in the framework of the “human-like AI” research challenge of the Flanders AI project to model empathy in multimodal conversational agents.

An important part of this Service Infrastructure Component will be the extension of the linguistic annotation and language understanding modules developed in the running CLARIAH-VL project, such as TextLens⁴ on various axes. We will benchmark and integrate additional modules for linguistic annotation, such as neural systems for parsing and Named Entity Recognition, with a specific focus on domain adaptability (e.g., parsing for Flemish and Dutch dialects). Another important focus area will be linguistic annotation for ancient languages (e.g., Latin and Greek), where we will collaborate with existing projects such as NIKAW (Beersmans et al., 2024) to exchange best practices for data annotation and model development. For this component, we will again cooperate with the VSC.

3 Conclusions

The CLARIN-related plans within CLARIAH-VL+ build upon previous infrastructure efforts while expanding into new and emerging areas of digital humanities and language technology. Our focus on generative AI and NLP will improve access to fine-tuning infrastructure for large language models, making these tools more accessible to researchers through tailored scripts, HPC integration, and user training.

The explainability infrastructure will address a critical challenge in AI-assisted research: generating reliable, context-aware explanations. Through retrieval-augmented generation and fine-tuned models, we aim to provide more transparent and interpretable AI outputs for research and educational applications.

In the domain of linguistic analysis, the cross-lingual linguistic query interface will enhance syntactic and semantic search capabilities by incorporating Universal Dependencies and transformer-based representations. This will extend existing tools, such as GrETEL, to facilitate research across languages and linguistic phenomena.

Finally, the multimodal annotation environment will enable collaborative and machine-learning-enhanced annotation for various modalities, including text, speech, image, and video. By supporting manual annotation, automatic validation, and model fine-tuning, this component will foster interdisciplinary collaboration and provide valuable resources for multiple research domains, including Flemish Sign Language studies.

⁴<https://portal.clarin.ivdnt.org/textlens/>

Through these initiatives, CLARIAH-VL+ will significantly advance the research infrastructure available to Flemish and international scholars, strengthening the integration of AI, NLP, and linguistic research within the CLARIN network. Future work will focus on refining these components based on user feedback and ensuring sustainability beyond the project's initial timeframe.

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Opravidlo 2.0: AI-powered Proofreader for Czech Texts

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Abstract

Opravidlo 2.0 is an advanced AI-powered proofreader for Czech that combines rule-based linguistic analysis with machine learning techniques to improve the accuracy and usability of automatic grammar correction. Building upon the success of Beta Opravidlo, a rule-based tool developed in 2022, the new version addresses its limitations—particularly low recall—by integrating neural models capable of handling complex linguistic phenomena. The hybrid architecture ensures explainability and minimal correction. The system is deployed as public service and supported by institutional infrastructure, with plans to release correction rules and annotated datasets aligned with FAIR principles and GDPR compliance. Integration with CLARIN and LINDAT/CLARIAH ensures sustainability, interoperability, and future extensibility to other Slavic languages. Opravidlo 2.0 thus represents a significant step forward in the development of language technology for morphologically rich languages.

1 Introduction

Correct written and spoken language is highly valued in the Czech environment. Authors of texts with spelling mistakes often face distrust, and their credibility diminishes. Human proofreaders ensure correctness but are costly and slow. Therefore, automatic proofreading tools have been developed, though Czech's inflectional nature and homonymy pose challenges. The rule-based online proofreader, Beta Opravidlo, is a significant development in this field, released in mid-2022. It has been widely adopted by users of Czech, native speakers, and language learners. Initially the most precise proofreader available, it now faces competition from large language models (LLMs). This article describes the challenges posed by the development of Opravidlo 2.0, which combines a rule-based system from Beta Opravidlo and an AI-powered approach. The project Opravidlo 2.0 was supported by the OSCARS project, funded by the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme (grant agreement No. 101129751). This paper reflects on how the CLARIN infrastructure can help the research team complete the intended project, which could ultimately apply to other Slavic languages besides Czech. In addition, we propose services within the CLARIN infrastructure that support both research in grammar error correction and the usability of the tool by the general public.

A general proofreading workflow can span several scenarios. For example, simple spell checkers only correct mistyped words. State-of-the-art proofreaders such as Grammarly (2025) or LanguageTool (Rüdian et al., 2022) not only correct spellchecking, grammar, and punctuation but also suggest style and clarity improvements. Using general-purpose LLMs for proofreading has been studied e.g. in (Wu et al., 2023), where the major problems are not only under-correction (i.e. the model does not discover all errors) and mis-correction (i.e. the model detects an error but the suggested correction is incorrect) but also over-correction where the model does not respect the original user text creation. In contrast, we focus on a workflow of minimum corrections with the human in the loop. The tool suggests a minimal number of interventions that must be resolved to obtain grammatically, syntactically, and typographically concise text. Besides the corrections, the user obtains explanations of why a certain part is wrong, including the description of the phenomena.

2 Beta Opravidlo

Beta Opravidlo (2022) is a free online tool (www.opravidlo.cz) developed by an interdisciplinary team consisting of linguists and programmers under the auspices of Masaryk University. Users input text into the interface and receive correction suggestions, as well as explanations from the Internet Language Reference Book (2025) for more complex phenomena such as grammatical agreement. Beta Opravidlo is a rule-based system with over 7,500 linguistic rules divided into several modules, including punctuation, spelling, agreement, and typography. The modular system allows parallel processing but struggles with speed, taking several seconds per text. Precision for individual modules ranges from 91% to 96%, with recall varying between 40% and 80%, depending on text complexity. While it gained over 200,000 correction requests per month, users noted its low recall as a drawback.

Beta Opravidlo is closely related to three areas of NLP: grammar error correction (GEC), grammar error detection (GED), and grammar error explanation (GEE)(Song et al. 2023).

3 Transition to Opravidlo 2.0

User feedback on Beta Opravidlo was positive, particularly because its precision and provided explanations, but discussions arose regarding machine learning integration. Studies (Machura et al., 2022; Medková & Horák, 2022) revealed that neural networks could increase recall and precision in Czech proofreading. While rule-based systems excel at error classification and explanation, they struggle, for example, with syntactic ambiguity, agreement, and more complex linguistic structures. In contrast, transformer models can process long-range dependencies. While pretrained models can correct many errors successfully, they are limited in the minimum correction condition; it is difficult to instruct the model not to change the text. In addition, pretrained models often do not provide correct explanations for the corrections. When trained in the machine translation scenario (ungrammatical text is “translated” to correct text), transformer models lack explainability. A hybrid approach balancing both methods appears optimal.

3.1 A Hybrid Approach

Opravidlo 2.0 will integrate rule-based corrections for well-defined errors and machine-learning models for more complex grammar issues to improve precision and recall. In the later stages of developing neural approaches, we will assess whether the neural model outperforms the rule-based system in certain aspects. Additionally, an ensemble model incorporating multiple models may be considered. While the rule-based system lacks scalability, the prediction time of neural models can be influenced by hardware. Currently, we plan to deploy the proofreading service on GPU servers at the Faculty of Informatics, Masaryk University. Future GPU deployment will depend on the availability of large research infrastructures such as CLARIN.

4 Opravidlo 2.0 as a Public Service

We intend to roll out Opravidlo 2.0 as a public service. We started by localizing the user interface into the languages of the most numerous minorities in the Czech Republic (Vietnamese, Ukrainian, Russian) and English. We believe this step will contribute to human capital development in the Czech Republic.

We also focus on sustainability through institutional support. The long-term sustainability of our service is ensured through institutional backing and strategic deployments. The service is actively deployed at Masaryk University, contributing to research and academic initiatives. Additionally, the Internet Language Reference Book (2025) is hosted both at the Academy of Sciences and Masaryk University and is among the LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ large infrastructure projects. All that ensures accessibility and reliability.

To promote openness while preserving data security, we plan to publish data sets following FAIR in LINDAT/CLARIAH, which is in line with best practices for linguistic data sharing. First, we plan to release the correction rules since a large part of them is reusable in other languages as well. The most effective way is to convert the grammar rules into existing standards, such as Universal Dependencies

(2025) and ERRANT (Error Annotation Toolkit)(Bryant, Felice, and Briscoe 2017). The second dataset we plan to release is a proofreading benchmark. Currently, the Czech language has the GECCC dataset, a non-synthetic dataset of grammar errors made by native speakers and language learners mainly from Ukraine, Russia, Belarus, and the Romani community (Náplava et al., 2022). Synthetic datasets were used for GEC-related tasks (i. e., Machura et al., 2023). In this situation, another dataset from real data will contribute to the development of proofreading tools for Czech and maybe for teaching Czech as a second language. Publication of a dataset with user texts, proposed corrections, and information on whether users accepted them is where further collaboration with the CLARIN infrastructure is desired, as our data often contains sensitive user information and needs to be pseudonymized before publication to comply with the GDPR. Standardization and publication of data can support similar proofreading services for different (Slavic) languages.

In addition, our service will be integrated into the Switchboard Tools registry, ensuring seamless access and interoperability into the broader community. To our knowledge, SwitchBoard does not offer any proofreading tools (footnote: <https://switchboard.clarin.eu/tools>), however, it offers tools for text enhancements (parsing, stylometry, coreference resolution).

5 Current state of [Opravidlo.cz](https://opravidlo.cz)

As of August 2025, users are still using the beta version, in which the spell checker has been modified to increase the speed of corrections. Users now have four language versions of the user interface (UI) available, in addition to Czech, English, Vietnamese, Ukrainian, and Russian. These languages were selected based on data on the largest foreign minorities living in the Czech Republic. Slovak was excluded from the selection since it is very close to Czech and Slovaks understand the Czech UI.

We analyzed the texts that users want to correct. It turned out that they are diverse in style, with schoolwork being the most common, followed by reports, emails, administrative texts, and advertisements. However, the data also includes specific texts such as speeches, greetings, and legal documents.

Since punctuation errors are between the most prevalent, we focused on comma prediction. We trained three transformer-based models: RobeCzech-base and XLM-RoBERTa-large as token classifiers, and mT5-large as a text-to-text model inserting commas into unpunctuated text. Training used the SYN v9 dataset from the LINDAT repository, filtered to include lines with at least one comma, with subsets of 100k, 300k, and 500k lines selected for their curated and proofread content, offering more diverse comma usage than raw internet text. The results are published in Machura et al. 2025. The main outcome is, 98.5% precision can be achieved RoBERTa with 100k dataset (recall=75.8%) and 93.1% F1 can be achieved using RobeCzech-base (here, precision is 94.5%).

In October 2025, we plan to publish a set of approximately 6,000 rules through which corrections are made in the beta version.

6 Conclusion

The development of Opravidlo 2.0 represents a significant step forward in Czech language proofreading, combining the strengths of rule-based systems with AI-powered approaches. By addressing the limitations of Beta Opravidlo and incorporating machine learning, we aim to enhance precision, recall, and overall usability. Deploying the service as a public tool with multilingual support underscores its broader societal impact, fostering inclusivity and accessibility.

Sustainability is ensured through institutional support from Masaryk University and integration into research infrastructures like CLARIN and LINDAT/CLARIAH. Data security remains a priority, with GDPR-compliant pseudonymization enabling responsible data sharing. Furthermore, standardization efforts can facilitate the adaptation of Opravidlo 2.0 to other Slavic languages, expanding its reach and usability beyond Czech.

As of August 2025, users are working with the beta version, featuring a faster spell checker and interfaces in Czech, English, Vietnamese, Ukrainian, and Russian. Our analysis of the texts sent for correction shows that they are very diverse, most often school assignments, followed by reports, emails, and administrative documents.

For comma prediction, models base on RobeCzech-base, XLM-RoBERTa-large, and mT5-large on the SYN v9 dataset from the LINDAT repository were trained. In October 2025, we plan to release about 6,000 rules used for corrections in the beta version.

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Language and Division in Swedish Social Media Discourse

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Abstract

This study examines how language shapes perceptions and interactions between societal groups, focusing on online discourse in Sweden. Using sentiment analysis and topic modelling on posts from two major Swedish social media platforms, we identify patterns in how social divisions are expressed, reinforced, and contested. Drawing on linguistic resources and tools from SpråkbankenText, part of the Swe-CLARIN infrastructure, we analyse the linguistic constructions of *segregation* as they appear in digital spaces. This approach allows us to examine how language both mirrors and molds public attitudes—often framing complex social issues in emotionally charged or polarized terms. The findings shed light on the complex ways digital communication influences social discourse in contemporary Sweden. By tracing how specific lexical and thematic choices contribute to the normalization or contestation of social boundaries, the study highlights the centrality of language in mediating inclusion, exclusion, and identity.

1 Introduction and Background

Current research highlights how linguistic practices both reflect and reinforce social divisions, with language barriers contributing to disparities in education, employment, and access to services. Studies on linguistic expression in public discourse, institutional policy, and media representation reveal underlying power dynamics, the construction of cultural identities, and the dominance of certain narratives. In this context, social media plays a crucial role by amplifying marginalized voices, exposing discrimination, and shaping public understanding of social issues. One example is the case of *segregation* in Swedish cities, shaped by historical migration patterns, housing policies, and socioeconomic structures. These conditions have contributed to visible divides between neighbourhoods, often along lines of income, ethnicity, and access to public resources. Immigrant communities frequently reside in outer suburbs with lower housing costs, while more affluent, predominantly native-born Swedes tend to live in central or well-serviced areas. According to Andersson et al. (2018), housing and labour market dynamics have helped maintain these patterns, making spatial inequality a persistent feature of urban Sweden.

Language, particularly in social media, serves as a pivotal factor in societal segregation, and linguistic barriers can perpetuate social divisions, leading to the marginalization of non-dominant language speakers. A study by Rosa & Flores (2022) emphasizes that perceptions of linguistic diversity often become sites for marginalization and exclusion, suggesting that advocacy for language and social justice must move beyond merely acknowledging linguistic diversity to confronting underlying inequalities. This study has two aims: to analyse temporal and sentiment patterns in social media discourse on social division, and to examine how language constructs segregation in contemporary Sweden using corpus linguistics and language technology. Using segregation as a case, we show how online discussions reflect broader social dynamics and can inform future research on communication and inequality.

2 Method

We begin with sentiment analysis to assess the emotional tone of the texts. Next, we use a modern topic modelling technique based on transformer neural network architecture to generate dense clusters, ena-

bling interpretable topics while preserving key terms in the topic descriptions. We apply a prompt engineering approach with OpenAI’s GPT-4o model from OpenAI¹ to generate topic labels; cf. Fig. 1). Lastly, we provide a close reading and interpretation of the results to derive some meaningful insights.

```
prompt = """
I have a topic that contains the following documents:
[DOCUMENTS]
The topic is described by the following keywords: [KEYWORDS]

Based on the information above, extract a short topic label in the following format:
topic: <topic label>
```

Figure 1. Prompt engineering for topic labelling.

2.1 Data Collection

For the experiment we use data from two popular Swedish online discussion platforms, *Flashback Forum* and *Familjeliv.se*, selected for their extensive user engagement and diverse perspectives on societal issues ($n \approx 2415$). Data selection follows a set of criteria, ensuring relevance to themes of language and segregation, with posts collected to capture temporal variations in discourse, while striving to reflect diverse perspectives on the segregation over time. Specifically, we chose 34 threads where the word “segregation” appeared in the title of the threads. For data analysis, a lexicon-based sentiment analysis approach was employed, specifically utilizing VADER (Hutto & Gilbert, 2014), a tool grounded in natural language processing (NLP) techniques to classify posts and, to the greatest extent possible, identify their underlying emotional tones. Most of the lexical resources utilized were sourced from SpråkbankenText². Additionally, BERTopic (Grootendorst, 2022) is applied to uncover thematic structures within the discussions, identifying dominant positive and negative narratives and recurring concerns related to segregation. The results provide insights into public perception, showing sentiment and discourse patterns that reflect broader attitudes toward linguistic diversity and social inclusion.

2.2 Exploratory Empirical Findings

The sentiment analysis outcomes reveal the distribution of sentiments—positive, neutral, and negative—across the topics, highlighting prevailing attitudes toward language and segregation (cf. Ding, Horning & Rho, 2023). This distribution provides insights into the emotional polarization of public (social media) discourse (cf. Karjus & Cuskley, 2024). Through topic modelling, dominant themes within each sentiment category are identified, uncovering recurring narratives and key discussion points. Although more experimentation is required, a preliminary comparative analysis of topics across the two dominant sentiment categories (negative and positive) further elucidates how different the perspectives shift depending on the emotional tone, offering a nuanced understanding of how language-related issues are framed in online discourse (cf. Section 3). These findings contribute to a deeper comprehension of public sentiment dynamics and their implications for societal cohesion. BERTopic utilizes pre-trained language models, and class-based Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (c-TF-IDF) and then applies clustering techniques to identify prevailing topics. This enables nuanced exploration of overarching themes, using a state-of-the-art pre-trained Swedish language model to analyse the dataset’s posts / discussions, trained by the National Library of Sweden³).

Overall, 52% of the posts were categorized as exhibiting a negative tone, whereas 37.6% were identified as positive. The remaining 10.4% were classified as neutral, either because no sentiment label was assigned or because the posts contained mixed sentiments, such as equal positive and negative annotations. All three groups were then used in the topic modelling experiment. Most of the generated topics exhibit a distinctly negative tone and reveal some notable patterns in the data.

Regarding the topics of the *negative subset* most prominent (cf. Figure 2) were: topic 9 which is about *Two-State Solution & Territorial Conflict* (keywords: “tvåstatslösning” – two-state solution,

¹ LLM & Generative AI: https://maartengr.github.io/BERTopic/getting_started/representation/llm.html.

² Sentimentlex: <https://spraakbanken.gu.se/en/resources/sentimentlex> and senSALDO: <https://spraakbanken.gu.se/en/resources/sensaldo>.

³ The Swedish transformer model: <https://huggingface.co/KBLab/sentence-bert-swedish-cased>.

“stat” – state, “stater” – states and “mark” – land/territory); topic 11 about *Demographics and Economic Indicators* (keywords: “nolla” – zero, “normän” – Norwegians, “finnar” – Finns, “utrikesfödda” – foreign-born;) and topic 4 about *Education and Children’s Issues* (keywords: “skola” – school, “föräldrar” – parents, “elever” – students, “barnen” – children. Further down you find a topic (topic 10) on *Islamic Communities and Religious Identity* and topic 8 on *Gang Crime and Socioeconomic Factors*. Regarding the topics of the *postive subset* most prominent (cf. Figure 3) were generated topics which highlight the writer’s stance in the data: topic 9 is about *Government Budget and Tax Funding* (keywords: “mkr” – million SEK, “miljarder” – billions, “kostar” - costs, “pengar” – money); topic 7 about Empathy and Emotional Responses (keywords: “empati” – empathy, “empatistörning” – empathy disorder, “skriker” – screaming, “reagera” – reacting), and topic 11 on *Housing and Social Welfare* (“lägenheter” – apartments, “förort” – suburb, “socialsekreterare” – social secretary, “förfogande” – disposal). Further down you find a topic (topic 4) on *Education and School Integration* and topic 0 on *Housing and Urban Areas*.

Figure 2. The three most significant identified topics in the *negative* subset.

Figure 3. The three most significant identified topics in the *postive* subset.

Figures 2 and 3 (above) present a detailed visualization of the word scores analysis across the three most significant identified topics, with each subplot showing the most significant terms and their relative weights within each topic cluster. The scores represent how important or characteristic each word is for that topic—the higher the score, the more relevant the word is to the topic. This quantitative representation helps validate the qualitative topic interpretations and shows minimal overlap between primary terms across different topics.

3 Discussion

The findings underscore the critical role of the linguistic construction of segregation in shaping social divisions, as reflected in online discourse. The correlation between digital discussions and physical segregation patterns suggests that the narratives are not merely abstract concerns but are deeply embedded in lived experiences (‘we’ vs ‘they’), influencing access to social integration, and group identity formation. The prevalence of negative sentiments in discussions on linguistic diversity mirrors real-world exclusionary tendencies, reinforcing societal divides. These insights show how language can both unite and divide, influencing inclusion and exclusion. The study underscores the importance of policies to address language-based marginalization for more equitable societies. The research highlights a computational framework for studying these dynamics between language and segregation, in the context of contemporary Swedish society. By leveraging a modern topic modelling framework, we can uncover

the underlying discursive patterns that sustain social media representations of segregation. The findings can provide empirical evidence on the role of language in shaping public perceptions of segregation, offering new insights into how discourses evolve and influence societal attitudes. Moreover, they encourage a deeper, more critical examination of the assumptions underlying these analyses, highlighting the ways in which language not only reflects but actively constructs social realities and shapes collective understandings of segregation.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

The purpose of this paper is to provide an exploratory overview of the conceptual and methodological foundations for studying segregation through computational and linguistic lenses. This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of sentiment analysis and topic modelling in analysing segregation-related posts, using a test corpus as a case study. Topic modelling results identify clusters of words that tend to co-occur, pointing to underlying themes or subjects. Interpreting these clusters is essential to understand what the themes represent, regardless of the reader's prior background knowledge. A key objective is to identify the most effective ways to apply these NLP techniques to ensure reliable and meaningful results—that is, to understand how NLP can shape, reinforce, or challenge societal biases, which is crucial for analysing segregation discourses (Blodgett et al., 2020). Future work will extend this methodology to larger datasets to further evaluate its robustness and refine its application. While corpus linguistic methods offer several advantages in analysing large-scale textual data, it is essential to critically engage with their limitations, particularly issues of sample bias and the risk of reinforcing pre-existing narratives embedded in training data. This concern is particularly pertinent in studies of segregation discourses, where different text genres—policy documents, media reports, and public discussions—frame the issue in distinct and often conflicting ways. Therefore, the selection of data sources and methodological approaches must be rigorously examined to avoid overly simplistic or skewed interpretations.

This study contributes to the growing field of *computational social science* by applying advanced NLP techniques to a pressing societal issue (Rodriguez & Storer, 2019). The ongoing collection of national and local textual data will serve as the foundation for a longitudinal analysis of how the concept of 'segregation' is addressed across media, policy, and public narratives. Moreover, qualitative discourse analysis will further contextualize linguistic representations to ensure that computational methods capture not only frequency-based trends but also the deeper ideological structures embedded in segregation-related discourses.

The findings can provide empirical evidence on the role of language in shaping public perceptions of segregation, offering new insights into how discourses evolve and influence societal attitudes. By integrating linguistic analysis of texts and discourses with critical policy analysis and ethnographic fieldwork, we aim to contribute to a more holistic understanding of segregation that can inform future policy and intervention strategies. Currently (Summer, 2025) the collection and structuring of national and local textual data (media, press and policy documents) is ongoing: with a focus on the analysis through a critical examination of how the concept of 'segregation' is addressed across different text types, genres and time. Comparing results from different types of texts will likely provide deeper insights into how the concept of 'segregation' is understood, framed, and communicated across various contexts.

5 Limitations and Ethical Considerations

One challenge we faced was the selection and representativeness of the data, which is crucial for drawing generalizable conclusions. The social media articles used in this study come from a small subset of national media sources. We recognize this limitation, but we are currently working to gain access to a much larger Swedish dataset from *Språkbanken Text*—a repository for Swedish textual documents and infrastructural tools (Borin, Forsberg & Roxendal, 2012)—with the aim of refining and strengthening our results. Further experimentation is necessary on larger, perhaps manually curated datasets to verify the efficacy of our approach and tools and even combine with other suitable tools. Apart from the text selection process, this paper didn't provide a comparison for sentiment analysis with other learning methods (Hägglöf, 2023), a task we left for future research.

Acknowledgments

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Designing a Repository for FAIR Learning Objects: H2IOSC Training Library

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Abstract

This contribution describes the design and implementation process of the H2IOSC Training Library, a repository to support managing and curating training materials in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) sector. Developed within the Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) project by the Istituto di Linguistica Computazionale “A. Zampolli” hosting the CLARIN-IT leading centre ILC4CLARIN, with the support of Centrica S.r.l., the repository was designed according to the FAIR-by-Design methodology promoted by the Skills for the European Open Science commons: creating a training ecosystem for Open and FAIR science (Skills4EOSC) project as a standard in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Allowing structured deposit, discovery and reuse of modular learning resources by using persistent identifiers (PIDs), multilingual metadata and open formats, H2IOSC Training Library contributes to creating a scalable, open and sustainable training infrastructure integrated with other digital environments such as SSHOC¹ and H2IOSC Marketplace.

1 Introduction

The H2IOSC project is part of Italy’s National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRPP). It aims to create a federated cluster of the National nodes of four Research Infrastructures (RIs) in the SSH disciplinary sector: CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS and OPERAS (Degl’Innocenti et al., 2023). Aligning with other national and European initiatives promoting training resources to enhance the acquisition of new competencies by the end users, such as DARIAH-Campus and CLARIN Training Hub, H2IOSC dedicates a whole work package to training: WP8 – Training, Capacity Building and Engagement, where several CNR institutes participate in the creation of a training infrastructure. The output of WP8 includes the application of a methodology shared by the four federated national nodes and the implementation of two different platforms: H2IOSC Training Environment, allowing students to enrol in courses and actively learn digitally and collaboratively, and H2IOSC Training Library, the first repository entirely dedicated to training materials as reusable digital objects complying to the FAIR principles for data management and stewardship.

¹ <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/>

The methodology applied to reuse existing training materials and design new ones was adapted from the FAIR-by-Design Methodology (Filiposka et al., 2023) developed by the Skills4EOSC project and follows a six-step process (preparation, discovery, design, development, publication and quality control) to ensure a structured and scalable approach. Apart from building modular and reusable training materials on topics relevant to the four RIs (such as, for example, tutorials on language resources and specific digital heritage diagnostic tools), this methodology was used in H2IOSC as a base to build the two platforms mentioned above, considering the two different types of end users for which training materials are accessible to: students and teachers. While the H2IOSC Training Environment focuses on making courses and modules findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable to end users who want to learn actively, the H2IOSC Training Library fills a gap in the infrastructural landscape by creating a repository where teachers can both publish their training materials and access an open catalogue for finding and reusing existing resources to enrich their teaching experience. As there is no other repository for training materials as FAIR digital objects in the EOSC, the H2IOSC Training Library is a novelty.

2 Reusable training Materials on H2IOSC Training Library

The H2IOSC Training Library (from here on “the Library”) was designed to host and display FAIR training materials structured according to Skills4EOSC methodology, as adapted in H2IOSC. This platform allows authenticated users to access a back-office interface for uploading training materials, which will be licensed and published after a two-step revision process. The validation process was modelled on the best practices of data repositories, such as CLARIN DSpace. It involves a workflow and notifications whereby the author submits their proposal. The first-level supervisor accesses the dashboard, where they find a list of courses awaiting approval, along with a notification of the new submission. They can review the course content and then approve the material for second-level verification or reject it by sending the author feedback for modification, allowing for a second submission. In the event of a second submission by the author, who must incorporate the recommended changes, the workflow will start again from the beginning. If approved at the first level, the resource will be sent to the second-level editor, who will check that the material complies with publication regulations in accordance with FAIR principles. If rejected, the material will be sent back to the author with a request for changes; otherwise, it will be published. If changes are necessary for second-level validation, the author will make a new submission, which will be re-evaluated only by the second-level editor.

Published training materials will be displayed on an open interface, allowing for faceted search and bookmarking. After a single sign-on authentication, users can download the selected training materials from this same public interface. While the authentication process is still being developed along with the functionalities of H2IOSC Marketplace, which is the single access point to all H2IOSC data, tools and services, including the training infrastructure (Section 3), the Library has reached a mature point of implementation on both interfaces (the back-office and the catalogue), which will be described in the following sub-sections. Due to the page limit, this paper details only the main features and includes only one picture of each interface. Still, the authors will be happy to further detail the user experience in an extended version of this proposal.

2.1 Publishing your Training Materials

The Library design was tested on an example teaching material, namely the course *Introduction to Language Data: Standards and Repositories* (van der Lek, 2023), originally developed by CLARIN for the UPSKILLS project and later translated and readapted for the Italian community within the H2IOSC framework (van der Lek, 2024). Following the FAIR-by-Design methodology, the contents of the course translated into Italian were converted into .md files (Markdown) and structured in a hierarchy that allows users to locate and download individual parts of the course according to their needs.

The content hierarchy follows the definition of “Learning Object” proposed by Skills4EOSC, considering it as a modular lesson characterised by one specific learning objective that includes activities and tools for evaluating acquired competencies. The Learning Object is the building block of the modular structure, considering that groups of learning objects with logically connected learning objectives make a Module, connected Modules make a Unit, aggregates of Units make Sections, and all the learning content is considered a Course.

According to this, the back-office interface of the Library allows the selection of various containers organised from the most general to the most specific: the Learning Path, i.e. the root that connects to the

catalogue of the research infrastructures participating in H2IOSC; the Course, which is the largest container, and its intermediate containers: Section, Unit and Module, which will allow the selection of specific portions of material to be downloaded, up to the smallest container that represents the most basic teaching portion, the Learning Object. The only compulsory elements to be created to upload files in the repository are: 1) the Learning Path, which acts as the root and includes essential documents to facilitate the reuse of the learning material according to the guidelines of Skills4EOSC methodology (such as the README file, the citation in .cff format, the code of conduct, the facilitation guide and the license applied to the material, together with the syllabus and any release notes accompanying the management of subsequent versions); and 2) the Learning Object, i.e. the leaf node whose function is to contain the actual learning materials in an open, reproducible format (text, images, audio-video, etc.). The user can upload the required documents by selecting the tab “Media” in the selected container (either Learning Object or Learning Path).

In addition, all H2IOSC training materials at all content levels must be described with the Minimal Metadata Set for Learning Resources proposed by the Research Data Alliance (Hoebelheinrich, 2022) as enriched by the CLARIN model (van der Lek, 2025), which adds fields such as contributors, workload in ECTS and PID to improve the usability and documentation of the resources. Each content level can inherit and modify the metadata fields already compiled in the superordinate sections. An example of the uploading interface with structure and metadata selection is provided in Figure 1. This picture also shows the possibility of inserting an existing PID if the material was already published elsewhere by selecting “yes” in the dedicated field of the interface. Should the PID be attributed for the first time when deposited in the Library, the system will automatically generate it, but this process is still under development.

Figure 1 - Selecting the file structure and inserting the metadata

After creating the file structure, uploading all the required documents, generating a PID and choosing a license, the user can submit their request for review. Once the two-step reviewing process is approved, the training materials will be published in the Library’s catalogue with an automatically generated citation format and the link to the author’s personal page with the information provided via single sign-on authentication.

2.2 Discovering Modular and Reusable Training Materials

H2IOSC Training Library also supports search and discovery functionalities of training materials by users interested in reuse: all resources are open for consultation and are available for download after user authentication through a federated login system. A demo version of the search interface² demonstrates the discovery experience of a trainer browsing the catalogue for reusable training materials. The catalogue and search interface allows a simple natural language search to sort the results based on keywords entered in the “keyword” section of the RDA metadata schema (Section 2.1). A faceted system allows the search to be further narrowed down based on a broader metadata selection, such as “publication date”, “language”, “author”, “format” and “topic”. Clicking on the title of the selected resource redirects the user to a landing page with details of the contents and the download button. Figure 2 presents a preview of the search interface and the possible results of a simple search, with the faceted filters in the top right-

² <https://h2iosc-training-library.ilc4clarin.ilc.cnr.it/>

hand corner allowing refinement.

Figure 2 - Faceted search and results

More functionalities are available after authentication via the CLARIN SSO, such as the possibility of clipping the standard citation form of a selected result and exploring different collections. The last section of this abstract is dedicated to the interaction of the Library's contents with H2IOSC Marketplace, especially using standard multilingual metadata.

3 Harvesting Training Materials in the H2IOSC Marketplace and Beyond

The H2IOSC Marketplace is a platform designed to offer a centralised access point to data, tools, and services related to the humanities, social, and cultural sciences. It enables the integration and aggregation of internal and external resources through standard protocols and dedicated APIs that allow users to share training materials, among other resources. Its structure is inspired by the Social Sciences and Humanities Marketplace, which shares a similar typology of objects (Barbot, 2024). In such a context, the H2IOSC Marketplace will accommodate, along with other types of data, the shared metadata set describing the training resources on the two training platforms, respectively, the H2IOSC Training Environment for courses directed at students and the Library for teaching materials reusable by teachers and trainers. A set of controlled vocabulary taken from the SSHOC Marketplace will be linked to specific metadata, and an open vocabulary is also planned for keywords related to the services and resources in the H2IOSC Marketplace catalogue, including training materials. To ensure greater interoperability and accessibility, we are currently working on the selective harvesting of metadata in other platforms, such as the CLARIN Learning Hub, which is being upgraded to an interactive catalogue with faceted search.

To conclude, this contribution aims to open the design process of a repository specifically created for FAIR training materials. Many details can be highlighted in the future, such as the versioning system implemented to ensure the findability and long-term accessibility of highly flexible training materials and the discovery interface with its virtual collection tool. The Library's features will benefit training communities in the SSH, such as the CLARIN Trainers' Network, by providing a single access point to publish, access, and share learning resources.

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The ParlaSpeech v3 Collection of Spoken Parliamentary Corpora from the Croatian, Czech, Polish and Serbian Parliament Enriched with Linguistic and Paralinguistic Annotation Layers

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Abstract

ParlaSpeech is a collection of spoken parliamentary corpora, currently spanning the Croatian, Czech, Polish, and Serbian parliaments, built by automatically aligning speech recordings to the corresponding ParlaMint transcripts, ensuring also the availability of the rich ParlaMint metadata. In this abstract, we present work on automatically annotating these corpora on multiple levels, thereby constructing the ParlaSpeech v3 corpus collection. The first enrichment level, ParlaSpeech-Ling, is performed on the textual modality in the form of linguistic annotation that follows the Universal Dependencies format. The second level, ParlaSpeech-Senti is performed on the textual level as well, adding sentiment information on the level of each sentence with a multilingual transformer model. The third level of enrichment, ParlaSpeech-Pause, is performed on the spoken modality by identifying filled pauses with a fine-tuned multilingual speech transformer model. The following two layers are applied at this point only to the Croatian and the Serbian corpora. The fourth layer, ParlaSpeech-Align, additionally aligns the spoken and textual modality with highly accurate grapheme-level and word-level alignments based on an acoustic-model-based forced aligner. The final layer, ParlaSpeech-Stress, adds the primary stress information to each multi-syllabic word via predicting primary stress on the spoken modality with a fine-tuned speech transformer model. The spoken modality prediction is post-processed to be aligned to a syllable nucleus on the textual modality for simpler downstream use of primary stress information. All corpora are available through the CLARIN.SI repository as JSONL files with all available information encoded for computational use, and as TextGrid files to facilitate use by phoneticians and other speech specialists. The corpora are also available for search via the CLARIN.SI concordancer.

1 Introduction

There is a lack of speech corpora for too many European languages. The CLARIN Resource Family (Fišer et al., 2018) for spoken corpora¹ shows a rather skewed language distribution. The best covered languages in this resource family are Finnish (7 corpora: 12,705 hrs), German (61 corpora: 2,640 hrs), Czech (6 corpora: 1,678 hrs), and Estonian (7 corpora: 371 hrs). In contrast, many languages – such as Serbian (1 corpus: 50 hrs), Hungarian (1 corpus: 38 hrs), Polish (1 corpus: 38 hrs), Croatian (1 corpus: 35 hrs), and Arabic (1 corpus: 3.7 hrs) – are represented by only a single small corpus, with most languages not having a single speech corpus available. In addition, most of the reviewed spoken corpora have only transcripts available as their enrichment. Sometimes, transcripts are linguistically processed, but most

¹<https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/spoken-corpora>

Language	Croatian	Czech	Polish	Serbian
Hours	3 110	1 218	1 010	896
Words	24 755 742	9 114 266	7 515 333	7 024 294
Sentences	922 679	717 682	535 465	290 778
Filled pauses	323 514	205 528	196 671	73 861
Grapheme-level aligned words	17 765 585	-	-	3 138 747
Stress labels	11 341 813	-	-	1 998 020

Table 1: The general statistics of the ParlaSpeech v3 corpora.

corpora lack any further annotations that are necessary to unlock the richness of the speech signal for downstream research. In this paper, we present an approach to rectify both identified shortcomings in the current landscape of speech corpora. We present a collection of spoken parliamentary corpora for languages that are, in this regard, largely under-resourced. We enrich these corpora both on the linguistic and paralinguistic levels via automatic methods, empowering downstream linguistic and phonetic research.

Our primary source of spoken data is ParlaSpeech, a follow-up initiative to the ParlaMint CLARIN ERIC flagship project². ParlaSpeech was led mainly by the CLARIN.SI national consortium and the CLASSLA Knowledge Centre for South Slavic Languages³. The initiative originated from a task within the second iteration of the ParlaMint project (Erjavec et al., 2024), which committed to providing 50 hours of text and speech material aligned on the sentence and word level at least for three languages, with the aim of laying the groundwork for future large-scale efforts.

The first approach to the rather hard problem of aligning the spoken and the textual modality, with content being in different order and partly missing in both modalities, has been piloted on Croatian (Ljubešić et al., 2022). Quite many lessons learnt on this pilot have been smartly integrated into the second version of the pipeline, which was applied to Croatian, Polish, and Serbian (Ljubešić, Rupnik, & Koržinek, 2024). Czech was added by exploiting the alignments already performed in a separate project (Kopp et al., 2021), while ensuring consistent encoding in all four languages for simple usage. The final ParlaSpeech corpora are a collaboration between the CLASSLA Knowledge Centre and the Slovenian national CLARIN consortium with the Czech and the Polish national CLARIN consortia.

The final statistics of the four corpora can be found in Table 1. Important to note is that the enrichments with annotation layers we still see as pilots, meant to showcase to the interested communities how spoken data can be annotated in an automated fashion. We will continue to collaborate with various SSH communities to better understand their needs and requirements. This will guide further development of the ParlaSpeech corpora and their derivatives.

In the remainder of this paper, we present the four annotation layers that we added to the ParlaSpeech corpora to empower downstream research on the data.

2 The ParlaSpeech-Ling Layer

The first layer added is the one of linguistic annotation of transcripts following the Universal Dependencies formalism (De Marneffe et al., 2021). Although the original transcripts in the ParlaMint corpora (Erjavec et al., 2024) have already been linguistically annotated, the annotations in the ParlaSpeech corpora were made anew to follow the word tokenization rules used during the production of the corpora. These rules aim to simplify the alignment of the manual transcripts with the automatic speech recognition (ASR) output, hence giving preference to shorter words. For Croatian and Serbian, the CLASSLA-Stanza (Ljubešić, Terčon, & Dobrovoljc, 2024) tool was used, while for Czech and Polish, the Stanza (Qi et al., 2020) tool was applied. Both tools report very high annotation quality for standard text.

²<https://www.clarin.eu/parlamint>

³<https://www.clarin.si/info/k-centre/>

3 The ParlaSpeech-Senti Layer

For sentiment annotation, we use the domain-specific ParlaSent model⁴ (Mochtak et al., 2024) that is based on the XLM-R-Parla parliamentary pre-trained model⁵. The XLM-R-Parla model is based on the large-size XLM-RoBERTa model (Conneau et al., 2020) and was further pre-trained on 1.7B words of parliamentary proceedings and fine-tuned on 13k manually annotated sentences in seven languages (EN, BS, HR, CS, SL, SR, SK) (Mochtak et al., 2023).

Ablation experiments showed that the sentiment annotation quality is robust across languages, even for languages not seen during fine-tuning (Mochtak et al., 2024). Compared with a state-of-the-art proprietary LLM, performance is comparable, with Spearman correlation coefficients twice as high as on a dictionary approach, namely the ParlaSent model achieved an average correlation of 0.786, the GPT-4o model (OpenAI, 2024) of 0.807, while the Lexicoder dictionary approach (Duval & Pétry, 2016) achieved an average correlation of 0.408 (Mochtak et al., 2025).

4 The ParlaSpeech-Pause Layer

Recently, the first technologies for detecting filled pauses, one of the most frequent disfluencies in speech (Romana et al., 2024), have been developed for the Slovenian language. This task was part of the MEZZANINE project, a Slovenian national project focused on speech research and technologies⁶. Based on a manually-annotated dataset – the ROG dataset for training speech processing technologies (Verdonik et al., 2024) – a speech transformer model was developed which has shown great performance on the task of filled pause identification. Namely, the identification is based on the wav2vec2-bert model, with a 20 ms audio frame classification head that predicts whether there is a filled pause in a specific audio frame.

Evaluating the task on Slovenian on event level (abstracting from 20 ms frames to true and predicted events, intersection between the two being considered a true positive) showed very strong F1 results of 0.943. The model is available on the HuggingFace repository⁷.

Given our interest in expanding speech processing from Slovenian to other languages, we constructed test datasets for all four ParlaSpeech languages. The test datasets amounted to 400 sentences in every language with gender balance. The evaluation showed very good results, with F1 for Croatian of 0.913, Czech of 0.874, Polish of 0.924, and Serbian of 0.940 (Ljubešić, Porupski, & Rupnik, 2025b). Motivated by these strong results, we applied the model on all ParlaSpeech datasets, resulting in the ParlaSpeech-Pause layer of around 800 thousand filled pauses.

5 The ParlaSpeech-Align Layer

The third annotation layer adds detailed time alignment information to every character in the transcript, which enables phoneme-level processing and analysis. For now, this layer has been applied to the Croatian and Serbian corpora only, given that we follow the iterative development approach again, where we do not enrich all languages with specific annotation layers before obtaining experience on pilot languages first.

Alignment is based on the grapheme level, as both Croatian and Serbian are phonemic languages with minor deviations between grapheme and phoneme correspondence. For grapheme-level alignment, the forced alignment model from the Kaldi toolkit (Povey et al., 2011) has been applied. This model has previously been released as part of the pilot Croatian ParlaSpeech dataset construction efforts (Ljubešić et al., 2022).

Important to note is that around 80% of all Croatian and Serbian data have been aligned on the grapheme level. The remaining 20% could not be aligned due to two main reasons: (1) numbers and acronyms would need to be expanded to their pronounced form to be successfully aligned, which is a highly complex task that we prefer not to undertake hastily, and (2) in some infrequent cases, there is

⁴<https://huggingface.co/classla/xlm-r-parlasent>

⁵<https://huggingface.co/classla/xlm-r-parla>

⁶<https://mezzanine.um.si>

⁷<https://huggingface.co/classla/wav2vecbert2-filledPause>

significant deviation between what has been pronounced and the transcript, due to which the grapheme-level alignment fails. We are rather positive that with this removal of parts of the original corpora, no significant bias has been introduced in the final grapheme-aligned corpora.

6 The ParlaSpeech-Stress Layer

The final annotation layer is applied over the previous grapheme-alignment layer. It involves automatic annotation of each multi-syllabic word with the location of the primary stress. In Croatian, primary stress greatly varies between speakers, and remains a largely understudied area, particularly in analyses involving large amounts of spontaneously spoken speech. To give an example, the word *predstavljanje* (which means *(re)presentation*) has the primary accent by both Croatian and Serbian standard on the first syllable. However, once an inspection is performed through the ParlaSpeech corpus, we can observe that the Serbian part is very consistent in using the standard stress position (17 out of 17 occurrences), while the Croatian part shows such a level of variation that more instances have the primary stress on the second syllable than on the first (40 vs. 26)⁸.

The model⁹ used to annotate each multi-syllabic word of the grapheme-aligned subset is very similar to the model used for filled pause identification. It is a wav2vec2-bert speech transformer model, fine-tuned on a manually annotated dataset from Croatian ParlaSpeech (Ljubešić, Rupnik, Porupski, Robida, & Potočnjak, 2025), with a 20 ms audio frame classification head. It yields highly accurate results, with the word-level accuracy of the stressed syllable for both Croatian and Serbian above 99% (Ljubešić, Porupski, & Rupnik, 2025a).

To make these results simple to use in the downstream, we released both the raw predictions of the model (the timestamps of the primary stress span), and the position of the grapheme that represents the nucleus of the stressed syllable.

7 The Final Encoding of ParlaSpeech v3

We encode the final ParlaSpeech v3 corpora in two formats: the JSONL format, and TextGrid, a format of the widely adopted Praat tool (Boersma & Weenink, 2001) for speech analysis. JSONL files allow simple line-by-line processing, and encode for each sentence in the corpus all the available annotation layers and speaker metadata in the JSON format¹⁰. Secondly, we also provide the files in the TextGrid format, which allows speech professionals to analyse and potentially further enrich the available data inside the Praat tool. The dataset is available through the CLARIN.SI repository (Ljubešić, Rupnik, Porupski, Kuzman Pungertšek, et al., 2025).

This possibility for other users to enrich our data is particularly appealing, as any additional manual annotation on the data, given the open licence of the corpora, could contribute to the development of additional tools for automatic spoken data annotation.

Finally, we made all four corpora available for search through the CLARIN.SI concordancer¹¹. It was very straightforward to encode the transcripts and connect them to the recordings via sentence-level recordings, but also shorter spans of length of up to 6 seconds, as well as the two text-based layers, with word-level linguistic information and sentence-level sentiment predictions. The speech-based layers required more consideration. Our current approach to encoding filled pauses is to encode on the word level whether it is preceded or followed by a filled pause, but also encoding the filled pause as a positional element. Primary stress is encoded on the level of each word, by simply encoding the position of the stressed syllable. We will reconsider these encodings in the future through close collaboration with our downstream users.

A user guide for searching through the concordancer is available at <https://clarinsi.github.io/parlaspeech/concordancer/concordancer-guide.html>.

⁸These and similar inspections can be easily performed through the CLARIN.SI concordancer at <https://www.clarin.si/ske/>.

⁹<https://huggingface.co/classla/Wav2Vec2BertPrimaryStressAudioFrameClassifier>

¹⁰Details on the JSONL format can be found at <https://clarinsi.github.io/parlaspeech/>.

¹¹<https://www.clarin.si/ske/>

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Human Evaluation of Automated Text Simplification through Crowdsourcing

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Abstract

This paper describes the creation of a set of crowd-sourced human evaluations of automated simplifications. We created a synthetic simplification dataset which was assessed by the crowd on dimensions of *fluency*, *clarity*, *accuracy* and *complexity*. We briefly describe the crowdsourcing environment and some techniques to keep the crowd engaged. This resulted in a dataset of nearly 25,000 responses from 384 respondents on synthetically simplified Dutch data. In order to mitigate the low inter-annotator agreement we investigate the effect of outlier removal techniques on Krippendorff α .

Both the synthetic parallel data as well as the crowd assessments are made available to the CLARIN infrastructure.

1 Introduction

Automatic text simplification (ATS) enhances accessibility across various domains. In government communication, there is particular emphasis on *plain language*, as evidenced by national campaigns in Belgium (Vandeghinste et al., 2021) and the Netherlands. Clear and comprehensible communication is essential to ensure that all citizens, including those with limited literacy, can access and understand government information.

Recent advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) have enabled machine-based text simplification methods. However, a major challenge remains: the lack of reliable evaluation metrics, which depend on high-quality reference data. For most languages, including Dutch, such data is scarce and the development of robust training and evaluation datasets is still a key hurdle.

This pilot project investigates the feasibility of AI-driven text simplification and assesses its effectiveness. While AI can assist in simplifying text, human validation remains essential to ensure linguistic accuracy and contextual appropriateness.

We developed a crowdsourcing approach to manually assess and validate AI-generated simplifications. The evaluation focused on four dimensions: *fluency*, which measures grammatical correctness; *complexity*, which assesses ease (or difficulty) of understanding; *clarity*, which evaluates comparative clarity in text pairs; and *accuracy*, which determines how well the meaning is preserved.

To enhance engagement of the crowd, gamification elements such as scoring, leaderboards, and streaks were incorporated in the crowdsourcing environment, encouraging participants to contribute consistently.

2 Related Work

Earlier data-driven simplification models treated ATS as a machine translation problem (Xu et al., 2016). These approaches translated complex texts into simpler versions by treating the original and simplified versions as different languages. More recent advancements fine-tune large language models, such as Dutch T5 (Raffel et al., 2020), using parallel datasets (Seidl & Vandeghinste, 2024), allowing for more context-aware simplifications.

Existing datasets for Dutch simplification remain scarce. A manually created dataset compiled by Vlantis et al. (2024) focuses on municipal texts, offering one of the few resources in the field. Other datasets rely on automated translations (Seidl & Vandeghinste, 2024) or synthetic sources like GPT-4, raising concerns about reliability and consistency. A detailed list of available datasets for Dutch text simplification can be found at K-Dutch, the CLARIN Knowledge Centre for Dutch.¹

In their review of the ATS field, Alva-Manchego, Scarton, and Specia (2020) describe how 3-point or 5-point Likert scales are often used to assess grammatical correctness (also referred to as fluency), meaning preservation (adequacy), and complexity (simplicity). Fluency is evaluated solely on the output, while adequacy and complexity are assessed based on the text pair. This approach is refined in Alva-Manchego, Martin, et al. (2020), where evaluation is conducted on a continuous scale (0-100) for adequacy, fluency, and complexity. The use of continuous interval scales in crowdsourcing human evaluations is common practice in machine translation (Bojar et al., 2018), as it results in higher levels of inter-annotator consistency compared to ordinal Likert scales. In our approach, we also use continuous interval scales (without numerical indicators).

3 Methodology

Dataset The dataset consists of 6,986 sentence pairs extracted from the WRPEI component of the SONAR corpus (Oostdijk et al., 2013),² which is relevant for public communication. Source sentences were selected based on specific criteria: containing between 10 and 50 words, featuring at least one verb, having a readability index (Brouwer, 1963) above 60, and including at least one subordinate clause. The readability index is based on sentence length and syllables per word. Normal texts have a readability level between 50 and 75, with easier texts scoring higher. These criteria ensure that the source sentences exhibit a moderate level of complexity, making them suitable candidates for simplification.

The synthetic "*simplifications*" were generated using GPT-4 with structured prompts designed to produce *clear and accessible* Dutch text. The output revealed that these synthetic texts were often longer due to explanatory expansions. Additionally, the use of prepositions decreased, while noun and pronoun ratios increased. Readability scores (Vandeghinste & Bulté, 2019) paradoxically rated these texts as more complex, highlighting the difference between *complexity* and *clarity*. The statistical complexity might increase (lower readability) while still improving the clarity of the content compared to the source text, for instance by using longer sentences. This is most probably the result of not prompting explicitly for *simple* versions, but for *clear* versions. The question remains whether in general the goal of simplification is actually clarification. The created dataset is available in the CLARIN infrastructure at <http://hdl.handle.net/10032/tm-a2-y7>.

Crowdsourcing Application The crowdsourcing platform allowed users to assess simplifications by rating fluency and complexity at the sentence level and comparing pairs of texts for clarity and accuracy. Users provided feedback through a carefully designed interface that ensured efficient annotation while minimizing bias. The design emphasized ease of use, ensuring that contributors of varying linguistic expertise could participate effectively. To encourage user participation, a scoring system was implemented, along with a leaderboard and a streak-based incentive mechanism. These elements increased engagement and data collection rates while maintaining annotation quality.

¹https://kdutch.ivdnt.org/wiki/Simplification_Data

²Available in the CLARIN infrastructure at <http://hdl.handle.net/10032/tm-a2-h5>

Figure 1: Example of a complexity evaluation

Figure 2: Example of a pairwise clarity evaluation

Figure 1 shows a screenshot for a user judgement on the continuous scale *simple - neutral - complex* for a synthetically simplified fragment that translates as *This is the phone number of the customs officer on duty. You can call this number day and night.* Figure 2 shows a screenshot for a fragment pair, asking for a judgement which fragment is the *clearest*. Text A (Tekst A) translates as *This is the number of the customs officer on duty and is available 24 hours a day.*

The assessors The crowd was recruited through social media posting. Apart from an email address for the participants in the competition, no information was collected about the assessors. 384 people have assessed questions, with a maximum of 3756 questions answered by a single user, with an average of 64 and a median of 19, indicating that more than half of the users only answered a single questionnaire of 19 cases. The responses were stored in a database and are made available through the CLARIN infrastructure for further research.³

4 Evaluation Results

A total of 24,745 responses were collected. The results indicated that 83% of simplifications preserved meaning when evaluated at a 50% threshold, while only 49% were deemed accurate at a stricter 70% threshold, as shown in Table 1. These findings highlight the variability in AI-generated simplifications and the importance of human validation.

Condition	% of Texts
Accuracy 50%	83.00
Accuracy 70%	48.60
Complexity A > B	69.44
Fluency B > A	50.54
Clarity B > A	79.57

Table 1: Pairwise comparisons. Text A is the original text. Text B is the synthetic text.

Condition	Mean	Stdev
Accuracy	67.08	19.59
Complexity A	50.18	14.12
Complexity B	40.95	15.87
Fluency A	62.73	19.50
Fluency B	63.65	18.56
Clarity	64.19	19.47

Table 2: Raw averages of the evaluations

Simplified versions were rated as clearer in 80% of cases, though they were not necessarily rated as simpler, as in 31% of the cases the synthetic, so-called “simplified” version was rated as more complex. This suggests that clarity and complexity (or simplicity) are related but distinct aspects of text modification. Fluency ratings for the original and simplified texts were nearly identical, indicating that the synthetic data maintained grammatical correctness. The simplifications were perceived as less complex in 69% of comparisons, reinforcing the effectiveness of ATS in making texts more accessible.

Further analysis of the responses revealed patterns in user judgments, with certain linguistic structures consistently rated as clear or complex. This information can be leveraged to improve future ATS systems by focusing on aspects that most impact readability. Additionally, discrepancies between automatic readability scores and human judgments underscore the need for refined evaluation metrics that align more closely with human perception.

³<http://hdl.handle.net/10032/tm-a2-y8>

4.1 Inter-rater agreement

Table 3 presents baseline inter-annotator agreement (IAA) scores, measured by Krippendorff’s alpha, (Krippendorff, 2019) for the six evaluation scores. Overall, agreement levels are low across all conditions, with alpha values ranging from 0.10 (Clarity) to 0.17 (Complexity B), indicating substantial inconsistency among annotators. Accuracy and Clarity, despite having the highest number of ratings and items (around 1000), show particularly low agreement ($\alpha = 0.12$ and $\alpha = 0.10$ respectively), suggesting that raters may have interpreted these criteria in varied ways or applied them inconsistently. The other four scales (Complexity A and B, and Fluency A and B) exhibit slightly higher alphas (between 0.13 and 0.17) but are based on fewer ratings and items, around 3200–3300 ratings across approximately 740–750 items. These results collectively highlight the subjectivity of judgements on these criteria.

Condition	α	Ratings	Items	θ	α	Rat.	%Rat.	Items	%Items
Accuracy	0.12	5880	1000	0.80	0.70	3230	55	890	89
Clarity	0.10	5848	1013	0.70	0.72	2486	43	796	79
Complexity A	0.15	3263	746	0.70	0.76	1414	43	583	78
Complexity B	0.17	3276	749	0.70	0.79	1356	41	599	80
Fluency A	0.13	3222	744	0.70	0.78	1295	40	558	75
Fluency B	0.13	3256	750	0.70	0.76	1349	41	598	80

Table 3: Inter-annotator agreement measured in Krippendorff’s alpha. Behind the vertical line, you see the threshold (θ) for the Z-score, which was the best outlier removal method.

To improve the reliability of the human ratings by filtering out inconsistent judgments, we have tested three outlier removal methods: Z-score, Modified Z-score (Z-mod), and Interquartile Range (IQR). *Z-score* (Montgomery & Runger, 2010) identifies outliers by measuring how many standard deviations a value lies from the mean; values beyond a threshold θ are flagged as outliers. *Z-mod* (Iglewicz & Hoaglin, 1993) uses median and median absolute deviation, making it more robust to skewed or non-normal distributions. *IQR* (Tukey, 1977) classifies outliers as values that fall below the first quartile (Q1) minus θ times the IQR, or above the third quartile (Q3) plus θ times the IQR. While each technique balances sensitivity to outliers and robustness differently, results show that Z-score provided the best outlier filtering method, allowing us to keep the largest number of ratings while achieving an acceptable agreement ($\alpha > 0.667$).

5 Conclusion

This study underscores the importance of human-evaluated simplification datasets in Dutch. The findings confirm that clarity and simplicity are distinct concepts, as explaining difficult terms can enhance clarity without necessarily reducing syntactic complexity. These insights suggest that ATS should be designed with a nuanced approach, balancing explanation with conciseness.

Future research should refine AI prompts to ensure more concise simplifications, develop automatic evaluation metrics tailored for Dutch ATS, similar to the popular COMET metric for machine translation evaluation (Rei et al., 2020), and use the dataset to fine-tune ATS models (Seidl & Vandeghinste, 2024). Additionally, the insights from this study can be integrated into writing assistance tools such as Schrijfassistent⁴. The dataset and crowdsourcing infrastructure established in this project provide a solid foundation for future work in text simplification, usability testing, and automated assessment models.

In a broader context, these findings contribute to research on linguistic accessibility, particularly in government communication. Ensuring that official texts are understandable to diverse audiences can improve citizen engagement and public trust. The integration of ATS into communication workflows could streamline content adaptation while maintaining clarity and inclusivity. Ongoing research should explore the interplay between linguistic features and user comprehension, ultimately shaping the development of more effective text simplification technologies.

⁴<https://schrijfassistent.be/index.php>

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Challenges of Analysing Speech Acts in Organisational Communication

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Abstract

The research presented in this paper addresses the challenges of analysing organisational stakeholder communication using speech act theory, supported by a novel analytical model. We present a large, automatically annotated dataset focused on present- and future-oriented speech acts in Swedish organisational discourse, specifically within the context of the ISO/IEC 27001 standard. To evaluate the dataset, we fine-tuned a multilingual XLM-Roberta model on the annotated data and tested it against a manually annotated gold standard. Although the results were inconclusive, the study contributes valuable information to the CLARIN infrastructure and advances research in organisational communication and information security.

1 Introduction

In a joint project between the Swedish SMS CLARIN K-centre¹ and management researchers, we investigate stakeholder communication on Swedish corporate websites related to preventive cyber innovation. A specialised corpus of corporate texts from Swedish company websites was created to analyse discourse surrounding information security with a focus on the ISO/IEC 27001 standards (Jönsson et al., 2024). This corpus contains data from 291 companies, a total of 5,960,328 tokens, with a vocabulary size of 204,312 and an average entry length of 24.3 tokens. The ISO/IEC 27001 standard requires organisations to establish, implement and audit the rules and authorities relating to the legal and ethical aspects necessary for the proper functioning and accountability of the entire data and algorithm lifecycle (Janssen et al., 2020, p.3), see also (Culot et al., 2021; Disterer, 2013; Mirtsch et al., 2021). ISO/IEC 27001 certification ensures information security and encourages good corporate behaviour by requiring compliance to be audited by external groups.

For analysis, we applied content analysis along with novel computational sentiment analysis to uncover differences in communication about preventive cyber innovations (Jönsson et al., 2024). Our findings revealed three distinct organisational perspectives on preventive cyber innovation:

- Adopters emphasise the relative advantage and complexity of ISO/IEC 27001 and actively communicate about their information security efforts, often through company websites.
- Stewards, in contrast, highlight trialability and, to a lesser extent, the relative advantage of preventive innovation. Their communication includes commissives and other future-oriented statements about their organisation's information security efforts.
- Advocates communicate less frequently about the efforts, achievements, and challenges related to the adoption of preventive innovations, adopting a more indirect approach similar to companies that directly influence their organisational reality of information management.

These categories help to understand the varying approaches of companies to information security communication and are added manually to the dataset.

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¹https://sprakbanken-clarin.lingfil.uu.se/centra/sms_en.html

To capture future-versus-present-oriented communication in relation to InfoSec standards, we conducted a speech acts analysis, which is presented in this paper.

2 Model building

Our working assumption was that organisations express their adherence to standards through intentional statements (Commissives) or descriptive statements (Assertives). This approach aligns with the concept of direction of fit (Searle, 1985), where Commissives represent a world-to-word fit, expressing future intentions and commitments that an organisation plans to fulfil. Conversely, Assertives represent a word-to-world fit, stating current or past conditions within the organisation. For the purposes of streamlined analysis and because of their overlap with Assertives in expressing current realities, Declaratives were grouped under the Assertive class. As a result, the defined speech act categories were Assertives and Commissives, with all other speech acts categorised as Other.

The construction of the Speech Act classification model began with selecting a large language model (LLM) for an initial round of annotation. Specifically, only quantised models were considered due to computing restraints. The selection was based on performance on a small, manually curated dataset, sampled from the ISO/IES 27001 corpus (Jönsson et al., 2024), containing approximately 100 instances per class. Model hyperparameters were then optimised using this same dataset.

The selected model, Llama3-70B-2.4BPW (quantised to an average of 2.4 bits per weight), was deployed to annotate a larger corpus. Annotations from this first round were manually validated, and correctly labelled instances were organised into class-specific datasets, each containing the original text and its corresponding Speech Act label. Ultimately, each class contained 550 validated entries. To ensure diversity and mitigate model bias, 50 instances per class were manually curated by reviewing and correcting the model’s misclassifications. Due to data sparsity in the minority class, Commissive, ChatGPT-4 was employed for data augmentation. Forty carefully selected examples were expanded to better capture under-represented syntactic and semantic structures.

Next, a demonstration dataset was constructed for Clue and Reasoning Prompting (CARP) using the same LLM. Entries from the validated class collections were combined, and the LLM was prompted, following the procedure outlined in Sun et al. (2023), to generate supporting clues (e.g. keywords, phrases, syntactic features) for each entry. The model was then prompted to produce diagnostic reasoning based on the text, label, and generated clues. This process yielded a 1,650-entry demonstration dataset, evenly distributed across classes.

To support classification-sensitive demonstration retrieval in the second annotation round, an XLM-RoBERTa model (Conneau et al., 2020) was fine-tuned on the CARP demonstration dataset. Fine-tuning was essential for aligning the model not only with sentence embeddings but also with class annotations, enabling accurate retrieval of semantically and label-relevant examples for unseen sentences. The model was used to compute text embeddings, which were appended to each dataset entry.

A second round of annotation followed, using CARP. The Llama3 model was provided with task instructions, class definitions, and retrieved demonstrations via the fine-tuned retrieval model. Demonstrations were added up to the model’s token limit, sorted in ascending order of cosine distance to the input sentence, as described by Sun et al. (2023).

This resulted in an automatically annotated dataset, comprising a random 56% subset of the full corpus. A final XLM-RoBERTa classifier was fine-tuned on this dataset. The model and dataset are available to the CLARIN community². Training employed a linear learning rate scheduler with warm-up steps corresponding to 10% of batches per epoch and used the AdamW optimiser. To address class imbalance, the loss function incorporated class weights. Early stopping was triggered if validation loss increased for three consecutive evaluations. Weight decay was set to 0.01, and the learning rate was set to a conservative value of 4×10^{-5} to prevent premature convergence. A batch size of 16 was chosen to encourage generalisation. An 80/20 train/validation split was used, with evaluation occurring three times per epoch. Model selection was based on the weighted F1 score. The final model was trained for 2.33 epochs. Entries labelled as “No match found” were excluded from the training data.

²<https://huggingface.co/MarcusGrattan/classifier-model/tree/main>

To evaluate the classifier, a test set of 5,000 entries was manually annotated. An average of 1,000 sentences were labelled per day, split across two sessions. The final test set comprised 665 Commissive, 3,228 Assertive, and 1,107 Other instances. Following Abercrombie et al. (2023), intra-annotator agreement was measured on 10% of the test set one week after completion, yielding an agreement score of 0.8, indicating strong consistency.

For more details regarding the model-building process, see Grattan (2024).

3 Classifier model results

The classifier model achieved an accuracy of 0.73 and a weighted F1-score of 0.75 on the test dataset, outperforming the most frequent class baseline, which had an accuracy of 0.65 and a weighted F1-score of 0.51. The model's weighted precision and recall were 0.80 and 0.73, respectively. For the Commissive class, the model achieved precision, recall, and F1-scores of 0.34, 0.68, and 0.45, respectively. In the Assertive class, the model performed better with precision of 0.88, recall of 0.74, and an F1 score of 0.80. The Other class achieved a precision of 0.84, recall of 0.74, and F1 score of 0.79.

The automatically annotated dataset contained 138,052 entries, excluding instances with no annotation. Among these, 32,458 entries (24%) were classified as Commissives, 80,377 entries (58%) as Assertives, and 25,215 entries (18%) as Other. Notably, the model failed to annotate 301 entries.

In the context of Speech Act classification, large language models (LLMs) can significantly reduce the reliance on manually annotated data while producing high-quality, large-scale datasets. State-of-the-art results from similar domains, such as the Switchboard corpus and the MRDA corpus, report accuracy scores of 0.85 (Colombo et al., 2020) and 0.92 (Chapuis et al., 2021), respectively. The classifier model presented in this paper, with an accuracy score of 0.73, achieved these results using approximately 80% fewer manually labelled data compared to similar studies (Vosoughi & Roy, 2016; Zhang et al., 2011). These results suggest that leveraging techniques like Retrieval Augmented Prompting (RAG)(Lewis et al., 2021) and CARP(Sun et al., 2023) enables LLMs to not only generate large datasets but also achieve substantial quality.

4 Applying the model and discussion

The model was applied to the corpus of corporate websites of all Swedish companies that communicate with their stakeholders (e.g. clients, customers, government, non-profit organisations and other) about their ISO/IEC 27001 implementation efforts (Jönsson et al., 2024). The results are shown in Table 1 and visually in Figure 1, revealing little difference between the analysis categories Adopters, Stewards, and Advocates.

	Assertive	Commissive	Other
Adopters	55%	27%	18%
Stewards	55%	23%	22%
Advocates	61%	24%	15%

Table 1: Speech act distribution

Interestingly, contrary to expectations, Advocates exhibit a similar frequency of Assertive speech acts as the other categories. Manual analysis of these Assertive acts reveals that they primarily describe the actions of third parties. This poses a challenge for the model, as it struggles to determine whether a statement reflects the organization's own reality or that of others, which impacts classification results.

Moreover, the performance of the classification model revealed that it often confused Commissives with Assertives, and to a lesser degree, vice versa. The precision and recall metrics for the Commissive class suggest that the model had difficulty accurately identifying Commissive speech acts. Specifically, the precision was low (0.34), indicating that many instances labeled as Commissives were incorrect. On the other hand, the recall for Commissives was higher (0.68), suggesting that the model was relatively effective at identifying true Commissive statements, though not always accurately.

Figure 1: Diagram of the distribution

During manual annotation, it was noted that few Commissive instances were explicit commitments; instead, many were implicit guarantees or commitments. For instance, *The contracted supplier must be certified according to ISO 27001, which is a globally renowned information security standard.* is formulated as assertive, but not for the speaker itself, but for others, in this case suppliers.

This made it particularly challenging to differentiate between Assertives and Commissives. It is likely that the LLM used for automatic annotation faced similar difficulties in distinguishing between these two categories. Additionally, the indirect nature of Commissives may have contributed to ambiguities in the demonstration dataset, influencing the model's performance.

5 Conclusions

The research presented in this paper demonstrates how large language models (LLMs) can be effectively leveraged to reduce reliance on manually annotated datasets in the domain of Speech Act classification. Utilising techniques such as Clue and Reasoning Prompting (CARP) (Sun et al., 2023) and Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) (Lewis et al., 2021). The research successfully generated a substantial dataset of 138,052 entries. This dataset facilitated the training and evaluation of and a classifier, which achieved an accuracy of 73% and a weighted F1-score of 0.75.

This work builds upon existing frameworks and proposes novel approaches for dataset generation in text classification tasks, particularly within the context of organisational communication related to ISO/IEC 27001 standards. Beyond its technical contributions, the study also adds value to the CLARIN infrastructure and to the broader field of organisational communication research. Furthermore, it highlights the potential of quantised LLMs for Speech Act classification, offering valuable insights into their performance, especially in low-resource language settings.

However, the results of the model were not helpful for the management researchers to show differences in how the ISO/IEC 27001 standard was adopted by Swedish companies.

An expanded LLM selection process, incorporating a wider array of models more data and focused tests specifically aimed at indirect and/or context dependent commissives, could improve the selection process and extend to better Commissive classification results. Additionally, while LLM selection was restricted to quantised models, using un-quantised models while keeping similar model parameter size, would likely improve performance.

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Building IcePInt: The Icelandic Parliament Interviews corpus

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Abstract

We describe ongoing work constructing a corpus of interviews with Icelandic Members of Parliament. IcePInt, the Icelandic Parliament Interview Corpus, is currently being used to augment data from the Icelandic Parliament Corpus for a project that analyzes Icelandic political speech. It is an argument for doing such work in Iceland that Icelandic politicians are more approachable by researchers than politicians in larger language communities. We are able to carry out linguistic interviews with current and former MPs, including high-ranking ministers.

1 Introduction

We describe work in progress on building a novel CLARIN resource, a corpus of interviews with Icelandic Members of Parliament (MPs). This effort is a part of the ERC-funded project Explaining Individual Lifespan Change (EILisCh). The EILisCh project involves analyzing speeches from the Icelandic parliament and tracking changes over time in how individual MPs as well as entire political parties use certain linguistic features. This primary analysis uses the Icelandic Parliament Corpus, a subset of the Icelandic Gigaword Corpus, but in order to interpret linguistic lifespan change of individual politicians, a better understanding of their career and attitudes is needed. This is where the Icelandic Parliament Interview corpus, IcePInt, comes into play. IcePInt involves directly interviewing current and former Icelandic MPs, recording the interviews both in terms of audio and video, transcribing them, and using them for analysis. Thus, while the analysis of the parliament speeches yields quantitative analysis of how the speech of the MPs evolved over time, IcePInt adds qualitative detail that allows us to interpret the quantitative findings. This new interview corpus will then be released under a Creative Commons Attribution license at the end of the project, facilitating its use in a variety of future projects.

Stefánsdóttir and Ingason (2018) carried out a study which in some respects is a pilot study for the EILisCh project. In their analysis, they track the use of Stylistic Fronting (SF) (Thráinsson, 2007), a word order phenomenon that indexes formality, in the speech of Steingrímur J. Sigfússon, a former MP and former finance minister. They also interviewed Sigfússon and their analysis connects the evolution of SF in his speeches with events in his history that are discussed in the interview, such as the economic crisis of 2008, after which he became finance minister. The creation of IcePInt allows us to apply a similar approach of combining quantitative and qualitative findings, but on a much larger scale.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides some background for our paper, Section 3 describes the interviews that make up the contents of the corpus. In Section 4 we discuss the publication of the corpus in open access via CLARIN and Section 5 concludes this paper.

2 Background

The EILisCh project is a five year project, aiming to use data on political speech to study individual lifespan change. As mentioned, the core quantitative analysis focuses on parliament speeches from the Icelandic Gigaword Corpus (Steingrímsson et al., 2018), using automatic annotation in order to extract tokens of interesting variables which are then coded both automatically and semi-automatically and

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Figure 1: Our interview setup: In this case, one of the authors, Lilja Björk Stefánsdóttir, is interviewing Geir Haarde, a former MP who was the prime minister of Iceland during the economic crash of 2008.

analyzed further (Stefánsdóttir & Ingason, 2018). It has also been verified that the automatic coding of the primary variable, SF, is accurate enough to be used for analysis even without manual correction (Stefánsdóttir & Ingason, 2025).

Although there are not many other interview corpora for Icelandic, some previous projects compiled and made use of conversation data, which is similar to our data in some respects. To mention some examples, work by Hilmisdóttir (2024), who has examined conversations of young Icelanders in relation to their use of Anglicisms. Furthermore, Gísladóttir (2015) has studied repair strategies in Icelandic conversations. Despite these and various other efforts, there is a clear need for Icelandic interview corpora with audio and video that are annotated and published in open access. Note that in an international context, numerous studies of interviews and conversations have made use of similar data sources, for example, Fu and Ho (2022) on TV interviews and Oertel et al. (2014) who developed a multi-modal corpus for analyzing conversational behavior in group interviews. While the development of open access corpora for Icelandic specifically is a field that needs to be established further, our contribution is a step towards such work.

3 The Interviews

The most unique aspect of the IcePInt corpus is that the EILisCh project makes use of the small size of the Icelandic language community in order to get access to the most prominent national politicians as candidates for linguistic interviews. We are certain that it would be much more challenging to approach a number of former MPs, some of whom have been ministers, in a large language community where high-profile politicians are less approachable.

Our interview setting can be seen in Figure 1. In this case, one of the authors, Lilja Björk Stefánsdóttir, is interviewing Geir Haarde, a former MP who was the prime minister of Iceland during the economic crash of 2008. We are grateful for the participation of such prominent politicians in our project.

The interview structure is designed around a series of questions with possible follow-ups. We first give out information about the study, then we ask the participant about their background and family. Next we transition into a phase where we focus on the parliament, asking about what drove the person to go into politics and run for parliament and we also ask about their career in the context of how they felt about being in this workplace. We also pose questions about the Icelandic language, their views on the language in general and what they think about the use of Icelandic in the parliament setting. Because we

are interested in the evolution of their careers, we acquire information about events or periods that the participant experienced as particularly challenging, and how these affected them. We give our informants the opportunity to add anything that they may find relevant and finally, we show them a graph of how we measure their level of formality over the years (as in Stefánsdóttir & Ingason, 2018), and directly confront them with our findings, allowing for a discussion of what may have affected changes in their linguistic behavior. Each interview is about one hour in length.

For all interviews, we record video in 4K resolution on a Sony A7S III camera, and for the audio, we always use two independent recordings for redundancy.¹ The primary audio recording mechanism is a pair of wireless Sony microphones connected to the camera and attached to the interviewer and the participant, but we also have an Audio-Technica microphone on the table to capture backup audio (see Figure 1). All videos are edited to start at the beginning of the first question and end once the final discussion ends.

The audio and video are imported into ELAN for transcription (Sloetjes & Wittenburg, 2008). The primary use of the annotation for us is to be able to extract quotes that shed light on how the career and attitudes of the participant shed light on the evolution of their linguistic behavior. For this reason, our transcription is very simple: We transcribe all the words that are said manually, including repetitions and disfluencies that involve speaking words, but we do not write down non-word disfluencies or coughs or the like. This strikes a balance between using our resources primarily for our current project while constructing a resource that can be used for other purposes, possibly with further annotation. We note that discourse markers such as *heyrðu* ‘well’ (Jónsdóttir & Gísladóttir, 2025) are transcribed and can therefore be studied in the data.

Although it is not clear at this point how many politicians will accept our invitation in the project, we have already carried out thirteen interviews and continue to schedule further ones in order to grow the size of the corpus. We plan to add a substantial number of interviews until the end of the project in 2028. It should be noted that all participants sign an informed consent form that allows for publication of the data in open access.

4 Publication

While the data collection is ongoing, the data will remain closed. But before the end of the project, the entire corpus, video, audio, and transcriptions, will be released and made available through the CLARIN infrastructure. We will not release the data immediately because we aim to do the first analysis of the data within our project and because we want the corpus to be complete before releasing it. While we reserve the rights to use the corpus while the project is ongoing, it is possible that we will collaborate with members outside the project group during this period, but we do remain committed to an open access policy so that all the data will eventually be released with a Creative Commons Attribution license (the CC BY). Our lab has a good track record in this respect, having released various previous resources on CLARIN, such as the Icelandic Error Corpus (Arnardóttir et al., 2021) and IceTaboo, a database of contextually inappropriate words in Icelandic (Sólmundsdóttir et al., 2021).

Also, while the initial goal of the data collection is to shed light on linguistic lifespan change of Icelandic politicians, the nature of the data makes it suitable to studying various other topics. The interview data could be used for other linguistic topics such as discourse analysis, but also for studying phenomena beyond linguistics such as political history. In any case, the eventual publication of this corpus in open access via the CLARIN framework will facilitate future work that may make use of this resource in diverse ways.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we have described ongoing work constructing a corpus of interviews with Icelandic politicians that will be released in open access via CLARIN when it is completed. This corpus project is connected with a larger project that aims to analyze linguistic lifespan change of Icelandic politicians by studying their parliament speeches, but the present corpus will lead to more qualitative depth by asking

¹An exception is the first couple of interviews which were recorded in 1080p resolution.

Icelandic politicians directly about their personal histories and attitudes. A central argument for carrying out work of this type in Iceland is that in such a small language community, local celebrities such as prominent politicians are more approachable than in other larger communities. But it is also important in general to study a wide range of languages and work on lifespan change has been relatively biased to focus on English; including Icelandic in the range of languages being examined for lifespan change is therefore an important goal of our work.

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The Swiss FAIR-compliant ecosystem of infrastructures 2.0

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Abstract

This presentation aims at providing an overview of the current state of the Swiss ecosystem of infrastructures for language data. Since 2023, a series of upgrades have been performed with the aim of increasing the FAIR-compliance of Swiss language resources and infrastructure, consisting of the Linguistic Research Infrastructure LiRI, the national repository SWISSUbase, as well as several smaller institutional corpora and databases. In the framework of several projects co-funded through the Swiss national programme for Open Research Data, the ecosystem was upgraded thanks to various technical implementations, such as the development and launch of the LiRI Corpus Platform populated with the above-mentioned institutional corpora, the upgrade of the metadata schema of SWISSUbase, the implementation of the harvesting of the national repository of the Swiss national repository, the integration of the Swiss-AL language data platform for applied sciences, as well as several community engagement, standardization and workflow building initiatives.

1 Introduction

As of 2025, the Swiss node of CLARIN consists of the following components: (i) the CLARIN-CH Consortium of Swiss higher education institutions, which represent the kernel of the national network, (ii) CLARIN-CH Coordination Office, which is in charge of the operation of CLARIN-CH and its driving force, hosted at the University of Zurich, and (iii) an ecosystem of infrastructures for language data consisting of: (a) a technical center, the Linguistic Research Infrastructure LiRI (University of Zurich), which provides support services and tools such as the LiRI Corpus Platform (LCP); (b) the national repository SWISSUbase and its Data Service Unit called Language Repository of Switzerland (LaRS@SWISSUbase); (c) a multilingual corpus platform for applied sciences, developed by the Digital Discourse Lab of the Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW).

2 Overview of the CLARIN-CH ecosystem of infrastructures 2.0

Since the 2023 status of the CLARIN-CH ecosystem of infrastructures 1.0 (see Bubenhofer et al. 2023), a series of significant upgrades have been carried out in the CLARIN-CH ecosystem of infrastructures for language data with the aim of increasing their FAIR-compliance, their interoperability with the CLARIN infrastructure, and their capacity to support Swiss scholars working with language data. This upgrade was carried out in the framework of the Swiss national Open Research Data program. A series of implementations at the technical and community level were performed within three projects: [Up-LORD](#), [Swiss-AL: Linguistic Open Research Data Practices for Applied Sciences](#), and [FAIR-FI-LD](#). As a result, the CLARIN-CH ecosystem was upgraded to its 2.0 version, which is described below.

Technical implementations:

- **Software development and launch of the LiRI Corpus Platform.** The LCP is conceptualized to function as a web-based tool designed to handle and analyze linguistic data (see Schaber et al. 2023). The idea was to allow users to carry out various tasks on corpora, such as querying and performing analyses across multiple modalities: text, audio, and video. In 2025, LiRI Corpus Platform has reached its beta status. Functionalities that are already in place include data upload, basic converters, fast querying, and sharing submitted corpora with collaborators. Underlyingly, LCP uses PostgreSQL, which enables fast querying of large corpora (e.g., Swissdox corpora has over 10 million words). However, this dictates the necessity to have data converted to a set of predefined relational CSV files. The exact relationship between the files and the accompanying metadata must be specified via a JSON metadata file. The specification for the latter can be found in LCP’s website manual.

- **Building of data converters, data conversion and population of the LCP with Swiss textual, oral and video corpora.** Since the required format—relational CSV files—is not very common in fields related to language sciences, it was decided to create data converters to facilitate the submission of new corpora to the LCP. CoNLL-U Plus format is well known to the research community because of Universal Dependencies’ dataset and was selected as the first target for the data converter. Thus, instead of transforming one’s corpus to relational CSV files with a particular specification, data contributors may choose to perform a simpler transformation from the corpus’ original format to CoNLL-U Plus. In this version, headers allow referencing the original file name, and each sentence or word can include timing information to enable alignment with audio or video. After this is done, the data depositor simply has to use Python’s command line interface [lcpcli](#) to convert the corpus from CoNLL-U Plus to relational CSV files. The sample interface is then used to send the data to LCP’s server. A similar converter is planned for TEI format in the near future. Given the beta status of LCP, most submissions are still performed by LiRI and CLARIN-CH, which serves both to populate the LCP with corpora across all three modalities (text, audio, and video) and to test the submission process.

- **Creation of complex annotation representations.** The LiRI Corpus Platform employs a modular and multi-dimensional data model that enables the integration and querying of complex linguistic annotations across various modalities (text, audio, video, images). At the core of LCP’s design is a dimensional modularity framework, which aligns entities along one or more of three axes: symbol (text), time (audio/video), and space (images/scans/frames). This structure allows annotations—such as named entities, syntactic dependencies, or gestures—to be represented consistently and queried relationally, even across modalities. For example, a spoken utterance can be annotated both with syntactic structure (symbol axis) and with a time-aligned video frame showing a facial expression (time axis), enabling cross-modal queries. A sample query in DQD illustrates this:

```

1 # Find all the utterances...
2 Utterance u
3   # ... by a speaker from Berne
4   agent.region = "Berne"
5   # ... that last at least 1s
6   end(u) > start(u) + 1
7
8 # Look for sequences of tokens in that utterance...
9 sequence@u seq
10  # ... that contain a token whose pos is 'CON' or 'PRO'
11  Token
12  |   pos = /CON|PRO/
13  # ... followed by a token whose form is "euh"
14  Token
15  |   form = "euh"
16
17 # Display the sequences within their segment
18 results => plain
19   context
20   |   u
21   entities
22   |   seq

```

1: An example of DQD query for an audio corpus in the LCP

- **Development of a language query, the DQD, to allow for complex and powerful queries.** The DQD (Descriptive Query Definition) language is a central component of the Linguistic Corpus Platform (LCP), designed for querying linguistically annotated corpora. Rooted in the principles of Entity-Relationship modeling, DQD allows users to define sets of entities and specify logical constraints on their properties and interrelations. It supports complex query constructs including entity instantiation, scoping via indentation, regular expressions, sequences, and sets. DQD queries must include a result clause, which can return plain entity lists, statistical analyses, or collocational patterns. The philosophy behind designing DQD was to allow users maximally complex queries, while not requiring the use of a full-fledged programming language, like Python or R. The advantage of DQD is additionally represented by its uniformity across all corpora represented in the LCP, including corpora of different modalities.

- **Upgrade of the metadata schema of SWISSUbase for specific types of language data.** SWISSUbase was launched in July 2022 with a linguistic metadata schema that draws on the CLARIN CMDI and the META-SHARE schema. For instance, sign language metadata was almost completely lacking representation in SWISSUbase. After feedback from a researcher who attempted to deposit this type of data, additional consultations were organized, and a detailed plan for sign language metadata was created. All requirements have been submitted to the SWISSUbase IT team for implementation in 2025.

- **Creation of the Swiss CMDI profile.** SWISSUbase uses a custom metadata schema largely based on META-SHARE, reflecting the needs of the Swiss linguistic research community, which is strongly influenced by interdisciplinary initiatives such as the NCCR “Evolving Language.” This context explains why flexibility in metadata design is essential. A Swiss CMDI profile was created, and entries from SWISSUbase metadata were manually mapped to CMDI elements. Based on this mapping, a script generates CMDI files for harvesting by the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory (VLO). The profile is currently kept in development mode in the CLARIN Component Registry to accommodate future changes in SWISSUbase.

- **Implementation of the CLARIN federated authentication system and of the the harvesting of the national repository by the VLO.** The CLARIN Authentication Service for researchers in Europe and internationally to sign in to SWISSUbase is now functional. Since September 2024, VLO metadata from SWISSUbase’s linguistic schema has been harvested by the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory (VLO) catalogue. Research data from the Swiss linguistic research community can now be found on a European level, thus increasing their visibility and discoverability.

- **Construction of workflows and APIs to push data from LiRI to SWISSUbase.** A new version of the SWISSUbase API was implemented in November 2024. This allows searching the catalogue and downloading data on the one hand and registering, uploading, updating, and deleting datasets and data via the API on the other.

- **Implementation of the CLARIN Federated Content Search (FCS) for the LCP and the Swiss-AL platform.** The Swiss landscape is unique because Switzerland has multiple national languages (German, French, Italian, Romansh), and language data is often created and maintained by different institutions across linguistic regions. In this context, the FCS is especially important, as it allows seamless search across these decentralized and diverse resources, regardless of location or language. CLARIN-CH operates at the interface between the research infrastructures that implement the FCS and the researchers from various language regions, who provide insights into their specific needs and contribute datasets that must be properly integrated into the FCS.

- **Re-implementation of Swiss-AL workbench.** Swiss-AL consists of (1) a family of multilingual Swiss public communication corpora, (2) a corpus and computational linguistics pipeline for compiling and processing these corpora, and (3) a browser-based workbench for analyzing these corpora. The latest version of the Swiss-AL Workbench introduces a range of technical innovations aimed at improving performance, usability, and analytical flexibility. Corpus analysis methods have been modularized in the backend and now communicate their results to the frontend via a dedicated API. Search queries within individual modules are processed either through the established Corpus Workbench (CWB) or a newly developed database, which significantly speeds up query handling by precomputing data such as frequency information. The Swiss-AL corpora have also been systematically organized into defined

corpus types to ensure consistent data structure. A user management system has been implemented, relying on authentication via Switch-EDU-ID, and users are now required to associate their work with a research project through a new project management feature. On the frontend, a tab-based workspace allows for parallel analyses across multiple modules, while three distinct search modes (simple, basic, advanced) provide varying levels of query complexity. Additionally, users can now generate customized corpora based on metadata and search terms, enabling more targeted and efficient research workflows. Results can also be downloaded in various formats such as CSV or PNG, allowing for further processing or integration into reports and presentations.

- Personal support to Swiss corpus owners to increase the FAIR-compliance of their corpora. An important obstacle in increasing FAIR-compliance of corpora is the corpus owners' lack of time and of skills to prepare the data. To support them in this task, the CLARIN-CH Technical Officer provided personalized support consisting of bilateral meetings with the corpus owners to understand their data (format, storage, size, structure) and propose tailored solutions, such as data conversion and preparation for upload in the LCP. For example, for the corpus Archimob, the added challenge was represented by lack of audio files corresponding to certain utterances due to legal issues. The dilemma was whether to delete additional textual data or create a discrepancy between the text and audio representation of the corpus, with the latter being the ultimate solution. Text utterances that lack corresponding audio were marked as such using an additional category introduced specifically for this purpose. Creation of such categories is allowed by LCP's data modeling schema and is made possible thanks to the use of a query language, as opposed to GUI-only queries.

- Formulation of a metadata curation workflow and version control workflows, and publication of documentation and guides about language data archiving with LaRS@SWISSUbase. We created or substantially updated guides and documentation on the LaRS and SIWSSUbase Info Webpage, which now better addresses the challenges faced by the linguistic research community (see [documented workflows](#), [Linguistic Metadata Guide](#) and [SWISSUbase's Policy](#)).

- Collection recommended/standard data formats and the integration of the Swiss results into the CLARIN Standard Information System. CLARIN-CH conducted a survey to gather community input on recommended data formats in linguistic research as part of [its contribution](#) to the CLARIN Standards Information System (SIS). The survey targeted specific groups of researchers with extensive experience in working and sharing data in their fields. By collecting both common and less well-known format recommendations, we aimed to ensure broad coverage and relevance. Only formats that received support above a certain threshold ultimately made it to the list of Swiss suggested formats. Interestingly, a few formats had to be discarded from our list of accepted/discouraged formats as they were deemed "controversial" — recommended by some researchers and discouraged by others. This highlights different approaches to data formats and standards or different tools used by researchers.

3 Conclusion

As a result of the various implementations, in 2025, two certifications have recently been received for the Swiss ecosystem: the CoreTrustSeal certification for LaRS and the CLARIN K-certification for ZHAW Digital Discourse Lab. The CLARIN B-certification for the technical center and the repository is in progress. The upgrades we present in this paper were triggered by the identification of a series of gaps in the first version of the Swiss ecosystem of infrastructures 1.0 (see Bubenhofer et al. 2023) and the opportunity of three projects co-funded through the Swiss national programme for Open Research Data and carried out under the umbrella of the Swiss node of CLARIN – CLARIN-CH. The services proposed by the Swiss ecosystem of infrastructures provide access to and reuse of linguistic research data in Switzerland and abroad. Future work will focus on implementing the Federated Content Search (FCS), developing more automated pipelines for cross-depositions, improving metadata quality, and enhancing the API for scalable depositions. In sum, the Swiss FAIR-compliant ecosystem of infrastructures shares the vision of the European CLARIN infrastructure with respect to language resources, language technology, and Open Science.

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A Parallel Literary Corpus of Yiddish Texts with their French and Russian Translations

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Abstract

This article presents the trilingual Yiddish-French-Russian parallel corpus of literary translations that will be proposed to be available on CLARIN. Parallel corpora are fundamental resources for translation studies, contrastive linguistics, and natural language processing (NLP). Despite advances in neural machine translation, these corpora remain essential for improving automatic translation tools, particularly for less-resourced languages such as Yiddish. This article describes the construction of the corpus, including text alignment with the integration of a custom bilingual dictionary. The corpus is incorporated into a multilingual concordancer, facilitating data exploration and analysis.

1 Introduction

In this article, we present an aligned trilingual Yiddish-French-Russian corpus of literary translations, created and being developed within the framework of the project "Translation as a strategic issue for the survival of post-vernacular Jewish languages" (LJTRAD) coordinated by Arnaud Bikard. We hope that the corpus could be integrated into CLARIN's extensive network of repositories, because this work aligns with CLARIN's mission to advance language resource accessibility and multilingual research infrastructure. The corpus particularly enhances CLARIN's efforts to preserve and digitize resources for less-digitized languages like Yiddish, while creating new opportunities for comparative literary analysis and translation studies.

Our presentation of the corpus will be structured as follows. First, we will focus on the role and usefulness of aligned parallel corpora given existing resources for Yiddish, and in the context of recent advances in language models and machine translation. Next, we will discuss our corpus construction methodology, followed by a brief description of corpus exploration tools we provide. We will discuss the specific challenges associated with aligning these three languages with distinct syntactic structures and alphabets. Finally, we will provide a presentation of the corpus content. This section will also include a quantitative and qualitative analysis of the corpus content in its current state, highlighting the diversity of literary genres and historical periods represented.

2 The role of parallel corpora with respect to existing Yiddish resources

Yiddish has a long lexicographical tradition that includes several bilingual dictionaries and an ambitious project to create a monolingual dictionary (Moskovich, 2010). However, existing bilingual dictionaries are generally lacking in contextual examples, limiting their usefulness for in-depth analyses or nuanced language learning. This is the gap which parallel corpora attempt to fill.

Parallel corpora occupy an important position in the fields of translation studies and contrastive linguistics. An aligned parallel corpus constitutes a large collection of texts in digital format, establishing precise correspondences between versions of the same content in two or more languages, generally aligned at the sentence or paragraph level (Doval & Nieto, 2019; Lefer, 2021; Mikhailov & Cooper, 2016).

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Parallel corpora exist for several languages, many of which are listed on the CLARIN website¹ (De Jong et al., 2018). Within the typology of parallel corpora, our corpus falls into the type offering texts in the original language and their literary translations into the target language, with sentence-by-sentence alignment. It is therefore the first aligned multilingual corpus for Yiddish literature and its translations. Since literary texts are not translated word-for-word, the translations included in the parallel corpus should be understood as literary or interpretive translations, rather than exact equivalents. While this limits some types of linguistic analysis, it opens rich possibilities for comparative literary, stylistic, and cultural studies.² All alignments have been done at the excerpt level to reflect meaningful correspondences without implying strict literal equivalence.

Compared to other less-resourced languages, Yiddish benefits from several important resources available online. The largest is the corpus of Yiddish literature at the Yiddish Book Center in Amherst. This exceptional resource offers a sophisticated search engine on the OCR content and various filtering options³. Its main value lies in the breadth of its collection, which provides researchers with access to a vast set of digitized texts representative of Yiddish literature. Another smaller resource developed by the Russian Academy of Sciences is the Corpus of Modern Yiddish (CMY)⁴, as described by Birzer (2014). This corpus is distinguished by its sophisticated linguistic analysis capabilities, including part-of-speech tagging and morphosyntactic analysis. Both of these corpora were of particular use in the design and construction of our parallel corpus.

In the current context of considerable advances in language models and machine translation, aligned multilingual corpora remain a valuable resource. When manually aligned, they offer a quality that automatic models cannot guarantee, particularly for less-resourced languages such as Yiddish. Indeed, the only encoder model currently available for Yiddish is the multilingual model XLM-RoBERTa (Conneau et al., 2019), where Yiddish is one of 100 languages and represents far less than 1% of the source data. Although Kulick et al. (2023) have shown it is possible to fine-tune this model to improve Yiddish POS-tagging, considerable work is needed to provide a general-purpose high-quality Yiddish encoder model. We are not aware of any decoder models for Yiddish. We hope that our parallel corpus can thus be used as a reference for both the improvement and evaluation of automatic systems based on new Yiddish language models.

3 Corpus construction methodology and research tools

The development of our corpus required several steps: the creation of parallel data in Yiddish, French and Russian; the alignment of Yiddish-French and Yiddish-Russian texts; as well as the establishment of a platform integrating a search engine and concondancer interface. To compile the parallel data, we adopted a mixed strategy. We integrated openly accessible French and Russian translations into our corpus, and OCRed the Yiddish originals using OCR system, Jochre, developed by Urieli et al. (2025) for the Yiddish Book Center (Amherst). Before alignment, the Yiddish texts were manually proof-read, and then semi-automatically converted into a standardized orthography developed by the Yiddish Language Institute (YIVO) to ensure the proper functioning of the bilingual lexicon during alignment and to unify the entries within the corpus for information retrieval with the search engine.

Each text and translation were encoded in TEI format to enable their reuse in future scientific projects, such as possible research on machine translation.

The alignment of the Yiddish-French parallel texts was carried out using the Hunalign tool (Varga et al., 2008). This bilingual alignment system is based on a hybrid approach combining statistical and lexical methods. It operates in three main stages: a pre-alignment based on segment length; a lexical alignment based on a bilingual dictionary; and an iterative refinement of the correspondences. Hunalign can work even in the absence of pre-existing lexical resources, by automatically generating a probabilistic dictionary from the aligned texts. However, better results are obtained with a wide-coverage lexicon.

¹<https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/parallel-corpora>

²Several examples of this type of analysis, conducted using our corpus, are available at Bikard et al. (2025)

³<https://ocr.yiddishbookcenter.org/>

⁴<http://web-corpora.net/YNC>

We thus integrated an electronic version of Niborski and Vaisbrot (2002), a Yiddish-to-French dictionary, which significantly improved the accuracy of the Yiddish-French alignment. The addition of this lexical resource compensated for some of the difficulties inherent in aligning a non-Latin script language, such as Yiddish, with a Romance language such as French, particularly with regard to morphosyntactic divergences and cultural specificities of the lexicon. For the Yiddish-Russian alignment, we built a Yiddish-Russian electronic dictionary by automatically translating the Yiddish-French dictionary entries into Russian using the Python package *deep-translator*.

To maximize alignment accuracy despite morphosyntactic divergences, both the original texts and the dictionary were stemmed prior to alignment using the Snowball stemmer⁵, including the Yiddish stemmer contributed by Urieli in November 2020, and the French and Russian stemmers available in the original Snowball. Manual evaluation of a sample of alignments revealed a satisfactory accuracy rate, thus ensuring the reliability of the subsequent translation analyses planned in our study.

The alignment results were stored in a CSV file to simplify manual correction, including the original sentence with its TEI reference and the translated sentence with its TEI reference. In the case of one-to-many alignments, the source or target sentence is repeated.

Once the TEI files in all languages were ready, as well as the CSV alignment files, we uploaded the batch to our custom built search engine and concordancer. The search engine is based on Apache Lucene⁶, and allows phrase and wildcard searches. The interface allows users to select the source and target languages, and indicate the number of sentences to display before and after the match (from 1 to 4). The user can also decide whether to match on stems (using the Snowball stemmers), or on exact terms without stemming.

The concordancer is accessible through an authentication system using the Keycloak identity provider. Authenticated users are mapped to internal roles (e.g., “registered user”), which determines their access rights. This system allows the platform to identify users and grant access to the concordancer in a controlled and restricted manner.

4 Corpus content

The construction of a corpus of translations for Yiddish was made possible by the fact that French and Russian possess sophisticated schools of translation from Yiddish. These traditions have existed since the beginning of the 20th century and were particularly enriched after the Second World War. After the Holocaust and the drastic decline in the number of Yiddish speakers, a cultural preservation movement developed in several countries, including France and the former Soviet Union, albeit in very different political contexts.

In France, the historical presence of a large Ashkenazi Jewish community, with a significant number of translators and activists, has stimulated interest in Yiddish culture among French intellectuals. This led to the creation of specialized publishing houses and collections dedicated to Yiddish literature, including bilingual Yiddish-French editions pursuing educational goals (Chinski, 2024).

Our parallel corpus only partially reflects this rich literary output for a less-resourced language, but we plan to expand it to cover it as comprehensively as possible. Currently, the corpus is unidirectional, meaning it only includes translations from Yiddish into French and Russian. The number of translations into Yiddish from French or Russian is also significant, and the inclusion of these translations in the corpus is planned for a later stage. Corpus statistics are shown in Table 1.

In our bibliographic research on translations of Yiddish literature into French, we relied on the list prepared by the librarians of the Medem Library⁷, which includes 228 items (excluding anthologies). Our corpus currently covers only 8% of the entire dataset of French translations. The Yiddish-French corpus was designed from the outset with particular attention to chronological diversity: the Yiddish works cover a period of over a century, from Mendele Moykher-Sforim to Avrom Sutzkever.

The corpus comprises mostly recent translations (more accessible to automatic processing), but also

⁵<https://snowballstem.org/>

⁶<https://lucene.apache.org/>

⁷<https://www.yiddishweb.com/traductions-du-yiddish-en-francais/>

	Yiddish	French	Russian
Token count	1070K	1024K	178K
Document count	19	19	4
Author count	15	15	3
Translator count	15	15	4
Time span of original texts	1873-1972	1873-1972	1911-1972
Time span of translations	1933-2022	1933-2022	1928-2010

Table 1: Corpus statistics for Yiddish, French and Russian

contains some older translations to ensure a more meaningful diachronic representation. The high number of translators for this relatively modest corpus allows for a comparative analysis of their translation strategies. The diversity of authors ensures, from the first stage of development, a certain variety in the representation of Yiddish linguistic and stylistic variants within the corpus. Our corpus essentially comprises two literary forms: prose works (novels and short stories) and poetry (in much smaller quantities). This generic distribution reflects general trends in the publishing market for translations of Yiddish works, where novels and prose stories are favored over poetry and drama.

Copyright issues are important to our team, which is why we took care to address them properly by building a registered-user, limited-access parallel corpus. All original Yiddish works included in the corpus are in the public domain, with their copyright statuses individually verified. The French translations are mostly under copyright, while the Russian translations have a mixed copyright status.

For our parallel corpus, we adopted a snippet + access control model: the corpus stores the full texts of all works—regardless of copyright status—but only displays short aligned excerpts (2 to 5 lines of text) in response to each query. These snippets are minimal and necessary for research purposes. Full texts are not available for download. To reduce the risk of data scraping, a limit is placed on the number of queries allowed per day. Access to the concordancer is restricted to registered users only.

5 Conclusion

We presented a parallel corpus constructed for the project LJTRAD. Not only does the corpus complement and reinforce the information provided by bilingual dictionaries by providing a wealth of contextual information, but it also allows for a critical and reasoned analysis of the practice of translation from Yiddish into French and Russian over time and across individual translation practices. The corpus tools, by presenting the original texts and their translation face to face, allow us to decode, for each translator, what Berman (1995) calls their "translation contract," to see whether they are attentive to the sensitivity of the French or Russian reader, or whether, on the contrary, they seek to decenter the reader's vision by introducing foreign culture. The resource will ultimately allow for a detailed critique of individual translations and thus provide an informed assessment of Yiddish literature as it has been transmitted in French and Russian, as well as providing a valuable resource for the improvement and evaluation of automatic systems based on neural language models.

6 Acknowledgments

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Data governance for Indigenous and minoritised languages

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Abstract

Data from the languages of Indigenous and otherwise minoritized groups poses challenges for the development of language infrastructures that promote scientific endeavour while also protecting the rights of the Indigenous or otherwise minority language communities. In this presentation we outline how these challenges can be addressed by implementing the CARE principles using examples drawn from the work of the Language Data Commons of Australia.

1 Introduction

Working with data on the languages of Indigenous and otherwise minoritised groups poses particular challenges.¹ The CARE principles (Carroll et al., 2020) have set out a framework within which we can address these challenges. In this presentation, we discuss some of the aspects of Indigenous language data which are difficult to deal with, examining ways in which problems can be tackled within the CARE framework. We provide examples from the work of the Language Data Commons of Australia (LDaCA) and suggest that our organisation is well placed to share knowledge about these important issues.

Indigenous data, which can be defined as information or knowledge which is produced by or is about, or may affect, Indigenous peoples, collectively and individually, encompasses a very wide range of material. Here, we focus on Indigenous language data which can include historical (written) records, audio/video recordings, field notes, transcripts, as well as more recent documentation which can include multimedia, educational materials and academic publications presenting information about Indigenous languages.

The CARE framework (Carroll et al. 2020) provides four principles which are a basis for working with Indigenous data:

- **Collective Benefit:** Data ecosystems shall be designed and function in ways that enable Indigenous Peoples to derive benefit from the data.
- **Authority to Control:** Indigenous Peoples' rights and interests in Indigenous data must be recognised and their authority to control such data be empowered.
- **Responsibility:** Those working with Indigenous data have a responsibility to share how those data are used to support Indigenous Peoples' self-determination and collective benefit.
- **Ethics:** Indigenous Peoples' rights and wellbeing should be the primary concern at all stages

¹ In what follows, we will use the word *Indigenous* for convenience, but intend this to be read as including other minority or endangered language communities as well.

of the data life cycle and across the data ecosystem.

The CARE principles thus centre Indigenous Peoples in working with Indigenous language data.

2 Data governance and Indigenous languages

The distinction between the usual conditions facing Indigenous language data and languages considered to be high-status with more speakers has provided two fundamental considerations that have shaped our approach to Indigenous language data. First, Indigenous language data is not replaceable. Losing a collection of data representing a widely-used or 'high-status' language may be unfortunate, but it is not generally catastrophic. There are plenty of other sources of data and it may be possible to reproduce the lost data, or something similar to it. This is not the case for Indigenous languages. In many cases, the currently existing data is all that there is and all that there ever will be. Secondly, materials for Indigenous languages have user groups who are as important, if not more important, than researchers and scholars: the communities associated with the language and language variants. Given this, the first CARE principle, Collective Benefit, must be aimed at fostering greater autonomy and agency for Indigenous communities, allowing them to derive value from data in ways that respect their priorities and cultural ways of being. In this instance, the application of Indigenous data governance must be predicated on enabling community groups to: (1) find, (2) access, and (3) reuse or repurpose data in support of community-determined priorities. A practical example of this, and of its interaction with the second principle, Authority to Control, is the question of language names and language identifiers. Authority to Control means that speakers of a language should decide what names and descriptors are associated with a language. But it is often the case, particularly where there is a colonial history, that various names will be associated with a single language (or its dialects). For discovery to work well, that is, for community members to access as much relevant material as possible, consistent codes need to be employed (e.g. Glottolog) and the relationship between codes and preferred names has to be handled transparently. This example suggests that technological solutions, such as search facilities, have to be designed and implemented to be maximally accessible to users.

This is also a key point in considering questions which arise from the interaction of the A of FAIR (Accessibility) and the A of CARE (Authority to Control). In some instances, the speakers of Indigenous languages may wish to restrict access to some or all of the data relevant to their language. Authority to Control suggests they have the power to do so, and the application of data governance must therefore make this possible. LDaCA has developed a technological solution for access control, using the REMS resource management application² and CILogon³ (Sefton et al., 2023; Foley et al., 2024). This tech stack implements access control, but who has access to any particular data is decided by data owners or custodians. Before discussing some examples in more detail, we shall explain how including CILogon in the stack relates to the broader issues. As a project based in the Australian research environment, LDaCA would be expected to look to the Australian Access Federation (AAF). AAF manages access for employees of universities and other research institutions and does not provide services to a wider public. As already discussed, enabling community members to interact with language data is a key outcome for our work with Indigenous materials; CILogon allows for the use of credentials that are widely available, such as Google, and therefore it is part of our technical solution.

A central problem in deciding access conditions for data is often finding who has the Authority to Control. LDaCA is working with a range of individuals and groups to secure data and these activities provide a range of case studies which illustrate this point. The most straightforward case is one where all the material involved is associated with a single person who is – or their family are – in a position to make decisions about it. LDaCA is developing the idea of *person-centred collections*, with a pilot celebrating the work and achievements of Arrernte language worker and educator Veronica Dobson

² <https://www.elixir-finland.org/en/aai-rems-2/>

³ <https://www.cilogon.org/home>

which falls into this category.⁴ A more complex case is the collaboration between LDaCA and the Centre for Australian Languages and Linguistics Collection held by Bachelor Institute. The Bachelor Institute library has established and managed permissions for a large part of the collection, but not all of it. In collaborative work, those existing governance arrangements have to be respected and continued while the gaps also need to be addressed. Another complex example is the work which LDaCA has undertaken in association with the Nyingarn project⁵ on the field notes of Swedish linguist Nils Holmer. Holmer's notebooks have been made accessible as digital objects with machine-readable text using the Nyingarn tool, but the material cannot be shared yet. The work of identifying the various languages and speakers represented and tracing who might, fifty years after the data was collected, have authority to make decisions about it is ongoing. This last example illustrates the huge problem of establishing access control for legacy materials, where finding a balance between minimising risk for holding institutions and not completely stopping access is difficult (Thieberger et al., 2024).

3 Concluding Remarks

We have outlined some of the issues which arise in managing Indigenous language data, but we hope it is clear that we have only touched on some aspects of what is in reality a series of complex conversations which are only just beginning in our work and around the world. LDaCA is part of a HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons⁶ and our work therefore takes place in an environment where questions about governance of a full range of Indigenous data are being canvassed and members of our team have been involved in the development of a Framework for the Governance of Indigenous Data (McLellan et al., 2024). Whilst solutions to the issues outlined here will necessarily vary across contexts, the processes required to address them are, at least in part, generalisable. The examples mentioned briefly above, for instance, demonstrate how at least two of the CARE principles interact in such generalisations. A crucial step in placing Indigenous data under appropriate governance is identifying who has Authority to Control, and an Ethical approach to that problem implies that that process also must be under the control of the Indigenous group. LDaCA has already developed and continues to build experience in applying such processes on a case-by-case basis. We are pleased to share this knowledge with individuals and groups within CLARIN, initially through informal channels, and potentially, over time, through a more formalised collaboration

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⁴ <https://www.veronicadobson.au>

⁵ <https://nyingarn.net/>

⁶ <https://ardc.edu.au/hass-and-indigenous-research-data-commons/>

Opportunities for Collaboration between Research Infrastructures: The Case of HR-CLARIN and CROSSDA

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Abstract

This paper presents the first attempt of collaboration between CLARIN and CESSDA research infrastructures at the national level in Croatia. The CROSSDA repository catalogue was consulted in order to find the text-based or text-oriented entries. The manual inspection of metadata yielded 24 such entries. The relevant textual data were downloaded and their cumulative size calculated in tokens. Total of 256,902 tokens was found with only 3313 (1.29%) of tokens in the form of lexica, while all other were in the form of running text.

1 Introduction

Since in the European Union Research Infrastructures (RI) are already well established as ERICs and function well within their own communities, it might be interesting to check whether the collaboration between EU RIs could function at the level of national teams and even repositories. The collaboration between RIs in the humanities – CLARIN and DARIAH – is common in many countries, up to the level of joint national funding schemes, such as CLARIAH-AT in Austria, CLaDA in Bulgaria, LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ in Czechia, CLARIAH-NL in the Netherlands, and CLARIAH-ES in Spain. However, in this paper we would like to find out whether there are any opportunities for collaboration at the national level between humanities RI CLARIN and social sciences RI CESSDA. Effectively this means the collaboration between national participation teams for Croatia: HR-CLARIN and Croatian Social Science Data Archive (CROSSDA). This collaboration could be institutionally simplified by the fact that national coordinators (NCs) for both RIs are employed at the same institution – Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences at the University of Zagreb.

2 Infrastructural and Institutional Prerequisites for HR-CLARIN and CROSSDA Collaboration

CROSSDA¹ is a national public RI for the social sciences and a service provider for the CESSDA ERIC. It was established at the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Zagreb, which acts as the national coordinating institution for, both RIs CLARIN ERIC and CESSDA ERIC, with the support of the Ministry of Science, Education and Youth. Croatia became a full member of CESSDA in 2019. CROSSDA's main mission is to establish and develop a RI that enables long-term data preservation and reduces barriers to data reuse. The activities of the data archive are focused on supporting social sciences researchers in data management throughout the research process, in order to preserve the integrity and authenticity of the data along with all the information necessary for data interpretation. The data archive supports open and free access to data wherever possible. The archive fulfils its mission through continuous control of digital objects, respecting international professional standards, and cooperating with similar organizations across Europe and the rest of the world.

HR-CLARIN² is also a public RI and the national consortium of the CLARIN ERIC in Croatia. It is the full member of CLARIN ERIC since 2018. It provides language resources and technologies and expertise as well as knowledge transfer to researchers from humanities and social sciences with a focus on Croatian language resources and tools, but develops language technologies in other languages also. In 2024 HR-CLARIN repository was included in the list of CLARIN's C-type centres.

¹ <https://www.crossda.hr/>

² <https://www.clarin.hr/>

3 Text-related CROSSDA Catalogue Entries

As a first possible way to collaborate between these two RIs we selected the checking in the CROSSDA catalogue for the existence of text-based or text-related datasets. These textual data could be processed by CLARIN tools in any manner needed and could be used by both, social sciences and humanities scholars.

The CROSSDA catalogue was last checked on 2025-04-11 and it had a total of 32 published datasets. After manual inspection, in 24 entries text-based or text-oriented datasets were detected. These are considered candidates of interest for CLARIN.

All 24 entries with text-based or text-related datasets were inspected and they could tentatively be categorised in the following three categories:

3.1 Category 1

Entries in the CROSSDA catalogue where metadata could be mapped or copied in the HR-CLARIN repository in order to be visible through VLO since they represent a valuable psycholinguistic³ language data for Croatian also. They include these three entries: 1) MegaRT: Lexical Decision Times for Croatian Words, 2) Lexical Decision Times for Nouns from the Croatian Psycholinguistic Database, and 3) Norms of Free Associations for Croatian language.

3.2 Category 2

In social sciences, texts are often analysed through the content analysis method, done usually with proprietary software tools with limited NLP capabilities, especially for Croatian language, e.g. in the cases of semi-structured interviews of examinees. These texts could be pre-processed using standard or tailored NLP-tools for Croatian (e.g. NERC, sentiment analysis, SRL, etc.) that could provide the social scientists with the additional levels of visualisation and abstraction. This way, the overview of relations inherently present in the texts and that were not evident at the first glance, should enhance the quality of content analysis approach. Unfortunately, at the time of consulting the CROSSDA catalogue only one entry included such data and it was (Percepcije, 2024). This dataset includes transcripts of 12 group and 15 individual semi-structured interviews with 45 different participants.

3.3 Category 3

In this category we have put the texts of questionnaires used in different sociological, pedagogical, psychological or political surveys as well as documents describing the research methods used to collect and process data, and final research reports. In this way the CROSSDA could function as a source of language data from the repository that is not usually the first choice for linguists. In this category a total amount is twenty entries, with notable number of eleven political studies of pre- and post-election surveys in Croatia, accompanied by surveys from other social sciences.

In several cases the entries, mostly composed of tabular data, also contain additional textual materials that could be useful for linguistic research, e.g. notes which were added to the tabular data in the dataset on punishing wanderers during the First World War in Zagreb. This topic could be of interest also to historians of everyday life during that time.

The overall size of Croatian language data existing in 24 entries of CROSSDA repository is cumulatively calculated to 256,902 tokens. Only 3313 tokens (1.29%) are in the form of lexica, while the rest is in the form of running text. Although this cumulative number might seem quite limited in comparison to the contemporary corpora, it may still represent a source of specific linguistic data that has not been tackled so far.

The statistical distribution of entries by a particular social science can be seen in the Fig. 1., while the overall distribution of number of tokens is as follows: political studies 46828 (18%), sociology 188019 (73%), psychology 8684 (3%), pedagogy 6451 (3%), media studies 6920 (3%).

³ In the Croatian classification of scientific areas, fields and branches (Pravilnik, 2024), psychology is classified as a social science and this is why there are entries with psychological data in CROSSDA repository. In other countries psychology may appear within humanities

Fig. 1: Distribution of entries by particular social sciences.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

Here we present the first attempt of collaboration between CLARIN and CESSDA RI teams at the national level in Croatia. This is certainly not the only possible way to collaborate and in the future, we would like to examine other directions.

We would like to make scientists from the social sciences aware of possible new methods of pre-processing of their research textual data provided by CLARIN. In this respect, some steps have already been taken with regular participation of the HR-CLARIN national coordinator at CESSDA's annual conferences in Croatia. We believe that this first collaboration could serve as a role model to follow.

We would also examine whether the same approach could be applied to collaboration between HR-CLARIN and ESS in Croatia, i.e. whether in ESS there are any text-based or text-oriented datasets. Happily, the national coordinator of ESS in Croatia is again employed at the same institution as the national coordinators of CLARIN and CESSDA.

Furthermore, in order to detect more language data within the social sciences datasets, we believe that expanding the scope to other institutional repositories (e.g. Dabar, supported by the University of Zagreb Computing Centre) is necessary. For instance, the Croatian Psycholinguistic Database (2019) is stored in such repository and its metadata could be replicated in the HR-CLARIN repository and become visible through VLO.

For processing the results of checking other repositories, we could use the same categorisation, or expand the existing one upon finding new types of entries.

We strongly believe that this collaboration would benefit both RIs in a longer-term perspective.

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From Silos to Synergies: Implementing the Standard API Specification DTS in DraCor for Enhanced Data Access

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Abstract

This talk explores the integration of the standard API specification DTS (Distributed Text Services) into DraCor, a community-driven platform for drama corpora. By implementing DTS, DraCor enhances the accessibility and usability of its extensive repository of over 4,300 theatre plays across 21 literary corpora in more than 17 languages. The DTS API provides fine-granular access to textual data, improved citability, and advanced structural analysis capabilities, fostering interoperability and collaboration in digital humanities research.

1 DraCor

By building a community-driven platform for drama corpora, DraCor (<https://dracor.org>) supports open science principles and enhances the accessibility and usability of textual data for the field of computational literary studies. Currently, DraCor provides over 4,300 theatre plays in 21 literary corpora from more than 17 (mostly European) languages, reaching from Greek antiquity to the 20th century. This rich repository of dramatic texts is complemented by a comprehensive ecosystem of tools, a document- and research-driven API, programming libraries for Python and R, and Jupyter notebook-based training materials. DraCor not only serves as a hub for data-driven research on European drama and beyond but also acts as a competence center for Computational Literary Studies, with implications extending to Performance Studies, Theatre Studies, Digital Editing, Computational Linguistics, and the History of Ideas.

2 Programmable Corpora and Standardized APIs

Central to the DraCor initiative is the concept of Programmable Corpora – corpora that expose an open, transparently documented and (at least partly) research-driven API to make texts machine-actionable (Börner & Trilcke, 2023; Fischer, Börner, Göbel, Hechtel, Kittel, Milling, & Trilcke, 2019). This approach enables researchers to engage with dramatic texts in a programmatic manner, facilitating advanced computational analysis and research. By implementing the DraCor API (<https://dracor.org/api/v1>), DraCor significantly expands the research capabilities and computational analysis possibilities of its resources. This API allows researchers to seamlessly integrate DraCor’s data into their workflows, facilitating advanced computational studies of literature.

The DraCor API, while transparently documented through an OpenAPI specification (<https://dracor.org/doc/api>), remains a custom development tailored to the specific needs of the DraCor platform. As the project seeks to enhance integration with other digital humanities initiatives and infrastructures, it becomes evident that adhering to established standards and implementing standardized APIs, e.g. a OAI-PMH interface, is essential. Embracing standardized APIs will not only facilitate smoother interoperability and data exchange but also ensure that DraCor’s resources are more easily discoverable and usable across the broader digital humanities landscape.

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3 Implementing Standard APIs to DraCor: DTS as an example

Distributed Text Services (DTS) is an API Specification (<https://distributed-text-services.github.io/specifications>) designed to facilitate the interoperability and accessibility of textual data across different platforms and infrastructures (Almas et al., 2023). It provides a consistent framework for querying and retrieving textual data based on the formats JSON-LD for metadata and TEI-XML for textual content. By adopting DTS, projects like DraCor can enhance the discoverability, accessibility, and usability of their resources, fostering a more connected and collaborative research environment. The implementation of DTS in DraCor involves integrating the DTS API into the existing DraCor API (Version 1.1) by adding additional endpoints¹:

api/v1/dts (DraCor DTS Entry point):

This is the main entry point for accessing the DTS API within DraCor. It provides an overview of the other available DTS endpoints and can serve as a starting point for navigating the API's capabilities. Users can retrieve metadata about the DTS implementation, such as the version, and, in theory this endpoint should allow a DTS client to self configure by evaluating the provided URI Templates – a mechanism defined in RFC 6570 (<https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc6570>) that allows for the dynamic construction of URLs to request information from the API by variable expansion.

Example: <https://dracor.org/api/v1/dts>

api/v1/dts/collection (DraCor DTS Collection Endpoint):

This endpoint allows users to access information about the collections available. Users can retrieve a list of available corpora, including metadata such as title, corpus maintainer, and corpus language. This is useful for discovering and selecting specific collections for further exploration or analysis. Through the Collection endpoint, users can not only access lists of available drama corpora but also retrieve detailed metadata for individual resources, i.e. plays. A DTS response includes metadata using Dublin Core Terms, which provide a standardized set of descriptive elements. Additionally, the DTS framework allows for the integration of custom metadata as an extension, enabling us to incorporate DraCor-specific metadata by re-using terms of a custom OWL Ontology (<https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-ontology>). This flexible extension mechanism ensures that users have access to both standard and specialized metadata, enhancing the richness and utility of the information available through DraCor.

Examples:

- List all corpora:
<https://dracor.org/api/v1/dts/collection>
- Specific play with additional metadata:
<https://dracor.org/api/v1/dts/collection?id=https://dracor.org/id/ger000088>

api/v1/dts/navigation (DraCor DTS Navigation Endpoint):

The Navigation endpoint in DTS allows users to explore the structural organization of dramatic texts, facilitating access to various levels of the textual hierarchy. Central to this functionality is the concept of a Citable Unit, which represents a distinct, addressable segment within a text, in the context of DraCor an act, scene, speech, or stage direction. This granularity is particularly useful for detailed analysis and precise referencing. Through the Navigation endpoint, users can traverse a play's hierarchical tree, enabling actions such as fetching all scenes within an act or all speech acts within a scene. This capability supports fine-grained access to textual data, allowing researchers to focus on specific components of a dramatic work. Moreover, the Navigation endpoint employs the same extension mechanism as the Collection endpoint, allowing for the attachment of custom metadata to Citable Units. This flexibility

¹For implementation details and a comprehensive documentation including examples see Börner (2025); A Jupyter Notebook to try out DraCor's DTS implementation can be accessed at <https://github.com/dracor-org/dracor-notebooks/blob/main/dts/dts.ipynb>.

enables users to filter based on specific criteria. For instance, by including metadata that identifies which character is speaking, users can filter speech acts to focus on those of a particular character within a scene or act. This enriched metadata enhances the analytical capabilities of the DraCor DTS implementation, providing researchers with powerful tools for exploring and understanding plays, in a more granular way that has been possible with DraCor before.

Examples:

- All acts of a play:
<https://dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://dracor.org/id/ger000088&ref=body&down=1>
- Speeches in first scene:
[https://dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://dracor.org/id/ger000088&ref=body/div\[1\]/div\[1\]&down=1](https://dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://dracor.org/id/ger000088&ref=body/div[1]/div[1]&down=1)

api/v1/dts/document (DraCor DTS Document Endpoint):

This endpoint allows users to retrieve the actual textual content of dramatic works. Users can access full texts or specific segments, such as individual acts, scenes, speech acts or stage directions in a structured format. This is essential for performing textual analysis, extracting quotes, or conducting computational studies on the dramatic literature.

Examples:

- First act as TEI-XML:
[https://dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document?resource=https://dracor.org/id/ger000088&ref=body/div\[1\]](https://dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document?resource=https://dracor.org/id/ger000088&ref=body/div[1])
- Single speech as plain text:
[https://dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document?resource=https://dracor.org/id/ger000088&ref=body/div\[1\]/div\[1\]/sp\[1\]&mediaType=text/plain](https://dracor.org/api/v1/dts/document?resource=https://dracor.org/id/ger000088&ref=body/div[1]/div[1]/sp[1]&mediaType=text/plain)

4 New Capabilities Enabled by DTS

With the implementation of DTS, DraCor gained several new capabilities that significantly enhance its functionality and usability:

Fine-Granular Access: The DTS API allows for fine-granular access to textual data, enabling researchers to retrieve specific segments of plays. This granularity is crucial for detailed analysis and comparison of dramatic texts.

Before the implementation of DTS, the DraCor API already allowed researchers to retrieve predefined subsets of textual data, such as the complete spoken text by a specific character or all stage directions within a play.

With the implementation of DTS, researchers can now access text at a more granular level and apply various filtering strategies client-side. The Navigation endpoint enables users to traverse the hierarchical structure of plays, identifying citable units down to individual speech acts and stage directions within specific structural contexts. For example, researchers can now programmatically list all citable units within the second act of a play and subsequently filter for speeches by a particular character within that structural boundary.

Improved Citability: DTS enables precise referencing of specific segments within a play, thus improving the citability of dramatic works. Traditional drama scholarship often relies on act and scene numbering, as when Manfred Pfister in his book "The Theory and Analysis of Drama" references "Antony's spoken refrain 'Brutus is an honourable man' in his funeral oration for the central figure in Shakespeare's Julius Caesar (III, ii)." (Pfister, 2000, p. 56) However, such citations lack direct accessibility and vary across editions. The DTS implementation transforms this reference into a dereferenceable URI:

[https://dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://dracor.org/id/shake000030&ref=body/div\[3\]/div\[2\]](https://dracor.org/api/v1/dts/navigation?resource=https://dracor.org/id/shake000030&ref=body/div[3]/div[2])

This approach ensures scholarly citations remain accurate and verifiable while enabling direct text access via the document endpoint.

Structural Analysis: By providing standardized access to the structural elements of plays through the so-called Citation Tree object, DTS facilitates advanced structural analysis. The Citation Tree abstraction enables systematic comparison of dramatic organization across plays and corpora, allowing researchers to determine whether plays are structured into acts only, acts and scenes, or include additional elements such as dramatis personae in front matter. This programmatic approach to structural analysis significantly improves upon approaches that either required manual examination or complex parsing of individual TEI files.

Enhanced Interoperability: By adopting DTS, DraCor significantly enhances its interoperability. This standardized approach facilitates smoother data exchange and integration, although it is important to note that the tooling available for DTS is currently limited. Nonetheless, the adoption of DTS paves the way for greater collaboration and data sharing across the digital humanities community. Additionally, the use of JSON-LD in DTS responses enriches the semantic content, improving the understandability of API responses and opening new possibilities for using Linked Data approaches with DraCor corpora.

5 Outlook: Integration with CLARIN Infrastructure and EOSC

The capabilities enabled by DTS implementation extend beyond DraCor's immediate functionality to support broader infrastructure integration goals. The standardized approach demonstrated through DTS provides a pathway for connecting DraCor with major European research infrastructures.

One of the primary objectives of the Horizon 2020 Cascading Grant scheme funded OSCARS (<https://oscars-project.eu>) project DraCorOS (<https://oscars-project.eu/projects/dracoros-fostering-open-science-digital-humanities-connecting-dracor-ecosystem-eosc>) is to further develop the DraCor ecosystem. Particularly, the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory (VLO, <https://vlo.clarin.eu>) and the Digital Object Gateway (DOG, <https://www.clarin.eu/dog>) are intended to serve as potential gateways to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This integration with CLARIN as a first step towards EOSC-integration is designed to facilitate the discovery, access, and reuse of DraCor resources, promoting a more connected and collaborative open research environment. By implementing a standard API like DTS to DraCor, we experimented with adding additional API functionality to the legacy DraCor API. The experiences and lessons learned from this process will become invaluable as we embark on the CLARIN integration. This foundational work will help ensure that DraCor's resources are not only more accessible and interoperable but also aligned with the broader goals of open science and digital humanities research.

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Is a Party in Government or in Opposition?

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Abstract

This paper addresses the dichotomy between government and opposition in the speeches of two Danish parties from the left- and right-wing that alternated as being the leader of government or being part of the opposition from 2014 to 2022. The data is extracted from the linguistically annotated ParlaMint-DK 5, and we perform quantitative analyses of the speeches and test two classification approaches to automatically identify the status of the two parties from the transcriptions of their speeches. Our study confirms that there are differences between the speeches of the two parties depending on their status. A transformer-based classifier with a fine-tuned large language model identified the status of the two parties from the speeches of its members with a macro F1 score of 0.87 for the left-wing party, 0.86 for the right-wing party, and 0.82 for the speeches of both parties.

1 Introduction

This paper addresses the differences between government and opposition status in the speeches of two Danish parties, The Social Democratic Party (*Socialdemokratiet*), and Denmark's Liberal Party (*Venstre*) in the Danish parliament from 2014 to 2022. The two parties alternated as the leader of the government and as part of the opposition in this period.

Previous studies of parliament debates have found that the automatic classification of political positions of parties can be biased by the status of the parties, that is, whether they are in government or opposition (Hirst et al., 2010, 2014; Hix & Noury, 2016).

Inspired by these studies, we wanted to a) identify some of the characteristics of the speeches made by the two Danish parties when having different status using the linguistically annotated ParlaMint-DK 5 (Erjavec et al., 2024; Erjavec et al., 2025), and b) determine how well a transformer-based classifier with a fine-tuned large language model can identify a party's status from the speeches of its members compared with a support vector machine. Our investigations enlighten how the linguistic annotations and metadata in the ParlaMint corpora can be used to investigate various aspects of political discourse, as well as test different machine learning algorithms and language models. In the present study, we address the variation in the speeches of parties depending on their status.

The paper is organized as follows. In section 2, we present related studies, in section 3, we describe the data, and we present our analyses of the speeches. In section 4, we account for our classification experiments and in section 5, we conclude and present future work.

2 Background Studies

The dichotomy between government and opposition in political data has been addressed in various studies. For example, Hirst et al. (2010) apply a support vector machine to various features extracted from the questions in the French and English sessions of the Canadian parliament (1997-2000 and 2006-2008). They find that the classification is more influenced by the status of the parties than by their ideology. Hirst et al. (2014) compare the 10 most distinctive words in speeches by the liberal and conservative groups when in government or in opposition. More common words were discovered in the speeches of groups with the same status than in those of the same ideological group.

Izumi and Medeiros (2022) ran a Naive Bayes Classifier on the speeches of the Brazilian Senate to identify the sentiment of left- and right-wing politicians on different issues. They find that the largest differences in sentiment are in speeches by politicians in government or in opposition, in line with the findings in (Hirst et al., 2014). Zhang et al. (2017) used an unsupervised methodology to classify questions with different rhetorical roles. The proposed methodology consists of the following steps: a) identify lexico-syntactic patterns of questions, called *motifs*, b) construct a latent space based on answers and map motifs to this space, and c) use the obtained latent representations to cluster questions with similar rhetorical functions. They applied the method to the questions in the British parliament debates and compared the question types asked by members of parliament with respect to their party’s status (government/opposition/other) as well as their personal status (younger vs. more experienced politicians). The resulting typology showed differences in questioning behaviour between government and opposition parties.

Hofmann and Wissik (2024) find style differences in the Austrian parliament debates depending, inter alia, on the gender and party of the speakers, and on the status of their party.

In a previous study (Navarretta & Haltrup Hansen, 2024), we applied various classifiers to determine the status of 20 Danish parties in ParlaMint-DK speeches. We distinguished three groups: government, opposition, and *other*. The latter group consists of parties that are never in government, nor in direct opposition to it, deciding whether to support bills from case to case. Logistic regression achieved $F1score = 0.64$ on these data. Since some of the parties were only in opposition or in the *other* group during the studied period, this could have affected the classification results. Therefore, in the present work, we only consider the speeches of the social-democrats and liberals who were either in government or in opposition.

3 The data

ParlaMint-DK 5 contains the transcriptions of the speeches of the Danish parliament, *Folketinget*, from October 2014 to June 2022. In our study, we excluded the speeches made by the Speaker (the chair) who has the function of regulating the meetings, and we extracted the linguistically annotated speeches of the two parties, S and V, keeping the metadata that indicates the party status of the speakers. The tokenized transcriptions of speeches, their part of speech tags, and lemmas were used in the analyses.

In Table 1 the number of speeches and tokens, as well as the average length of the speeches of each party are given. The social-democrats spoke more often and uttered more words than the liberals (238

Party	Speeches	Tokens	Average Length
S in government	25,852	6,498,044	251
S in opposition	14,129	3,003,524	213
V in government	18,797	4,699,363	250
V in opposition	14,079	2,925,069	208

Table 1: Number of speeches and tokens of the two parties.

vs. 231 tokens per speech). Both parties spoke more often and uttered more words when they were in government than when they were in opposition. This is not surprising since ministers often propose new bills and present what the government has done or plans to do.

3.1 Analyses of the speeches

Following (Hirst et al., 2014), we extracted the 10 most distinctive lemmas from the speeches of the two parties when they had different status. Multi-word expressions were not included in the analysis. The results are in Table 2 with the lemmas provided in their English translation. In the table, the lemmas that are common in the speeches of the two parties when they have the same status are in bold, while the lemmas, which are used by the same party when having a different status, are in italics.

The table indicates that there are more lemmas in common in the speeches of the two parties when they have the same status than in the speeches of the same party with different status. This is in line with

S government	V government	S opposition	V opposition
I	I	minister	minister
apply	denmark	we	liberal party
our	line	social democracy	ask
society	apply	ask	answer
wide	simple market	people	spokesperson
need	society	think	government
inquirer	eu	spokesperson	think
frame	continue	discuss	look at
discussion	<i>choose</i>	bill	red-green union list
relation	work market	hear	<i>choose</i>

Table 2: The ten most distinctive lemmas in the speeches of S and V with different status.

what was found by Hirst et al. (2014) in the questions of the Canadian parliament.

We also investigated whether there are differences in the frequency of modality expressions in the speeches of the two parties while in government or opposition, following a strategy proposed in (Navaretta & Haltrup Hansen, 2024). Modality expressions have been addressed in several studies of political discourse because speakers can express their attitudinal state toward what they say or what others have expressed through modal expressions, e.g. (Lillian, 2008; Sharififar & Rahimi, 2015; Simon-Vandenberg, 1996).

More specifically, we compare the frequency of modal auxiliaries and modal clausal adverbs in the speeches of S and V when in government or in opposition. The modal auxiliary verbs in Danish are the following: *burde* (ought to), *gide* (bother), *kunne* (could), *måtte* (had to), *skulle* (should), *turde* (dare) and *ville* (would). When they are used in the past tense, they often indicate a non-factual (hypothetical) attitude to what is said. If they are used in the present tense, they often indicate a more factual attitude.

The Danish clausal adverbs can be distinguished into a) epistemic and b) factual (Jensen, 1997). The epistemic adverbs indicate a more hesitant attitude as the modal auxiliary verbs in the past tense, while the factual adverbs show more firmness as the modal auxiliary verbs in the present tense. Examples of epistemic adverbs are the following: *måske* (maybe), *nok* (probably), *dog* (though), *vist* (possibly), *formodentlig* (probably), *åbenbart* (apparently), while factual adverbs are *desværre* (unfortunately), *heldigvis* (fortunately), and *uheldigvis* (unfortunately).

We found statistically significant differences in the frequency of the past tense modal auxiliary verbs and epistemic adverbs in the speeches of both S and V depending on the status of the parties. The chi-square results were the following: $p < 0.001$ and $df = 1$ for the speeches of both parties. Thus, politicians used epistemic adverbs and the past tense modal auxiliary verbs statistically more frequently when they were in opposition than when they were in government. This can indicate that politicians in government are more confident about what they say than politicians in opposition. Politicians in opposition, on the other hand, often question the position and decisions of the government.

4 Classification experiments

Classifying text automatically is one of the main areas of application of natural language processing (NLP). Classification has been applied to parliamentary debates for, e.g., identifying ideology or position (Proksch & Slapin, 2012; Riabinin, 2009).

In our classification experiments, we wanted to determine how well two classifiers, a support vector machine trained on TF*IDF (Term Frequency * Inverse Document Frequency) and a Hugging face transformer classifier¹ with a fine-tuned large language model can identify the status of a party from the

¹<https://huggingface.co/docs/transformers/index>

speeches of its members. We run the classifiers first on the speeches of the social-democrats, then on the speeches of the liberals, and finally on the speeches of both parties. The data sets were randomly divided into a training set (80%), a testing set (10%), and a validation set (10%)². The SVM implementation is from the Python3 package *scikit-learn*.

We fine-tuned DanBERT³, a large language model, which was trained and made available by the Danish company Certainly⁴. The experiments with the transformer were carried out on a u3-gpu-2 provided by the interactive HPC system UCloud, which is managed by the eScience Center at the University of Southern Denmark.

The results of the classification of the two classes are shown in Table 3. The results are given in terms of Precision (P), Recall (R), macro-F1 score (F1). The best results for all data sets are obtained

Class.	Model	P	R	F1
Speeches of Social-democrats				
SVM	TF*IDF vect.	0.81	0.8	0.8
Transf.	DanBERT	0.88	0.86	0.87
Speeches of Liberals				
SVM	TF*IDF vect.	0.83	0.82	0.82
Transf.	DanBERT	0.87	0.85	0.86
Speeches of Both Parties				
SVM	TF*IDF	0.77	0.77	0.77
Transf	DanBERT	0.83	0.81	0.82

Table 3: Results of the binary government vs. opposition classification of the speeches of S, V and S and V.

by the transformer with the fine-tuned DanBERT. Its performance is nearly the same when identifying the status of the party from the speeches of the social democrats ($F1 - score = 0.87$) and the liberals ($F1 - score = 0.86$). The F score obtained by the transformer on the data set consisting of the speeches of both parties is 0.82.

Even if the results on the combined data set are lower than those obtained on the speeches of each of the two parties, they are still comparable to the state-of-the-art reported for text classification in other tasks (Fields et al., 2024; Minaee et al., 2021).

5 Conclusion and Future Work

In this study, we addressed the speeches of two Danish parties in ParlaMint-DK 5 focusing on their status (government or opposition).

We compared the use of modality expressions and the most distinctive lemmas in the speeches of the two parties when they had different status, and we performed classification experiments to identify the status of the two parties from their speeches automatically. Our linguistic analyses and classification experiments confirm that the speeches of politicians are influenced by the status of their party. Therefore, the status of the parties must be considered when investigating the parties' position toward different topics, as suggested by previous studies in various languages. Moreover, we found that transformer-based classification with a fine-tuned Danish Hugging Face large language model outperformed traditional classifiers in this task. The same classifier should be tested to identify other aspects, such as the speakers' party and age. The annotations and metadata in the ParlaMint corpora support these types of investigation. Since the corpora contain the same type of metadata, future work could address parliament speeches from the other ParlaMint corpora. Moreover, the classification experiments conducted on the Danish debates could be repeated on the English machine translations of the debates to evaluate the quality of translation for this classification task.

²The data sets were split without considering the speakers' identity, age or experience as members of the parliament.

³<https://huggingface.co/Maltehb/danish-bert-botxo>

⁴<https://certainly.io/>

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Expanding the Hungarian Gigaword Corpus

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Abstract

The MNSZ3 project aims to expand the Hungarian Gigaword Corpus (MNSZ2) from 1 billion to approximately 10 billion tokens while preserving its original structure, domains, and proportions. MNSZ2, a core resource for Hungarian language research, comprises various domains including journalism, literature, science, personal texts, official documents, and transcribed spoken language. In response to growing research demands and advances in language technology, our approach scales key domains and boosts international coverage by collecting additional texts from regions where Hungarian is spoken. This work presents our data collection methods, which include web scraping, custom parsing, and text cleaning routines, ensuring that the enhanced corpus remains balanced and representative. Preliminary analyses compare two state-of-the-art annotation pipelines, HuSpaCy and e-magyar, in order to establish an efficient processing framework. Ultimately, the enriched datasets will be integrated into the KorAP corpus handling tool, providing researchers with a powerful resource for linguistic analysis and supporting future applications in natural language processing.

1 Introduction

Representative corpora play an essential role in linguistic research by providing a reliable source of language data for both theoretical studies and practical applications. In Hungarian, a key resource has been the Hungarian Gigaword Corpus (MNSZ2, Oravecz et al., 2014), which was a HunCLARIN initiative¹. It marked a significant improvement over the earlier Hungarian National Corpus (HNC, Váradi, 2002),

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¹<https://clara.nytud.hu/mnsz2-dev/en/>

which contained about 187 million words: MNSZ2 comprises approximately 1 billion tokens, drawing on texts from a variety of domains: journalism (42%), literature (14.5%), science (7.2%), personal texts (22.1%), official documents (8.8%), and transcribed spoken language (5.4%). This broad domain coverage is complemented by regional diversity, as the corpus includes language variants used throughout Hungary as well as those from neighboring countries where Hungarian is spoken, forming a subset known as the Hungarian Minority Language Corpus.

Despite its significant size and balanced design, MNSZ2 is now considered outdated in light of the growing demand for larger and more representative corpora. To better address contemporary research needs and modern language technology applications, our project aims to expand MNSZ2 to a corpus roughly ten times larger – approximately 10 billion tokens² – by incorporating texts from all of its six domains and from all regions³. Importantly, while we increase the scale and international coverage of the corpus, we strive to preserve the original structure, domains, and proportions of MNSZ2. Some domains in MNSZ2 are currently underrepresented (or not represented at all) in one or two regions: by integrating data from these overlooked areas, we aim to build a more comprehensive and balanced resource that robustly reflects the linguistic variation found across all regions.

2 Data collection

In this phase of the project, we focus on three main domains – official documents, journalism, and literature – while concurrently collecting data from regions outside Hungary across all domains.

2.1 Official domain

We collected and processed over 900 million words from six key sources of official legal texts: three Hungarian and three EU-based. The objective was to create a clean, structured, and linguistically relevant corpus of legal language, covering national laws, court decisions, municipal decrees, and EU legislation.

The Hungarian documents were scraped using custom-built crawlers, often relying on browser automation tools such as Chrome and Selenium. These included:

- The National Law Repository, contributing 83 million words, posed challenges such as persistent footnotes, special characters (e.g., m², °C), and bilingual content. We used *Trafilatura* for initial HTML parsing, followed by complex regular expressions for cleaning and deduplication.
- The Repository of Municipal Decrees offered 290 million words in structurally simpler documents, requiring fewer manual interventions.
- The Anonymized Court Decisions source yielded 431 million words. Despite anonymization, extraneous content like case numbers, department names, and hearing dates had to be removed. Cleaning became more consistent over time as formatting improved.

From the European Union, the Hungarian parts of three widely known corpora were included: the JRC Acquis (44 million Hungarian tokens), the Europarl parallel corpus (12 million Hungarian tokens) and the Digital Corpus of the European Parliament (cc. 35 million tokens).

On top of these sources, we also included texts collected from the Hungarian National Parliament’s website, such as parliamentary speeches and committee meeting notes, adding up to 228 million words. It should be noted that the corpus will be made available with full topicalization and categorization, enabling users to filter and search not only across the entire collection but also within specific document types (e.g., parliamentary speeches, legislative texts, or court decisions).

2.2 Fiction

One of the most challenging subsections of the corpus proved to be the *belles lettres* domain. Our primary source was the collection received from the Hungarian Electronic Library (MEK). Beyond relying on the “*belle lettres*” tag of MEK, we defined the genre as prose works whose primary purpose is not to provide data or information, but to tell a story, entertain or entice through an elevated or unique creative

²To further support this choice, 10 billion seemed a nice, challenging but still realistic number, in line with the pace of development of the earlier versions of the corpus.

³Hungary and its neighbouring countries where Hungarian is spoken: Austria, Slovakia, Ukraine, Romania, Serbia, Croatia and Slovenia.

writing style. The following domains made the cut: novels, short stories, tales, religious texts and esoteric writings. In terms of the temporal scope, we included works dated after 1945 and for translated works, after 1990.⁴

Beyond the problems stemming from digitization (OCR errors, untidy metadata, encoding issues) there were also textual challenges. The domain had novels emulating chat messages, authors purposefully omitting punctuation or capitals, English and German phrases, made-up languages and sentences embedded in sentences.

We approached these problems on four levels, with manual, rule-based, statistical and neural techniques, respectively. First, statistical analyses were conducted to determine features of a literary work (including typical sentence and paragraph length) but the genre's diversity did not allow for this method as we learned looking at the resulting half-erased output. The neural approach also fell short with both GPT and our in-house mt5 model. They struggled with fictional names and unconventional grammar, often substituting the former with another word and overcorrecting the latter, at the cost of losing the richness of the texts. In the end, a blend of manual and rule-based methods proved to be the solution, in the form of running Python scripts with regular expressions and pattern recognition, then giving the resulting logfiles to annotators for manual review and cleaning. Our work resulted in 72.8 million cleaned tokens. It is important to note that, due to issues of availability and quality, the fiction domain cannot be expanded to ten times its current size.

2.3 Press

The majority of news articles in the corpus were sourced from the Common Crawl (CC) archive. To ensure quality and relevance, we identified and retained the top 100 domains that yielded the largest number of articles, primarily focusing on high-traffic news websites. Altogether, this subcorpus already exceeds two billion tokens, and additional material continues to be collected.

A general observation was that only about one-quarter of the downloaded content consisted of original, useful articles, while the remainder comprised repetitive or duplicated material. To mitigate this, a strong deduplication filter was implemented, designed to exclude near-identical pages and replicated content across different URLs.

An additional challenge was the frequent appearance of index-like pages – pages listing only headlines or article leads without full content. These often reside under base URLs of category pages or under structural pages such as “about”, “privacy”, or other footnote-level links. To address this, we used two complementary filtering strategies focusing on the syntax of the urls.

Another common complication was the presence of multi-page articles, where a single piece is split across several pages. These are difficult to identify and often contain overlapping or truncated content. Subscription-based content was also present in some sites but could not be accessed through Common Crawl and was therefore excluded.

To maintain journalistic relevance, we also discarded i) articles that were too short, incomplete, or trailing off in ellipses; ii) foreign-language content, typically in English; iii) blog-style entries, which often lacked the structure and editorial standards of journalistic article. A significant portion of repeated articles turned out to be press releases or media announcements, which were not retained as they typically lacked original reporting. In some cases, actual duplicates of full articles were also identified and removed. These filtering methodologies had to be adapted and fine-tuned to accommodate the diverse publishing habits of different news organizations, whose content management systems and URL structures varied considerably.

2.4 Hungarian texts from the neighbouring countries

The basis for scraping foreign domains containing Hungarian texts was a list from the Common Crawl dataset where Hungarian content had been detected. Initially, we identified which foreign countries to

⁴In practice, the corpus generally includes texts after 1990. For literary works we extend the coverage back to 1945 to secure sufficient material. Each work is supplied with a date, so users may restrict their queries to post-1990 texts if preferred. The 1990 cut-off for translations was chosen to keep all the subcorpora consistent.

examine; next, we categorized the domains according to the classifications set for the MNSZ3 project; and finally, we scraped the domains and cleaned the resulting data.

We extracted the list of domains containing Hungarian texts from the CC Corpus and selected those with extensions from neighboring countries: Austria (at), Slovakia (sk), Ukraine (ua), Romania (ro), Serbia (sr), Croatia (hr), and Slovenia (si), assuming these domains represent the language use of indigenous Hungarian speakers. We obtained up to 2,671 domains. We manually reviewed them, filtering and categorizing each into one of the following groups: press, official, personal, scientific, literature, or popular science. The largest group was the official category, which includes websites of governments, associations, companies, church communities, educational institutions, political parties, and cultural institutions. In this category, we identified 2,364 domains and scraped 512 of those with the highest token counts, while discarding many that contained only a few pages with only a few hundred tokens. The official category yielded a total of 50 million tokens. In contrast, the press category provided considerably more content; we scraped 160 press domains, which resulted in approximately 300 million tokens.

For scraping, we used custom scripts because no publicly available scraper was effective for such a large and structurally diverse set of domains. During scraping, we downloaded HTML files, from which we extracted text into TXT files and metadata (author, title, date, topic or column, if available) into XML files. After scraping, we deduplicated the files, removed those in non-Hungarian languages, and eliminated boilerplate content.

3 Linguistic Annotation

In preparation for the comprehensive analysis of the Hungarian Gigaword Corpus 3.0, we undertook a detailed comparison of two prominent Hungarian language processing pipelines: HuSpaCy (Orosz et al., 2022; Orosz et al., 2023) and e-magyar (Váradi et al., 2018). Our objective was to identify the most suitable tool, or a combination thereof, for the annotation of our large-scale corpus. To this end, we conducted an empirical evaluation using a representative sample from parliamentary records, which includes formal language, transcription errors, and non-standard elements such as speaker names, timestamps, and formatting markers.

Our analysis was structured around several key processing levels: tokenization, morphological analysis, lemmatization, dependency parsing, and named entity recognition (NER). For each of these levels, we standardized the outputs from both pipelines by developing a unified framework that aligns their respective outputs.

The comparison showed that HuSpaCy performs very well in tasks that require speed and consistency. Its tokenization and dependency parsing modules work robustly, producing outputs that are well-suited for applications where processing efficiency is important. In contrast, e-magyar showed better performance in morphological analysis and lemmatization. This suggests that a hybrid approach may be beneficial for our corpus annotation, as it can balance processing speed with annotation accuracy.

A comparison of the morphological analyses revealed differences between the EmMorph module (Novák et al., 2016) and the Universal Dependencies (UD) based approach. The EmMorph module, integrated in e-magyar, provides a more detailed set of morphological features, while the UD approach used by HuSpaCy is faster but offers a less fine-grained analysis. These differences are important for our corpus research, as they have a direct impact on the quality of subsequent lemmatization and syntactic parsing.

4 Conclusion

In summary, while our project has made significant progress in expanding and diversifying the corpus, it remains a work in progress. Our current phase has scaled key domains, and our new method for collecting texts from abroad has produced far more international material than in MNSZ2. Looking ahead, we will continue to gather more texts within the existing MNSZ2 domains, with a special focus on spoken language, scientific texts, and personal communications. Ultimately, all these enhanced datasets will be integrated into the KorAP concordancer⁵ (by the end of 2026), ensuring flexible and sophisticated

⁵<https://github.com/KorAP>

search capabilities similar to those already familiar from MNSZ2.

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A Digital Humanism perspective on providing language resources to CLARIN in an age of AI commodification: The case of UniTermGPT

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Abstract

The increasing use of large language models (LLMs) in translation and terminology work raises critical ethical and infrastructural questions, particularly regarding the commodification of open language resources. From a Digital Humanism perspective, this paper presents UniTermGPT, a project that examines how ChatGPT handles university-related terminology across German varieties, including Austrian, German and South Tyrolean and contributes FAIR-compliant, annotated corpora and resources to CLARIN.

UniTermGPT not only supports LLM benchmarking in specialized translation but also highlights the risks of open language resources being exploited by commercial LLM providers. By embedding CARE principles and Digital Humanism values such as transparency, inclusivity and epistemic justice into its methodology, this paper argues for stronger safeguards and ethical standards within public infrastructures. This includes mechanisms for provenance tracking, responsible licensing, transparent governance and the representation of minority language communities in decisions about their language resources.

Ultimately, UniTermGPT illustrates that openness in research data management can be balanced with responsibility, ethical reflection and attention to linguistic diversity. By demonstrating how open resources can support both technological development and broader societal benefits, the project provides a practical example of responsible openness and highlights ways in which infrastructures like CLARIN can facilitate the ethical sharing and use of language data.

1 Introduction

As large language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT become embedded in everyday professional practice, including (specialized) translation (Gao et al., 2023; He, 2024) and terminology work (Heinisch, 2025; Reineke, 2023), they challenge not only technical standards but also the ethical, social and epistemological foundations of our digital infrastructures. Under the accelerating pressure of AI commodification, (open) language resources risk being appropriated by commercial actors in ways that undermine transparency, human agency and academic values. Against this backdrop, Digital Humanism offers a useful lens for rethinking how we create and share language resources in infrastructures such as CLARIN.

This contribution presents UniTermGPT, a research project that operates at the intersection of translation studies, terminology work and language resource development. Its dual goals are to assess how ChatGPT handles university-related terminology across German language varieties (Austrian, German, South Tyrolean and Swiss) and to produce a set of ethically grounded, FAIR-compliant language resources to be shared with the CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure) community. Central to this work is a commitment to the principles of Digital Humanism, placing human knowledge, context and control at the center of digital systems.

2 Development and publication of language resources (as part of UniTermGPT)

The research project *University terminology in German in the age of ChatGPT* (UniTermGPT) has the creation and publication of language resources at its core. The background of this study is based on the fact that specialized translation and terminology work are impacted by the acceleration in AI breakthroughs, such as ChatGPT. However, in the field of specialized translation ChatGPT currently does not take terminological variation sufficiently into account (Heinisch, 2025). Since higher

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education systems differ between countries, there can be significant terminological variation, even within the same language (Terras et al., 2016), such as between the Austrian, German or South Tyrolean variety of the German language. Therefore, the question arises how ChatGPT can cope with this variation in translation in the field of German university terminology. The overall objective is to analyze how ChatGPT treats university terminology of German language varieties (depending on the prompt). For this, a corpus of Austrian, German, South Tyrolean and Swiss university texts will be compiled, from which terminology will be extracted and compared with existing terminological resources, such as university glossaries and terminological databases. Following prompt engineering, selected texts will be translated by means of ChatGPT, which will be annotated by experts to assess the outcome of translations from these language varieties into English and vice versa.

In addition to open research data and the integration of the needs of translators and terminologists, the results of UniTermGPT can be transferred to other areas characterized by the use of system-bound terminology. UniTermGPT supplements existing studies on specialized translation and terminology work by means of ChatGPT and addresses the overlooked topic of language-variety-specific terminology (in specialized translation and in large language models). The resulting recommendations for practitioners and a policy brief highlight the societal relevance of terminology in an age characterized by large language models.

2.1 UniTermGPT resources to be provided to CLARIN

As part of UniTermGPT, several language resources will be provided to CLARIN. The project's data pipeline includes:

- Monolingual and bilingual corpora of higher education texts from German-speaking regions, annotated for language variety and domain-specific terminology;
- Terminological resources containing university terminology in different language varieties. This resource may also be used for the retrieval-augmented generation or terminology-augmented generation (Di Nunzio, 2025) of translations generated by ChatGPT into different German language varieties in the field of university texts.
- ChatGPT translations of selected documents, creating a basis for comparative analysis;
- Expert annotations assessing ChatGPT's output's terminological accuracy and consistency across varieties. Together with the annotations, comprehensive annotation guidelines developed together with the experts will be provided.

These resources will be contributed to CLARIN (and other repositories) with open documentation, open usage licenses and a view to long-term reusability. They are intended not only to advance future research on how large language models handle terminology in specialized translation (through tools such as ChatGPT), but also to encourage ethical reflection on the provision of language resources to infrastructures like CLARIN, questioning what counts as "valuable" language resource and ensuring that the benefits of such resources are shared fairly.

2.2 AI commodification of language resources

The act of sharing language resources through an open infrastructure in the current artificial intelligence (AI) landscape invites several risks. Openness, compliance and ethics are closely connected yet often conflicting dimensions of open datasets for LLM training (Baack et al., 2025): openness promotes free access and collaborative sharing of data and code, compliance ensures adherence to evolving legal frameworks, and ethics addresses broader issues of justice, equality and responsibility beyond legal obligations (all three of which must be continuously balanced in the face of rapid technological change).

Commercial LLM providers increasingly scrape open repositories, including academic and governmental corpora, without license or copyright compliance (Baack et al., 2025). In doing so, they appropriate public intellectual labor and undermine the collaborative ecosystems that infrastructures like CLARIN are built upon.

This leads to questions related to the commodification of knowledge work (Popowich, 2024), which in turn form the basis of several fundamental inquiries raised within the UniTermGPT project:

- How can a researcher requesting language resources from experts, including terminological resources and translation memories, ensure that these resources are shared willingly under a non-commercial license? So, how can language resources provided under CLARIN, and other repositories, remain open while preventing extractive AI practices?
- What ethical obligations do researchers have when contributing to research infrastructures in a commodified digital landscape?
- How can CLARIN and similar platforms lead the way in ensuring reciprocity, transparency and accountability in AI data flows?

These are important questions, intertwined with questions also raised within Digital Humanism.

2.3 Digital Humanism

Digital Humanism is an interdisciplinary approach that places human values, rights and agency at the center of technological development and digital innovation (Werthner, 2022). It critically examines how digital technologies shape society and seeks to ensure that they serve democratic, inclusive and ethical goals rather than purely commercial or exploitative interests. The aim of Digital Humanism is to align digital transformation with the public good, thereby promoting transparency, accountability and human dignity in the design, deployment and governance of digital systems (Mayer & Strassnig, 2020; Nida-Rümelin, 2021). Translated to the context of language technologies and infrastructures like CLARIN, Digital Humanism calls for responsible data practices that respect contributors, safeguard cultural diversity and resist the unchecked commodification of knowledge.

2.4 Digital Humanism and its relation to FAIR and CARE principles

The FAIR and CARE principles provide complementary frameworks for research data management: while FAIR emphasizes making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable, CARE highlights the need for Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility and Ethics, ensuring that openness is balanced with respect for communities. While the FAIR principles are data-centric, technical and accessibility-oriented (Wilkinson et al., 2016), the CARE principles are people- and rights-centric, especially for indigenous data (Carroll et al., 2020). FAIR is rather technology-neutral and does not address ethical or societal issues. These principles guide how data should be structured and shared to ensure it can be easily located, understood and reused by humans and machines. CARE on the other hand, emphasizes equity, governance and the rights of data subjects, particularly indigenous communities. CARE ensures that data use aligns with ethical standards and governance and community interests.

The added value of Digital Humanism to these principles are human-centric values in digital technologies. Digital Humanism is not just about data and the use of data (as the FAIR and CARE principles are) but also critically examines the diverse impacts of (data use and) technologies. Digital Humanism thus extends beyond research data management and brings in broader human values and rights into digital technologies often overlooked by FAIR and CARE. Applied to research data management, Digital Humanism can add a normative layer to FAIR's technical focus, asking not only *can* we use this data, but *should* we? Digital Humanism promotes human rights and autonomy in the digital age as well as the design and governance of digital systems that respect and empower people, not just data efficiency. It pushes for accountability, democratic values and resistance to power imbalances created by opaque data practices and digital systems.

3 Making language resources openly accessible by taking Digital Humanism into account

The web operates on an extractive capitalist model that commodifies user data and labor, perpetuating historical inequalities while offering users minimal benefit beyond basic access to services (Lindgren et al., 2025). When applied to the domain of language resource creation and dissemination, the Digital Humanism perspective thus raises fundamental questions: Who creates language data? Who benefits from it? And how can we ensure that open access does not become a gateway to exploitation?

The UniTermGPT project provides a case study in navigating these tensions, focused on the creation of annotated and FAIR-compliant language resources for integration into the CLARIN infrastructure and other repositories. However, opening language resources is not a neutral act in today's AI landscape. This project unfolds in a context where commercial AI companies often scrape open resources (Baack et al., 2025) for use in proprietary models. This practice, frequently done without consent or licensing compliance, has led to growing concern and rising reluctance among experts and researchers about contributing to open repositories.

From a Digital Humanism perspective, this reluctance must be taken seriously. The aim is not to restrict access, but to redefine what responsible openness looks like. In UniTermGPT, this means involving experts (translators, terminologists and domain experts) not just as data providers, but as key stakeholders of the resource creation process. Their insights inform not only the content but also the ethical boundaries of data sharing. In addition, the project advocates for infrastructural mechanisms within CLARIN that can prevent unauthorized harvesting of data. While CLARIN already uses federated authentication (institutional login) to ensure that data is not openly exposed without identity verification, further measures could include the introduction of transparency reports that document who accessed which resources and for what declared purpose. CLARIN could also (further) incorporate the values of Digital Humanism, such as transparency, inclusivity and epistemic justice into policy and governance frameworks. Central to this effort is ensuring that marginalized and minority language communities are represented in decisions about how their resources are collected, stored, shared and used. For example, participatory governance could give data-contributing communities, such as speakers of minority languages or non-dominant language varieties, a direct role in shaping how their data is managed. Embedding values at multiple levels of the CLARIN infrastructure, from technical design to governance and culture, is key to achieving this.

The UniTermGPT project shows that openness in research data management must go hand in hand with responsibility, ethical reflection and respect for diversity. It provides concrete practices for balancing competing goals: making data interoperable and accessible while protecting communities from exploitation; enabling reuse while honoring epistemic diversity; and fostering innovation while ensuring accountability.

4 Conclusion

From a Digital Humanism standpoint, the provision of language resources to infrastructures like CLARIN must extend beyond technical compliance with the FAIR principles to embrace a broader commitment to accountability, ethics and epistemic justice. Language data (particularly when derived from public institutions and intellectual labor) carries cultural, social and political values that cannot be abstracted or repurposed without consent, attribution and respect for the (language) communities that produce it. CLARIN plays a vital role in safeguarding these values by providing a trusted, non-commercial space where contributors retain agency and users are held to clear ethical standards.

Ultimately, UniTermGPT aligns with this vision by demonstrating that open language resources can be designed to serve both technological advancement and the public interest without compromising the rights and values of those who create them. By involving translators and domain experts in the compilation and annotation of corpora, and by emphasizing the importance of language-variety-specific terminology, the project underscores the importance of linguistic diversity in global digital systems. This is not merely a matter of accuracy but an ethical commitment to epistemic justice: ensuring that different ways of expressing knowledge are represented and respected in multilingual large language models.

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